

Appendix 2

CEM2D Source Code

Cited in Chapter 3

```
//
//
// Modified version of the Coastline Evolution Model (CEM), originally
// developed by originally developed by Ashton et al. (2001), Ashton and
// Murray (2006) and Valvo et al. (2006)
//
//

using System.IO;
using System;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Collections;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data;
using System.Text;
using System.Net;
using System.Xml;
using System.Text.RegularExpressions;
using System.Linq;
using System.Drawing.Drawing2D;
using System.Collections.Generic;

namespace CEM1
{
    /// <summary>
    /// Summary description for Form1.
    /// </summary>
    public class Form1 : System.Windows.Forms.Form
    {
        private System.Drawing.Bitmap m_objDrawingSurface;

        //JMW
        [System.Runtime.InteropServices.DllImport("gdi32.dll")]

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

    public static extern long BitBlt(IntPtr hdcDest, int nXDest,
int nYDest, int nWidth, int nHeight, IntPtr hdcSrc, int nXSrc, int
nYSrc, int dwROP);

    private System.ComponentModel.IContainer components;

    //Jorge variables
    public static double sedOut = 0; //amount of
sediment at outlet, plotted
    public static double waterOut = 0; //amount of
water at outlet, plotted
    public static int plotType = 0;
    public static double magnifyValue = 0;
    public static int updateClick = 0;
    private double[] zoomFactor = { .25, .33, .50, .66, .80, 1,
1.25, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 };
    private double[] contrastFactor = { 1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8,
2.0, 2.2, 2.4, 2.6, 2.8, 3 };
    private double contrastMultiplier = 0;
    public int imageCount = 0;
    public int imageCount2 = 1;
    public string kml = "";
    public string KML_FILE_NAME = "animation\\animation.kml";
    int save_time2, save_interval2 = 0;
    public string startDate, kmlTime;
    public DateTime googleTime;
    public string[] DateArray;
    public string[] DateArray2;

    // toms global variables
    const Single g = 9.81F;
    const Single kappa = 0.4F;
    double time_1=1;
    double save_time=0;
    int input_type_flag=0; // 0 is water
input from points, 1 is input from hydrograph or rainfall file.
    double saveinterval=1000;
    int counter=0;
    Timer gameClock;
    int xmax, ymax;
    double xll, yll;
    const int ACTIVE_FACTOR=1;
    const int TRUE = 1;
    const int FALSE = 0;
    double DX=5;
    double root=7.07;
    double fiveroot=10.04;
    double time_factor;
    double baseflow=0.00000005; //end of hyd
model variables usually 0.0000005 changed 2/11/05
    public static double cycle=0;
    double init_cycle=0;
    double output_file_save_interval=60;
    int graphics_scale = 5; // value that
controls the number of bmp pixels per model pixel for the output
images.

    // Gez
    double tx = 60;

    // MJ global vars

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        int[] deltaX = new int[9] {0,0,1,1,1,0,-1,-1,-1};
        int[] deltaY = new int[9] {0,-1,-1,0,1,1,1,0,-1};

        double hue = 360.0;           // Ranges between 0 and 360
degrees
        double sat = 0.90;           // Ranges between 0 and 1.0
(where 1 is 100%)
        double val = 1.0;           // Ranges between 0 and 1.0
(where 1 is 100%)
        double red = 0.0;
        double green = 0.0;
        double blue = 0.0;

        string[] inputheader;       //Read from ASCII DEM <JOE
20050605>
        string basetext = "Modified Coastline Evolution Model (CEM)";
        private Graphics mygraphics;

        // CM CEM Variables
        const double pi = 3.141592654;
        double radtodeg = 180 / pi;
// Transform rads to degrees

        // Time Check
        TimeSpan startTime = DateTime.Now.TimeOfDay;
        TimeSpan endTime;
        TimeSpan speed;

        // Setup
        int TimeStepValue = 1;
// days - reflects rate of sediment transport per time step
        double StopAfter;
// Stop after what number of time steps
        int seed = 1;
// random seed: control value = 1 completely random = -999
        char StartFromFile;
// start from saved file?
        char InitialiseFile = 'n';
// use a file to initialise run? Over rides setup data
        string[] readcontrolname = new string[] {
"INPUT_FILES/CEM_control.dat" };
        double[] ControlFileIn = new double[20];
// Initialisation data read from file
        int NoPauseRun = 1;
// Disbale PauseRun subroutine
        string ConfigName = null;
// Name of default ConfigFile (blank!)
        int Resuldata_freq = 3650;

        // Dimensions - periodic boundary/display
        int xDisplayStart;
        int xDisplayEnd;
        int pbEnd;
        static int CellWidth = 100;
// size of cells (meters)
        static int MaxBeachLength;
// maximum length of arrays that contain beach data at each time step

        //DEM From File
        string fileContent_DEM;
// Used to read entire DEM file

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        string[] fileSplit;
        double coastrotation = 0;
// Angle (deg) used to align coastline with real wave climate
        string DEMFilePath;// = Directory.GetCurrentDirectory() +
"/INPUT_FILES/CEM_PertShort.dat"; // File path for loaded DEM

        int InitBeach = 25;
// cell where intial conditions changes from beach to ocean
        int InitRock = 5;
// cell where initial conditions change from beach to rock LMV

        int InitCType;
// 0: normal (columns/blocks), 1: wiggly, 2: one block
        int InitialDepth = 10;
// theoretical depth in meters of continental shelf at x = InitBeach
        int InitialPert;
// Start with a bump? if =1-->square pert, if =2-->pointy pert
        int DiffusiveHump = 0;
// Shoreline is sinusoidal LMV
        int InitialSmooth = 0;
// Smooth starting conditions (1=smooth 0=rough))
        int InitialSmoothRock = 1;
// Smooth rock interface starting conditions LMV (1=smooth 0=rough)

        // Waves
        int WaveIn;
// Input Wave Distribution file: no = 0, binned file = 1,
angle/period/height file = 2, manualentry = 3
        double WaveAngle;
// wave angle for current time step
        double OffShoreWvHt = 1.7;
// meters
        double Period = 8.0;
// seconds
        double Asym; //
fractional portion of waves coming from positive (left) direction
        double Highness; // .5
= even dist, > .5 high angle domination.
        double Duration = 1;
// Number of time steps calculations loop at same wave angle
        double waveheightchange = 1;
// Factor applied to the input wave height; 1 = no change, 0.5 = half
wave height, and 2 = double wave height
        double waveperiodchange = 1;
// Factor applied to the input wave period; 1 = no change, 0.5 = half
wave period, and 2 = double wave period
        string readwavename;
        string realWave_Content;
// Used to read entire real wave file
        string[] realWave_Split;
        int Wavecount = 0;
// Used to count cycle through wave data from file
        int NumWaveBins;
// For Input Wave - number of bins
        double[] WaveMax = new double[36];
// Max Angle for specific bin
        double[] WaveProb = new double[36];
// Probability of Certain Bin
        double WaveAngleIn;
        double WaveHeightIn;
        double WavePeriodIn;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```
// Tides
int DoTides;
// Run with tides = 1, run without tides = 0
double WaterLevel;
// What height is the tide?
double HighWaterHeight;
// Level of HighTide
double[] WLArray;
int WLCount = -1;

// SLR
int DoSLR;
// Run with SLR = 1, run without SLR = 0
double SLR;
// Amount of SLR
int SLRrate;
// Period over which SLR rises
double[] SLRArray;
// Stores incremental SLR over x years
int SLRCount = -1;

// Weathering/Erosion
int MaxFillCell = 1;
// Value representing that a cell is 100% full of material - Used as
// an indicator to see if a cell is 100% Full
const int NumberChunk = 0;
// Number of chunks of rock in alongshore direction with different
// weathering rates LMV
int ChunkLength;
// Alongshore length of a chunk of fast or slow weathering rock LMV
// (used to be xmax/NumberChunk)
double NoWeathering;
// weathering of rock only occurs below this amt of sed cover (vert
// equiv in meters) LMV */
double SlowWeatherCoeff;
// Weathering rate of slow rock e.g. 0.5 = slow weathering, 1/2 as
// fast LMV
double FastWeatherCoeff;
// Weathering rate of fast rock e.g. 2 = fast weathering, 2 times
// faster than normal LMV
double PercentFineFast;
// Percent of fast weathering rock lost because it is too fine to stay
// in nearshore LMV
double PercentFineSlow;
// Percent of slow weathering rock lost because it is too fine to stay
// in nearshore LMV
double ErosionRatePerYear;
// Amount of erosion to TotalBeachCells in m/year LMV
double CurrentPercentFine = 0;
double CliffHeight = 0;
// Average cliff height in (m)

// Shoreface
double ShelfSlope = 0.1;
// slope of continental shelf
double ShorefaceSlope = 0.01;
// for now, linear slope of shoreface
int DepthShoreface = 10;
// minimum depth of shoreface due to wave action (meters)
int MaxDist = 50;

// Overwash Parameters
```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```
        int OWType = 0;
// Overwash - 0 = use depth array, 1 = use geometric rule
        double CritBWidth = 350.0;
// Overwash - width barrier maintains due to overwash (m) important
scaling parameter!
        int InitBWidth = 4;
// Overwash - initial minimum width of barrier (Cells)
        double OWMinDepth = 0.01;
// Overwash - littlest overwash of all
        int OWflag = 0;
// A debugging flag for overwash routines
        double MaxOver = 0.01;
// Maximum overwash step size (enforced at back barrier)
        double OverwashLimit = 60;
// Don't do over wash if the angle is > 60 degrees
        double[,] CellDepth;
// Depth array

        // Beach
        int TimeToSweepFullBeach = 50;
// Spacing of full beach sweep for each rock cell i=0:TotalBeachCells
LMV
        int LookDist = 10;
// For short rock to beach sweep, +- number of beach cells to look at
LMV
        double BigDistanceToBeach = 1000.0 * CellWidth;
// Used to find minimum distance to beach in rock to beach sweep LMV
        double MassInitial;
// For conservation of mass calcs
        double MassCurrent;

        // Find Beach/Rock - Draw the 'Coast'
        int FindStart;
// Used to tell FindBeach at what Y value to start looking
        int FindRockStart;
// Used to tell FindRock at what Y value to start looking LMV
        int NextX;
// Global variables used to iterate FindNextCell in global array
        int NextY;
// Would've used pointer but wouldn't work
        int BehindX;
        int BehindY;
        int BehindRockX;
        int BehindRockY;
        int NextRockX;
// Global variables used to iterate FindNextRockCell in global array
LMV
        int NextRockY;
        int TotalBeachCells;
// Number of cells describing beach at particular iteration
        int TotalRockCells;
// Number of cells describing rock at an iteration LMV
        char FellOffArray;
// Flag used to determine if accidentally went off array
        char FellOffRockArray;
// Flag used to determine if accidentally went off rock array LMV
        int FindCellError = 5;
// if we run off of array, how far over do we try again?

        //Shadow
        double ShadowStepDistance = 0.2;
// step size for shadow cell checking
```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```
        int ShadowYMax;
// used to determine maximum extent of beach cells

        // Sources and Sinks
        int HaveSinks;
// include sediment sinks in model run?  0 no, 1 yes
        int NumSinks;
        int ColumnSinks;
// if this is turned on, X vector is disregarded and a sink is
considered to span a whole column
        int[] SinkY;
// a sink is a cell that is routinely emptied (if it is on the beach)
        int[] SinkX;
        double Sinkiness;
// fractional value determines chance that sediment in the sink is
deleted
        int NumSources;
        int ColumnSources;
// if this is turned on, X vector is disregarded and a sink is
considered to span a whole column
        int[] SourceY;
// a source cell when on beach
        int[] SourceX;

        //Age Cells
        int AgeMax = 1000000;
// Maximum 'age' of cells - loops back to zero
        int AgeUpdate = 10;
// Time space for updating age of non-beach cells

        // Save
        int SaveFrequency;
// Counter interval to save image
        int SaveDEM = 1;
        int SaveSpacing;
// space between saved files
        string savefilename;
        char Metadata = 'y';
// Create a metadata file?
        string[] metasavename = new string[] {
"OUTPUT_FILES/Metadata.out" }; // array size was originally 24?
        char Wavedata = 'y';
// Create a wavedata file?
        string wavesavename;
        int SaveImage = 1;
// Save as PNG image?
        int StartSavingAt = 0;
// Number to start saving at
        int SaveFile = 2;
// 1 = line output, 2 = array output
        int SaveAge = 0;
// Save/update age of cells?
        int SaveLine = 0;
// Save line instead of whole array?

        int SandOutCol = 150;
// save the amount of sand in the cells of this column at each time
step
        //double SandAmount = 0;
        string[] sandamountsave = new string[] { "SandAmount.out" };
```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        double TotalVolumePerIt;
// Counts how much sediment is moved across the entire area on each
iteration
        //string MovedSedVolPath = "OUTPUT_FILES/MovedSedVol.dat";

        // Overall Shoreface Configuration Arrays
        int[,] AllBeach;
// Flag indicating of cell is entirely beach - 1 = yes, 0 = no
        int[,] AllRock;
// Flag indicating if cell is entirely rock LMV
        double[,] PercentFullSand;
// Fractional amount of cell full of sediment LMV
        double[,] PercentFullRock;
// Fractional amount of a cell full of rock LMV
        char[,] TypeOfRock;
// Array to control weathering rates of rock along the beach LMV
        int[,] Age;
// Age since cell was deposited
        bool[,] AboveTideOLD;
// Flag indicating if a cell is above the tide mark - OLD WAY!! Not
        int[,] AboveWater;
// Is cell above water mark? 1 = yes, 0 = no (WaterHeight)

        int[,] ShorelineCell;
// 1 = yes, 0 = no
        int[,] Linear_Shoreline;

        // Computational Arrays (determined for each time step)
        int[] X;
// X Position of ith beach element
        int[] Y;
// Y Position of ith beach element
        int[] initialX;
        int[] initialY;
        int[] XBehind;
// Cell that is "behind" X[i] LMV
        int[] YBehind;
// Cell that is "behind" Y[i] LMV
        int[] XRock;
// X Position of ith rock element LMV
        int[] YRock;
// Y Position of ith rock element LMV
        int[] XRockBehind;
// Cell that is "behind" XRock[i] LMV
        int[] YRockBehind;
// Cell that is "behind" YRock[i] LMV
        char[] InShadow;
// Is ith beach element in shadow?
        double[,] InShadow_domain;
        double[] ShorelineAngle;
// Angle between cell and right (z+1) neighbor
        double[] SurroundingAngle;
// Angle between left and right neighbors
        char[] UpWind;
// Upwind or downwind condition used to calculate sediment transport
        double[] VolumeIn;
// Sediment volume into ith beach element
        double[] VolumeOut;
// Sediment volume out of ith beach element
        double[] VolumeAcrossBorder;
// Sediment volume across border of ith beach element in m^3/day LMV

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        double[] ActualVolumeAcross;
// Sediment volume that actually gets passed across border LMV -
amount sed is limited by volumes across border upstream and downstream
        char[] DirectionAcrossBorder;
// Flag to indicate if transport across border is L or R LMV
        char[] FlowThroughCell;
// Is flow through ith cell Left, Right, Convergent, or Divergent LMV
        double[] DistanceToBeach;
// Distance in meters from rock to beach LMV
        double[] MinDistanceToBeach;
// From a rock cell j, min distance (in meters) to closest beach LMV
        int[] ClosestBeach = new int[MaxBeachLength];
// i position of closest rock to beach LMV
        double[] AmountWeathered;
// Amount of rock weathered from rock cell j LMV

        // Depth
        double Depth;
// Depth of current cell
        double Distance;
// distance from shore to intercept of equilib. profile and overall
slope (m)
        double Yintercept;
// Y position of intercept of equilib. profile and overall slope
        double DepthEffective;
// depth at x intercept, Brad: where slope becomes < equilib slope, so
sand stays piled against shoreface

        // CM - Adding elevation volumes
        int[,] LowestX;
// X position of lowest neighbour
        int[,] LowestY;
// Y position of lowest neighbour
        double CriticalAngle = 34;
// Specified Angle of Repose
        double[,] SedimentChange;
// Used to keep track of sed. vol. added and removed from each cell
during diffusion
        double[,] VolumeChange;
        double[,] DepthEffectiveArray;
        double heighestElev = 0;
        double WDThreshold = 0.005;
// Wet/Dry Threshold - Amount cell needs to be above/below water level
for it to be entirely above/below based on local SFS

        double TotalSediment = 0;
// Total amount of sediment in the DEM at the start of the simulation
        double[] Angle_1;

        // CM - Graphics
        double zElevMin;
        double zElevMax;
        double zDepthvMin;
        double zDepthMax;

        // CM - 2D structure
        double[,] Elevation;
// Elevation of beach
        double[,] WaterDepth0;
// Water depth from DEM (ref: 0m)
        double[,] DepthShelf;
// Depth from '0' to Shelf

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        double[,] DomainDepthCS;
// Depth to domain bottom from continental shelf
        double maxDomainDepth;
// Used as a reference point for elevation, cell depth etc (contant
flat)
        double[,] DepthShelfMaterial;
// Depth of material to shelf from 0 level (will sometimes be same as
depthShelf)
        double[,] TElevationCS;
// Total elevation of material from continental shelf (used to work
out volume!)
        double[,] TElevationDomain;
// Total elevation of material from bottom of the domain (used to work
out above/below water)
        double[,] Volume;
// Volume of material in each cell
        double[,] OriginalVol;
        double[,] PreviousVolume;
        double TotalVolumeStart = 0;
        double TotalVolAboveStart = 0;
        double TotalVolumeEnd = 0;
        double TotalVolAboveEnd = 0;
        int[] XSt;
        int[] YSt;
        double WetDryThreshold;
// Hight of cell above/below water to consider it a wet/dry cell

        int[] direction;
// 1 = Top  2 = Top right  3 = Right  4 = Bottom Right  5 = Bottom  6
= Bottom left  7 = Left  8 = Top Left
        int[] numCells;
// How many cells from the coastline do we extend out for the
shoreface slope?
        double[] localSFS;

// Recording Output Data
        double Vol_Wet = 0;
        double Cells_Wet = 0;
        double Vol_Dry = 0;
        double Cells_Dry = 0;

        double Start_Vol_Wet = 0;
        double Start_Cells_Wet = 0;
        double Start_Vol_Dry = 0;
        double Start_Cells_Dry = 0;

// Batch
        static int Restart_count;
// Counter for restart loop
        static int autorestart = 1;
// 1 = yes autorestart, 0 = no autorestart
        static int maxRuns = 1;

// De-debugging Parameters
        int debug0 = 0; // misc. printf's--don't leave them in
        int debug1 = 0; // Find Next Beach Cell
        int debug1a = 0; // Find Next Rock Cell LMV
        int debug1b = 0; // More find next cell LMV
        int debug1c = 0; // More find next rock cell LMV
        int debug2 = 0; // Shadow Routine
        int debug2a = 0; // In-Depth Shadow Results

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

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int debug2b = 0;           // More shadow results
int debug3 = 0;           // Determine Angles
int debug4 = 0;           // Upwind/Downwind
int debug5 = 0;           // Sediment Transport Decisions
int debug6 = 0;           // Sediment Trans Calculations
int debug6a = 0;          // Volume In/Out/AcrossBorder LMV
int debug7 = 0;           // Transport Sweep (move sediment)
int debug7a = 0;          // Slope Calcs
int debug8 = 0;           // Full/Empty
int debug80 = 0;          // Temp Full
int debug8a = 0;          // More Full/Empty LMV
int debug9 = 0;           // FixBeach
int debug9a = 0;          // More FixBeach LMV
int debug10 = 0;          // Distance to Beach LMV
int debug11 = 0;          // Min Distance to Beach & Closest
Beach LMV
int debug12 = 0;          // Weathering Rate LMV
int debug12a = 0;         // Percent Fines lost LMV
int debug13 = 0;          // Sed Flow LMV
int debug14 = 0;          // Actual Volume Across Border & PFS
LMV
int debug15 = 0;          // Erosion Rate per Year LMV
int debug16 = 0;          // Total Percent Full LMV
int debug17 = 0;          // graphics stuff
int debug18 = 0;          // reading wave data AB
int debugNearest = 0;     // graphs a pixel at nearest beach
cell to a given rock cell (for weathering)
string DebugFilePath = "OUTPUT_FILES/DebugFile.out";
// Debugs above write to this file
string TestFilePath = "OUTPUT_FILES/TestFile.out";
// Used to print values for quick checks/debugging
int FlagLandslide = 0;

double lost = 0;
int hit = 0;
int FlowZeroCount = 0;

// END CM CEM Variables //

//Buttons and Menus
private System.Windows.Forms.Button loadDataButton;
private System.Windows.Forms.MainMenu mainMenu1;
private System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem menuItemFile;
private System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem menuItemFileOpen;
private System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem menuItemFileSave;
private System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem menuItemFileSaveAs;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBar statusBar1;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel
IterationStatusPanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel TimeStatusPanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel QwStatusPanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel QsStatusPanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel InfoStatusPanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel waveAnglePanel;
private System.Windows.Forms.Button startButton;
private System.Windows.Forms.Button quitSaveButton;
private System.Windows.Forms.Button updateGraphicsButton;
private System.Windows.Forms.Panel UpdateGraphPanel;

```

```

        private Smallwisdom.Windows.Forms.ZoomPanImageBox
zoomPanImageBox1;
        private TrackBar trackBar1;
        private GroupBox Graphic_ContrastSlider;
        private Label ContrastLab;
        private GroupBox ZoomSlider;
        private Label ZoomLab;
        private TrackBar trackBar2;
        private CheckBox ViewTabsCheck;
        private Button pauseButton;
        private Button resumeButton;
        private OpenFileDialog openFileDialog1;
        private TabPage DescriptionTab;
        private TabPage WaveTab;
        private TextBox WPLoadTB;
        private TextBox WALoadTB;
        private TextBox WHLoadTB;
        private TextBox WPeriodTB;
        private TextBox WAngleTB;
        private TextBox WHeightTB;
        private TextBox WaveFileTB;
        private Label WPLoadLab;
        private Label WALoadLab;
        private Label WHLoadLab;
        private Label ManWavLabel;
        private CheckBox ManWavTick;
        private Label WavSourceTitle;
        private Label ManWavTitle;
        private Label LoadWaveTitle;
        private Label BinnedLabel;
        private CheckBox BinnedTick;
        private Label WaveTickLabel;
        private CheckBox WaveFileTick;
        private Label WPeriodLabel;
        private Label WAngleLabel;
        private Label WHeightLabel;
        private Button WaveBrowseButton;
        private Label WaveFileLabel;
        private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer
shapeContainer2;
        private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShape2;
        private TabPage DEMTab;
        private Label DEMDimTitle;
        private Label DEMSourceTitle;
        private TextBox RowsTB;
        private Label RowLabel;
        private Label ColLabel;
        private TextBox ColumnTB;
        private Label BlockLabel;
        private CheckBox BlockTick;
        private Label WigglyLabel;
        private CheckBox WigglyTick;
        private Label NormLabel;
        private CheckBox NormTick;
        private Label CompDEMLabel;
        private CheckBox CompDEMTick;
        private Label DEMLabel;
        private CheckBox DEMTick;
        private Button DEMBrowseButton;
        private TextBox DEMTextBox;
        private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer
shapeContainer1;

```

```

private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShapel;
private TabControl MainWindowTabs;
private TabPage TideTab;
private TextBox LowTideTB;
private Label LowTideLab;
private TextBox HighTideTB;
private Label HighTideLab;
private TabPage ErosionTab;
private TextBox ErosRateTB;
private Label ErosRateLab;
private TextBox SlowWeatherTB;
private Label SlowWeatherLab;
private TextBox RockWeatherTB;
private Label RockWeatherLab;
private TextBox PercentSlowTB;
private Label PercentSlowLab;
private TextBox PercentFastTB;
private Label PercentFastLab;
private TextBox FastWeatherTB;
private Label FastWeatherLab;
private TabPage SourceSinkTab;
private Label WeatheringTitle;
private Label ErosionTitle;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer
shapeContainer3;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShape4;
private Label SinksTab;
private Label SourcesTab;
private TextBox NumSourceTB;
private Label NumSourceLab;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer
shapeContainer4;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShape5;
private TextBox NumSinkTB;
private Label NumSinkLab;
private CheckBox SinkTick;
private Label SinkTickLab;
private CheckBox SourceTick;
private Label SourceTickLab;
private CheckBox ColSinkTick;
private Label ColSinkLab;
private TextBox YSinkTB;
private Label YSinkLab;
private TextBox XSinkTB;
private Label XSinkLab;
private TextBox YSourceTB;
private Label YSourceLab;
private TextBox XSourceTB;
private Label XSourceLab;
private CheckBox ColSourceTick;
private Label ColSourceLab;
private TextBox SinkinessTB;
private Label SinkinessLab;
private ToolTip CoordTT;
private Label DoTidesLabel;
private CheckBox DoTidesTick;
private Button SeeTabsButton;
private TabPage Outputs;
private TextBox DescripTB;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphics;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphicsRock;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphicsSand;

```

```

private MenuItem menuItemGraphicsXY;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphicInitialXY;
private TextBox SaveFreqTB;
private Label SaveFreqLab;
private TextBox OutputNameTB;
private Label OutputNameLab;
private Label label1;
private Label orText;
private Label InitPertLab;
private CheckBox InitPertTick;
private Label PertLab;
private CheckBox PertTick;
private TextBox RunLengthTB;
private Label RunLengthLab;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphicDepth;
private MenuItem menuItemGraphicVolume;
private Label SLRTitle;
private Label TidesTitle;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer
shapeContainer5;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShape6;
private TextBox SLR_TB;
private Label SLRLab;
private Label DoSLRLab;
private CheckBox DoSLRTick;
private TextBox RateSLR_TB;
private Label RateSLRLab;
private Label UALab;
private CheckBox UA_WaveTick;
private MenuItem menuItemShadow;
private TextBox AsymTB;
private TextBox HighTB;
private Label AsymLab;
private Label HighLab;
private Label label2;
private Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape lineShape3;
private Label label3;
private Label StepSLR_Lab;
private CheckBox StepSLR_Tick;
private Button SandOutputButton;

// The main entry point for the application.

[STAThread]

// Start the program
static void Main()
{
    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        string dir_name = Environment.CurrentDirectory;
        string[] split = dir_name.Split(new[] { "_Split" },
StringSplitOptions.None);
        //string[] split_2 = split[1].Split(new[] { '\\' },
StringSplitOptions.None);

        Restart_count = Convert.ToInt32(split[1]);
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //string Restart_Count_FILE =
"INPUT_FILES/Restart_Count_FILE.txt";

        //StreamReader reader = new
StreamReader(Restart_Count_FILE);
        //Restart_Count = Convert.ToInt32(reader.ReadToEnd());
        //reader.Close();

        //StreamWriter writer = new
StreamWriter(Restart_Count_FILE);
        //writer.Write(Restart_count + 1);
        //writer.Close();

        Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count);
        Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Simulation");
    }

    Application.Run(new Form1());
}
public Form1()
{
    InitializeComponent();
}
private void Form1_Load(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    zoomPanImageBox1.Height = this.Height - 225;
    zoomPanImageBox1.Width = this.Width - 20;

    HttpWebRequest req;
    HttpWebResponse res;

    try
    {
        req =
(HttpWebRequest)WebRequest.Create("http://www.coulthard.org.uk/");
        res = (HttpWebResponse)req.GetResponse();
    }
    catch
    {
        /// do nothing.
    }

    this.Text = basetext;
}
protected override void Dispose(bool disposing)
{
    if (disposing)
    {
        if (components != null)
        {
            components.Dispose();
        }
    }
    base.Dispose(disposing);
}

// Form Show/Close
private void Form1_Shown(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    // Batch

```

```

        if (autorestart == 1)
        {
            if (Restart_count > 1)
            {
                loadDataButton.PerformClick();
            }
        }
    }
    private void Form1_FormClosing(object sender,
    FormClosingEventArgs e)
    {
        // Batch
        if (autorestart == 1)
        {
            e.Cancel = false;
        }
        else
        {
            pauseButton_Click(pauseButton, EventArgs.Empty);

            endTime = DateTime.Now.TimeOfDay;
            speed = (endTime - startTime);
            DialogResult Result = MessageBox.Show("Program at " +
(counter - 1) + " days \nDo you want to exit? \n\nSpeed: " +
speed.Hours + ":" + speed.Minutes + ":" + speed.Seconds +
"(hh:mm:ss)", " ", MessageBoxButtons.YesNo, MessageBoxIcon.Warning,
MessageBoxDefaultButton.Button1,
MessageBoxOptions.DefaultDesktopOnly);

            if (Result == DialogResult.Yes)
            {
                StreamWriter EndVol = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/EndVol" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

                EndVol.Write("ncols " + ColumnTB.Text +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + RowsTB.Text + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);

                for (int yyyy = ymax - 1; yyyy >= 0; yyyy--)
                {
                    for (int xxxx = 0; xxxx < pbEnd; xxxx++)
                    {
                        EndVol.Write(Volume[xxxx, yyyy] + " ");
                        TotalVolumeEnd += Volume[xxxx, yyyy];

                        if (AboveWater[xxxx, yyyy] == 1)
                        {
                            TotalVolAboveEnd += Volume[xxxx,
yyyy];
                        }
                    }
                    EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine);
                }
                EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine + TotalVolumeEnd
+ ", " + TotalVolAboveEnd);

                EndVol.Close();
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```
        StreamWriter XY_End = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/XY_End_" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

        for (int Loop = 0; Loop < X.Length; Loop++)
        {
            XY_End.Write(X[Loop] + ", " + Y[Loop] +
Environment.NewLine);
        }
        XY_End.Close();

        e.Cancel = false;
    }
    else
    {
        resumeButton_Click(resumeButton, EventArgs.Empty);
    }
}

// Set-up the GUI
private void InitializeComponent()
{
    this.components = new System.ComponentModel.Container();
    this.loadDataButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
    this.mainMenu1 = new
System.Windows.Forms.MainMenu(this.components);
    this.menuItemFile = new System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemFileOpen = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemFileSaveAs = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemFileSave = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphics = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicsRock = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicsSand = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicsXY = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicDepth = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemGraphicVolume = new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.menuItemShadow = new System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem();
    this.statusBar1 = new System.Windows.Forms.StatusBar();
    this.InfoStatusPanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
    this.IterationStatusPanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
    this.TimeStatusPanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
    this.QwStatusPanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
    this.QsStatusPanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
```

```

        this.waveAnglePanel = new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel();
        this.startButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.quitSaveButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.updateGraphicsButton = new
System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.UpdateGraphPanel = new System.Windows.Forms.Panel();
        this.SandOutputButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.ViewTabsCheck = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.trackBar1 = new System.Windows.Forms.TrackBar();
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider = new
System.Windows.Forms.GroupBox();
        this.ContrastLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ZoomSlider = new System.Windows.Forms.GroupBox();
        this.ZoomLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.trackBar2 = new System.Windows.Forms.TrackBar();
        this.pauseButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.resumeButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.openFileDialog1 = new
System.Windows.Forms.OpenFileDialog();
        this.DescriptionTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
        this.DescripTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WaveTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
        this.AsymTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.HighTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.AsymLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.HighLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.label2 = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.UALab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.UA_WaveTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.labell1 = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WaveBrowseButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.WaveFileTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WPLoadTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WALoadTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WHLoadTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WPeriodTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WAngleTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WHeightTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.WPLoadLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WALoadLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WHLoadLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ManWavLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ManWavTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.WavSourceTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ManWavTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.LoadWaveTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.BinnedLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.BinnedTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.WaveTickLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WaveFileTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.WPeriodLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WAngleLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WHeightLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.WaveFileLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.shapeContainer2 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer();
        this.lineShape3 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
        this.lineShape2 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
        this.DEMTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();

```

```

this.label3 = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.InitPertLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.InitPertTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.PertLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.PertTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.orText = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DEMDimTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DEMSourceTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.RowsTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.RowLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.ColLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.ColumnTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.BlockLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.BlockTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.WigglyLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.WigglyTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.NormLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.NormTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.CompDEMLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.CompDEMTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.DEMLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DEMTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.DEMBrowseButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
this.DEMTextBox = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.shapeContainer1 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer();
this.lineShapel = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
this.MainWindowTabs = new
System.Windows.Forms.TabControl();
this.TideTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
this.StepSLR_Lab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.StepSLR_Tick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.DoSLRLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DoSLRTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.RateSLR_TB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.RateSLRLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.SLR_TB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.SLRLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.SLRTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.TidesTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DoTidesLabel = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.DoTidesTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
this.HighTideTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.HighTideLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.LowTideTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.LowTideLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.shapeContainer5 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer();
this.lineShape6 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
this.ErosionTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
this.WeatheringTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.ErosionTitle = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.RockWeatherTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.PercentSlowTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.PercentSlowLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.PercentFastTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.PercentFastLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.FastWeatherTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
this.FastWeatherLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
this.SlowWeatherTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();

```

```

        this.SlowWeatherLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ErosRateTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.ErosRateLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.shapeContainer3 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer();
        this.lineShape4 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
        this.RockWeatherLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SourceSinkTab = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
        this.SinkinessTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.SinkinessLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.YSourceTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.YSourceLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.XSourceTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.XSourceLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ColSourceTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.ColSourceLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.YSinkTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.YSinkLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.XSinkTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.XSinkLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.ColSinkTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.ColSinkLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SinkTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.SinkTickLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SourceTick = new System.Windows.Forms.CheckBox();
        this.SourceTickLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.NumSinkTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.NumSinkLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SinksTab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SourcesTab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.NumSourceTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.NumSourceLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.shapeContainer4 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.ShapeContainer();
        this.lineShape5 = new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.LineShape();
        this.Outputs = new System.Windows.Forms.TabPage();
        this.RunLengthTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.RunLengthLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.OutputNameTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.OutputNameLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.SaveFreqTB = new System.Windows.Forms.TextBox();
        this.SaveFreqLab = new System.Windows.Forms.Label();
        this.CoordTT = new
System.Windows.Forms.ToolTip(this.components);
        this.SeeTabsButton = new System.Windows.Forms.Button();
        this.zoomPanImageBox1 = new
Smallwisdom.Windows.Forms.ZoomPanImageBox();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.InfoStatusPanel)).Begin
Init();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.IterationStatusPanel)
).BeginInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.TimeStatusPanel)).Begin
Init();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.QwStatusPanel)).Begin
Init();

```

```

((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.QsStatusPanel)).BeginInit();

((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.waveAnglePanel)).BeginInit();
    this.UpdateGraphPanel.SuspendLayout();

((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.trackBar1)).BeginInit();
    this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.SuspendLayout();
    this.ZoomSlider.SuspendLayout();

((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.trackBar2)).BeginInit();
    this.DescriptionTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.WaveTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.DEMTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.MainWindowTabs.SuspendLayout();
    this.TideTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.ErosionTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.SourceSinkTab.SuspendLayout();
    this.Outputs.SuspendLayout();
    this.SuspendLayout();
    //
    // loadDataButton
    //
    this.loadDataButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
    this.loadDataButton.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(6,
291);
    this.loadDataButton.Name = "loadDataButton";
    this.loadDataButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(100,
24);
    this.loadDataButton.TabIndex = 7;
    this.loadDataButton.Text = "Load Data";
    this.loadDataButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.loadDataButton_Click);
    //
    // mainMenu1
    //
    this.mainMenu1.MenuItems.AddRange(new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem[] {
    this.menuItemFile,
    this.menuItemGraphics});
    //
    // menuItemFile
    //
    this.menuItemFile.Index = 0;
    this.menuItemFile.MenuItems.AddRange(new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem[] {
    this.menuItemFileOpen,
    this.menuItemFileSaveAs,
    this.menuItemFileSave});
    this.menuItemFile.Text = "FILE";
    //
    // menuItemFileOpen
    //
    this.menuItemFileOpen.Index = 0;
    this.menuItemFileOpen.Text = "Open";

```

```

        this.menuItemFileOpen.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemFileOpen_Click);
        //
        // menuItemFileSaveAs
        //
        this.menuItemFileSaveAs.Index = 1;
        this.menuItemFileSaveAs.Text = "Save As";
        this.menuItemFileSaveAs.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemFileSave_Click);
        //
        // menuItemFileSave
        //
        this.menuItemFileSave.Index = 2;
        this.menuItemFileSave.Text = "Save";
        this.menuItemFileSave.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemFileSave_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphics
        //
        this.menuItemGraphics.Index = 1;
        this.menuItemGraphics.MenuItems.AddRange(new
System.Windows.Forms.MenuItem[] {
        this.menuItemGraphicsRock,
        this.menuItemGraphicsSand,
        this.menuItemGraphicsXY,
        this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY,
        this.menuItemGraphicDepth,
        this.menuItemGraphicVolume,
        this.menuItemShadow});
        this.menuItemGraphics.Text = "GRAPHICS";
        //
        // menuItemGraphicsRock
        //
        this.menuItemGraphicsRock.Index = 0;
        this.menuItemGraphicsRock.Text = "Ero / Depo";
        this.menuItemGraphicsRock.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicsRock_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphicsSand
        //
        this.menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked = true;
        this.menuItemGraphicsSand.Index = 1;
        this.menuItemGraphicsSand.Text = "Sand";
        this.menuItemGraphicsSand.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicsSand_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphicsXY
        //
        this.menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked = true;
        this.menuItemGraphicsXY.Index = 2;
        this.menuItemGraphicsXY.Text = "XY Coastline";
        this.menuItemGraphicsXY.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicsXY_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphicInitialXY
        //
        this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Index = 3;
        this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Text = "Initial XY";
        this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicInitialXY_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphicDepth

```

```

        //
        this.menuItemGraphicDepth.Enabled = false;
        this.menuItemGraphicDepth.Index = 4;
        this.menuItemGraphicDepth.Text = "Depth";
        this.menuItemGraphicDepth.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicDepth_Click);
        //
        // menuItemGraphicVolume
        //
        this.menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked = true;
        this.menuItemGraphicVolume.Index = 5;
        this.menuItemGraphicVolume.Text = "Volume";
        this.menuItemGraphicVolume.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemGraphicVolume_Click);
        //
        // menuItemShadow
        //
        this.menuItemShadow.Index = 6;
        this.menuItemShadow.Text = "Shadow";
        this.menuItemShadow.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.menuItemShadow_Click);
        //
        // statusBar1
        //
        this.statusBar1.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(0,
343);
        this.statusBar1.Name = "statusBar1";
        this.statusBar1.Panels.AddRange(new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanel[] {
        this.InfoStatusPanel,
        this.IterationStatusPanel,
        this.TimeStatusPanel,
        this.QwStatusPanel,
        this.QsStatusPanel,
        this.waveAnglePanel});
        this.statusBar1.ShowPanels = true;
        this.statusBar1.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1088, 19);
        this.statusBar1.SizingGrip = false;
        this.statusBar1.TabIndex = 144;
        this.statusBar1.Text = "statusBar1";
        this.statusBar1.PanelClick += new
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanelClickEventHandler(this.statusBar1_P
anelClick);
        //
        // InfoStatusPanel
        //
        this.InfoStatusPanel.Name = "InfoStatusPanel";
        this.InfoStatusPanel.Text = "info";
        this.InfoStatusPanel.Width = 200;
        //
        // IterationStatusPanel
        //
        this.IterationStatusPanel.Name = "IterationStatusPanel";
        this.IterationStatusPanel.Text = "iterations";
        this.IterationStatusPanel.Width = 120;
        //
        // TimeStatusPanel
        //
        this.TimeStatusPanel.Name = "TimeStatusPanel";
        this.TimeStatusPanel.Text = "time";
        this.TimeStatusPanel.Width = 120;
        //

```

```

// QwStatusPanel
//
this.QwStatusPanel.Name = "QwStatusPanel";
this.QwStatusPanel.Text = "Qw";
this.QwStatusPanel.Width = 120;
//
// QsStatusPanel
//
this.QsStatusPanel.Name = "QsStatusPanel";
this.QsStatusPanel.Text = "Qs";
this.QsStatusPanel.Width = 120;
//
// waveAnglePanel
//
this.waveAnglePanel.Name = "waveAnglePanel";
this.waveAnglePanel.Text = "Wave Angle";
//
// startButton
//
this.startButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles
s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
this.startButton.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(112,
291);

this.startButton.Name = "startButton";
this.startButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(88, 24);
this.startButton.TabIndex = 146;
this.startButton.Text = "Start!";
this.startButton.Visible = false;
this.startButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.main_loop);
//
// quitSaveButton
//
this.quitSaveButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles
s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
this.quitSaveButton.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(341, 291);
this.quitSaveButton.Name = "quitSaveButton";
this.quitSaveButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(100,
24);

this.quitSaveButton.TabIndex = 147;
this.quitSaveButton.Text = "Quit and Save";
this.quitSaveButton.Visible = false;
this.quitSaveButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.quitSaveButton_Click);
//
// updateGraphicsButton
//
this.updateGraphicsButton.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(3, 4);
this.updateGraphicsButton.Name = "updateGraphicsButton";
this.updateGraphicsButton.Size = new
System.Drawing.Size(112, 40);
this.updateGraphicsButton.TabIndex = 144;
this.updateGraphicsButton.Text = "Update Graphics";
this.updateGraphicsButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.updateGraphics_Click_1);
//
// UpdateGraphPanel
//

```

```

        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Anchor =
        ((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles
        s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.BorderStyle =
        System.Windows.Forms.BorderStyle.Fixed3D;
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Controls.Add(this.SandOutputButton);

this.UpdateGraphPanel.Controls.Add(this.updateGraphicsButton);
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Location = new
        System.Drawing.Point(8, 239);
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Name = "UpdateGraphPanel";
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(854,
45);

        this.UpdateGraphPanel.TabIndex = 145;
        this.UpdateGraphPanel.Visible = false;
        //
        // SandOutputButton
        //
        this.SandOutputButton.Location = new
        System.Drawing.Point(121, 4);
        this.SandOutputButton.Name = "SandOutputButton";
        this.SandOutputButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(112,
40);

        this.SandOutputButton.TabIndex = 145;
        this.SandOutputButton.Text = "PercentFullSand Output";
        this.SandOutputButton.Click += new
        System.EventHandler(this.SandOutputButton_Click);
        //
        // ViewTabsCheck
        //
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Anchor =
        ((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles
        s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
        this.ViewTabsCheck.AutoSize = true;
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Checked = true;
        this.ViewTabsCheck.CheckState =
        System.Windows.Forms.CheckState.Checked;
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Location = new
        System.Drawing.Point(455, 469);
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Name = "ViewTabsCheck";
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(82, 17);
        this.ViewTabsCheck.TabIndex = 151;
        this.ViewTabsCheck.Text = "View Tabs?";
        this.ViewTabsCheck.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        //
        // trackBar1
        //
        this.trackBar1.AutoSize = false;
        this.trackBar1.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(54, 9);
        this.trackBar1.Name = "trackBar1";
        this.trackBar1.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.trackBar1.TabIndex = 149;
        this.trackBar1.Scroll += new
        System.EventHandler(this.trackBar1_Scroll);
        //
        // Graphic_ContrastSlider
        //

this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Controls.Add(this.ContrastLab);
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Controls.Add(this.trackBar1);
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Location = new
        System.Drawing.Point(8, -3);

```

```

        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Name =
"Graphic_ContrastSlider";
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Size = new
System.Drawing.Size(164, 35);
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.TabIndex = 151;
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.TabStop = false;
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.Visible = false;
        //
        // ContrastLab
        //
        this.ContrastLab.AutoSize = true;
        this.ContrastLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(8,
14);

        this.ContrastLab.Name = "ContrastLab";
        this.ContrastLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(46, 13);
        this.ContrastLab.TabIndex = 152;
        this.ContrastLab.Text = "Contrast";
        //
        // ZoomSlider
        //
        this.ZoomSlider.Controls.Add(this.ZoomLab);
        this.ZoomSlider.Controls.Add(this.trackBar2);
        this.ZoomSlider.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(176, -
3);

        this.ZoomSlider.Name = "ZoomSlider";
        this.ZoomSlider.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(156, 35);
        this.ZoomSlider.TabIndex = 152;
        this.ZoomSlider.TabStop = false;
        this.ZoomSlider.Visible = false;
        //
        // ZoomLab
        //
        this.ZoomLab.AutoSize = true;
        this.ZoomLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(8, 13);
        this.ZoomLab.Name = "ZoomLab";
        this.ZoomLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(34, 13);
        this.ZoomLab.TabIndex = 154;
        this.ZoomLab.Text = "Zoom";
        //
        // trackBar2
        //
        this.trackBar2.AutoSize = false;
        this.trackBar2.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(44, 9);
        this.trackBar2.Minimum = 1;
        this.trackBar2.Name = "trackBar2";
        this.trackBar2.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.trackBar2.TabIndex = 153;
        this.trackBar2.Value = 5;
        this.trackBar2.Scroll += new
System.EventHandler(this.trackBar2_Scroll);
        //
        // pauseButton
        //
        this.pauseButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyle
s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
        this.pauseButton.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(206,
291);

        this.pauseButton.Name = "pauseButton";
        this.pauseButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(66, 24);
        this.pauseButton.TabIndex = 153;
        this.pauseButton.Text = "Pause";

```

```

        this.pauseButton.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.pauseButton.Visible = false;
        this.pauseButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.pauseButton_Click);
        //
        // resumeButton
        //
        this.resumeButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyle
s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
        this.resumeButton.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(278,
291);

        this.resumeButton.Name = "resumeButton";
        this.resumeButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(57, 24);
        this.resumeButton.TabIndex = 154;
        this.resumeButton.Text = "Resume";
        this.resumeButton.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.resumeButton.Visible = false;
        this.resumeButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.resumeButton_Click);
        //
        // DescriptionTab
        //
        this.DescriptionTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.Color.White;
        this.DescriptionTab.Controls.Add(this.DescripTB);
        this.DescriptionTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4,
22);

        this.DescriptionTab.Name = "DescriptionTab";
        this.DescriptionTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027,
255);

        this.DescriptionTab.TabIndex = 5;
        this.DescriptionTab.Text = "Description";
        //
        // DescripTB
        //
        this.DescripTB.BorderStyle =
System.Windows.Forms.BorderStyle.None;
        this.DescripTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(9, 9);
        this.DescripTB.Multiline = true;
        this.DescripTB.Name = "DescripTB";
        this.DescripTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(825, 221);
        this.DescripTB.TabIndex = 0;
        //
        // WaveTab
        //
        this.WaveTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.AsymTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.HighTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.AsymLab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.HighLab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.label2);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.UALab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.UA_WaveTick);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.label1);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WaveBrowseButton);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WaveFileTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WPLoadTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WALoadTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WHLoadTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WPeriodTB);

```

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        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WAngleTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WHeightTB);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WPLoadLab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WALoadLab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WHLoadLab);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.ManWavLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.ManWavTick);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WavSourceTitle);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.ManWavTitle);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.LoadWaveTitle);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.BinnedLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.BinnedTick);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WaveTickLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WaveFileTick);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WPeriodLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WAngleLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WHeightLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.WaveFileLabel);
        this.WaveTab.Controls.Add(this.shapeContainer2);
        this.WaveTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4, 22);
        this.WaveTab.Name = "WaveTab";
        this.WaveTab.Padding = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(3);
        this.WaveTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027, 255);
        this.WaveTab.TabIndex = 10;
        this.WaveTab.Text = "Wave Climate";
        //
        // AsymTB
        //
        this.AsymTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(418, 193);
        this.AsymTB.Name = "AsymTB";
        this.AsymTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.AsymTB.TabIndex = 193;
        this.AsymTB.Text = "-9999";
        //
        // HighTB
        //
        this.HighTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(418, 230);
        this.HighTB.Name = "HighTB";
        this.HighTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.HighTB.TabIndex = 192;
        this.HighTB.Text = "-9999";
        //
        // AsymLab
        //
        this.AsymLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.AsymLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.AsymLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(280,
190);
        this.AsymLab.Name = "AsymLab";
        this.AsymLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(132, 24);
        this.AsymLab.TabIndex = 191;
        this.AsymLab.Text = "Wave Asymmetry (%):";
        this.AsymLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // HighLab
        //

```

```

        this.HighLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.HighLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.HighLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(283,
227);

        this.HighLab.Name = "HighLab";
        this.HighLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(129, 24);
        this.HighLab.TabIndex = 190;
        this.HighLab.Text = "Wave Highness (%)";
        this.HighLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // label2
        //
        this.label2.BackColor = System.Drawing.Color.Transparent;
        this.label2.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Italic))));
        this.label2.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.label2.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(183, 131);
        this.label2.Name = "label2";
        this.label2.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(34, 18);
        this.label2.TabIndex = 189;
        this.label2.Text = "OR";
        this.label2.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // UALab
        //
        this.UALab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.UALab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.UALab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(25, 96);
        this.UALab.Name = "UALab";
        this.UALab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189, 32);
        this.UALab.TabIndex = 188;
        this.UALab.Text = "Wave Asymmetry and Highness";
        this.UALab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // UA_WaveTick
        //
        this.UA_WaveTick.Checked = true;
        this.UA_WaveTick.CheckState =
System.Windows.Forms.CheckState.Checked;
        this.UA_WaveTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(220,
105);

        this.UA_WaveTick.Name = "UA_WaveTick";
        this.UA_WaveTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.UA_WaveTick.TabIndex = 187;
        this.UA_WaveTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.UA_WaveTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.UA_WaveTickTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // label1
        //
        this.label1.BackColor = System.Drawing.Color.Transparent;

```

```

        this.labell1.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Italic))));
        this.labell1.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.labell1.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(180, 76);
        this.labell1.Name = "labell1";
        this.labell1.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(34, 18);
        this.labell1.TabIndex = 186;
        this.labell1.Text = "OR";
        this.labell1.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // WaveBrowseButton
        //
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
        this.WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(833, 58);
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Name = "WaveBrowseButton";
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(54,
20);

        this.WaveBrowseButton.TabIndex = 105;
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Text = "Browse";
        this.WaveBrowseButton.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.WaveBrowseButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.WaveBrowseButton_Click);
        //
        // WaveFileTB
        //
        this.WaveFileTB.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.WaveFileTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(716,
59);

        this.WaveFileTB.Name = "WaveFileTB";
        this.WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WaveFileTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WaveFileTB.TabIndex = 104;
        this.WaveFileTB.Text = "WaveClimate_1.dat";
        //
        // WPLoadTB
        //
        this.WPLoadTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WPLoadTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(716,
135);

        this.WPLoadTB.Name = "WPLoadTB";
        this.WPLoadTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WPLoadTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WPLoadTB.TabIndex = 185;
        this.WPLoadTB.Text = "6.65";
        //
        // WALoadTB
        //
        this.WALoadTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WALoadTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(716,
98);

        this.WALoadTB.Name = "WALoadTB";
        this.WALoadTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WALoadTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WALoadTB.TabIndex = 184;

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```

        this.WALoadTB.Text = "67.5";
        //
        // WHLoadTB
        //
        this.WHLoadTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WHLoadTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(716,
172);
        this.WHLoadTB.Name = "WHLoadTB";
        this.WHLoadTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WHLoadTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WHLoadTB.TabIndex = 183;
        this.WHLoadTB.Text = "1.85";
        //
        // WPeriodTB
        //
        this.WPeriodTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WPeriodTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(418,
96);
        this.WPeriodTB.Name = "WPeriodTB";
        this.WPeriodTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WPeriodTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WPeriodTB.TabIndex = 159;
        this.WPeriodTB.Text = "7.3";
        //
        // WAngleTB
        //
        this.WAngleTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WAngleTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(418,
59);
        this.WAngleTB.Name = "WAngleTB";
        this.WAngleTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WAngleTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WAngleTB.TabIndex = 158;
        this.WAngleTB.Text = "45";
        //
        // WHeightTB
        //
        this.WHeightTB.Enabled = false;
        this.WHeightTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(418,
133);
        this.WHeightTB.Name = "WHeightTB";
        this.WHeightTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.WHeightTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.WHeightTB.TabIndex = 157;
        this.WHeightTB.Text = "0.9";
        //
        // WPLoadLab
        //
        this.WPLoadLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WPLoadLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(606,
131);
        this.WPLoadLab.Name = "WPLoadLab";
        this.WPLoadLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 24);
        this.WPLoadLab.TabIndex = 182;
        this.WPLoadLab.Text = "Wave Period:";
        this.WPLoadLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // WALoadLab
        //

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```

        this.WALoadLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WALoadLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(606,
96);
        this.WALoadLab.Name = "WALoadLab";
        this.WALoadLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.WALoadLab.TabIndex = 181;
        this.WALoadLab.Text = "Wave Angle:";
        this.WALoadLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // WHLoadLab
        //
        this.WHLoadLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WHLoadLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(606,
168);
        this.WHLoadLab.Name = "WHLoadLab";
        this.WHLoadLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 24);
        this.WHLoadLab.TabIndex = 180;
        this.WHLoadLab.Text = "Wave Height:";
        this.WHLoadLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ManWavLabel
        //
        this.ManWavLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.ManWavLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.ManWavLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(28,
40);
        this.ManWavLabel.Name = "ManWavLabel";
        this.ManWavLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189, 32);
        this.ManWavLabel.TabIndex = 179;
        this.ManWavLabel.Text = "Manual Entry";
        this.ManWavLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ManWavTick
        //
        this.ManWavTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(223,
51);
        this.ManWavTick.Name = "ManWavTick";
        this.ManWavTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.ManWavTick.TabIndex = 178;
        this.ManWavTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.ManWavTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.ManWavTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // WavSourceTitle
        //
        this.WavSourceTitle.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.WavSourceTitle.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(34, 10);
        this.WavSourceTitle.Name = "WavSourceTitle";
        this.WavSourceTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(226,
32);
        this.WavSourceTitle.TabIndex = 177;

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        this.WavSourceTitle.Text = "Wave Climate Source";
        this.WavSourceTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // ManWavTitle
        //
        this.ManWavTitle.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.ManWavTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(308,
10);

        this.ManWavTitle.Name = "ManWavTitle";
        this.ManWavTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(268, 32);
        this.ManWavTitle.TabIndex = 176;
        this.ManWavTitle.Text = "Enter Wave Climate";
        this.ManWavTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // LoadWaveTitle
        //
        this.LoadWaveTitle.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.LoadWaveTitle.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(597, 10);
        this.LoadWaveTitle.Name = "LoadWaveTitle";
        this.LoadWaveTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(311,
32);

        this.LoadWaveTitle.TabIndex = 175;
        this.LoadWaveTitle.Text = "Load Wave File";
        this.LoadWaveTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // BinnedLabel
        //
        this.BinnedLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Italic))));
        this.BinnedLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.BinnedLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(25,
186);

        this.BinnedLabel.Name = "BinnedLabel";
        this.BinnedLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189, 32);
        this.BinnedLabel.TabIndex = 155;
        this.BinnedLabel.Text = "Binned Wave Climate File";
        this.BinnedLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        this.BinnedLabel.Visible = false;
        //
        // BinnedTick
        //
        this.BinnedTick.Enabled = false;
        this.BinnedTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(220,
196);

        this.BinnedTick.Name = "BinnedTick";
        this.BinnedTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.BinnedTick.TabIndex = 154;
        this.BinnedTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;

```

```

        this.BinnedTick.Visible = false;
        //
        // WaveTickLabel
        //
        this.WaveTickLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.WaveTickLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WaveTickLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(25,
149);

        this.WaveTickLabel.Name = "WaveTickLabel";
        this.WaveTickLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189,
32);

        this.WaveTickLabel.TabIndex = 153;
        this.WaveTickLabel.Text = "Load Wave Climate from File";
        this.WaveTickLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // WaveFileTick
        //
        this.WaveFileTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(220,
159);

        this.WaveFileTick.Name = "WaveFileTick";
        this.WaveFileTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.WaveFileTick.TabIndex = 152;
        this.WaveFileTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.WaveFileTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.WaveFileTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // WPeriodLabel
        //
        this.WPeriodLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.WPeriodLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WPeriodLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(308,
93);

        this.WPeriodLabel.Name = "WPeriodLabel";
        this.WPeriodLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 24);
        this.WPeriodLabel.TabIndex = 110;
        this.WPeriodLabel.Text = "Wave Period:";
        this.WPeriodLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // WAngleLabel
        //
        this.WAngleLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte) 0));
        this.WAngleLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WAngleLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(308,
58);

        this.WAngleLabel.Name = "WAngleLabel";
        this.WAngleLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.WAngleLabel.TabIndex = 108;
        this.WAngleLabel.Text = "Wave Angle:";
        this.WAngleLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;

```

```

//
// WHeightLabel
//
this.WHeightLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
this.WHeightLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.WHeightLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(308,
130);
this.WHeightLabel.Name = "WHeightLabel";
this.WHeightLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 24);
this.WHeightLabel.TabIndex = 106;
this.WHeightLabel.Text = "Wave Height:";
this.WHeightLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// WaveFileLabel
//
this.WaveFileLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
this.WaveFileLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.WaveFileLabel.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(590, 56);
this.WaveFileLabel.Name = "WaveFileLabel";
this.WaveFileLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
24);
this.WaveFileLabel.TabIndex = 103;
this.WaveFileLabel.Text = "Wave Climate File:";
this.WaveFileLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// shapeContainer2
//
this.shapeContainer2.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(3, 3);
this.shapeContainer2.Margin = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(0);
this.shapeContainer2.Name = "shapeContainer2";
this.shapeContainer2.Shapes.AddRange(new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.Shape[] {
this.lineShape3,
this.lineShape2});
this.shapeContainer2.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1021,
249);
this.shapeContainer2.TabIndex = 160;
this.shapeContainer2.TabStop = false;
//
// lineShape3
//
this.lineShape3.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
this.lineShape3.Name = "lineShape3";
this.lineShape3.X1 = 574;
this.lineShape3.X2 = 574;
this.lineShape3.Y1 = 12;
this.lineShape3.Y2 = 279;
//

```

```

        // lineShape2
        //
        this.lineShape2.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
        this.lineShape2.Name = "lineShape2";
        this.lineShape2.X1 = 275;
        this.lineShape2.X2 = 275;
        this.lineShape2.Y1 = 11;
        this.lineShape2.Y2 = 278;
        //
        // DEMTab
        //
        this.DEMTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.label3);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.InitPertLab);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.InitPertTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.PertLab);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.PertTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.orText);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMDimTitle);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMSourceTitle);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.RowsTB);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.RowLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.ColLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.ColumnTB);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.BlockLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.BlockTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.WigglyLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.WigglyTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.NormLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.NormTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.CompDEMLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.CompDEMTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMLabel);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMTick);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMBrowseButton);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.DEMTextBox);
        this.DEMTab.Controls.Add(this.shapeContainer1);
        this.DEMTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4, 22);
        this.DEMTab.Name = "DEMTab";
        this.DEMTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027, 255);
        this.DEMTab.TabIndex = 0;
        this.DEMTab.Text = "DEM";
        //
        // label3
        //
        this.label3.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 6F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Italic);
        this.label3.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.label3.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(34, 126);
        this.label3.Name = "label3";
        this.label3.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(155, 32);
        this.label3.TabIndex = 185;
        this.label3.Text = "Note: Computer Generated DEMs are not
enabled in this version";
        this.label3.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // InitPertLab
        //

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        this.InitPertLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.InitPertLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.InitPertLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(186,
131);

        this.InitPertLab.Name = "InitPertLab";
        this.InitPertLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(101, 32);
        this.InitPertLab.TabIndex = 184;
        this.InitPertLab.Text = "Initial Pert:";
        this.InitPertLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // InitPertTick
        //
        this.InitPertTick.Enabled = false;
        this.InitPertTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(293,
141);

        this.InitPertTick.Name = "InitPertTick";
        this.InitPertTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.InitPertTick.TabIndex = 183;
        this.InitPertTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.InitPertTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.InitPertTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // PertLab
        //
        this.PertLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.PertLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.PertLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(186,
168);

        this.PertLab.Name = "PertLab";
        this.PertLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(101, 32);
        this.PertLab.TabIndex = 182;
        this.PertLab.Text = "Pert:";
        this.PertLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // PertTick
        //
        this.PertTick.Enabled = false;
        this.PertTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(293,
178);

        this.PertTick.Name = "PertTick";
        this.PertTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.PertTick.TabIndex = 181;
        this.PertTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.PertTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.PertTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // orText
        //
        this.orText.BackColor = System.Drawing.Color.Transparent;
        this.orText.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Italic))));
        this.orText.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.orText.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(155, 74);

```

```

        this.orText.Name = "orText";
        this.orText.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(34, 18);
        this.orText.TabIndex = 177;
        this.orText.Text = "OR";
        this.orText.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // DEMDimTitle
        //
        this.DEMDimTitle.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.DEMDimTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(481,
6);

        this.DEMDimTitle.Name = "DEMDimTitle";
        this.DEMDimTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(369, 32);
        this.DEMDimTitle.TabIndex = 175;
        this.DEMDimTitle.Text = "DEM Dimensions";
        this.DEMDimTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // DEMSourceTitle
        //
        this.DEMSourceTitle.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.DEMSourceTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(9,
6);

        this.DEMSourceTitle.Name = "DEMSourceTitle";
        this.DEMSourceTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(454,
32);

        this.DEMSourceTitle.TabIndex = 174;
        this.DEMSourceTitle.Text = "DEM Source";
        this.DEMSourceTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // RowsTB
        //
        this.RowsTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(638, 86);
        this.RowsTB.Name = "RowsTB";
        this.RowsTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.RowsTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(142, 20);
        this.RowsTB.TabIndex = 172;
        this.RowsTB.Text = "200";
        //
        // RowLabel
        //
        this.RowLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F);
        this.RowLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(502,
79);

        this.RowLabel.Name = "RowLabel";
        this.RowLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(130, 32);
        this.RowLabel.TabIndex = 171;
        this.RowLabel.Text = "Number of Rows:";
        this.RowLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ColLabel
        //

```

```

        this.ColLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F);
        this.ColLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(499,
41);
        this.ColLabel.Name = "ColLabel";
        this.ColLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(133, 32);
        this.ColLabel.TabIndex = 170;
        this.ColLabel.Text = "Number of Columns:";
        this.ColLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ColumnTB
        //
        this.ColumnTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(638,
47);
        this.ColumnTB.Name = "ColumnTB";
        this.ColumnTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.ColumnTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(142, 20);
        this.ColumnTB.TabIndex = 169;
        this.ColumnTB.Text = "300";
        //
        // BlockLabel
        //
        this.BlockLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.BlockLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.BlockLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(227,
241);
        this.BlockLabel.Name = "BlockLabel";
        this.BlockLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(60, 32);
        this.BlockLabel.TabIndex = 168;
        this.BlockLabel.Text = "Block:";
        this.BlockLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // BlockTick
        //
        this.BlockTick.Enabled = false;
        this.BlockTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(293,
251);
        this.BlockTick.Name = "BlockTick";
        this.BlockTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.BlockTick.TabIndex = 167;
        this.BlockTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.BlockTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.BlockTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // WigglyLabel
        //
        this.WigglyLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.WigglyLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.WigglyLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(227,
205);
        this.WigglyLabel.Name = "WigglyLabel";
        this.WigglyLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(60, 32);
        this.WigglyLabel.TabIndex = 166;
        this.WigglyLabel.Text = "Wiggly:";
        this.WigglyLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;

```

```

//
// WigglyTick
//
this.WigglyTick.Enabled = false;
this.WigglyTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(293,
215);
this.WigglyTick.Name = "WigglyTick";
this.WigglyTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
this.WigglyTick.TabIndex = 165;
this.WigglyTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
this.WigglyTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.WigglyTick_CheckedChanged);
//
// NormLabel
//
this.NormLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
this.NormLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.NormLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(227,
94);
this.NormLabel.Name = "NormLabel";
this.NormLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(60, 32);
this.NormLabel.TabIndex = 164;
this.NormLabel.Text = "Normal:";
this.NormLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// NormTick
//
this.NormTick.Enabled = false;
this.NormTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(293,
104);
this.NormTick.Name = "NormTick";
this.NormTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
this.NormTick.TabIndex = 163;
this.NormTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
this.NormTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.NormTick_CheckedChanged);
//
// CompDEMLabel
//
this.CompDEMLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
this.CompDEMLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.CompDEMLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(3,
94);
this.CompDEMLabel.Name = "CompDEMLabel";
this.CompDEMLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189, 32);
this.CompDEMLabel.TabIndex = 162;
this.CompDEMLabel.Text = "Computer Generated DEM";
this.CompDEMLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// CompDEMTick
//
this.CompDEMTick.Enabled = false;
this.CompDEMTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(198,
104);
this.CompDEMTick.Name = "CompDEMTick";

```

```

        this.CompDEMTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.CompDEMTick.TabIndex = 161;
        this.CompDEMTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.CompDEMTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.CompDEMTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // DEMLabel
        //
        this.DEMLabel.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.DEMLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(3, 40);
        this.DEMLabel.Name = "DEMLabel";
        this.DEMLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(189, 32);
        this.DEMLabel.TabIndex = 160;
        this.DEMLabel.Text = "Load from DEM File";
        this.DEMLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // DEMTick
        //
        this.DEMTick.Checked = true;
        this.DEMTick.CheckState =
System.Windows.Forms.CheckState.Checked;
        this.DEMTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(198, 51);
        this.DEMTick.Name = "DEMTick";
        this.DEMTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.DEMTick.TabIndex = 159;
        this.DEMTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.DEMTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.DEMTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // DEMBrowseButton
        //
        this.DEMBrowseButton.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(385, 47);
        this.DEMBrowseButton.Name = "DEMBrowseButton";
        this.DEMBrowseButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(54,
20);
        this.DEMBrowseButton.TabIndex = 102;
        this.DEMBrowseButton.Text = "Browse";
        this.DEMBrowseButton.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.DEMBrowseButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.DEMFileExplorer_Click);
        //
        // DEMTextBox
        //
        this.DEMTextBox.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(246,
47);
        this.DEMTextBox.Name = "DEMTextBox";
        this.DEMTextBox.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(142, 20);
        this.DEMTextBox.TabIndex = 100;
        this.DEMTextBox.Text = "Paper_coast_4.txt";
        //
        // shapeContainer1
        //
        this.shapeContainer1.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(0, 0);
        this.shapeContainer1.Margin = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(0);
        this.shapeContainer1.Name = "shapeContainer1";
        this.shapeContainer1.Shapes.AddRange(new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.Shape[] {

```

```

        this.lineShapel});
        this.shapeContainer1.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027,
255);
        this.shapeContainer1.TabIndex = 173;
        this.shapeContainer1.TabStop = false;
        //
        // lineShapel
        //
        this.lineShapel.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
        this.lineShapel.Name = "lineShapel";
        this.lineShapel.X1 = 475;
        this.lineShapel.X2 = 475;
        this.lineShapel.Y1 = 14;
        this.lineShapel.Y2 = 204;
        //
        // MainWindowTabs
        //
        this.MainWindowTabs.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)(((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Top | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Bottom)
| System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)
| System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Right)));
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.DEMTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.WaveTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.TideTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.ErosionTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.SourceSinkTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.Outputs);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Controls.Add(this.DescriptionTab);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(8,
3);
        this.MainWindowTabs.MinimumSize = new
System.Drawing.Size(0, 269);
        this.MainWindowTabs.Name = "MainWindowTabs";
        this.MainWindowTabs.SelectedIndex = 0;
        this.MainWindowTabs.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1035,
281);
        this.MainWindowTabs.TabIndex = 143;
        //
        // TideTab
        //
        this.TideTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.StepSLR_Lab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.StepSLR_Tick);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.DoSLRLab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.DoSLRTick);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.RateSLR_TB);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.RateSLRLab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.SLR_TB);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.SLRLab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.SLRTitle);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.TidesTitle);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.DoTidesLabel);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.DoTidesTick);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.HighTideTB);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.HighTideLab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.LowTideTB);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.LowTideLab);
        this.TideTab.Controls.Add(this.shapeContainer5);
        this.TideTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4, 22);

```

```

        this.TideTab.Name = "TideTab";
        this.TideTab.Padding = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(3);
        this.TideTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027, 255);
        this.TideTab.TabIndex = 11;
        this.TideTab.Text = "Water Level";
        //
        // StepSLR_Lab
        //
        this.StepSLR_Lab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.StepSLR_Lab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.StepSLR_Lab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(487,
94);

        this.StepSLR_Lab.Name = "StepSLR_Lab";
        this.StepSLR_Lab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(136, 32);
        this.StepSLR_Lab.TabIndex = 192;
        this.StepSLR_Lab.Text = "Stepped SLR";
        this.StepSLR_Lab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // StepSLR_Tick
        //
        this.StepSLR_Tick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(629,
105);

        this.StepSLR_Tick.Name = "StepSLR_Tick";
        this.StepSLR_Tick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.StepSLR_Tick.TabIndex = 191;
        this.StepSLR_Tick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        //
        // DoSLRLab
        //
        this.DoSLRLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.DoSLRLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.DoSLRLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(487,
53);

        this.DoSLRLab.Name = "DoSLRLab";
        this.DoSLRLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(136, 32);
        this.DoSLRLab.TabIndex = 190;
        this.DoSLRLab.Text = "Run With SLR";
        this.DoSLRLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // DoSLRTick
        //
        this.DoSLRTick.Checked = true;
        this.DoSLRTick.CheckState =
System.Windows.Forms.CheckState.Checked;
        this.DoSLRTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(629,
64);

        this.DoSLRTick.Name = "DoSLRTick";
        this.DoSLRTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.DoSLRTick.TabIndex = 189;
        this.DoSLRTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.DoSLRTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.DoSLRTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // RateSLR_TB
        //

```

```

        this.RateSLR_TB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(629,
176);
        this.RateSLR_TB.Name = "RateSLR_TB";
        this.RateSLR_TB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.RateSLR_TB.TabIndex = 188;
        this.RateSLR_TB.Text = "3000";
        //
        // RateSLRLab
        //
        this.RateSLRLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.RateSLRLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.RateSLRLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(465,
175);
        this.RateSLRLab.Name = "RateSLRLab";
        this.RateSLRLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(158, 20);
        this.RateSLRLab.TabIndex = 187;
        this.RateSLRLab.Text = "Rate of SLR (yrs)";
        this.RateSLRLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // SLR_TB
        //
        this.SLR_TB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(629, 139);
        this.SLR_TB.Name = "SLR_TB";
        this.SLR_TB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.SLR_TB.TabIndex = 186;
        this.SLR_TB.Text = "60";
        //
        // SLRLab
        //
        this.SLRLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans
Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.SLRLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.SLRLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(482, 138);
        this.SLRLab.Name = "SLRLab";
        this.SLRLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(141, 20);
        this.SLRLab.TabIndex = 185;
        this.SLRLab.Text = "Sea Level Rise (m)";
        this.SLRLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // SLRTitle
        //
        this.SLRTitle.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.SLRTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(440,
15);
        this.SLRTitle.Name = "SLRTitle";
        this.SLRTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(380, 32);
        this.SLRTitle.TabIndex = 183;
        this.SLRTitle.Text = "Sea Level Rise";
        this.SLRTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // TidesTitle

```

```

        //
        this.TidesTitle.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.TidesTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(32,
15);
        this.TidesTitle.Name = "TidesTitle";
        this.TidesTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(371, 32);
        this.TidesTitle.TabIndex = 182;
        this.TidesTitle.Text = "Tides";
        this.TidesTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // DoTidesLabel
        //
        this.DoTidesLabel.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold);
        this.DoTidesLabel.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.DoTidesLabel.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(80,
54);
        this.DoTidesLabel.Name = "DoTidesLabel";
        this.DoTidesLabel.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(136, 32);
        this.DoTidesLabel.TabIndex = 181;
        this.DoTidesLabel.Text = "Run With Tides";
        this.DoTidesLabel.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // DoTidesTick
        //
        this.DoTidesTick.Checked = true;
        this.DoTidesTick.CheckState =
System.Windows.Forms.CheckState.Checked;
        this.DoTidesTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(222,
65);
        this.DoTidesTick.Name = "DoTidesTick";
        this.DoTidesTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.DoTidesTick.TabIndex = 180;
        this.DoTidesTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.DoTidesTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.DoTidesTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // HighTideTB
        //
        this.HighTideTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(222,
138);
        this.HighTideTB.Name = "HighTideTB";
        this.HighTideTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.HighTideTB.TabIndex = 163;
        this.HighTideTB.Text = "0";
        //
        // HighTideLab
        //
        this.HighTideLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.HighTideLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.HighTideLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(83,
137);

```

```

        this.HighTideLab.Name = "HighTideLab";
        this.HighTideLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(133, 20);
        this.HighTideLab.TabIndex = 162;
        this.HighTideLab.Text = "High Tide (m):";
        this.HighTideLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // LowTideTB
        //
        this.LowTideTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(222,
101);
        this.LowTideTB.Name = "LowTideTB";
        this.LowTideTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.LowTideTB.TabIndex = 159;
        this.LowTideTB.Text = "0";
        //
        // LowTideLab
        //
        this.LowTideLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.LowTideLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlText;
        this.LowTideLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(112,
100);
        this.LowTideLab.Name = "LowTideLab";
        this.LowTideLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.LowTideLab.TabIndex = 109;
        this.LowTideLab.Text = "Low Tide (m):";
        this.LowTideLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // shapeContainer5
        //
        this.shapeContainer5.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(3, 3);
        this.shapeContainer5.Margin = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(0);
        this.shapeContainer5.Name = "shapeContainer5";
        this.shapeContainer5.Shapes.AddRange(new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.Shape[] {
this.lineShape6});
        this.shapeContainer5.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1021,
249);
        this.shapeContainer5.TabIndex = 184;
        this.shapeContainer5.TabStop = false;
        //
        // lineShape6
        //
        this.lineShape6.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
        this.lineShape6.Name = "lineShape6";
        this.lineShape6.X1 = 420;
        this.lineShape6.X2 = 420;
        this.lineShape6.Y1 = 38;
        this.lineShape6.Y2 = 204;
        //
        // ErosionTab
        //
        this.ErosionTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.WeatheringTitle);

```

```

        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.ErosionTitle);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.RockWeatherTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.PercentSlowTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.PercentSlowLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.PercentFastTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.PercentFastLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.FastWeatherTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.FastWeatherLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.SlowWeatherTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.SlowWeatherLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.ErosRateTB);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.ErosRateLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.shapeContainer3);
        this.ErosionTab.Controls.Add(this.RockWeatherLab);
        this.ErosionTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4,
22);
        this.ErosionTab.Name = "ErosionTab";
        this.ErosionTab.Padding = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(3);
        this.ErosionTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027, 255);
        this.ErosionTab.TabIndex = 12;
        this.ErosionTab.Text = "Erosion & Weathering";
        //
        // WeatheringTitle
        //
        this.WeatheringTitle.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.WeatheringTitle.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(440, 15);
        this.WeatheringTitle.Name = "WeatheringTitle";
        this.WeatheringTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(380,
32);
        this.WeatheringTitle.TabIndex = 178;
        this.WeatheringTitle.Text = "Weathering";
        this.WeatheringTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // ErosionTitle
        //
        this.ErosionTitle.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.ErosionTitle.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(32,
15);
        this.ErosionTitle.Name = "ErosionTitle";
        this.ErosionTitle.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(371, 32);
        this.ErosionTitle.TabIndex = 177;
        this.ErosionTitle.Text = "Erosion";
        this.ErosionTitle.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleCenter;
        //
        // RockWeatherTB
        //
        this.RockWeatherTB.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(700, 64);
        this.RockWeatherTB.Name = "RockWeatherTB";
        this.RockWeatherTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
20);
        this.RockWeatherTB.TabIndex = 173;

```

```

        this.RockWeatherTB.Text = "5.0";
        //
        // PercentSlowTB
        //
        this.PercentSlowTB.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(283, 149);
        this.PercentSlowTB.Name = "PercentSlowTB";
        this.PercentSlowTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
20);

        this.PercentSlowTB.TabIndex = 169;
        this.PercentSlowTB.Text = "0.5";
        //
        // PercentSlowLab
        //
        this.PercentSlowLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.PercentSlowLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.PercentSlowLab.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(21, 148);
        this.PercentSlowLab.Name = "PercentSlowLab";
        this.PercentSlowLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(256,
20);

        this.PercentSlowLab.TabIndex = 168;
        this.PercentSlowLab.Text = "Percentage of Fine, Slow
Eroding Material:";
        this.PercentSlowLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // PercentFastTB
        //
        this.PercentFastTB.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(283, 106);
        this.PercentFastTB.Name = "PercentFastTB";
        this.PercentFastTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
20);

        this.PercentFastTB.TabIndex = 167;
        this.PercentFastTB.Text = "0.5";
        //
        // PercentFastLab
        //
        this.PercentFastLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.PercentFastLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.PercentFastLab.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(29, 105);
        this.PercentFastLab.Name = "PercentFastLab";
        this.PercentFastLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(248,
20);

        this.PercentFastLab.TabIndex = 166;
        this.PercentFastLab.Text = "Percentage of Fine, Fast
Eroding Material:";
        this.PercentFastLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // FastWeatherTB
        //

```

```

        this.FastWeatherTB.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(700, 149);
        this.FastWeatherTB.Name = "FastWeatherTB";
        this.FastWeatherTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
20);

        this.FastWeatherTB.TabIndex = 165;
        this.FastWeatherTB.Text = "1.5";
        //
        // FastWeatherLab
        //
        this.FastWeatherLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.FastWeatherLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.FastWeatherLab.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(471, 148);
        this.FastWeatherLab.Name = "FastWeatherLab";
        this.FastWeatherLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(223,
20);

        this.FastWeatherLab.TabIndex = 164;
        this.FastWeatherLab.Text = "Fast Weathering Coefficient:";
        this.FastWeatherLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // SlowWeatherTB
        //
        this.SlowWeatherTB.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(700, 106);
        this.SlowWeatherTB.Name = "SlowWeatherTB";
        this.SlowWeatherTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120,
20);

        this.SlowWeatherTB.TabIndex = 163;
        this.SlowWeatherTB.Text = "0.125";
        //
        // SlowWeatherLab
        //
        this.SlowWeatherLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.SlowWeatherLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.SlowWeatherLab.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(468, 105);
        this.SlowWeatherLab.Name = "SlowWeatherLab";
        this.SlowWeatherLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(226,
20);

        this.SlowWeatherLab.TabIndex = 162;
        this.SlowWeatherLab.Text = "Slow Weathering Coefficient:";
        this.SlowWeatherLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ErosRateTB
        //
        this.ErosRateTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(283,
64);

        this.ErosRateTB.Name = "ErosRateTB";
        this.ErosRateTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.ErosRateTB.TabIndex = 161;
        this.ErosRateTB.Text = "2";

```

```

//
// ErosRateLab
//
this.ErosRateLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte) 0));
this.ErosRateLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
this.ErosRateLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(93,
63);

this.ErosRateLab.Name = "ErosRateLab";
this.ErosRateLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(184, 20);
this.ErosRateLab.TabIndex = 160;
this.ErosRateLab.Text = "Erosion Rate Per Year (m)";
this.ErosRateLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// shapeContainer3
//
this.shapeContainer3.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(3, 3);
this.shapeContainer3.Margin = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(0);
this.shapeContainer3.Name = "shapeContainer3";
this.shapeContainer3.Shapes.AddRange(new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.Shape[] {
this.lineShape4});
this.shapeContainer3.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1021,
249);

this.shapeContainer3.TabIndex = 179;
this.shapeContainer3.TabStop = false;
//
// lineShape4
//
this.lineShape4.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
this.lineShape4.Name = "lineShape4";
this.lineShape4.X1 = 420;
this.lineShape4.X2 = 420;
this.lineShape4.Y1 = 14;
this.lineShape4.Y2 = 180;
//
// RockWeatherLab
//
this.RockWeatherLab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.Color.Transparent;
this.RockWeatherLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
this.RockWeatherLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
this.RockWeatherLab.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(427, 63);
this.RockWeatherLab.Name = "RockWeatherLab";
this.RockWeatherLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(267,
20);

this.RockWeatherLab.TabIndex = 172;
this.RockWeatherLab.Text = "Elevation that Rock Weathering
Occurs (m)";
this.RockWeatherLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;

```

```

//
// SourceSinkTab
//
this.SourceSinkTab.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SinkinessTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SinkinessLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.YSourceTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.YSourceLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.XSourceTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.XSourceLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.ColSourceTick);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.ColSourceLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.YSinkTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.YSinkLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.XSinkTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.XSinkLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.ColSinkTick);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.ColSinkLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SinkTick);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SinkTickLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SourceTick);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SourceTickLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.NumSinkTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.NumSinkLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SinksTab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.SourcesTab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.NumSourceTB);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.NumSourceLab);
this.SourceSinkTab.Controls.Add(this.shapeContainer4);
this.SourceSinkTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4,
22);

this.SourceSinkTab.Name = "SourceSinkTab";
this.SourceSinkTab.Padding = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(3);
this.SourceSinkTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027,
255);

this.SourceSinkTab.TabIndex = 13;
this.SourceSinkTab.Text = "Sources & Sinks";
//
// SinkinessTB
//
this.SinkinessTB.Enabled = false;
this.SinkinessTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
142);

this.SinkinessTB.Name = "SinkinessTB";
this.SinkinessTB.ReadOnly = true;
this.SinkinessTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
this.SinkinessTB.TabIndex = 201;
//
// SinkinessLab
//
this.SinkinessLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
this.SinkinessLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.SinkinessLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(441,
141);

this.SinkinessLab.Name = "SinkinessLab";
this.SinkinessLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(135, 20);

```

```

        this.SinkinessLab.TabIndex = 200;
        this.SinkinessLab.Text = "Sinkiness (%):";
        this.SinkinessLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // YSourceTB
        //
        this.YSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        this.YSourceTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(169,
177);
        this.YSourceTB.Name = "YSourceTB";
        this.YSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.YSourceTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(235, 20);
        this.YSourceTB.TabIndex = 199;
        this.CoordTT.SetToolTip(this.YSourceTB, "Comma Separated
(e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4)");
        //
        // YSourceLab
        //
        this.YSourceLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.YSourceLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.YSourceLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(27,
176);
        this.YSourceLab.Name = "YSourceLab";
        this.YSourceLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(136, 20);
        this.YSourceLab.TabIndex = 198;
        this.YSourceLab.Text = "Y-Coordinate(s)";
        this.YSourceLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // XSourceTB
        //
        this.XSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        this.XSourceTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(169,
143);
        this.XSourceTB.Name = "XSourceTB";
        this.XSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.XSourceTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(235, 20);
        this.XSourceTB.TabIndex = 197;
        this.CoordTT.SetToolTip(this.XSourceTB, "Comma Separated
(e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4)");
        //
        // XSourceLab
        //
        this.XSourceLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.XSourceLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.XSourceLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(24,
142);
        this.XSourceLab.Name = "XSourceLab";
        this.XSourceLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(139, 20);
        this.XSourceLab.TabIndex = 196;
        this.XSourceLab.Text = "X-Coordinate(s)";
        this.XSourceLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ColSourceTick

```

```

//
this.ColSourceTick.Enabled = false;
this.ColSourceTick.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(169, 75);
this.ColSourceTick.Name = "ColSourceTick";
this.ColSourceTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
this.ColSourceTick.TabIndex = 195;
this.ColSourceTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
this.ColSourceTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.ColSourceTick_CheckedChanged);
//
// ColSourceLab
//
this.ColSourceLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte)0));
this.ColSourceLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.ColSourceLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(18,
64);
this.ColSourceLab.Name = "ColSourceLab";
this.ColSourceLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(145, 35);
this.ColSourceLab.TabIndex = 194;
this.ColSourceLab.Text = "Source To Span Whole Column";
this.ColSourceLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// YSinkTB
//
this.YSinkTB.Enabled = false;
this.YSinkTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
207);
this.YSinkTB.Name = "YSinkTB";
this.YSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
this.YSinkTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(235, 20);
this.YSinkTB.TabIndex = 193;
this.CoordTT.SetToolTip(this.YSinkTB, "Comma Separated
(e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4)");
//
// YSinkLab
//
this.YSinkLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
this.YSinkLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
this.YSinkLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(460,
206);
this.YSinkLab.Name = "YSinkLab";
this.YSinkLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(116, 20);
this.YSinkLab.TabIndex = 192;
this.YSinkLab.Text = "Y-Coordinate(s)";
this.YSinkLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// XSinkTB
//
this.XSinkTB.Enabled = false;
this.XSinkTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
177);
this.XSinkTB.Name = "XSinkTB";

```

```

        this.XSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.XSinkTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(235, 20);
        this.XSinkTB.TabIndex = 191;
        this.CoordTT.SetToolTip(this.XSinkTB, "Comma Seperated
(e.g. 1, 2, 3, 4)");
        //
        // XSinkLab
        //
        this.XSinkLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.XSinkLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.XSinkLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(444,
176);

        this.XSinkLab.Name = "XSinkLab";
        this.XSinkLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(132, 20);
        this.XSinkLab.TabIndex = 190;
        this.XSinkLab.Text = "X-Coordinate(s)";
        this.XSinkLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // ColSinkTick
        //
        this.ColSinkTick.Enabled = false;
        this.ColSinkTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
75);

        this.ColSinkTick.Name = "ColSinkTick";
        this.ColSinkTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.ColSinkTick.TabIndex = 189;
        this.ColSinkTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.ColSinkTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.ColSinkTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // ColSinkLab
        //
        this.ColSinkLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.ColSinkLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.ColSinkLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(434,
64);

        this.ColSinkLab.Name = "ColSinkLab";
        this.ColSinkLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(142, 35);
        this.ColSinkLab.TabIndex = 188;
        this.ColSinkLab.Text = "Sink To Span Whole Column";
        this.ColSinkLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // SinkTick
        //
        this.SinkTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
40);

        this.SinkTick.Name = "SinkTick";
        this.SinkTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
        this.SinkTick.TabIndex = 187;
        this.SinkTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
        this.SinkTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.SinkTick_CheckedChanged);
        //
        // SinkTickLab

```

```

//
this.SinkTickLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
this.SinkTickLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
this.SinkTickLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(437,
36);

this.SinkTickLab.Name = "SinkTickLab";
this.SinkTickLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(139, 20);
this.SinkTickLab.TabIndex = 186;
this.SinkTickLab.Text = "Include Sinks";
this.SinkTickLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// SourceTick
//
this.SourceTick.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(169,
40);

this.SourceTick.Name = "SourceTick";
this.SourceTick.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(15, 14);
this.SourceTick.TabIndex = 185;
this.SourceTick.UseVisualStyleBackColor = true;
this.SourceTick.CheckedChanged += new
System.EventHandler(this.SourceTick_CheckedChanged);
//
// SourceTickLab
//
this.SourceTickLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte)0));
this.SourceTickLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
this.SourceTickLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(10,
36);

this.SourceTickLab.Name = "SourceTickLab";
this.SourceTickLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(153,
20);

this.SourceTickLab.TabIndex = 184;
this.SourceTickLab.Text = "Include Sources";
this.SourceTickLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
//
// NumSinkTB
//
this.NumSinkTB.Enabled = false;
this.NumSinkTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(582,
107);

this.NumSinkTB.Name = "NumSinkTB";
this.NumSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
this.NumSinkTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
this.NumSinkTB.TabIndex = 183;
//
// NumSinkLab
//
this.NumSinkLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
this.NumSinkLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;

```

```

        this.NumSinkLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(441,
106);
        this.NumSinkLab.Name = "NumSinkLab";
        this.NumSinkLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(135, 20);
        this.NumSinkLab.TabIndex = 182;
        this.NumSinkLab.Text = "Number of Sinks:";
        this.NumSinkLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MidRight;
        //
        // SinksTab
        //
        this.SinksTab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.SinksTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(433, 4);
        this.SinksTab.Name = "SinksTab";
        this.SinksTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(406, 32);
        this.SinksTab.TabIndex = 180;
        this.SinksTab.Text = "Sinks";
        this.SinksTab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MidCenter;
        //
        // SourcesTab
        //
        this.SourcesTab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F,
((System.Drawing.FontStyle)((System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold |
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Underline))));
        this.SourcesTab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(7, 4);
        this.SourcesTab.Name = "SourcesTab";
        this.SourcesTab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(405, 32);
        this.SourcesTab.TabIndex = 179;
        this.SourcesTab.Text = "Sources";
        this.SourcesTab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MidCenter;
        //
        // NumSourceTB
        //
        this.NumSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        this.NumSourceTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(169,
107);
        this.NumSourceTB.Name = "NumSourceTB";
        this.NumSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        this.NumSourceTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.NumSourceTB.TabIndex = 163;
        //
        // NumSourceLab
        //
        this.NumSourceLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.NumSourceLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.GrayText;
        this.NumSourceLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(21,
106);
        this.NumSourceLab.Name = "NumSourceLab";
        this.NumSourceLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(142, 20);
        this.NumSourceLab.TabIndex = 162;
        this.NumSourceLab.Text = "Number of Sources:";

```

```

        this.NumSourceLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // shapeContainer4
        //
        this.shapeContainer4.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(3, 3);
        this.shapeContainer4.Margin = new
System.Windows.Forms.Padding(0);
        this.shapeContainer4.Name = "shapeContainer4";
        this.shapeContainer4.Shapes.AddRange(new
Microsoft.VisualBasic.PowerPacks.Shape[] {
        this.lineShape5});
        this.shapeContainer4.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1021,
249);

        this.shapeContainer4.TabIndex = 181;
        this.shapeContainer4.TabStop = false;
        //
        // lineShape5
        //
        this.lineShape5.BorderColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ControlDarkDark;
        this.lineShape5.Name = "lineShape5";
        this.lineShape5.X1 = 428;
        this.lineShape5.X2 = 428;
        this.lineShape5.Y1 = 11;
        this.lineShape5.Y2 = 210;
        //
        // Outputs
        //
        this.Outputs.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.RunLengthTB);
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.RunLengthLab);
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.OutputNameTB);
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.OutputNameLab);
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.SaveFreqTB);
        this.Outputs.Controls.Add(this.SaveFreqLab);
        this.Outputs.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(4, 22);
        this.Outputs.Name = "Outputs";
        this.Outputs.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(1027, 255);
        this.Outputs.TabIndex = 14;
        this.Outputs.Text = "Outputs";
        //
        // RunLengthTB
        //
        this.RunLengthTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(163,
112);

        this.RunLengthTB.Name = "RunLengthTB";
        this.RunLengthTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.RunLengthTB.TabIndex = 184;
        this.RunLengthTB.Text = "1095000";
        //
        // RunLengthLab
        //
        this.RunLengthLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte) 0));
        this.RunLengthLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;

```

```

        this.RunLengthLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(33,
111);
        this.RunLengthLab.Name = "RunLengthLab";
        this.RunLengthLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(124, 20);
        this.RunLengthLab.TabIndex = 183;
        this.RunLengthLab.Text = "Run Length (Days):";
        this.RunLengthLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // OutputNameTB
        //
        this.OutputNameTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(163,
39);
        this.OutputNameTB.Name = "OutputNameTB";
        this.OutputNameTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.OutputNameTB.TabIndex = 182;
        this.OutputNameTB.Text = "CEM";
        //
        // OutputNameLab
        //
        this.OutputNameLab.Font = new
System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft Sans Serif", 8.25F,
System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold, System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point,
((byte)0));
        this.OutputNameLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.OutputNameLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(53,
38);
        this.OutputNameLab.Name = "OutputNameLab";
        this.OutputNameLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104,
20);
        this.OutputNameLab.TabIndex = 181;
        this.OutputNameLab.Text = "File Name:";
        this.OutputNameLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // SaveFreqTB
        //
        this.SaveFreqTB.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(163,
76);
        this.SaveFreqTB.Name = "SaveFreqTB";
        this.SaveFreqTB.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(120, 20);
        this.SaveFreqTB.TabIndex = 180;
        this.SaveFreqTB.Text = "3650";
        //
        // SaveFreqLab
        //
        this.SaveFreqLab.Font = new System.Drawing.Font("Microsoft
Sans Serif", 8.25F, System.Drawing.FontStyle.Bold,
System.Drawing.GraphicsUnit.Point, ((byte)0));
        this.SaveFreqLab.ForeColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.ActiveCaptionText;
        this.SaveFreqLab.Location = new System.Drawing.Point(53,
75);
        this.SaveFreqLab.Name = "SaveFreqLab";
        this.SaveFreqLab.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(104, 20);
        this.SaveFreqLab.TabIndex = 179;
        this.SaveFreqLab.Text = "Save Frequency:";
        this.SaveFreqLab.TextAlign =
System.Drawing.ContentAlignment.MiddleRight;
        //
        // CoordTT

```

```

//
this.CoordTT.AutoPopDelay = 5000;
this.CoordTT.BackColor =
System.Drawing.SystemColors.InactiveBorder;
this.CoordTT.InitialDelay = 500;
this.CoordTT.ReshowDelay = 100;
this.CoordTT.ShowAlways = true;
//
// SeeTabsButton
//
this.SeeTabsButton.Anchor =
((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles)((System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyle
s.Bottom | System.Windows.Forms.AnchorStyles.Left)));
this.SeeTabsButton.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(447, 291);
this.SeeTabsButton.Name = "SeeTabsButton";
this.SeeTabsButton.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(86, 24);
this.SeeTabsButton.TabIndex = 178;
this.SeeTabsButton.Text = "See Tabs";
this.SeeTabsButton.Visible = false;
this.SeeTabsButton.Click += new
System.EventHandler(this.SeeTabsButton_Click);
//
// zoomPanImageBox1
//
this.zoomPanImageBox1.AutoScroll = true;
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Image = null;
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Location = new
System.Drawing.Point(8, 34);
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Name = "zoomPanImageBox1";
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Size = new System.Drawing.Size(855,
212);
this.zoomPanImageBox1.TabIndex = 148;
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Visible = false;
this.zoomPanImageBox1.Load += new
System.EventHandler(this.zoomPanImageBox1_Load);
//
// Form1
//
this.AutoScaleBaseSize = new System.Drawing.Size(5, 13);
this.AutoScroll = true;
this.BackColor = System.Drawing.SystemColors.Control;
this.ClientSize = new System.Drawing.Size(1088, 362);
this.Controls.Add(this.SeeTabsButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.pauseButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.quitSaveButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.startButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.loadDataButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.resumeButton);
this.Controls.Add(this.MainWindowTabs);
this.Controls.Add(this.statusBar1);
this.Controls.Add(this.zoomPanImageBox1);
this.Controls.Add(this.UpdateGraphPanel);
this.Controls.Add(this.ZoomSlider);
this.Controls.Add(this.ViewTabsCheck);
this.Controls.Add(this.Graphic_ContrastSlider);
this.Menu = this.mainMenu1;
this.MinimumSize = new System.Drawing.Size(920, 400);
this.Name = "Form1";
this.StartPosition =
System.Windows.Forms.FormStartPosition.CenterScreen;
this.Text = "Coastline Evolution Model (v.6)";

```

```

        this.Load += new System.EventHandler(this.Form1_Load);
        this.Shown += new System.EventHandler(this.Form1_Shown);
        this.Resize += new System.EventHandler(this.Form1_Resize);

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.InfoStatusPanel)).EndInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.IterationStatusPanel)).EndInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.TimeStatusPanel)).EndInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.QwStatusPanel)).EndInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.QsStatusPanel)).EndInit();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.waveAnglePanel)).EndInit();

        this.UpdateGraphPanel.ResumeLayout(false);

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.trackBar1)).EndInit();
        ;
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.Graphic_ContrastSlider.PerformLayout();
        this.ZoomSlider.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.ZoomSlider.PerformLayout();

        ((System.ComponentModel.ISupportInitialize)(this.trackBar2)).EndInit();
        ;
        this.DescriptionTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.DescriptionTab.PerformLayout();
        this.WaveTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.WaveTab.PerformLayout();
        this.DEMTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.DEMTab.PerformLayout();
        this.MainWindowTabs.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.TideTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.TideTab.PerformLayout();
        this.ErosionTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.ErosionTab.PerformLayout();
        this.SourceSinkTab.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.SourceSinkTab.PerformLayout();
        this.Outputs.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.Outputs.PerformLayout();
        this.ResumeLayout(false);
        this.PerformLayout();

    }

    // Run when the 'Load' button is clicked
    private void loadDataButton_Click(object sender,
    System.EventArgs e)
    {
        // Check for errors
        List<string> errors = new List<string>();
        errors.Add("Some data is missing or invalid, please
    check:" + Environment.NewLine + Environment.NewLine);
    }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if ((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.ColumnTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.RowsTB.Text)))
        {
            errors.Add("        - DEM" + Environment.NewLine);
        }
        else if (CompDEMTick.Checked == true &&
((Convert.ToDouble(ColumnTB.Text) < 50) ||
(Convert.ToDouble(RowsTB.Text) < 50)))
        {
            errors.Add("        - Minimum DEM size = 50 x 50" +
Environment.NewLine);
        }
        if ((ManWavTick.Checked == true) &&
((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WAngleTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WPeriodTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WHeightTB.Text))))
        {
            errors.Add("        - Wave Data" + Environment.NewLine);
        }
        else if ((WaveFileTick.Checked == true) &&
((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WALoadTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WPLoadTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.WHLoadTB.Text))))
        {
            errors.Add("        - Wave Data" + Environment.NewLine);
        }
        else if (ManWavTick.Checked == false &&
WaveFileTick.Checked == false && UA_WaveTick.Checked == false)
        {
            errors.Add("        - Wave Data" + Environment.NewLine);
        }
        if (DoTidesTick.Checked == true &&
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.LowTideTB.Text)))
        {
            errors.Add("        - Tide Data" + Environment.NewLine);
        }
        if ((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.ErosRateTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.PercentFastTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.PercentSlowTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.RockWeatherTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.SlowWeatherTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.FastWeatherTB.Text)))
        {
            errors.Add("        - Erosion and Weathering Rates" +
Environment.NewLine);
        }
        if (SourceTick.Checked == true)
        {
            if ((ColSourceTick.Checked == true) &&
((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.NumSourceTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.XSourceTB.Text))))
            {
                errors.Add("        - Sediment Source(s)" +
Environment.NewLine);
            }
            else if ((ColSourceTick.Checked == false) &&
((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.NumSourceTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.XSourceTB.Text)) ||
(string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.YSourceTB.Text))))
            {
                errors.Add("        - Sediment Source(s)" +
Environment.NewLine);
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
  }
  if (SinkTick.Checked == true)
  {
    if ((ColSinkTick.Checked == true) &&
        ((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.NumSinkTB.Text)) ||
         (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.XSinkTB.Text))))
    {
      errors.Add("      - Sediment Sink(s)" +
Environment.NewLine);
    }
    else if ((ColSinkTick.Checked == false) &&
              ((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.NumSinkTB.Text)) ||
               (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.XSinkTB.Text)) ||
               (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.YSinkTB.Text))))
    {
      errors.Add("      - Sediment Sink(s)" +
Environment.NewLine);
    }
  }
  if ((string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.SaveFreqTB.Text)) ||
      (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.OutputNameTB.Text)) ||
      (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.RunLengthTB.Text)))
  {
    errors.Add("      - Outputs" + Environment.NewLine);
  }
  else if (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.RunLengthTB.Text))
  {
    errors.Add("      - Outputs" + Environment.NewLine);
  }
  else if (Convert.ToDouble(this.RunLengthTB.Text) % 1 != 0)
  {
    errors.Add("      - Run Length must be a whole number
(Days)" + Environment.NewLine);
  }
  if(errors.Count > 1)
  {
    DialogResult Result = MessageBox.Show((string.Join("
", errors.ToArray())), "Missing Data", MessageBoxButtons.OK,
MessageBoxIcon.Warning, MessageBoxDefaultButton.Button1,
MessageBoxOptions.DefaultDesktopOnly);

    if (Result == DialogResult.OK)
    {
      return;
    }
  }

  // Initialise Arrays, Variables and Graphics
  initialise();
  load_DEM();

  // Which items in the designer will be visible once the
'Load' button is clicked
  MainWindowTabs.Visible = false;
  ViewTabsCheck.Checked = false;
  zoomPanImageBox1.Visible = true;
  UpdateGraphPanel.Visible = true;
  loadDataButton.Enabled = false;
  Graphic_ContrastSlider.Visible = true;
  ZoomSlider.Visible = true;

```

```

        startButton.Visible = true;

        // Batch
        if (autorestart == 1 && Restart_count > 1)
        {
            startButton.PerformClick();
        }
    }
    private void initialise()
    {
        this.InfoStatusPanel.Text = "Initialising...";

        DEMFilePath = Directory.GetCurrentDirectory() +
"/INPUT_FILES/" + DEMTextBox.Text;

        //Setup
        //StartFromFile?
        if (DEMTick.Checked == true)
        {
            StartFromFile = 'y';
        }
        else if (DEMTick.Checked == false)
        {
            StartFromFile = 'n';
        }

        //InitCType - 0: normal (columns/blocks), 1: wiggly,
2: one block
        if (NormTick.Checked == true)
        {
            InitCType = 0;
        }
        else if (WigglyTick.Checked == true)
        {
            InitCType = 1;
        }
        else if (BlockTick.Checked == true)
        {
            InitCType = 2;
        }
        else if (PertTick.Checked == true)
        {
            InitCType = 0;
            InitialPert = 1;
        }
        else if (InitPertTick.Checked == true)
        {
            InitCType = 0;
            InitialPert = 3;
        }
        else
        {
            InitCType = -999;
            InitialPert = 0;
        }

        //xmax ymax
        if (StartFromFile == 'y')
        {
            int z;
            string[] lineArray2;
            int sp;

```

```

        inputheader = new string[6];

        //read headers (lines 0 - 5)
        StreamReader sr = File.OpenText(DEMFilePath);

        for (z = 1; z <= 6; z++)
        {
            inputheader[z - 1] = sr.ReadLine();
        }
        sr.Close();

        // get xmax, ymax and DX from input headers
        lineArray2 = inputheader[0].Split(new char[] { ' ' });
// Number of Columns
        sp = 1;
        while (lineArray2[sp] == "") sp++;
        xmax = int.Parse(lineArray2[sp]);

        lineArray2 = inputheader[1].Split(new char[] { ' ' });
// Number of Rows
        sp = 1;
        while (lineArray2[sp] == "") sp++;
        ymax = ((int.Parse(lineArray2[sp])));

        lineArray2 = inputheader[2].Split(new char[] { ' ' });
// xllcorner
        sp = 1;
        while (lineArray2[sp] == "") sp++;
        xll = double.Parse(lineArray2[sp]);

        lineArray2 = inputheader[3].Split(new char[] { ' ' });
// yllcorner
        sp = 1;
        while (lineArray2[sp] == "") sp++;
        yll = double.Parse(lineArray2[sp]);

        //lineArray2 = inputheader[4].Split(new char[] { ' '
}); // cell size
        //sp = 1;
        //while (lineArray2[sp] == "") sp++;
        //DX = int.Parse(lineArray2[sp]);
        //root = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX,
2)));
        //fiveroot = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX,
2)));

        //Trying to test why changing cell width makes a big
difference in NEW model
        DX = CellWidth;
        root = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX, 2)));
        fiveroot = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX,
2)));
    }
    else if (StartFromFile == 'n')
    {
        xmax = Convert.ToInt32(this.ColumnTB.Text);
        ymax = Convert.ToInt32(this.RowsTB.Text);
        xll = 0;
        yll = 0;
        DX = CellWidth;
        root = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX, 2)));

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        fiveroot = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX,
2)));
    }

    // Create a drawing surface with the same dimensions DEM
    m_objDrawingSurface = new Bitmap((xmax*2) *
graphics_scale,
    ymax * graphics_scale,
System.Drawing.Imaging.PixelFormat.Format24bppRgb);
    save_interval2 = 1000;
    save_time2 = save_interval2;
    root = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX, 2)));
    fiveroot = (Math.Sqrt(Math.Pow(DX, 2) + Math.Pow(DX, 2)));
    init_cycle = cycle;
    tx = output_file_save_interval;

    // Dimensions - periodic boundary/display
    xDisplayStart = xmax / 2;
    xDisplayEnd = (3 * xmax) / 2;
    pbEnd = xmax*2;

    // Tides
    Highness = 1 - Highness;
//Compensate for highness error
    if (DoTidesTick.Checked == true)
    {
        DoTides = 1;
        WaterLevel = Convert.ToDouble(this.LowTideTB.Text);
// What height is the tide?
        HighWaterHeight =
Convert.ToDouble(this.HighTideTB.Text); // Level of
HighTide

        int Rate = 4380;
//Convert.ToInt32(Math.Floor(HighWaterHeight) * 2);
// How many iterations to get from low to high water?
        double WLIncrement = HighWaterHeight / Rate;
// How much does the water need to raise on each iteration?
        WLArray = new double[(Rate * 2) + 1];
        double WLValue = WaterLevel;

        for (int x = 0; x <= Rate; x++)
        {
            WLArray[x] = WLValue;
            WLValue += WLIncrement;
        }
        WLValue -= WLIncrement;
        for (int x = Rate + 1; x < WLArray.Length; x++)
        {
            WLValue -= WLIncrement;
            WLArray[x] = WLValue;
            if (x == WLArray.Length - 1)
            {
                WLArray[x] = WaterLevel;
            }
        }
    }
    else if (DoTidesTick.Checked == false)
    {

```

```

        DoTides = 0;
    }

    if (DoSLRTick.Checked == true)
    {
        DoSLR = 1;

        SLR = Convert.ToDouble(this.SLR_TB.Text);
        SLRrate = (Convert.ToInt32(this.RateSLR_TB.Text) *
365);

        if (StepSLR_Tick.Checked == false)
        {
            double SLRIncrement = SLR / SLRrate;
            SLRArray = new double[SLRrate + 1];

            double SLRValue = 0;

            for (int x = 0; x <= SLRrate; x++)
            {
                SLRArray[x] = SLRValue;
                SLRValue += SLRIncrement;
            }
        }
        else if (StepSLR_Tick.Checked == true)
        {
            double SLRIncrement = SLR;
            SLRArray = new
double[Convert.ToInt32(this.RunLengthTB.Text) + 1];

            double SLRValue = 0;

            for (int x = 0; x <=
Convert.ToInt32(this.RunLengthTB.Text); x++)
            {
                if (x % SLRrate == 0 && x > 0)
                {
                    SLRValue += SLRIncrement;
                }
                SLRArray[x] = SLRValue;
            }
        }
    }
    else
    {
        DoSLR = 0;
    }

    // Waves - NEED TO LOOK AT WAVE = 0?
    if (autorestart == 0)
    {
        if (ManWavTick.Checked == true)
        {
            WaveIn = 3;
        }
        else if (WaveFileTick.Checked == true &&
BinnedTick.Checked == false)
        {
            WaveIn = 2;
        }
    }

```

```

        else if (BinnedTick.Checked == true)
        {
            WaveIn = 1;
            ReadWaveIn();
// Initialise WaveMax and WaveProb
        }
        else if (UA_WaveTick.Checked == true)
        {
            WaveIn = 0;
            Asym = Convert.ToDouble(this.AsymTB.Text);
// fractional portion of waves coming from positive (left) direction
            Highness = Convert.ToDouble(this.HighTB.Text);
// .5 = even dist, > .5 high angle domination.
            Highness = 1 - Highness;
        }
    }

    // Erosion
    NoWeathering = Convert.ToDouble(this.RockWeatherTB.Text);
// weathering of rock only occurs below this amt of sed cover (vert
equiv in meters) LMV */
    SlowWeatherCoeff =
Convert.ToDouble(this.SlowWeatherTB.Text);           // Weathering
rate of slow rock e.g. 0.5 = slow weathering, 1/2 as fast LMV
    FastWeatherCoeff =
Convert.ToDouble(this.FastWeatherTB.Text);           // Weathering
rate of fast rock e.g. 2 = fast weathering, 2 times faster than normal
LMV
    PercentFineFast =
Convert.ToDouble(this.PercentFastTB.Text);           // Percent
of fast weathering rock lost because it is too fine to stay in
nearshore LMV
    PercentFineSlow =
Convert.ToDouble(this.PercentSlowTB.Text);           // Percent
of slow weathering rock lost because it is too fine to stay in
nearshore LMV
    ErosionRatePerYear =
Convert.ToDouble(this.ErosRateTB.Text);
    ChunkLength = xmax;

    // Shadow
    ShadowYMax = ymax;

    // Sinks
    if (SinkTick.Checked == true)
    {
        // Have Sinks?
        HaveSinks = 1;
// yes
        NumSinks = Convert.ToInt32(this.NumSinkTB.Text);
// Number of Sinks

        //Sinkiness
        if (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.SinkinessTB.Text))
        {
            Sinkiness = 0;
        }
        else
        {

```

```

        Sinkiness =
        ((Convert.ToDouble(this.SinkinessTB.Text)) / 100); // fractional
value determines chance that sediment in the sink is deleted
    }

    //XYSink
    string XSinkInput = XSinkTB.Text;
    XSinkInput = XSinkInput.Replace("\r\n", " ");
    XSinkInput = XSinkInput.Replace("\t", " ");
    XSinkInput = XSinkInput.Replace(",", " ");
    XSinkInput = Regex.Replace(XSinkInput, @"\s+", " ");
    XSinkInput = XSinkInput.Trim();
    string[] XSinkInput_Split = XSinkInput.Split(' ');
    SinkX = new int[XSinkInput_Split.Length];
    int x;

    for (x = 0; x < XSinkInput_Split.Length; x++)
    {
        SinkX[x] = Convert.ToInt32(XSinkInput_Split[x]);
    }

    // Column Sink?
    if (ColSinkTick.Checked == true)
    {
        ColumnSinks = 1;
// Sink spans whole column
    }
    else if (ColSinkTick.Checked == false)
    {
        ColumnSinks = 0;

        string YSinkInput = YSinkTB.Text;
        YSinkInput = YSinkInput.Replace("\r\n", " ");
        YSinkInput = YSinkInput.Replace("\t", " ");
        YSinkInput = Regex.Replace(YSinkInput, @"\s+", "
");

        YSinkInput = YSinkInput.Replace(",", " ");
        YSinkInput = YSinkInput.Trim();
        string[] YSinkInput_Split = YSinkInput.Split(' ');
        SinkY = new int[YSinkInput_Split.Length];
        int y;

        for (y = 0; y < YSinkInput_Split.Length; y++)
        {
            SinkY[y] =
Convert.ToInt32(YSinkInput_Split[y]);
        }
    }
    else if (SinkTick.Checked == false)
    {
        HaveSinks = 0; // 0 = No
        NumSinks = 0; // N/A
    }

    //Sources
    if (SourceTick.Checked == true)
    {
        // Have Source?
        NumSources = Convert.ToInt32(this.NumSourceTB.Text);
// Number of Sources

```

```

//XYSink
string XSourceInput = XSourceTB.Text;
XSourceInput = XSourceInput.Replace("\r\n", " ");
XSourceInput = XSourceInput.Replace("\t", " ");
XSourceInput = XSourceInput.Replace(",", " ");
XSourceInput = Regex.Replace(XSourceInput, @"\s+", "
");

XSourceInput = XSourceInput.Trim();
string[] XSourceInput_Split = XSourceInput.Split(' ');
SourceX = new int[XSourceInput_Split.Length];
int x;

for (x = 0; x < XSourceInput_Split.Length; x++)
{
    SourceX[x] =
Convert.ToInt32(XSourceInput_Split[x]);
}

// Column Source?
if (ColSourceTick.Checked == true)
{
    ColumnSources = 1;
// Source spans whole column
}
else if (ColSourceTick.Checked == false)
{
    ColumnSources = 0;

    string YSourceInput = YSourceTB.Text;
YSourceInput = YSourceInput.Replace("\r\n", " ");
YSourceInput = YSourceInput.Replace("\t", " ");
YSourceInput = Regex.Replace(YSourceInput, @"\s+",
" ");

YSourceInput = YSourceInput.Replace(",", " ");
YSourceInput = YSourceInput.Trim();
string[] YSourceInput_Split = YSourceInput.Split('
');

SourceY = new int[YSourceInput_Split.Length];
int y;

for (y = 0; y < YSourceInput_Split.Length; y++)
{
    SourceY[y] =
Convert.ToInt32(YSourceInput_Split[y]);
}
}
else if (SourceTick.Checked == false)
{
    NumSources = 0;    // N/A
}

// Outputs
SaveFrequency = Convert.ToInt32(this.SaveFreqTB.Text);
// Counter interval to save image
SaveSpacing = SaveFrequency;
// space between saved files
StopAfter = Convert.ToInt32(this.RunLengthTB.Text);

// Batch

```

```

if (autorestart == 1)
{
    savefilename = "Run_" + Restart_count;
}
else
{
    savefilename = this.OutputNameTB.Text;
}

// General Arrays
AllBeach = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
// Flag indicating of cell is entirely beach
AllRock = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
// Flag indicating if cell is entirely rock LMV
PercentFullSand = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Fractional amount of cell full of sediment LMV
PercentFullRock = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Fractional amount of a cell full of rock LMV
AboveWater = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
AboveTideOLD = new bool[pbEnd, ymax];
// Flag indicating if a cell is above the tide mark
TypeOfRock = new char[pbEnd, ymax];
// Array to control weathering rates of rock along the beach LMV
Age = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
// Age since cell was deposited
MaxBeachLength = xmax * ymax; //20 * ymax;
CellDepth = new double[pbEnd, ymax];

ShorelineCell = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
Linear_Shoreline = new int[pbEnd, ymax];

// CM - Adding elevation volumes
DepthEffectiveArray = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
//LocalAngle = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
LowestX = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
LowestY = new int[pbEnd, ymax];
SedimentChange = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
VolumeChange = new double[pbEnd, ymax];

Elevation = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Elevation of beach
WaterDepth0 = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Water depth from DEM (ref: 0m)
DepthShelf = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Depth from '0' to Shelf
DomainDepthCS = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Depth to domain bottom from continental shelf
DepthShelfMaterial = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Depth of material to shelf from 0 level (will sometimes be same as
depthShelf)
TElevationCS = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Total elevation of material from continental shelf (used to work
out volume!)
TElevationDomain = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
// Total elevation of material from bottom of the domain (used to work
out above/below water)
Volume = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
OriginalVol = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
PreviousVolume = new double[pbEnd, ymax]; ;

```

```

        direction = new int[MaxBeachLength];
// 1 = Top    2 = Top right  3 = Right  4 = Bottom Right  5 = Bottom  6
= Bottom left  7 = Left  8 = Top Left
        numCells = new int[MaxBeachLength];
// How many cells from the coastline do we extend out for the
shoreface slope?
        localSFS = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        XSt = new int[MaxBeachLength];;
        YSt = new int[MaxBeachLength];;

// Computational Arrays (determined for each time step)
        X = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        Y = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        initialX = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        initialY = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        XBehind = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        YBehind = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        XRock = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        YRock = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        XRockBehind = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        YRockBehind = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        InShadow = new char[MaxBeachLength];
        InShadow_domain = new double[pbEnd, ymax];
        ShorelineAngle = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        SurroundingAngle = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        UpWind = new char[MaxBeachLength];
        VolumeIn = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        VolumeOut = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        VolumeAcrossBorder = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        ActualVolumeAcross = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        DirectionAcrossBorder = new char[MaxBeachLength];
        FlowThroughCell = new char[MaxBeachLength];
        DistanceToBeach = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        MinDistanceToBeach = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        ClosestBeach = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        AmountWeathered = new double[MaxBeachLength];
        //LostMaterial = new double[Convert.ToInt32(StopAfter)];
        Angle_1 = new double[MaxBeachLength];

// This needs to be placed better - the above shouldn't
run if InitialiseFile = 'y', but not using this atm
        if (InitialiseFile == 'y')
        {
            //ControlFile(); // Read in
initialisation data to control model
        }

// Save Files
        if (SaveLine == 1)
        {
            SaveLineToFile();
        }
        if (Metadata == 'y')
        {
            MetaFile(); // Read in
initialisation data to control model
        }
    }
    void load_DEM()

```

```

    {
        // DEM loaded from file
        if (StartFromFile == 'y')
        {
            //int x;
            //int i = 0, j = 0, k = 0;
            //int y = xDisplayStart - 1;
            //string Original_DEM =
"INPUT_FILES/CEM_PertShort.dat";

            //StreamReader read_originalDEM = new
StreamReader(Original_DEM);

            //string[] fileTrimmed_Original = new string[xmax *
(ymax * 3)];
            //string fileContent_DEMOriginal =
File.ReadAllText(Original_DEM);
            //fileContent_DEMOriginal =
fileContent_DEMOriginal.Replace("\r\n", " ");
            //fileContent_DEMOriginal =
Regex.Replace(fileContent_DEMOriginal, @"\s+", " ");
            //string[] fileSplit_DEMOriginal =
fileContent_DEMOriginal.Split(' ');

            //if (!File.Exists(Original_DEM))
            //{
            //    return;
            //}

            //// Remove headers from array
            //for (i = 12; i < fileSplit_DEMOriginal.Length - 1;
i++)
            //{
            //    fileTrimmed_Original[j] =
fileSplit_DEMOriginal[i];
            //    j++;
            //}

            //k = 0;

            //// Create TypeOfRock Array
            //for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
            //{
            //    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
            //    {
            //        TypeOfRock[x, y] =
Convert.ToChar(fileTrimmed_Original[k]);
            //        k++;
            //    }
            //}

            //// Create PercentFullRock Array
            //for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
            //{
            //    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
            //    {
            //        PercentFullRock[x, y] =
Convert.ToDouble(fileTrimmed_Original[k]);

            //        if (PercentFullRock[x, y] >= 1.0)
            //        {
            //            AllRock[x, y] = 1;

```

```

//      }
//      else
//      {
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//      }

//      k++;
//  }
//}

//// Create PercentFullSand Array
//for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
//{
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//        PercentFullSand[x, y] =
Convert.ToDouble(fileTrimmed_Original[k]);

//        if ((PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y]) >= MaxFillCell)
//        {
//            AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//        }
//        else
//        {
//            AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//        }

//        k++;
//    }
//}

//read_originalDEM.Close();
}
// Computer Generated DEM
//CM - need to sort out elevation if computer-
generated file is created!
else if (StartFromFile == 'n')
{
    InitConds();

    //if (InitialPert == 1)
    //{
    //    InitPert();
    //}

}

// Depth to ContinentalShelf (DepthShelf)
int r, s;
for (s = ymax - 1; s >= 0; s--)
{
    for (r = xDisplayStart; r < xDisplayEnd; r++)
    {
        Depth = InitialDepth + ((s - InitBeach) *
CellWidth * ShelfSlope);
        Distance = Depth / (ShorefaceSlope - ShelfSlope
/** Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i])*/);
        Yintercept = s + Distance /**
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i])*/ / CellWidth;

        DepthShelf[r, s] = Depth;

```

```

        if (DepthShelf[r, s] < DepthShoreface)
        {
            DepthShelf[r, s] = DepthShoreface;
        }
    }
}

// Max domain depth (reference point)
maxDomainDepth = DepthShelf[xDisplayEnd - 1, ymax - 1];

// Create Elevaiton Array
string DEMFilePath = "INPUT_FILES/Paper_coast_4.txt";
string fileContent_DEM = File.ReadAllText(DEMFilePath);
fileContent_DEM = fileContent_DEM.Replace("\r\n", " ");
fileContent_DEM = Regex.Replace(fileContent_DEM, @"\s+", " ");
");
string[] fileSplit_DEM = fileContent_DEM.Split(' ');

// Elevation (positive) and water depth (negative) array
int m = 12;
int a,b;
for (b = ymax - 1; b >= 0; b--)
{
    for (a = xDisplayStart; a < xDisplayEnd; a++)
    {
        if (Convert.ToDouble(fileSplit_DEM[m]) > 0)
        {
            Elevation[a, b] =
Convert.ToDouble(fileSplit_DEM[m]);
            WaterDepth0[a, b] = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            Elevation[a, b] = 0;
            WaterDepth0[a, b] =
Convert.ToDouble(fileSplit_DEM[m]) * -1;

            if (WaterDepth0[a, b] > DepthShelf[a, b])
            {
                WaterDepth0[a, b] = DepthShelf[a, b];
            }
        }
        m++;
    }
}

// Calculate Domain Depth from continental shelf depth
for (s = ymax - 1; s >= 0; s--)
{
    for (r = xDisplayStart; r < xDisplayEnd; r++)
    {
        DomainDepthCS[r, s] = maxDomainDepth -
DepthShelf[r, s];
    }
}

// Calculate amount of material in cells, BELOW 0m

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //StreamWriter DepthShelfMaterial_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/DepthShelfMaterial_File.dat");
        //StreamWriter TElevationCS_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationCS_File.dat");
        //StreamWriter Volume_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Volume_File.dat");
        //StreamWriter AboveWater_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/AboveWater_File.dat");
        //DepthShelfMaterial_FILE.Write("ncols 150" +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows 100" + Environment.NewLine + "xllcorner
0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine +
"cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine + "NODATA_value -9999" +
Environment.NewLine);
        //TElevationCS_FILE.Write("ncols 150" +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows 100" + Environment.NewLine + "xllcorner
0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine +
"cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine + "NODATA_value -9999" +
Environment.NewLine);
        //Volume_FILE.Write("ncols 150" + Environment.NewLine +
"nrows 100" + Environment.NewLine + "xllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "cellsize
100" + Environment.NewLine + "NODATA_value -9999" +
Environment.NewLine);
        //AboveWater_FILE.Write("ncols 150" + Environment.NewLine
+ "nrows 100" + Environment.NewLine + "xllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "cellsize
100" + Environment.NewLine + "NODATA_value -9999" +
Environment.NewLine);

        // Batch
        StreamWriter TElevationDomain_FILE;
        if (autorestart == 1)
        {
            TElevationDomain_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/TElevationDomain_File_" + Restart_count + "_" + counter + ".dat");
            wavesavename = "OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/wavedata.out";
        }
        else
        {
            TElevationDomain_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationDomain_File_" + counter +
".dat");
            wavesavename = "OUTPUT_FILES/wavedata.out";
        }

        TElevationDomain_FILE.Write("ncols 150" +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows 100" + Environment.NewLine + "xllcorner
0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine +
"cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine + "NODATA_value -9999" +
Environment.NewLine);

        for (s = ymax - 1; s >= 0; s--)
        {
            for (r = xDisplayStart; r < xDisplayEnd; r++)
            {
                DepthShelfMaterial[r, s] = DepthShelf[r, s] -
WaterDepth0[r, s]; // ONLY FOR
CELLS ABOVE THE WATER
                TElevationCS[r, s] = DepthShelfMaterial[r, s] +
Elevation[r, s];
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        TElevationDomain[r, s] = TElevationCS[r, s] +
DomainDepthCS[r, s];
        Volume[r, s] = TElevationCS[r, s] * CellWidth *
CellWidth;

        if (TElevationDomain[r,s] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold)
        {
            AboveWater[r, s] = 1;
        }
        else
        {
            AboveWater[r,s] = 0;
        }

        TElevationDomain_FILE.Write(TElevationDomain[r, s]
+ " ");
    }
    TElevationDomain_FILE.Write(Environment.NewLine);
}

TElevationDomain_FILE.Close();

// Finish off creating the arrays with PBCopy
PeriodicBoundaryCopy();

for (int wy = ymax - 1; wy >= 0; wy--)
{
    for (int ex = 0; ex < pbEnd; ex++)
    {
        TotalSediment += Volume[ex, wy];
    }
}

this.InfoStatusPanel.Text = "Loaded: type = " +
input_type_flag.ToString();
}

// Run when 'Start' button is clicked
private void start_button_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
{
    quitSaveButton.Visible = false;
    loadDataButton.Visible = false;
    SeeTabsButton.Visible = false;
}
private void main_loop(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
{
    int n;
    double tempflow=baseflow;
    double ince=cycle+60;

    gameClock = new Timer();

    pauseButton.Visible = true;
    resumeButton.Visible = true;
    quitSaveButton.Visible = true;
    SeeTabsButton.Visible = true;

```

```

        cycle = 0;
        time_1 = 1;
        time_factor = 60;
        time_factor = 1;
        save_time = cycle;
        time_1 = cycle;

        // Creates the system drawing graphics
        mygraphics = this.CreateGraphics();

        this.InfoStatusPanel.Text="Starting main loop";
        this.InfoStatusPanel.Text="Running";

        // Here we go into the main loop,
        // not sure why its within a game clock thing, but I
        copied this bit of code to get
        // the event handler to work - and it seems OK so why
        change it.
        // so the main loop is really in erodedepo()

        for(n=1;n<=1;n++)
        {
            gameClock.Interval = 1;
            gameClock.Tick += new EventHandler(CEMmain);
            gameClock.Start();
        }
    }

    //protected override void OnFormClosing(FormClosingEventArgs
e)
    //{
    //    pauseButton_Click(pauseButton, EventArgs.Empty);

    //    endTime = DateTime.Now.TimeOfDay;
    //    speed = (endTime - startTime);
    //    DialogResult Result = MessageBox.Show("Program at " +
(counter - 1) + " days \nDo you want to exit? \n\nSpeed: " +
speed.Hours + ":" + speed.Minutes + ":" + speed.Seconds +
"(hh:mm:ss)", " ", MessageBoxButtons.YesNo, MessageBoxIcon.Warning,
MessageBoxDefaultButton.Button1,
MessageBoxOptions.DefaultDesktopOnly);

        //    if (Result == DialogResult.Yes)
        //    {
        //        //StreamWriter EndVol = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/EndVol" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");
        //        //EndVol.Write("ncols " + ColumnTB.Text +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + RowsTB.Text + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);

        //        //for (int yyyy = ymax - 1; yyyy >= 0; yyyy--)
        //        //{
        //            for (int xxxx = 0; xxxx < pbEnd; xxxx++)
        //            {
        //                EndVol.Write(Volume[xxxx, yyyy] + " ");
        //                TotalVolumeEnd += Volume[xxxx, yyyy];
        //            }
        //        }

        //        if (AboveWater[xxxx, yyyy] == 1)
        //        {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //          //          TotalVolAboveEnd += Volume[xxxx,
YYYYY];
        //          //          }
        //          //          }
        //          //          EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine);
        //          //          }
        //          //EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine + TotalVolumeEnd
+ ", " + TotalVolAboveEnd);

        //          //EndVol.Close();

        //          //StreamWriter XY_End = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/XY_End_" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

        //          //for (int Loop = 0; Loop < X.Length; Loop++)
        //          //{
        //          //          XY_End.Write(X[Loop] + ", " + Y[Loop] +
Environment.NewLine);
        //          //          }
        //          //XY_End.Close();

        //          Application.Exit();
        //          }
        //          else
        //          {
        //          //          resumeButton_Click(resumeButton, EventArgs.Empty);
        //          }
        //          }
        //          }

        //private void Form1_FormClosing(object sender,
FormClosingEventArgs e)
        //{
        //          pauseButton_Click(pauseButton, EventArgs.Empty);

        //          endTime = DateTime.Now.TimeOfDay;
        //          speed = (endTime - startTime);
        //          DialogResult Result = MessageBox.Show("Program at " +
(counter - 1) + " days \nDo you want to exit? \n\nSpeed: " +
speed.Hours + ":" + speed.Minutes + ":" + speed.Seconds +
"(hh:mm:ss)", " ", MessageBoxButtons.YesNo, MessageBoxIcon.Warning,
MessageBoxDefaultButton.Button1,
MessageBoxOptions.DefaultDesktopOnly);

        //          if (Result == DialogResult.Yes)
        //          {
        //          //          StreamWriter EndVol = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/EndVol" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");
        //          //          EndVol.Write("ncols " + ColumnTB.Text +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + RowsTB.Text + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);

        //          //          for (int yyyy = ymax - 1; yyyy >= 0; yyyy--)
        //          //          {
        //          //          //          for (int xxxx = 0; xxxx < pbEnd; xxxx++)
        //          //          //          {
        //          //          //          EndVol.Write(Volume[xxxx, yyyy] + " ");
        //          //          //          TotalVolumeEnd += Volume[xxxx, yyyy];

```

```

//          if (AboveWater[xxxx, yyyy] == 1)
//          {
//              TotalVolAboveEnd += Volume[xxxx, yyyy];
//          }
//          EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//      }
//      EndVol.Write(Environment.NewLine + TotalVolumeEnd +
", " + TotalVolAboveEnd);

//      EndVol.Close();

//      StreamWriter XY_End = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/XY_End_" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

//      for (int Loop = 0; Loop < X.Length; Loop++)
//      {
//          XY_End.Write(X[Loop] + ", " + Y[Loop] +
Environment.NewLine);
//      }
//      XY_End.Close();

//      e.Cancel = false;
//  }
//  else
//  {
//      resumeButton_Click(resumeButton, EventArgs.Empty);
//  }
//}

void save_data(int typeflag, double tempcycle)
{
    int x,y,nn;
    string FILENAME = "OUTPUT_FILES/DEM.out";

    // turns file name into days from mins.
    tempcycle=tempcycle/1440;

    if (typeflag == 3 && tempcycle == 0)
    {
        FILENAME = "DEM_2.out";
    }

    if(typeflag >= 1 && typeflag < 4)
    {
        using (StreamWriter sw = new StreamWriter(FILENAME))
        {
            sw.Write("ncols          " + xmax);
            sw.Write("\n");
            sw.Write("nrows          " + (ymax*3));
            sw.Write("\n");

            for (nn=2; nn<=5; nn++)
            {
                sw.Write(inputheader[nn]);
                sw.Write("\n");
            }

            for(x = 0; x < xmax; x++)

```

```

        {
            for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
            {
                if (typeflag == 3)
                {
                    sw.Write(PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y]);
                    sw.Write(" ");
                }
            }
            sw.Write("\n");
        }
    }
}

// .....CEM
FUNCTIONS.....
..... //

private void CEMmain(Object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    if (counter == 0)
    {
        ResultsData();
    }

    //WetDryThreshold = (CellWidth/2) * Math.Tan // or
A.tan?((ShorefaceSlope * CellWidth) * (Math.PI/180)); //This will be
the local slope, but only using a threshold of 1m at the moment -
erosion/depo not dependnt on slope)

    // ----- PRIMARY
PROGRAM LOOP ----- //

    int xx;

    int x, y;

    // Random Seed - not sure if this is doing anything atm..
leaving it in for now just incase
    if (seed == -999)
    {
        RandZeroToOne();
    }
    else
    {
        RandZeroToOne();
    }

    if (autorestart == 1 && counter == 0)
    {
        WaveIn = 0;
        if (WaveIn == 0)
        {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        string UA_Wave_Content =
File.ReadAllText("INPUT_FILES/UA_WaveClimate/UA_WC_Run_" +
Restart_count + ".txt");
        UA_Wave_Content = UA_Wave_Content.Replace("\r\n",
" ");
        UA_Wave_Content = UA_Wave_Content.Replace("\t", "
");
        UA_Wave_Content = Regex.Replace(UA_Wave_Content,
@"\s+", " ");
        UA_Wave_Content = UA_Wave_Content.Replace(", ", "
");
        UA_Wave_Content = UA_Wave_Content.Trim();
string[] UA_Wave_Split = UA_Wave_Content.Split('
');

        Asym = Convert.ToDouble(UA_Wave_Split[0]);
        Highness = Convert.ToDouble(UA_Wave_Split[1]);
        Highness = 1 - Highness;
    }
    else
    { }

}

// FindWaveAngle Outside loop - loop is duration of
current wave climate
//if (autorestart == 0)
//{
//    WaveAngle = FindWaveAngle();
//}

if (Wavedata == 'y')
{
    WaveOutFile();
}

//-----
// Main Loop
//-----

// Loop for Duration at the current wave sign and wave
angle
for (xx = 0; xx < Duration; xx++)
{
    for (int yyy = ymax - 1; yyy >= 0; yyy--)
    {
        for (int xxx = 0; xxx < pbEnd; xxx++)
        {
            PreviousVolume[xxx, yyy] = Volume[xxx, yyy];
            VolumeChange[xxx, yyy] = 0;
        }
    }

    if (DoTidesTick.Checked == true)
    {
        // Set the water level
        WLCount++;
    }
}

```

```

        if (WLCount > WLArray.Length - 1)
        {
            //WaterLevel = WLArray[WLArray.Length - 1];
            WLCount = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            WaterLevel = WLArray[WLCount];
        }
    }
else
{
    WaterLevel = 0;
}
if (DoSLRTick.Checked == true)
{
    SLRCount++;

    if (SLRCount > SLRArray.Length - 1)
    {
        WaterLevel += SLR;
    }
    else
    {
        WaterLevel += SLRArray[SLRCount];
    }
}

PeriodicBoundaryCopy();

ZeroVars();

//-----
// Find the Beach (w or w/ tides)
//-----

// Initialize for Find Beach Cells (make sure strange
beach does not cause trouble)
FellOffArray = 'y';
FindStart = 1;
FellOffRockArray = 'y';
FindRockStart = 0;

// TIDES
if (DoTides == 1)
{
    FindTideBeach();

    while (FellOffArray == 'y')
    {
        FindTideBeachCells(FindStart);
        FindStart += FindCellError;

        if (FindStart > (pbEnd/2))//xDisplayStart + 1)
        {
            return;
        }
    }
}
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// NO TIDES
else if (DoTides == 0)
{
    while (FellOffArray == 'y')
    {
        // Look for beach - if you fall off of array,
bump over a little and try again
        FindBeachCells(FindStart);
        FindStart += FindCellError;

        //// Get Out if no good beach spots exist -
finish program
        //if (FindStart > (pbEnd / 2))
        //{
        //    FindLooseMaterial();
        //}

        // Get Out if no good beach spots exist -
finish program
        if (FindStart > (pbEnd/2))//xDisplayStart + 1)
        {
            return;
        }
    }

//while (FellOffRockArray == 'y')
//{
//    FindRockCells(FindRockStart);
//    FindRockStart += FindCellError;

//    if (FindRockStart > xDisplayStart + 1)
//    {
//        return;
//    }
//}

//-----
// Sediment Transport
//-----

//if (counter == 0)
//{
//    StreamWriter OriginalVol = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/OriginalVol.out");
//    OriginalVol.Write("ncols " + ColumnTB.Text +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + RowsTB.Text + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);

//    for (int yyy = ymax - 1; yyy >= 0; yyy--)
//    {
//        for (int xxx = 0; xxx < pbEnd; xxx++)
//        {
//            OriginalVol.Write(Volume[xxx, yyy] + "
");
//            TotalVolumeStart += Volume[xxx, yyy];

//            if (AboveWater[xxx, yyy] == 1)
//            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          TotalVolAboveStart += Volume[xxx,
yyy];
//          }
//          }
//          OriginalVol.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//          }
//          OriginalVol.Write(Environment.NewLine +
TotalVolumeStart + ", " + TotalVolAboveStart);

//          OriginalVol.Close();

//          StreamWriter XY_Start = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/XY_Start.out");

//          for (int Loop = 0; Loop < X.Length; Loop++)
//          {
//          XY_Start.Write(X[Loop] + ", " + Y[Loop] +
Environment.NewLine);
//          }
//          XY_Start.Close();

//}

//RockCalculations();

ShadowSweep();

DetermineAngles();

DetermineSedTransport();

//-----
// Sources/Sinks
//-----

//if (HaveSinks == 1)
//{
//    DoSink();
//    VolumeRecal();
//}
//if (NumSources >= 1)
//{
//    DoSource();
//    VolumeRecal();
//}

//-----
// More Sediment Transport
//-----

//CheckOverwashSweep();

FlowInCell();

FixFlow();

FindAverageShoreface();

TransportSedimentSweep();

VolumeRecal();

```

```

//RedrawCoastline();

//FixBeach();

//OopsImDiffusing();

OopsImLandsliding();

//VolumeRecal();

//PeriodicBoundaryCopy();

//-----
// Clean Up
//-----

// Age Empty Cells
if ((counter % AgeUpdate == 0) && SaveAge == 1)
{
    AgeCells();
}

//if (counter == 0)
//{
//    SandOutput();
//}

// Save File/Image
if (counter == 0)
{
    SaveImageFunct();
}

// Save results data
if (counter % Resuldata_freq == 0)
{
    ResultsData();
}

if ((counter % SaveFrequency == 0 && counter >
StartSavingAt) || (counter == StopAfter)) ||| (counter > 36500 &&
counter < 44000 && counter % 365 == 0))
{
    //if (SaveLine == 1)
    //{
    //    SaveLineToFile();
    //}
    //if (SaveFile == 1 || SaveFile == 2)
    //{
    //    SaveSandToFile();
    //}

    if (SaveImage == 1)
    {
        SaveImageFunct();
    }
}
}

```

```

//SandOutput ();

if ((counter == 0 || counter % SaveFrequency == 0) &&
SaveDEM == 1)
{
    // Batch
    StreamWriter TElevationDomain_FILE2;
    StreamWriter TElevationCS_FILE;
    StreamWriter TElevationCS_Above;
    StreamWriter TElevationCS_Below;
    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        TElevationDomain_FILE2 = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/TElevationDomain_File_" + Restart_count + "_" + counter + ".dat");
        TElevationCS_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/TElevationCS_File_" + Restart_count + "_" + counter + ".dat");
        TElevationCS_Above = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/TElevationCS_Above_" + Restart_count + "_" + counter + ".dat");
        TElevationCS_Below = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" + Restart_count +
"/TElevationCS_Below_" + Restart_count + "_" + counter + ".dat");
    }
    else
    {
        TElevationDomain_FILE2 = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationDomain_File_" + counter +
".dat");
        TElevationCS_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationCS_File_" + counter + ".dat");
        TElevationCS_Above = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationCS_Above_" + counter + ".dat");
        TElevationCS_Below = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TElevationCS_Below_" + counter + ".dat");
    }

    TElevationDomain_FILE2.Write("ncols " + pbEnd +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + ymax + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);
    TElevationCS_FILE.Write("ncols " + pbEnd +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + ymax + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);
    TElevationCS_Above.Write("ncols " + pbEnd +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + ymax + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);
    TElevationCS_Below.Write("ncols " + pbEnd +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + ymax + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);
}

```

```

        int r, s;
        for (s = ymax - 1; s >= 0; s--)
        {
            for (r = 0; r < pbEnd; r++)
            {

TElevationDomain_FILE2.Write(TElevationDomain[r, s] + " ");
                TElevationCS_FILE.Write(TElevationCS[r, s]
+ " ");

                if (AboveWater[r, s] == 1)
                {
TElevationCS_Above.Write(TElevationCS[r, s] + " ");
                    TElevationCS_Below.Write("0 ");
                }
                else if (AboveWater[r, s] == 0)
                {
                    TElevationCS_Above.Write("0 ");

TElevationCS_Below.Write(TElevationCS[r, s] + " ");
                    }
                    else
                    {
                        TElevationCS_Above.Write(-9999);
                        TElevationCS_Below.Write(-9999);
                    }
                }

TElevationDomain_FILE2.Write(Environment.NewLine);
                TElevationCS_FILE.Write(Environment.NewLine);
                TElevationCS_Above.Write(Environment.NewLine);
                TElevationCS_Below.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            }
            TElevationDomain_FILE2.Close();
            TElevationCS_FILE.Close();
            TElevationCS_Above.Close();
            TElevationCS_Below.Close();
        }

        counter++;
        cycle += time_factor / 60;

        // A day!
        time_factor = 86400;

        // Set the iteration number
        this.IterationStatusPanel.Text = "it = " +
counter.ToString();

        // Set the time
        if (cycle <= 1440)
        {
            this.TimeStatusPanel.Text = string.Format("t =
{0:F6} min", cycle); // 0 is the placeholder, F6 is the format (fixed
point, 6 decimal digits)
        }
        else
        {
            this.TimeStatusPanel.Text = string.Format("t =
{0:F6} day", cycle / 1440);
        }

```

```

        // save data every specified interval. Passes the
cycle which becomes the file extension
        if (cycle >= save_time)
        {
            save_time += saveinterval;
        }

        hit = 0;

        // ----- END OF CEM
MAIN -----

//-----
// Have we reached the end?
//-----

if (counter == (StopAfter + 1))
{
    // Batch
    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        if (Restart_count <= maxRuns)
        {
            Application.Restart();
        }
        else
        {
            StreamWriter Restart_count_zero = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Restart_Count_FILE.txt");
            Restart_count_zero.Write("0");
            Restart_count_zero.Close();
        }
        Application.Exit();
    }
    else
    {
        endTime = DateTime.Now.TimeOfDay;
        speed = (endTime - startTime);
        DialogResult Result =
MessageBox.Show(("Program at " + (counter - 1) + " days \nDo you want
to exit? \n\nSpeed: " + speed.Hours + ":" + speed.Minutes + ":" +
speed.Seconds + "(hh:mm:ss)", " ", MessageBoxButtons.YesNo,
MessageBoxIcon.Warning, MessageBoxDefaultButton.Button1,
MessageBoxOptions.DefaultDesktopOnly);

        if (Result == DialogResult.Yes)
        {
            StreamWriter EndVol = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/EndVol" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

            EndVol.Write("ncols " + ColumnTB.Text +
Environment.NewLine + "nrows " + RowsTB.Text + Environment.NewLine +
"xllcorner 0" + Environment.NewLine + "yllcorner 0" +
Environment.NewLine + "cellsize 100" + Environment.NewLine +
"NODATA_value -9999" + Environment.NewLine);

            for (int yyyy = ymax - 1; yyyy >= 0; yyyy-
-)
            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

                                for (int xxxx = 0; xxxx < pbEnd;
xxxxx++)
                                {
                                    EndVol.Write (Volume [xxxx, yyyy] +
" ");
                                    TotalVolumeEnd += Volume [xxxx,
yyyy];
                                    if (AboveWater [xxxx, yyyy] == 1)
                                    {
                                        TotalVolAboveEnd +=
Volume [xxxx, yyyy];
                                    }
                                }
                                EndVol.Write (Environment.NewLine);
                                EndVol.Write (Environment.NewLine +
TotalVolumeEnd + ", " + TotalVolAboveEnd);
                                EndVol.Close ();

                                StreamWriter XY_End = new
StreamWriter ("OUTPUT_FILES/MorphChange/XY_End_" + WaveFileTB.Text +
".out");

                                for (int Loop = 0; Loop < X.Length;
Loop++)
                                {
                                    XY_End.Write (X [Loop] + ", " + Y [Loop]
+ Environment.NewLine);
                                }
                                XY_End.Close ();
                                Application.Exit ();
                            }
                        }
                    }

// Set Up
void PeriodicBoundaryCopy ()
{
    // Simulates periodic boundary conditions by copying middle
section to front and end of arrays

    int x, y;

    for (x = xmax; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
    {
        for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
        {
            //AllBeach [x - xmax, y] = AllBeach [x, y];
            AllRock [x - xmax, y] = AllRock [x, y];
            TypeOfRock [x - xmax, y] = TypeOfRock [x, y];
            PercentFullSand [x - xmax, y] = PercentFullSand [x,
y];
            PercentFullRock [x - xmax, y] = PercentFullRock [x,
y];

```

```

        AboveTideOLD[x - xmax, y] = AboveTideOLD[x, y];
        AboveWater[x - xmax, y] = AboveWater[x, y];
        ShorelineCell[x - xmax, y] = ShorelineCell[x, y];
        Linear_Shoreline[x - xmax, y] =
Linear_Shoreline[x, y];

        Age[x - xmax, y] = Age[x, y];

        Elevation[x - xmax, y] = Elevation[x, y];
        Volume[x - xmax, y] = Volume[x, y];
        PreviousVolume[x - xmax, y] = PreviousVolume[x,
y];

        VolumeChange[x - xmax, y] = VolumeChange[x, y];
        DepthShelf[x - xmax, y] = DepthShelf[x, y];
        DepthShelfMaterial[x - xmax, y] =
DepthShelfMaterial[x, y];

        WaterDepth0[x - xmax, y] = WaterDepth0[x, y];
        DomainDepthCS[x - xmax, y] = DomainDepthCS[x, y];
        TElevationCS[x - xmax, y] = TElevationCS[x, y];
        TElevationDomain[x - xmax, y] =
TElevationDomain[x, y];
    }
}

for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xmax; x++)
{
    for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
    {
        //AllBeach[x + xmax, y] = AllBeach[x, y];
        AllRock[x + xmax, y] = AllRock[x, y];
        TypeOfRock[x + xmax, y] = TypeOfRock[x, y];
        PercentFullSand[x + xmax, y] = PercentFullSand[x,
y];

        PercentFullRock[x + xmax, y] = PercentFullRock[x,
y];

        AboveTideOLD[x + xmax, y] = AboveTideOLD[x, y];
        AboveWater[x + xmax, y] = AboveWater[x, y];
        ShorelineCell[x + xmax, y] = ShorelineCell[x, y];
        Linear_Shoreline[x + xmax, y] =
Linear_Shoreline[x, y];

        Age[x + xmax, y] = Age[x, y];

        Elevation[x + xmax, y] = Elevation[x, y];
        Volume[x + xmax, y] = Volume[x, y];
        PreviousVolume[x + xmax, y] = PreviousVolume[x,
y];

        VolumeChange[x + xmax, y] = VolumeChange[x, y];
        DepthShelf[x + xmax, y] = DepthShelf[x, y];
        DepthShelfMaterial[x + xmax, y] =
DepthShelfMaterial[x, y];

        WaterDepth0[x + xmax, y] = WaterDepth0[x, y];
        DomainDepthCS[x + xmax, y] = DomainDepthCS[x, y];
        TElevationCS[x + xmax, y] = TElevationCS[x, y];
        TElevationDomain[x + xmax, y] =
TElevationDomain[x, y];
    }
}

```

```

    }

    //for (int i = 0; i < 100; i++)
    //{
    //    Elevation[0, i] = 60;
    //    TElevationCS[0, i] = DepthShelf[0, i] + Elevation[0,
i];
    //    TElevationDomain[0, i] = TElevationCS[0, i] +
DomainDepthCS[0, i];
    //    Volume[0, i] = TElevationCS[0, i] * CellWidth *
CellWidth;
    //    PreviousVolume[0, i] = Volume[0, i];
    //    WaterDepth0[0, i] = 0;
    //    AboveWater[0, i] = 1;

    //    Elevation[1, i] = 60;
    //    TElevationCS[1, i] = DepthShelf[1, i] + Elevation[1,
i];
    //    TElevationDomain[1, i] = TElevationCS[1, i] +
DomainDepthCS[0, i];
    //    Volume[1, i] = TElevationCS[1, i] * CellWidth *
CellWidth;
    //    PreviousVolume[0, i] = Volume[0, i];
    //    WaterDepth0[1, i] = 0;
    //    AboveWater[1, i] = 1;
    //}

    ////StreamWriter AbovWater = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/abovpb.out");
    ////for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
    ////{
    ////    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
    ////    {
    ////        AbovWater.Write(AboveWater[x, y] + " ");
    ////    }
    ////    AbovWater.Write(Environment.NewLine);
    ////}
    ////AbovWater.Close();

    ////updateGraphics_Click_1(updateGraphicsButton,
EventArgs.Empty);
    }
    void AgeCells()
    {
        //// Age Cells

        //int x, y;

        //for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        //{
        //    for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
        //    {
        //        if (PercentFullSand[x, y] == 0)
        //        {
        //            Age[x, y] = counter % AgeMax;
        //        }
        //    }
        //}
    }
}

```

```

// Computer-Generated DEM
void InitConds()
{
    //counter = 0;

    //if (InitCType == 0)
    //{
    //    InitNormal();
    //}
    //else if (InitCType == 1)
    //{
    //    while (InitWiggly() == -1)
    //    {
    //    }
    //}

    //else if (InitCType == 2)
    //{
    //    initBlock();
    //}

    //if (InitialPert != 0)
    //{
    //    InitPert();
    //}

    //else
    //{
    //    MessageBox.Show("Error InitConds");
    //}
    //return;
}

void InitNormal()
{
    ///// Creates initial beach conditions
    ///// Flat beach with zone of AllBeach = 'y' separated by
AllBeach = 'n'
    ///// Block of rock parallel to beach begins at InitRock
LMV
    ///// LMV Assume that AllBeach = 'Y' for AllRock cells (and
All Full cells)
    ///// Bounding layer set to random fraction of fullness

    //int x, y, n;
    //int InitialBeach;
    //int InitialRock = 0;
    //int Amp; // Amplitude of cos curve
    //int blocks = 1; // Have hard stuff just as
blocks near the beach, or columns?

    //Amp = 10;

    //for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    //{
    //    for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
    //    {
    //        InitialBeach = InitBeach;
    //        InitialRock = InitRock;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          // shoreline is a cosine curve, diffusive LMV
//          if (DiffusiveHump == 1)
//          {
//              InitialRock = Convert.ToInt32((InitRock + (-
Amp * Math.Cos((2 * pi * x) / xmax)) - (InitBeach - InitRock - 1)));
//              InitialBeach = Convert.ToInt32((InitBeach +
(-Amp * Math.Cos((2 * pi * x) / xmax))));
//          }

//          if (y < InitialRock)
//          {
//              PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//              PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//              AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//              AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//          }

//          else if (y == InitialRock)
//          {
//              if (InitialSmoothRock == 1)
//              {
//                  PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.20;
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.80;
//              }
//              else
//              {
//                  PercentFullRock[x, y] = RandZeroToOne();
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1 -
PercentFullRock[x, y];
//              }

//              AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//              AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//          }

//          else if ((y > InitialRock) && (y <
InitialBeach))
//          {
//              PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//              PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1.0;
//              AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//              AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//          }

//          else if (y == InitialBeach)
//          {
//              if (InitialSmooth == 1)
//              {
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.5;
//              }
//              else
//              {
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y] = RandZeroToOne();
//              }
//              AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//              AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//          }

//          else if (y > InitialBeach)
//          {
//              PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0;
//              AllRock[x, y] = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//      }

//          Age[x, y] = 0;
//      }
//}

//if (NumberChunk != 0)
//{
//    for (y = 0; y <= ymax; y++) // Assign fast and slow
weathering portions
//    {
//        for (n = 0; n <= 2 * NumberChunk; n++)
//        {
//            for (x = n * ChunkLength; x < ((n + 2) *
ChunkLength); x++)
//            {
//                if (n % 3 == 0 && (blocks == 0 || x >
InitialRock - 3))
//                    // if even
//                    {
//                        TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';
//                    }
//                else
//                    // if odd
//                    {
//                        TypeOfRock[x, y] = 'f';
//                    }
//            }
//        }
//    }
//}
//else //make everything fast
//{
//    for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//    {
//        for (x = 0; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//        {
//            TypeOfRock[x, y] = 'f';
//        }
//    }
//}
}

void InitPert()
{
    //// Andrew's initial bump

    //int x, y;
    //int PWidth;
    //int PHeight;
    //int PYstart;

    //// Square perturbation
    //if (InitialPert == 1)
    //{
    //    PWidth = (xmax / (xmax / 2));
    //    PHeight = PWidth;
    //    PYstart = 2;

    //    // Fill AllBeach areas

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// while ((PYstart + PWidth) < pbEnd)
// {
//     for (y = InitBeach; y < InitBeach + PHeight;
y++)
//     {
//         for (x = PYstart; x < PYstart + PWidth; x++)
//         {
//             PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1.0;
//             AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//         }
//     }

//     //// PercentFull Top
//     //for (x = PYstart - 1; x <= PYstart + PWidth +
1; x++)
//     //{
//         PercentFullSand[x, InitBeach + PHeight +
1] = RandZeroToOne();
//     }

//     //// PercentFull Sides
//     //for (y = InitBeach; y <= InitBeach + PHeight;
y++)
//     //{
//         PercentFullSand[PYstart - 1, y] =
RandZeroToOne();
//         PercentFullSand[PYstart + PWidth + 1, y] =
RandZeroToOne();
//     }

//     PYstart = PYstart + (PWidth * 3);
// }
//}

//// Another Perturbation - steep point
//else if (InitialPert == 2)
//{
//     y = InitBeach;

//     PercentFullSand[17, y] = 0.8;
//     PercentFullSand[18, y] = 1.0;
//     AllBeach[18, y] = 1;
//     PercentFullSand[19, y] = 0.8;

//     y = InitBeach + 1;

//     PercentFullSand[17, y] = 0.6;
//     PercentFullSand[18, y] = 1.0;
//     AllBeach[18, y] = 1;
//     PercentFullSand[19, y] = 0.6;

//     y = InitBeach + 2;

//     PercentFullSand[17, y] = 0.2;
//     PercentFullSand[18, y] = 1.0;
//     AllBeach[18, y] = 1;
//     PercentFullSand[19, y] = 0.2;

//     y = InitBeach + 3;

//     PercentFullSand[18, y] = 0.3;
//}

```

```

///// Square perturbation
//else if (InitialPert == 3)
//{
//    PWidth = xmax / (xmax / 10);
//    PHeight = PWidth / 2;
//    PYstart = xmax - (PWidth / 2);

//    for (y = InitBeach; y < InitBeach + PHeight; y++)
//    {
//        for (x = PYstart; x < PYstart + PWidth; x++)
//        {
//            PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1.0;
//            AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//        }
//    }

//    ///// PercentFull Top
//    //for (x = PYstart - 1; x <= PYstart + PWidth + 1;
x++)
//    //{
//        PercentFullSand[x, InitBeach + PHeight + 1] =
RandZeroToOne();
//    }

//    ///// PercentFull Sides
//    //for (y = InitBeach; y <= InitBeach + PHeight; y++)
//    //{
//        PercentFullSand[PYstart - 1, y] =
RandZeroToOne();
//        PercentFullSand[PYstart + PWidth + 1, y] =
RandZeroToOne();
//    }
}

//CM: Comp-generated, but having issues getting these to work
using InitPert instead at the moment
int InitWiggly()
{
    //int x, y, curve;
    //int NumCurves = 4;
    //double[] RockLine = new double[pbEnd];
    //int curveFactor = 3;
    // decrease fundamental wavelength/increase frequency (by a factor) --
    // make it 1 for wavelength = xmax
    //double Amp, AmpMax = InitRock / 6.0;
    // maximum amplitude of the component sin waves
    //int Min = Convert.ToInt32(0.10 * ymax);
    //int Max = Convert.ToInt32(0.95 * ymax);
    // determines acceptable max amplitude of resulting curve
    //double[] BeachLine = new double[pbEnd];

    //for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    //{
//        RockLine[x] = InitRock;
//    }

    //for (curve = 1; curve <= NumCurves; curve++)
    //{
//        Amp = RandZeroToOne() * AmpMax;

```

```

//      for (x = 1; x < pbEnd; x++)
//      {
//          RockLine[x] = Math.Ceiling(RockLine[x] + (Amp *
Math.Sin(x * (curve * curveFactor) * 2.0 * pi / xmax)));
//          BeachLine[x] = RockLine[x] + 1;

//          if (RockLine[x] < Min || RockLine[x] > Max)
//          {
//              return -1;
//          }
//      }
//}

//for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//{
//    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
//    //{
//        //    if (y < RockLine[x])
//        //    {
//            //        PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//            //        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//            //        AllRock[x, y] = 'y';
//            //        TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';
//            //        AllBeach[x, y] = 'y';
//            //    }
//            //    else if (y == RockLine[x])
//            //    {
//                //        PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.5;
//                //        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.5;
//                //        AllRock[x, y] = 'n';
//                //        AllBeach[x, y] = 'n';
//                //    }
//            //    else
//            //    {
//                //        PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//                //        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//                //        AllRock[x, y] = 'n';
//                //        AllBeach[x, y] = 'n';
//                //    }

//            //    if (y == BeachLine[x])
//            //    {
//                //        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1.0;
//            //    }

//            //    Age[x, y] = 0;
//            //}
//            //}
//            {
//                TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';

//            if (y < RockLine[x])
//            {
//                PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//                PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//                AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//                AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//            }
//            else if (y == RockLine[x])
//            {
//                PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;

```

```

//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.5;
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//      }
//      else
//      {
//          PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//      }
//      Age[x, y] = 0;
//  }
//}
return 0;
}

int initBlock()
{
//int x, y, n;
//int blockHeight = 4;
//int NumBlocks = 2;      // makes NumBlocks evenly spaced
blocks
//int blockWidth = (xmax / (NumBlocks * 2));

//for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//{
//  for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
//  {
//      TypeOfRock[x, y] = 'f';
//      if (y < InitRock)
//      {
//          PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//          AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//      }
//      else if (y < InitBeach)
//      {
//          PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 1.0;
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//      }
//      else if (y == InitBeach)
//      {
//          PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = RandZeroToOne();
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//      }
//      else
//      {
//          PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//          AllRock[x, y] = 0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//      }
//      Age[x, y] = 0;
//  }
//}
///// the regularly-spaced blocks

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//for (n = 1; n <= NumBlocks; n++)
//{
//    for (y = InitRock; y >= InitRock - blockHeight; y--)
//    {
//        // block starts @ upper left corner
//        for (x = xDisplayStart + n * xmax / (NumBlocks +
1); x < xDisplayStart + n * xmax / (NumBlocks + 1) + blockWidth && x <
pbEnd; x++)
//            {
//                PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//                PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//                AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//                TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';
//                AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//            }
//    }
//}
///// now here's space for ad hoc blocks
///// ad hoc block 1
//for (y = InitRock; y >= InitRock - blockHeight; y--)
//{
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayStart + 10; x++)
//    {
//        PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//        AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//        TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';
//        AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//    }
//}
///// ad hoc block 2
//for (y = InitRock; y >= InitRock - blockHeight; y--)
//{
//    for (x = xDisplayEnd - 90; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//        PercentFullRock[x, y] = 1.0;
//        PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//        AllRock[x, y] = 1;
//        TypeOfRock[x, y] = 's';
//        AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
//    }
//}
return 0;
}

```

```

// Get Wave Climate
double FindWaveAngle()
{
    // calculates wave angle for given time step

    double Angle = 0.0;

    double RandBin;           // Random number to pick wave
angle bin
    double RandAngle;        // Random number to pick wave
angle within the bin
    int flag = 1;
    int i = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (WaveIn == 0)
        {
            // Method using wave probability step function
            // variable Asym will determine fractional
distribution of waves coming from the
            // positive direction (positive direction coming
from left) -i.e. fractional wave asymmetry
            // Note: Highness actually means lowness, for some
reason

            Angle = RandZeroToOne() * pi / 4.0;

            if (RandZeroToOne() >= Highness)
            {
                Angle += pi / 4.0;                // make
high angle
            }

            if (RandZeroToOne() >= Asym)
            {
                Angle = -1.0 * Angle;
            }
        }

        // Method using input binned wave distribution -
variables: WaveProb[], WaveMax[], previously input from file using
ReadWaveIn()
        if (WaveIn == 1)
        {
            RandBin = RandZeroToOne();
            RandAngle = RandZeroToOne();

            while (flag == 1)
            {
                i++;

                if (RandBin < WaveProb[i])
                {
                    flag = 0;
                }
            }

            Angle = -(RandAngle * (WaveMax[i] - WaveMax[i - 1]) +
WaveMax[i - 1]) * pi / 180;
        }

        if (WaveIn == 2)
        {
            RealWaveIn();                //
Read real data (angle/period/height)

            Angle = WaveAngleIn + coastrotation;                //
Align waveclimate to coastline in CEM

            //if (Angle >= 180.0)
            //{
            //    Angle -= 360.0;                //
Conversion to CEM angles (-180 -- 0 -- +180)
            //}

            ////Angle *= -1;
// -1 is there as wave angle is from 90 in the west to -90 in the east

```

```

        //Period = WavePeriodIn * waveperiodchange;
        //OffShoreWvHt = WaveHeightIn * waveheightchange;

        //if ((Angle > 90) || (Angle < -90))
        //{
        //    Angle = 0;
        //}
if waves were to come from behind coast*/
        //    OffShoreWvHt = 1e-10;
if waves were to come from behind coast set to inf small
        //}

        //ADDED
        Period = WavePeriodIn;
        OffShoreWvHt = WaveHeightIn;

        Angle /= radtodeg;
    }

    if (WaveIn == 3)
    {
        WaveAngleIn = Convert.ToDouble(this.WAngleTB.Text);
        WavePeriodIn = Convert.ToDouble(this.WPeriodTB.Text);
        WaveHeightIn = Convert.ToDouble(this.WHeightTB.Text);

        Angle = WaveAngleIn + coastrotation;
// Align waveclimate to coastline in CEM

        if (Angle >= 180.0)
        {
            Angle -= 360.0;
// Conversion to CEM angles (-180 -- 0 -- +180)
        }

        //Angle *= -1;
// -1 is there as wave angle is from 90 in the west to -90 in the east

        Period = WavePeriodIn * waveperiodchange;
        OffShoreWvHt = WaveHeightIn * waveheightchange;

        if ((Angle > 90) || (Angle < -90))
        {
            Angle = 0;
// if waves were to come from behind coast*/
            OffShoreWvHt = 1e-10;
// if waves were to come from behind coast set to inf small
        }

        Angle /= radtodeg;
    }

    return Angle;
}

void RealWaveIn()
{
    // Input real wave data from file
    // Batch
    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        readwavename = "INPUT_FILES/WaveClimate/WaveClimate_"
+ Restart_count + ".dat";

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        this.WaveFileTB.Text = "WaveClimate_" + Restart_count;
    }
    else
    {
        readwavename = "INPUT_FILES/WaveClimate/" +
this.WaveFileTB.Text;
    }

    //WaveAngleIn = 67.5;
    //WavePeriodIn = 6.65;
    //WaveHeightIn = 1.85;

    if (counter == 0)
    {
        StreamReader ReadWaveFile = new
StreamReader(readwavename);

        realWave_Content = File.ReadAllText(readwavename);
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\r\n", "
");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\t", "
");
        realWave_Content = Regex.Replace(realWave_Content,
@"\s+", " ");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Trim();
        realWave_Split = realWave_Content.Split(' ');

        ReadWaveFile.Close();

        Wavecount = 0;
    }

    if (Wavecount == realWave_Split.Length)
    {
        Wavecount = 0;
    }

    WaveAngleIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[Wavecount]);
    Wavecount++;
    WavePeriodIn =
Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[Wavecount]);
    Wavecount++;
    WaveHeightIn =
Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[Wavecount]);
    Wavecount++;
}

void ReadWaveIn()
{
    //      ////////// HAVE NOT YET CONVERTED!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!!
    //      ////      /*

    //      ////      // Input Wave Distribution

    //      ////      int i;

    //      ////      StreamReader ReadWaveFile = new
StreamReader(readwavename);

    //      ////      for (i = 0; i <= 36; i++)
    //      ////      {
    //      ////          WaveMax[i] = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      ////      WaveProb[i] = 0;
//      ////      }

//      ////      NumWaveBins = ReadWaveFile.Read();
//      ////      fscanf(ReadWaveFile, " %d \n", &NumWaveBins);
//      ////      printf("Wave Bins %d \n",NumWaveBins);

//      ////      WaveMax[0] = -90;
//      ////      WaveProb[0] = 0;

//      ////      for (i=1 ; i<= NumWaveBins ; i++)
//      ////      {
//      ////      fscanf(ReadWaveFile, " %f %f", &WaveMax[i] ,
&WaveProb[i]);
//      ////      printf("i= %d Wave= %f Prob= %f \n",i,
WaveMax[i], WaveProb[i]);
//      ////      }

//      ////      fclose(ReadWaveFile);
//      ////      printf("wave file read! \n");

//      ////      */
//      }

// Beach Misc
double MassCount()
{
    //// Counts the total volume occupied by beach cells
    //// Uses same algorithm as AdjustShore
    //// returns a float of the total sum
    //// Uses AllBeach[][] and PercentFullSand[][]
    //// and InitialDepth, CellWidth, ShelfSlope

    //int x, y;
    //double DepthMC;          // Depth of current cell
    double Mass = 0.0;

    //for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
    //{
    //    DepthMC = InitialDepth + ((y - InitBeach) *
CellWidth * ShelfSlope);

    //    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    //    {
    //        Mass += PercentFullSand[x, y] * DepthMC;
    //    }
    //}

    return Mass;
}

// Find shoreline cells - with tides
void FindTideBeach()
{
    int x, y, i;

```

```

change          // Don't need this beacuse only the shorelne ones will
                for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
                {
                    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
                    {
                        if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold)
                        {
                            AboveWater[x, y] = 1;
                        }
                        else
                        {
                            AboveWater[x, y] = 0;
                        }
                    }
                }

void FindTideBeachCells(int Xstart)
{
    // Determines locations of beach cells moving from left to
right direction
    // This function will affect and determine the global
arrays: X[] and Y[]
    // This function calls FindNextCell
    // This will define TotalBeachCells for this time step

    int x = Xstart;
    int ystart = ymax - 1;
    int z = 1;

    // Finding the start position of the tide beach
    //while (AboveTideOLD[x, ystart] == false)
    while (AboveWater[x, ystart] == 0)
    {
        ystart -= 1;
    }

    //ystart += 1;

    X[0] = Xstart;
    Y[0] = ystart + 1;

    //Need to give these some values for 'weathered rock'
    XBehind[0] = X[0];
    YBehind[0] = Y[0];

    ystart = ymax - 1;
    //while (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, ystart] == false)
    while (AboveWater[x + 1, ystart] == 0)
    {
        ystart -= 1;
    }

    //ystart += 1;

```

```

X[1] = Xstart + 1;
Y[1] = ystart + 1;

XBehind[1] = X[0];
YBehind[1] = Y[0];

while ((X[z] < pbEnd - 1) && (z < MaxBeachLength - 1))
{
    z++;

    NextX = -2;
    NextY = -2;
    BehindX = -2;
    BehindY = -2;

    FindNextTideCell(X[z - 1], Y[z - 1], z - 1);
    X[z] = NextX;
    Y[z] = NextY;
    XBehind[z] = BehindX;
    YBehind[z] = BehindY;

    //Print to file X[] and Y[] Arrays
    //XYFile.Write(counter + " " + z + " " + X[z] + " " +
Y[z] + Environment.NewLine);

    // If return to start point or go off left side of
array, going the wrong direction
    // Jump off and start again closer to middle
    if ((NextX < 1) || ((NextX == X[0]) && (NextY ==
Y[0])) || (z > MaxBeachLength - 2))
    {
        FellOffArray = 'y';
        ZeroVars();
        return;
    }
}
TotalBeachCells = z;
FellOffArray = 'n';

if(counter == 0)
{
    Array.Copy(X, initialX, X.Length);
    Array.Copy(Y, initialY, Y.Length);
}

Array.Clear(ShorelineCell, 0, ShorelineCell.Length);

for (int ii = 0; ii < TotalBeachCells; ii++)
{
    ShorelineCell[X[ii], Y[ii]] = 1;
}

//XYFile.Close();
}

//void FindNextTideCell(int x, int y, int z)
//{
//    // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in
the general positive X direction
//    // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
for the next beach cell

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      // This function will use but not affect the global
arrays: AllBeach [][], X[], and Y[]

//      // Came from left
//      if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
//      {
//          // Top
//          if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Left

```

```

//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

//      // Came from top left
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] -
1))
//      {
//          // Top Right
//          if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom

```

```

//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

//      // Came from above
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
//      {
//          // Right
//          if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Right
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)

```

```

//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Above
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;

```

```

//          return;
//      }
//  }

//  // Came from upper right
//  else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] +
1))
//  {
//      // Bottom Right
//      if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;

```

```

//         return;
//     }
//     // Top
//     else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//     {
//         NextX = x;
//         NextY = y + 1;
//         BehindX = NextX;
//         BehindY = NextY + 1;
//         //BehindX = x;
//         //BehindY = y;
//         return;
//     }
//     // Upper Right
//     else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//     {
//         NextX = x + 1;
//         NextY = y + 1;
//         BehindX = NextX;
//         BehindY = NextY + 1;
//         //BehindX = x;
//         //BehindY = y;
//         return;
//     }
// }

// // Came from right
// else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
// {
//     // Bottom
//     if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//     {
//         NextX = x;
//         NextY = y - 1;
//         BehindX = NextX;
//         BehindY = NextY + 1;
//         //BehindX = x;
//         //BehindY = y;
//         return;
//     }
//     // Bottom left
//     else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//     {
//         NextX = x - 1;
//         NextY = y - 1;
//         BehindX = NextX;
//         BehindY = NextY + 1;
//         //BehindX = x;
//         //BehindY = y;
//         return;
//     }
//     // Left
//     else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//     {
//         NextX = x - 1;
//         NextY = y;
//         BehindX = NextX;
//         BehindY = NextY + 1;
//         //BehindX = x;
//         //BehindY = y;
//         return;
//     }
// }

```

```

//      // Top Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//      // Came from lower right
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] +
1))
//      {
//          // Bottom left
//          if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Left

```

```

//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }

//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 2, y] == true
//              || AboveTideOLD[x + 2, y - 1] == true
//              || AboveTideOLD[x + 2, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;

```

```

//      BehindX = NextX + 1;
//      BehindY = NextY;
//      //BehindX = x;
//      //BehindY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  // LowerRight
//  else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//  {
//      NextX = x + 1;
//      NextY = y - 1;
//      BehindX = NextX + 1;
//      BehindY = NextY;
//      //BehindX = x;
//      //BehindY = y;
//      return;
//  }

//  }
//  // Came from below
//  else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
//  {
//      // Left
//      if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;

```

```

//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Below
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//      // Came from bottom left
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] -
1))
//      {
//          // Top Left
//          if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y + 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX + 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top
//          else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y + 1] == true)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX + 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;

```

```

//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y + 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Right
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x + 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Left
//      else if (AboveTideOLD[x - 1, y - 1] == true)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//  }
//}

```

```

/* This version is for the volumes */
void FindNextTideCell_1(int x, int y, int z)
{
    // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in the
    general positive X direction
    // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
    for the next beach cell
    // This function will use but not affect the global
    arrays: AllBeach [][], X[], and Y[]

    // Came from left
    if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
    {
        // Top
        if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y + 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Top Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + 1;
            NextY = y + 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + 1;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + 1;
            NextY = y - 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom
        else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - 1;

```

```

        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from top left
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
{
    // Top Right
    if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;

```

```

        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from above
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
{
    // Right
    if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;

```

```

        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Above

```

```

else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX - 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
}

// Came from upper right
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
{
    // Bottom Right
    if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)

```

```

    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
// Top
else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY + 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
// Upper Right
else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY + 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
}

// Came from right
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
{
    // Bottom
    if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;

```

```

        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from lower right
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
{
    // Bottom left
    if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;

```

```

        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // LowerRight

```

```

else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y - 1;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}

else if (AboveWater[x + 2, y] == 1
|| AboveWater[x + 2, y - 1] == 1
|| AboveWater[x + 2, y + 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
}
// Came from below
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
{
    // Left
    if (AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)

```

```

    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
// Right
else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
// Bottom Right
else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y - 1;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
// Below
else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x;
    NextY = y - 1;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
}
// Came from bottom left
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
{
    // Top Left
    if (AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;

```

```

        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
}

```

```

    }
}

void FindNextTideCell_Jan23(int x, int y, int z)
{
    // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in the
    general positive X direction
    // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
    for the next beach cell
    // This function will use but not affect the global
    arrays: AllBeach [][], X[], and Y[]

    int a = 1;          // if can't find where we came from,
    look + cell out again
    int b = 1;          // if we can't find the next cell,
    look another cell out

    //int getOut_a = 0;

    //while (getOut_a == 0 && Y[z - a] > 0 && X[z - a] > 0)
    //{
    // Came from left
    if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z]) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
    {
        int getOut = 0;

        while (getOut == 0)
        {
            // Top
            if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
            {
                NextX = x;
                NextY = y + b;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - b;
                //BehindX = x;
                //BehindY = y;
                getOut = 1;
                return;
            }
            // Top Right
            else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
            {
                NextX = x + b;
                NextY = y + b;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - b;
                //BehindX = x;
                //BehindY = y;
                getOut = 1;
                return;
            }
            // Right
            else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
            {
                NextX = x + b;
                NextY = y;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - b;
                //BehindX = x;
                //BehindY = y;
                getOut = 1;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from top left
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
{

```

```

int getOut = 0;

while (getOut == 0)
{
    // Top Right
    if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
    }
}

```

```

        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from above
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z]))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Right
        if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Above
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;

```

```

        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from upper right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom Right
        if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom
        else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Upper Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z]) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom
        if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;

```

```

        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from lower right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }

    // LowerRight
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }

    //else if (AboveWater[x + 2, y] == 1
    //    || AboveWater[x + 2, y - 1] == 1
    //    || AboveWater[x + 2, y + 1] == 1)
    //{
    //    NextX = x + 1;
    //    NextY = y;
    //    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    //    BehindY = NextY;
    //    //BehindX = x;

```

```

//      //BehindY = y;
//      return;
//}

else
{
    b++;
    getOut = 0;
}
}
}
// Came from below
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z]))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top
        else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Below
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from bottom left
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Top Left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;

```

```

        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
//}
//else
//{
//    a++;
//    getOut_a = 0;
//}
}
else if (X[z - a] < X[z])
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0 && (x + b < pbEnd - 1))
    {
        // Top
        if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;

```

```

        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
else if (X[z - a] > X[z])
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0 && (x - b > 0))
    {
        // Bottom
        if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;

```

```

        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
}

void FindNextTideCell(int x, int y, int z)
{
    // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in the
    general positive X direction
    // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
    for the next beach cell
    // This function will use but not affect the global
    arrays: AllBeach [][], X[], and Y[]

    int a = 1;          // if can't find where we came from,
    look + cell out again
    int b = 1;          // if we can't find the next cell,
    look another cell out

    //int getOut_a = 0;

    //while (getOut_a == 0 && Y[z - a] > 0 && X[z - a] > 0)
    //{
    // Came from left
    if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z]) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
    {
        int getOut = 0;

        while (getOut == 0)
        {
            // Top
            if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
            {
                NextX = x;
                NextY = y + b;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - b;
                //BehindX = x;
                //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }

```

```

    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from top left
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Top Right
        if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from above
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z]))

```

```

{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Right
        if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom
        else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Above
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX - b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from upper right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] + a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom Right
        if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom
        else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX - b;
            BehindY = NextY;

```

```

        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Upper Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z]) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom
        if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top Left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from lower right
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] + a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Bottom left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y - b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + b;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;

```

```

        return;
    }

    // LowerRight
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }

    //else if (AboveWater[x + 2, y] == 1
    //    || AboveWater[x + 2, y - 1] == 1
    //    || AboveWater[x + 2, y + 1] == 1)
    //{
    //    NextX = x + 1;
    //    NextY = y;
    //    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    //    BehindY = NextY;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}

    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from below
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z]))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top left
        else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;

```

```

        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Below
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;

```

```

        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}

// Came from bottom left
else if ((Y[z - a] == Y[z] - a) && (X[z - a] == X[z] - a))
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0)
    {
        // Top Left
        if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top
        else if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX + b;
            BehindY = NextY;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Top Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y + b;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - b;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            getOut = 1;
            return;
        }
        // Right
        else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x + b;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY - b;
            //BehindX = x;

```

```

        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
//}
//else
//{
//    a++;
//    getOut_a = 0;
//}
}
else if (X[z - a] < X[z])
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0 && (x + b < pbEnd - 1))
    {
        // Top
        if (AboveWater[x, y + b] == 1)
        {

```

```

        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX + b;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if (AboveWater[x + b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
else if (X[z - a] > X[z])
{
    int getOut = 0;

    while (getOut == 0 && (x - b > 0))
    {
        // Bottom
        if (AboveWater[x, y - b] == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;

```

```

        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y - b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y - b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if (AboveWater[x - b, y + b] == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - b;
        NextY = y + b;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + b;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        getOut = 1;
        return;
    }
    else
    {
        b++;
        getOut = 0;
    }
}
}

// Find Shoreline cells - withOUT tides
void FindBeachCells(int XStart)
{
    // Determines locations of beach cells moving from left to
    right direction
    // This function will affect and determine the global
    arrays: X[] and Y[]
    // This function calls FindNextCell

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// This will define TotalBeachCells for this time step

int x, z, ystart;

ystart = ymax - 1;
x = XStart;

// Two while loops finding the start position of the beach
(0) and second position (1)
//while (AllBeach[x, ystart] == 0)
while (AboveWater[x, ystart] == 0)
{
    ystart -- 1;
}

// Step back to where partially full beach
//ystart += 1;

X[0] = XStart;
Y[0] = ystart;

//Need to give these some values for 'weathered rock'
XBehind[0] = X[0];
YBehind[0] = Y[0];

//while (AllBeach[x + 1, ystart] == 0)
while (AboveWater[x + 1, ystart] == 0)
{
    ystart -- 1;
}

//ystart += 1;

X[1] = XStart + 1;
Y[1] = ystart;

XBehind[1] = X[0];
YBehind[1] = Y[0];

//XYFile.Write("Iteration: " + "Z: " + "X: " + "Y: " +
Environment.NewLine);

//XYFile.Write(counter + " 0 " + X[0] + " " + Y[0] +
Environment.NewLine
//      + counter + " 1 " + X[1] + " " + Y[1] +
Environment.NewLine);

z = 1;

while ((X[z] < pbEnd - 1) && (z < MaxBeachLength - 1))
{
    z++;

    NextX = -2;
    NextY = -2;
    BehindX = -2;
    BehindY = -2;

    FindNextCell(X[z - 1], Y[z - 1], z - 1);
    X[z] = NextX;
    Y[z] = NextY;
    XBehind[z] = BehindX;

```

```

        YBehind[z] = BehindY;

        // If return to start point or go off left side of
array, going the wrong direction
        // Jump off and start again closer to middle

        //Print to file X[] and Y[] Arrays
        //XYFile.Write(counter + " " + z + " " + X[z] + " " +
Y[z] + Environment.NewLine);

        if ((NextX < 1) || ((NextX == X[0]) && (NextY ==
Y[0])) || (z > MaxBeachLength - 2))
        {
            FellOffArray = 'y';
            ZeroVars();
            return;
        }
    }
    TotalBeachCells = z;
    FellOffArray = 'n';

    //XYFile.Close();
}

//void FindNextCell(int x, int y, int z)
//{
//    // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in
the general positive X direction
//    // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
for the next beach cell
//    // This function will use but not affect the global
arrays: AllBeach [], X[], and Y[]

//    // Came from left
//    if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
//    {
//        // Top
//        if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] + PercentFullRock[x,
y + 1]) > 0.0)
//        {
//            NextX = x;
//            NextY = y + 1;
//            BehindX = NextX;
//            BehindY = NextY - 1;
//            //BehindX = x;
//            //BehindY = y;
//            return;
//        }
//        // Top Right
//        else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//        {
//            NextX = x + 1;
//            NextY = y + 1;
//            BehindX = NextX;
//            BehindY = NextY - 1;
//            //BehindX = x;
//            //BehindY = y;
//            return;
//        }
//        // Right

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      //{
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      // Came from top left
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] -
1))
//      {
//          // Top Right
//          if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Right
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Right
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY - 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Left
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      ////// Top Left
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      //{
//          //      NextX = x - 1;
//          //      NextY = y + 1;
//          //      BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          //      BehindY = NextY;
//          //      //BehindX = x;
//          //      //BehindY = y;
//          //      return;
//          //}
//      }

//      // Came from above
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
//      {
//          // Right
//          if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] + PercentFullRock[x +
1, y]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom Right
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX - 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y - 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      ////// Top
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      //{{
//          //      NextX = x;
//          //      NextY = y + 1;
//          //      BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          //      BehindY = NextY;
//          //      //BehindX = x;
//          //      //BehindY = y;
//          //      return;
//          //}}
//      }

//      // Came from upper right
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] +
1))
//      {
//          // Bottom Right

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX - 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      //// Right
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      //{
//          //      NextX = x + 1;
//          //      NextY = y + 1;
//          //      BehindX = NextX;
//          //      BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //      //BehindX = x;
//          //      //BehindY = y;
//          //      return;
//          //}
//      }

//      // Came from right
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
//      {
//          // Bottom
//          if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] + PercentFullRock[x,
y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Bottom left
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y - 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Left
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//      }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          // Top Left
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top Right
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          //// Right
//          //else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
//          //{
//              NextX = x + 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX;
//              BehindY = NextY + 1;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          }

//          // Came from lower right
//          else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] +
1))
//          {
//              // Bottom left
//              if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//              {
//                  NextX = x - 1;
//                  NextY = y - 1;
//                  BehindX = NextX;
//                  BehindY = NextY + 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Left
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x - 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY + 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          return;
//      }

//      else if (PercentFullSand[x + 2, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 2, y] > 0.0
//          || PercentFullSand[x + 2, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 2, y - 1] > 0.0
//          || PercentFullSand[x + 2, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 2, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }

//      //// Bottom Right
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//      //{
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }

//      // Came from below
//      else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
//      {
//          // Left
//          if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] + PercentFullRock[x -
1, y]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y;
//              BehindX = NextX + 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top left
//          else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextX = x - 1;
//              NextY = y + 1;
//              BehindX = NextX + 1;
//              BehindY = NextY;
//              //BehindX = x;
//              //BehindY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          // Top

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Top Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y + 1;
//          BehindX = NextX + 1;
//          BehindY = NextY;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Bottom Right
//      else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1]) +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextX = x + 1;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      // Below
//      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1]) +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      //{
//          NextX = x;
//          NextY = y - 1;
//          BehindX = NextX;
//          BehindY = NextY - 1;
//          //BehindX = x;
//          //BehindY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//      // Came from bottom left

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

1)) // else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] -
// {
// // Top Left
// // if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
// {
//     NextX = x - 1;
//     NextY = y + 1;
//     BehindX = NextX + 1;
//     BehindY = NextY;
//     //BehindX = x;
//     //BehindY = y;
//     return;
// }
// // Top
// // else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0)
// {
//     NextX = x;
//     NextY = y + 1;
//     BehindX = NextX + 1;
//     BehindY = NextY;
//     //BehindX = x;
//     //BehindY = y;
//     return;
// }
// // Top Right
// // else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
// {
//     NextX = x + 1;
//     NextY = y + 1;
//     BehindX = NextX;
//     BehindY = NextY - 1;
//     //BehindX = x;
//     //BehindY = y;
//     return;
// }
// // Right
// // else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0)
// {
//     NextX = x + 1;
//     NextY = y;
//     BehindX = NextX;
//     BehindY = NextY - 1;
//     //BehindX = x;
//     //BehindY = y;
//     return;
// }
// // Bottom Right
// // else if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
// {
//     NextX = x + 1;
//     NextY = y - 1;
//     BehindX = NextX;
//     BehindY = NextY - 1;
//     //BehindX = x;
//     //BehindY = y;
//     return;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //      }
        //      // Bottom
        //      else if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0)
        //      {
        //          NextX = x;
        //          NextY = y - 1;
        //          BehindX = NextX;
        //          BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //          //BehindX = x;
        //          //BehindY = y;
        //          return;
        //      }
        //      // Bottom Left
        //      //else if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
        //      //{
        //          //      NextX = x - 1;
        //          //      NextY = y - 1;
        //          //      BehindX = NextX;
        //          //      BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //          //          //BehindX = x;
        //          //          //BehindY = y;
        //          //          return;
        //      }
        //      }
        //  }
    //}

    // Rock Calculations (weathering)

    void FindNextCell(int x, int y, int z)
    {
        // Function to find next cell that is beach moving in the
general positive X direction
        // changes global variables NextX and NextY, coordinates
for the next beach cell
        // This function will use but not affect the global
arrays: AllBeach [][], X[], and Y[]

        // Came from left
        if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
        {
            // Top
            if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1]) == 1)
            {
                NextX = x;
                NextY = y + 1;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - 1;
                //BehindX = x;
                //BehindY = y;
                return;
            }
            // Top Right
            else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
            {
                NextX = x + 1;
                NextY = y + 1;
                BehindX = NextX;
                BehindY = NextY - 1;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    ///// Left
    //else if ((Elevation[x - 1, y] + PercentFullRock[x -
1, y]) > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x - 1;
    //    NextY = y;
    //    BehindX = NextX;
    //    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}
}

```

```

// Came from top left
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
{
    // Top Right
    if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
    {

```

```

        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    ///// Top Left
    //else if ((Elevation[x - 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x - 1;
    //    NextY = y + 1;
    //    BehindX = NextX - 1;
    //    BehindY = NextY;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}
}

// Came from above
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
{
    // Right
    if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {

```

```

        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    //else if ((Elevation[x, y + 1] + PercentFullRock[x, y
+ 1]) > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x;
    //    NextY = y + 1;
    //    BehindX = NextX - 1;
    //    BehindY = NextY;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}
}

// Came from upper right
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] + 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
{
    // Bottom Right
    if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
    {

```

```

        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX - 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    }
    //// Right
    //else if ((Elevation[x + 1, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1]) > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x + 1;
    //    NextY = y + 1;
    //    BehindX = NextX;
    //    BehindY = NextY + 1;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;

```

```

        // return;
        //}
    }

    // Came from right
    else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z]) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
    {
        // Bottom
        if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y - 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Bottom left
        else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - 1;
            NextY = y - 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Left
        else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - 1;
            NextY = y;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Top Left
        else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
        {
            NextX = x - 1;
            NextY = y + 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
        // Top
        else if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1]) == 1)
        {
            NextX = x;
            NextY = y + 1;
            BehindX = NextX;
            BehindY = NextY + 1;
            //BehindX = x;
            //BehindY = y;
            return;
        }
    }
}

```

```

// Top Right
else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX;
    BehindY = NextY + 1;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
//// Right
//else if ((Elevation[x + 1, y] + PercentFullRock[x +
1, y]) > 0.0)
//{
//    NextX = x + 1;
//    NextY = y;
//    BehindX = NextX;
//    BehindY = NextY + 1;
//    //BehindX = x;
//    //BehindY = y;
//    return;
//}
}

// Came from lower right
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] + 1))
{
    // Bottom left
    if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY + 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
}
// Top

```

```

else if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1]) == 1)
{
    NextX = x;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
// Top Right
else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y + 1;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}
// Right
else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}

else if (AboveWater[x + 2, y] == 1
        || AboveWater[x + 2, y - 1] == 1
        || AboveWater[x + 2, y + 1] == 1)
{
    NextX = x + 1;
    NextY = y;
    BehindX = NextX + 1;
    BehindY = NextY;
    //BehindX = x;
    //BehindY = y;
    return;
}

///// Bottom Right
//else if ((Elevation[x + 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
//{
//    NextX = x + 1;
//    NextY = y - 1;
//    BehindX = NextX + 1;
//    BehindY = NextY;
//    //BehindX = x;
//    //BehindY = y;
//    return;
//}
}

// Came from below

```

```

else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z]))
{
    // Left
    if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top left
    else if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1] ) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;

```

```

        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    ///// Below
    //else if ((Elevation[x, y - 1]) + PercentFullRock[x,
y - 1] > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x;
    //    NextY = y - 1;
    //    BehindX = NextX;
    //    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}
}

// Came from bottom left
else if ((Y[z - 1] == Y[z] - 1) && (X[z - 1] == X[z] - 1))
{
    // Top Left
    if ((AboveWater[x - 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x - 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX + 1;
        BehindY = NextY;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Top Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y + 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y + 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y;
        BehindX = NextX;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Right
    else if ((AboveWater[x + 1, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x + 1;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom
    else if ((AboveWater[x, y - 1]) == 1)
    {
        NextX = x;
        NextY = y - 1;
        BehindX = NextX;
        BehindY = NextY - 1;
        //BehindX = x;
        //BehindY = y;
        return;
    }
    // Bottom Left
    //else if ((Elevation[x - 1, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1]) > 0.0)
    //{
    //    NextX = x - 1;
    //    NextY = y - 1;
    //    BehindX = NextX;
    //    BehindY = NextY - 1;
    //    //BehindX = x;
    //    //BehindY = y;
    //    return;
    //}
    }
}

void FindRockCells(int XStart)
{
    //LMV
    //Determines locations of rock cells moving from left to
right direction
    //This function will affect and determine the global arrays:
XRock[] and YRock[]
    //This function calls FindNextRockCell
    //This will define TotalRockCells for this time step

    int x, z, ystart;
    //StreamWriter XYRockFile = new
StreamWriter("TEST_FILES/XYRock.dat");

    // Starting at left end, find the x - value for first cell
that is 'allbeach'
    ystart = ymax - 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        x = XStart;

        // Two while loops finding the start position of the Rock
(0) and second position (1)
        while (AllRock[x, ystart] == 0)
        {
            ystart -= 1;
        }

        // Step back to where partially full beach
        ystart += 1;

        YRock[0] = ystart;
        XRock[0] = XStart;

        //Need to give these some values for 'weathered rock'
        XRockBehind[0] = XRock[0];
        YRockBehind[0] = YRock[0];

        while (AllRock[x + 1, ystart] == 0)
        {
            ystart -= 1;
        }

        ystart += 1;

        YRock[1] = ystart;
        XRock[1] = XStart + 1;

        XRockBehind[1] = XRock[0];
        YRockBehind[1] = YRock[0];

        // XYRockFile.Write("Iteration: " + "Z: " + "X: " + "Y: " +
Environment.NewLine);

        // XYRockFile.Write(counter + " 0 " + XRock[0] + " " +
YRock[0] + Environment.NewLine
        // + counter + " 1 " + XRock[1] + " " + YRock[1] +
Environment.NewLine);

        z = 1;

        while ((XRock[z] < pbEnd - 1) && (z < MaxBeachLength - 1))
        {
            z++;

            NextRockX = -2;
            NextRockY = -2;
            BehindRockX = -2;
            BehindRockY = -2;

            FindNextRockCell(XRock[z - 1], YRock[z - 1], z - 1);
            XRock[z] = NextRockX;
            YRock[z] = NextRockY;
            XRockBehind[z] = BehindRockX;
            YRockBehind[z] = BehindRockY;

            //Print to file XRock[] and YRock[] Arrays
            // XYRockFile.Write(counter + " " + z + " " + XRock[z]
+ " " + YRock[z] + Environment.NewLine);

```

```

        // If return to start point or go off left side of
array, going the wrong direction
        // Jump off and start again closer to middle
        if ((NextRockX < 1) || ((NextRockX == XRock[0]) &&
(NextRockY == YRock[0])) || (z > MaxBeachLength - 2))
        {
            FellOffRockArray = 'y';
            ZeroVars();
            return;
        }
    }

    TotalRockCells = z;
    FellOffRockArray = 'n';

    //XYRockFile.Close();
}

//void FindNextRockCell(int x, int y, int z)
//{
//    // Function to find next cell that is rock moving in the
general positive X direction
//    // changes global variables NextRockX and NextRockY,
coordinates for the next beach cell
//    // This function will use but not affect the global
arrays: AllRock [][], XRock[], and YRock[]

//    // Came from left
//    if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z]) && (XRock[z - 1] ==
XRock[z] - 1))
//    {
//        if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//        {
//            NextRockY = y + 1;
//            NextRockX = x;
//            //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//            //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//            BehindRockX = x;
//            BehindRockY = y;
//            return;
//        }
//        else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//        {
//            NextRockY = y + 1;
//            NextRockX = x + 1;
//            //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//            //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//            BehindRockX = x;
//            BehindRockY = y;
//            return;
//        }
//        else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//        {
//            NextRockY = y;
//            NextRockX = x + 1;
//            //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//            //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//            BehindRockX = x;
//            BehindRockY = y;
//            return;
//        }
//    }
}

```

```

//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

//      // Came from upper left
//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] - 1))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y + 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;

```

```

//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//      // Came from above
//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z]))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)

```

```

//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

//      // Came from upper right
//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] + 1))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;

```

```

//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//      // Came from right
//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z]) && (XRock[z - 1] ==
XRock[z] + 1))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;

```

```

//      NextRockX = x - 1;
//      //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//      //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//      BehindRockX = x;
//      BehindRockY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//  {
//      NextRockY = y;
//      NextRockX = x - 1;
//      //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//      //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//      BehindRockX = x;
//      BehindRockY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//  {
//      NextRockY = y + 1;
//      NextRockX = x - 1;
//      //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//      //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//      BehindRockX = x;
//      BehindRockY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//  {
//      NextRockY = y + 1;
//      NextRockX = x;
//      //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//      //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//      BehindRockX = x;
//      BehindRockY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//  {
//      NextRockY = y + 1;
//      NextRockX = x + 1;
//      //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//      //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//      BehindRockX = x;
//      BehindRockY = y;
//      return;
//  }
//  }
//  }

//  // Came from lower right
//  else if ((XRock[z - 1] == XRock[z] - 1) && (YRock[z - 1]
== YRock[z] + 1))
//  {
//      if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;

```

```

//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }

//      // Came from below
//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] - 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z]))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y;
//              NextRockX = x - 1;

```

```

//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;

//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x - 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y + 1;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          NextRockY = y - 1;
//          NextRockX = x + 1;
//          //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//          //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//          BehindRockX = x;
//          BehindRockY = y;
//          return;
//      }
//      }
//  }

//      // Came from lower left

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] - 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] - 1))
//      {
//          if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y + 1;
//              NextRockX = x - 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y + 1;
//              NextRockX = x;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y + 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x + 1;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }
//          else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//              NextRockY = y - 1;
//              NextRockX = x;
//              //BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
//              //BehindRockX = NextRockX;
//              BehindRockX = x;
//              BehindRockY = y;
//              return;
//          }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      }
//    }
//}

void FindNextRockCell(int x, int y, int z)
{
    // Function to find next cell that is rock moving in the
    general positive X direction
    // changes global variables NextRockX and NextRockY,
    coordinates for the next beach cell
    // This function will use but not affect the global
    arrays: AllRock [][], XRock[], and YRock[]

    // Came from left
    if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z]) && (XRock[z - 1] ==
XRock[z] - 1))
    {
        if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
        {
            NextRockY = y + 1;
            NextRockX = x;
            BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
            BehindRockX = NextRockX;
            //BehindRockX = x;
            //BehindRockY = y;
            return;
        }
        else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
        {
            NextRockY = y + 1;
            NextRockX = x + 1;
            BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
            BehindRockX = NextRockX;
            //BehindRockX = x;
            //BehindRockY = y;
            return;
        }
        else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
        {
            NextRockY = y;
            NextRockX = x + 1;
            BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
            BehindRockX = NextRockX;
            //BehindRockX = x;
            //BehindRockY = y;
            return;
        }
        else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
        {
            NextRockY = y - 1;
            NextRockX = x + 1;
            BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
            BehindRockX = NextRockX;
            //BehindRockX = x;
            //BehindRockY = y;
            return;
        }
        else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
        {
            NextRockY = y - 1;
            NextRockX = x;
            BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;

```

```

        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}

}

// Came from upper left
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] - 1))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
}

```

```

else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
}
// Came from above
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z]))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;

```

```

        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from upper right
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] + 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] + 1))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX - 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
    {

```

```

        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
}
// Came from right
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z]) && (XRock[z - 1] ==
XRock[z] + 1))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;

```

```

        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from lower right
else if ((XRock[z - 1] == XRock[z] - 1) && (YRock[z - 1]
== YRock[z] + 1))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;

```

```

        BehindRockY = NextRockY + 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
}

// Came from below
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] - 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z]))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x - 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;

```

```

        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y - 1;
        NextRockX = x + 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
}

// Came from lower left
else if ((YRock[z - 1] == YRock[z] - 1) && (XRock[z - 1]
== XRock[z] - 1))
{
    if (PercentFullRock[x - 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;
        NextRockX = x - 1;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
    else if (PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
    {
        NextRockY = y + 1;

```

```

        NextRockX = x;
        BehindRockY = NextRockY;
        BehindRockX = NextRockX + 1;
        //BehindRockX = x;
        //BehindRockY = y;
        return;
    }
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y + 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y + 1;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x + 1, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x + 1;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
else if (PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
{
    NextRockY = y - 1;
    NextRockX = x;
    BehindRockY = NextRockY - 1;
    BehindRockX = NextRockX;
    //BehindRockX = x;
    //BehindRockY = y;
    return;
}
}
}

void RockCalculations()
{
    // For each Rock cell j, moves along the beach and determines
    distance from rock to beach and amount of rock to weather
    // This function calls FindNearestBeach and WeatherRock
    // This function will use but not adjust the variable
    TotalRockCells
    // Determines the total amount of rock weathered in one time
    step

    int j;
    double TotalAmountWeathered = 0.0;

```

```

CurrentPercentFine = 0;

for (j = 0; j <= TotalRockCells; j++)
{
    FindNearestBeach(j);
    WeatherRock(j);
    TotalAmountWeathered += AmountWeathered[j];

    if (TypeOfRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] == 'f')
    {
        CurrentPercentFine = PercentFineFast;
    }
    else if (TypeOfRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] == 's')
    {
        CurrentPercentFine = PercentFineSlow;
    }
    else
    {
        MessageBox.Show("Problem with 'Rock Calculation' -
CurrentPercentFine");
    }

    if (AmountWeathered[j] > 0.0 && CurrentPercentFine >
0.0)
    {
        RemoveFines(j, (CurrentPercentFine *
AmountWeathered[j]));
    }
}

void FindNearestBeach(int j)
{
    // Calculates the Euclidean distance between Rock and
Beach for entire beach array
    // Finds the minimum beach to rock distance
    // This function will use but not adjust the global
arrays: X[], Y[], XRock[], YRock[], PercentFullSand[][]
    // This function will use but not adjust the variables
MinDistanceToBeach and TotalBeachCells

    int i;
    double DeltaX, DeltaY;
    int LookStart, LookEnd;

    MinDistanceToBeach[j] = BigDistanceToBeach;

    // Do a full sweep every now and then
    if (counter % TimeToSweepFullBeach == 0)
    {
        for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells; i++)
        {
            // Vertical Distance
            if (Y[i] != YRock[j])
            {
                //Saying that all cells will be max cell
width, so can just take PFS out of this equation
                //DeltaY = ((Y[i] - YRock[j] - 1) +
(PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] + PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]])) *
CellWidth;

                DeltaY = (Y[i] - YRock[j] - 1) * CellWidth;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

else
{
    //DeltaY = ((PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]) *
CellWidth);
    DeltaY = CellWidth;
}

// Horizontal Distance
if (XRock[j] <= X[i])
{
    DeltaX = (X[i] - XRock[j]) * CellWidth;
}
else
{
    DeltaX = (XRock[j] - X[i]) * CellWidth;
}

DistanceToBeach[j] = Math.Sqrt((DeltaX * DeltaX) +
(DeltaY * DeltaY));

if (DistanceToBeach[j] < MinDistanceToBeach[j])
{
    MinDistanceToBeach[j] = DistanceToBeach[j];
    ClosestBeach[j] = i;
}
}

else
// LookDist allows the program to skip the full beach
sweep at every iteration by looking at
// the location of the previous closest beach and sweeping
out a small arc plus or minus LookDist
{
    if (ClosestBeach[j] - LookDist >= 0)
    {
        LookStart = ClosestBeach[j] - LookDist;
    }
    // Only sweep right when on left end
    else
    {
        LookStart = 0;
    }

    if (ClosestBeach[j] + LookDist <= TotalBeachCells)
    {
        LookEnd = ClosestBeach[j] + LookDist;
    }
    // Only sweep left when at right end
    else
    {
        LookEnd = TotalBeachCells;
    }
    for (i = LookStart; i < LookEnd; i++)
    {
        if (Y[i] != YRock[j])
        {
            //DeltaY = ((Y[i] - YRock[j] - 1) +
(PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] + PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]])) *
CellWidth;

```

```

        DeltaY = (Y[i] - YRock[j] - 1) * CellWidth;
    }
    else
    {
        //DeltaY = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]) *
CellWidth;
        DeltaY = CellWidth;
    }
    // Horizontal distance
    if (XRock[j] <= X[i])
    {
        DeltaX = (X[i] - XRock[j]) * CellWidth;
    }
    else
    {
        DeltaX = (XRock[j] - X[i]) * CellWidth;
    }

    DistanceToBeach[j] = Math.Sqrt(DeltaY * DeltaY +
DeltaX * DeltaX);

    if (DistanceToBeach[j] < MinDistanceToBeach[j])
    {
        MinDistanceToBeach[j] = DistanceToBeach[j];
        ClosestBeach[j] = i;
    }
    }
}

void WeatherRock(int j)
{
    // With Cliffs
    // Fuction changes PercentFullRock[][] and PercentFullSand[][]
along the rock beach interface only
    // At this point, weathering rate is pretty arbitrary
    // Fuction also changes AllRock[][]
    // Weathering rate changes along the shore, 'f' = fast
weather, 's' = slow weathering
    // Function uses (but does not change) TypeOfRock[][] to
determine rate

    double WeatheringRatePerYear;

    // Slow rock weathering
    if (TypeOfRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] == 's')
    {
        // Think in terms of Vertical Equivalence
        if ((MinDistanceToBeach[j] / CellWidth) <=
NoWeathering)
        {
            // Exponential weathering based on sed cover
            WeatheringRatePerYear = SlowWeatherCoeff *
(Math.Exp((-MinDistanceToBeach[j]) / CellWidth));
        }
        else
        {
            WeatheringRatePerYear = 0;
        }
    }

    // Fast rock weathering

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        else if (TypeOfRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] == 'f')
        {
            // Think in terms of vertical equivalence
            if ((MinDistanceToBeach[j] / CellWidth) <=
NoWeathering)
            {
                //Exponential weathering based on sed cover
                WeatheringRatePerYear = FastWeatherCoeff *
(Math.Exp((-MinDistanceToBeach[j]) / CellWidth));
            }
            else
            {
                WeatheringRatePerYear = 0;
            }
        }

        else
        {
            WeatheringRatePerYear = 0;
        }

        // Amount weathering per time step (Percent weathered
which correlates with TimeStepValue)
        AmountWeathered[j] = ((WeatheringRatePerYear *
TimeStepValue) / 365) / CellWidth;

        if (PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] >=
AmountWeathered[j])
        {
            PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] -=
AmountWeathered[j];

            //Include cliff height
            //PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +=
AmountWeathered[j] + (AmountWeathered[j]
*(CliffHeight/DepthShoreface)*(1-PercentFineFast));
            PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +=
AmountWeathered[j] + (AmountWeathered[j] * (CliffHeight /
DepthShoreface) * (1 - PercentFineFast));

            if (PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] < MaxFillCell)
            {
                AllRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] = 0;
            }
        }

        else if (PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] <
AmountWeathered[j])
        {
            if ((PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +
PercentFullRock[XRockBehind[j], YRockBehind[j]]) >=
AmountWeathered[j])
            {
                AllRock[XRockBehind[j], YRockBehind[j]] = 0;
                PercentFullRock[XRockBehind[j], YRockBehind[j]] -=
(AmountWeathered[j] - PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]]);
                PercentFullSand[XRockBehind[j], YRockBehind[j]] +=
(AmountWeathered[j] - PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +
((AmountWeathered[j] - PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]]) *
(CliffHeight / DepthShoreface) * (1 - CurrentPercentFine)));
            }
        }
    }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +=
PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] + (PercentFullRock[XRock[j],
YRock[j]] * (CliffHeight / DepthShoreface) * (1 -
CurrentPercentFine));
        PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] = 0.0;
    }
    else
    {
        PauseRun(-1, -1, j);
        PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] +=
PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]];
        PercentFullRock[XRock[j], YRock[j]] = 0.0;
    }
}

    if (PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] < 0.0)
    {
        PercentFullSand[XRock[j], YRock[j]] = 0.0;
    }

    // After weathering, lose a percentage of weathered rock
in the closest beach cell
    // This represents fine grained material that does not
stay in nearshore system

        if ((AmountWeathered[j] > 0.0) && (TypeOfRock[XRock[j],
YRock[j]] == 'f'))
        {
            PercentFullSand[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] -= PercentFineFast * AmountWeathered[j];
        }

        if ((AmountWeathered[j] > 0.0) && (TypeOfRock[XRock[j],
YRock[j]] == 's'))
        {
            PercentFullSand[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] -= PercentFineSlow * AmountWeathered[j];
        }
    }

void RemoveFines(int j, double Fines)
{
    //// After weathering, lose a percentage of weathered rock
in the closest beach cell
    //// This represents fine grained material that does not
stay in nearshore system
    //// Note, if closest beach cell doesn't have enough, take
from cell behind.
    //// if both don't have enough, take from the cells in
which you created sed earlier.
    //// those don't have enough, just empty them

    //int takefrom;
    //double Available;

    ////Fines from Percentage to volume
    //Fines = Fines * CellWidth * TElevationCS[X[j], Y[j]];

    //if (ClosestBeach[j] > 0 && ClosestBeach[j] < pbEnd &&
ClosestBeach[j] > 0 && ClosestBeach[j] < ymax)
    //{

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]
>= Fines)
//      {
//          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] -
= Fines;

//          if ((Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]) > WaterLevel)
//          {
//              AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 1;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//              AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
//          }
//      }
//      else if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] + Volume[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] >= Fines)
//      {
//          Volume[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] -= (Fines - Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]);
//          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] =
0;

//          if ((Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]) > WaterLevel)
//          {
//              AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 1;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//              AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
//          }

//          if ((Volume[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]]) > WaterLevel)
//          {
//              AboveWater[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 1;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//              AboveWater[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
//          }

//      }
//      // Try to find enough...
//      else if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1]
//          + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]
+ 1]
//          + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1]
//          + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]
- 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1]
//      >= 0)
//      {
//      Available = Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]
+ 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]], Y[ClosestBeach[j]]
- 1]
//      + Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1];

//      if (Available > Fines)
//      {
//      Available = Fines;
//      }

//      takefrom = 0;

//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0) takefrom++;
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0) takefrom++;

//      if (takefrom > 0)
//      {
//      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0)
//      {
//      Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] -= Available / takefrom;
//      AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] = 0;
        //      }
        //      if (Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] > 0)
        //      {
        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] -= Available / takefrom;
        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]] + 1,
Y[ClosestBeach[j]] - 1] = 0;
        //      }
        //      }
        //      else // if can't find enough, just remove what's
available
        //      {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //          Volume[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
        //          Volume[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;

        //          AboveWater[X[ClosestBeach[j]],
Y[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
        //          AboveWater[XBehind[ClosestBeach[j]],
YBehind[ClosestBeach[j]]] = 0;
        //      }
        //  }
        //}
    }

    // Full or Empty
    void OopsImFull(int x, int y)
    {
        // If a cell is overfull, push beach out in new
direction
        // Completely revised 5/20/02 sandrevt.c to resolve 0%
full problems, etc.
        // New approach: put sand wherever 0% full in adjacent
cells
        // if not 0% full, then fill all non-allbeach
        // Function adjusts primary data arrays:
        // AllBeach[][] and PercentFullSand[][]
        // LMV add rock adjustments

        //int fillcells = 0;
        //int fillcells2 = 0;

        //if (x < pbEnd - 2)
        //{
        //    // find out how many cells will be filled up
        //    if (y > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) == 0.0)
        //        {
        //            fillcells += 1;
        //        }
        //    if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] + PercentFullRock[x,
y + 1]) == 0.0)
        //        {
        //            fillcells += 1;
        //        }
        //    if (x > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) == 0.0)
        //        {
        //            fillcells += 1;
        //        }
        //    if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] + PercentFullRock[x +
1, y]) == 0.0)
        //        {
        //            fillcells += 1;
        //        }

        //    if (fillcells > 0)
        //        {
        //            // Now Move Sediment
        //            if (y > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) == 0.0)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //      {
        //          PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells;
        //      }

        //      if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) == 0.0)
        //      {
        //          PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells;
        //      }

        //      if (x > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) == 0.0)
        //      {
        //          PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells;
        //      }

        //      if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) == 0.0)
        //      {
        //          PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells;
        //      }
        //  }

        //  else
        //  {
        //      // No fully empty neighbors, so distribute to
partially full neighbors

        //      if (y > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) < MaxFillCell)
        //      {
        //          fillcells2 += 1;
        //      }
        //      if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < MaxFillCell)
        //      {
        //          fillcells2 += 1;
        //      }
        //      if (x > 0 && (PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < MaxFillCell)
        //      {
        //          fillcells2 += 1;
        //      }
        //      if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < MaxFillCell)
        //      {
        //          fillcells2 += 1;
        //      }

        //      if (fillcells2 > 0)
        //      {
        //          if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) < MaxFillCell)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //          {
        //          PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells2;
        //          }

        //          if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < MaxFillCell)
        //          {
        //          PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells2;
        //          }

        //          if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < MaxFillCell)
        //          {
        //          PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells2;
        //          }

        //          if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < MaxFillCell)
        //          {
        //          PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +=
((PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y]) - MaxFillCell) /
fillcells2;
        //          }
        //          }
        //          }

        //          if (PercentFullSand[x, y] + PercentFullRock[x, y] >=
MaxFillCell)
        //          {
        //          AllBeach[x, y] = 1;
        //          }

        //          PercentFullSand[x, y] = MaxFillCell -
PercentFullRock[x, y];
        //          }
    }

    void OopsImEmpty(int x, int y)
    {
        //// If a cell is under-full, this will find source for
desparity and move brach in
        //// Function completly changed 5/21/02 sandrevt.c
        //// New Approach - steal from all neighboring AllBeach
cells
        //// Backup plan - steal from all neighboring percent full
> 0
        //// Function adjusts primary data arrays:
        //// AllBeach[][] and PercentFullSand[][]
        //// LMV Needs to be adjusted -- can't take sand from rock
cells, uses AllRock[][]

        //int emptycells = 0;
        //int emptycells2 = 0;

        ////if (debug8) printf("\n OOPS I'm EMPTY! X: %d Y: %d
PFS: %f PFR: %f", x, y, PercentFullSand[x][y], PercentFullRock[x][y]);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//if (x < pbEnd - 2)
//{

//    if (y > 0 && (AllBeach[x, y - 1] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] == 0.0))
//    {
//        emptycells += 1;
//    }
//    if ((AllBeach[x, y + 1] == 1) && (PercentFullRock[x,
y + 1] == 0.0))
//    {
//        emptycells += 1;
//    }
//    if ((x > 0 && AllBeach[x - 1, y] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] == 0.0))
//    {
//        emptycells += 1;
//    }
//    if ((AllBeach[x + 1, y] == 1) && (PercentFullRock[x
+ 1, y] == 0.0))
//    {
//        emptycells += 1;
//    }

//    if (emptycells > 0)
//    {
//        // Now Move Sediment

//        if (y > 0 && (AllBeach[x, y - 1] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x, y - 1] == 0.0))
//        {
//            PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells;
//            AllBeach[x, y - 1] = 0;

//            //if (debug8) printf(" E MOVEDBACK\n");
//            //if (debug8) printf(" PFR behind: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x - 1][y]);
//            //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x - 1][y] <
0.0)
//                // printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x-1: %d y:%d %f \n", x - 1, y, PercentFullSand[x -
1][y]);
//            //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x - 1][y] >
1.0)
//                // printf("PFS went >1 in OopsI'mEmpty x-
1: %d y:%d %f \n", x - 1, y, PercentFullSand[x - 1][y]);
//        }

//        if ((AllBeach[x, y + 1] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x, y + 1] == 0.0))
//        {
//            PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells;
//            AllBeach[x, y + 1] = 0;

//            //if (debug8) printf(" E MOVEDUP\n");
//            //if (debug8) printf(" PFR up: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x + 1][y]);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

0.0)          //          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x + 1][y] <
//          //          printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x+1: %d y:%d %f \n", x + 1, y, PercentFullSand[x +
1][y]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x + 1][y] >
1.0)          //          //          printf("PFS went >1 in OopsI'mEmpty
x+1: %d y:%d %f \n", x + 1, y, PercentFullSand[x + 1][y]);
//          //          }

//          if (x > 0 && (AllBeach[x - 1, y] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x - 1, y] == 0.0))
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells;
//          AllBeach[x - 1, y] = 0;

//          //if (debug8) printf(" E MOVEDLEFT\n");
//          //if (debug8) printf(" PFR left: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x][y - 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y - 1] <
0.0)          //          //          printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x: %d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1, PercentFullSand[x][y -
1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y - 1] >
1.0)          //          //          printf("PFS went >1 in OopsI'mEmpty x:
%d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1, PercentFullSand[x][y - 1]);
//          //          }

//          if ((AllBeach[x + 1, y] == 1) &&
(PercentFullRock[x + 1, y] == 0.0))
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells;
//          AllBeach[x + 1, y] = 0;

//          //if (debug8) printf(" E MOVEDRIGHT\n");
//          //if (debug8) printf(" PFR right: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x][y + 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y + 1] <
0.0)          //          //          printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x: %d y+1:%d %f \n", x, y + 1, PercentFullSand[x][y +
1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y - 1] >
1.0)          //          //          printf("PFS went >1 in OopsI'mEmpty x:
%d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1, PercentFullSand[x][y - 1]);
//          //          }
//          }

//          else
//          {
//          // No full neighbors, so take away from
partially full neighbors

//          if (y > 0 && PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] > 0.0)
//          {
//          emptycells2 += 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      }
//      if (PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//      {
//          emptycells2 += 1;
//      }
//      if (x > 0 && PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          emptycells2 += 1;
//      }
//      if (PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//      {
//          emptycells2 += 1;
//      }

//          //if (debug8) printf("no full neighbors, counted
%d partials\n", emptycells2);

//          if (emptycells2 > 0)
//          {
//              if (y > 06 && PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] >
0.0)
//              {
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells2;

//                      //if (debug8) printf(" E NOTFULL
MOVEDBACK\n");
//                      //if (debug8) printf(" PFR behind:
%f\n", PercentFullRock[x - 1][y]);
//                      //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x -
1][y] < 0.0)
//                      //      printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x-1: %d y:%d %f \n", x - 1, y, PercentFullSand[x -
1][y]);
//                      //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x -
1][y] > 1.0)
//                      //      printf("PFS went >1 in
OopsI'mEmpty x-1: %d y:%d %f \n", x - 1, y, PercentFullSand[x -
1][y]);
//                      }

//              if (PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] > 0.0)
//              {
//                  PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells2;

//                      //if (debug8) printf(" E NOTFULL
MOVEDUP\n");
//                      //if (debug8) printf(" PFR up: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x + 1][y]);
//                      //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x +
1][y] < 0.0)
//                      //      printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty x+1: %d y:%d %f \n", x + 1, y, PercentFullSand[x +
1][y]);
//                      //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x +
1][y] > 1.0)
//                      //      printf("PFS went >1 in
OopsI'mEmpty x+1: %d y:%d %f \n", x + 1, y, PercentFullSand[x +
1][y]);
//                      }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

0.0)          //          if (x > 0 && PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] >
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells2;

//          //if (debug8) printf(" E NOTFULL
MOVEDLEFT\n");
//          //if (debug8) printf(" PFR left: %f\n",
PercentFullRock[x][y - 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y -
1] < 0.0)
//          //    printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty...Bummer x: %d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1,
PercentFullSand[x][y - 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y -
1] > 1.0)
//          //    printf("PFS went >1 in
OopsI'mEmpty...Bummer x: %d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1,
PercentFullSand[x][y - 1]);
//          }

//          if (PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] > 0.0)
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / emptycells2;

//          //if (debug8) printf(" E NOTFULL
MOVEDRIGHT\n");
//          //if (debug8) printf(" PFR right:
%f\n", PercentFullRock[x][y + 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y +
1] < 0.0)
//          //    printf("PFS went Negative in
OopsI'mEmpty...Bummer x: %d y+1:%d %f \n", x, y + 1,
PercentFullSand[x][y + 1]);
//          //if (debug8a && PercentFullSand[x][y -
1] > 1.0)
//          //    printf("PFS went >1 in
OopsI'mEmpty...Bummer x: %d y-1:%d %f \n", x, y - 1,
PercentFullSand[x][y - 1]);
//          }
//          //else
//          //{
//          //    printf("@@@ Didn't find anywhere to steal
sand from!! x: %d y: %d\n", x, y);
//          //}

//          }

//          if ((PercentFullSand[x, y]) + (PercentFullRock[x,
y]) < MaxFillCell)
//          {
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//          }

//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;

//          if (debug0 == 1 && PercentFullSand[58, 269] < 0.0)
//          {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //          StreamWriter DebugFile = new
StreamWriter(DebugFilePath);
        //          DebugFile.Write("PercentFullSand(58,259) made
underfull (" + PercentFullSand[58, 269] + ") after calling oops(" + x
+ ", " + y + ")\n");
        //          DebugFile.Close();
        //          //printf("^^^^^^(58,259) made underfull (%f)
after calling oops(%d,%d)^^^^\n", PercentFullSand[58][269], x, y);
        //      }
        //}
    }

    ///Diffusion for X[i] Y[i]
    void OopsImDiffusing_old()
    {

        int CellCount = 0;
        int xHolder;
        int s = 0;

        //for (int k = 1; k < TotalBeachCells - 1; k++)
        //{
        //    if (TElevationDomain[X[k], Y[k]] > (maxDomainDepth +
WaterLevel + 2))
        //        {
        //            double extra = (((TElevationDomain[X[k], Y[k]] -
(maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + 0.5)) * CellWidth * CellWidth));
        //            Volume[X[k], Y[k]] -= extra;

        //            if (direction[k] == 1) // Up
        //                {
        //                    extra = extra / numCells[k];

        //                    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[k]; j++)
        //                        {
        //                            Volume[X[k], Y[k] + j] += extra;
        //                        }
        //                }
        //            else if (direction[k] == 3) // Right
        //                {
        //                    extra = extra / numCells[k];
        //                    xHolder = X[k];

        //                    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[k]; j++)
        //                        {
        //                            if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
        //                                {
        //                                    xHolder = 0;
        //                                    s = 0;
        //                                    Volume[xHolder + s, Y[k]] += extra;
        //                                    s++;
        //                                }
        //                            else
        //                                {
        //                                    Volume[xHolder + s, Y[k]] += extra;
        //                                    s++;
        //                                }
        //                        }
        //                }
        //            else if (direction[k] == 5) // Bottom
        //                {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          extra = extra / numCells[k];

//          for (int j = 0; j < numCells[k]; j++)
//          {
//              Volume[X[k], Y[k] - j] += extra;
//          }
//      }
//      else if (direction[k] == 7) // Left
//      {
//          extra = extra / numCells[k];

//          xHolder = X[k];

//          for (int j = 0; j < numCells[k]; j++)
//          {
//              if (xHolder - s < 0)
//              {
//                  xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
//                  s = 0;
//                  Volume[xHolder - s, Y[k]] += extra;
//                  s++;
//              }
//              else
//              {
//                  Volume[xHolder - s, Y[k]] += extra;
//                  s++;
//              }
//          }
//      }
//  }
//}

//for (int i = 1; i < TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
//{
//    int count = 0;
//    double extra = 0;
//    int a = 0;
//    int b = 0;

//    if (TElevationDomain[X[i] + a, Y[i] + b] >
(maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + 0.005))
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[i] + a, Y[i] + b + 1] == 0)
// Top
//        {
//            count++;
//        }
//        //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
// Top right
//        //{
//            count++;
//        }
//        if (AboveWater[X[i] + a + 1, Y[i] + b] == 0)
// Right
//        {
//            count++;
//        }
//        //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
// Bottom Right
//        //{
//            count++;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //}
//      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - a, Y[i] - b - 1] == 0)
// Bottom
//      //      {
//      //          count++;
//      //      }
//      //      //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
// Bottom Left
//      //      //{
//      //          //      count++;
//      //      //}
//      //      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - a - 1, Y[i] - b] == 0)
// Left
//      //      //      {
//      //          //          count++;
//      //          //      }
//      //      //      //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
// Top Left
//      //      //      //{
//      //          //          count++;
//      //          //      //}
//
//      //      //      extra = ((TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] -
//      //      //      (maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + 0.0025)) / count) * CellWidth *
//      //      //      CellWidth;
//      //      //      Volume[X[i], Y[i]] -= (extra * count);
//
//      //      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] + a, Y[i] + b + 1] == 0)
// Top
//      //      //      {
//      //          //          Volume[X[i] + a, Y[i] + b + 1] += extra;
//      //          //      }
//      //      //      //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
// Top right
//      //      //      //{
//      //          //          Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] += extra;
//      //          //      //}
//      //      //      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] + a + 1, Y[i] + b] == 0)
// Right
//      //      //      //      {
//      //          //          Volume[X[i] + a + 1, Y[i] + b] += extra;
//      //          //          //      }
//      //      //      //      //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
// Bottom Right
//      //      //      //      //{
//      //          //          //          Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] += extra;
//      //          //          //      //}
//      //      //      //      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - a, Y[i] - b - 1] == 0)
// Bottom
//      //      //      //      {
//      //          //          //          Volume[X[i] - a, Y[i] - b - 1] += extra;
//      //          //          //          //      }
//      //      //      //      //      //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
// Bottom Left
//      //      //      //      //      //{
//      //          //          //          //          Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] += extra;
//      //          //          //          //          //      //}
//      //      //      //      //      //      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - a - 1, Y[i] - b] == 0)
// Left
//      //      //      //      //      //      //      {
//      //          //          //          //          //          Volume[X[i] - a - 1, Y[i] - b] += extra;
//      //          //          //          //          //          //      //}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          //          //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
// Top Left //          //          //
//          //          //{
//          //          //          Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] += extra;
//          //          //          //
//          //          //          }

//else if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] <
(maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel - 1))
//          //          //{
//          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + 1] == 1)
// Top //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 1)
// Top right //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 1) //
Right //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 1)
// Bottom Right //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - 1] == 1) //
Bottom //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 1)
// Bottom Left //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 1) //
Left //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }
//          //          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 1)
// Top Left //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          count++;
//          //          //          //          }

//          //          //          extra = (((maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel - 0.5) -
TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]) / count) * CellWidth * CellWidth;
//          //          //          Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += (extra * count);

//          //          //          if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + 1] == 0)
// Top //          //          //          {
//          //          //          //          Volume[X[i], Y[i] + 1] -= extra;
//          //          //          //          }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// Top right      //      if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] -= extra;
//              //      }
Right            //      if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 0)          //
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] -= extra;
//              //      }
// Bottom Right   //      if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] -= extra;
//              //      }
Bottom          //      if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - 1] == 0)          //
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i], Y[i] - 1] -= extra;
//              //      }
// Bottom Left    //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] -= extra;
//              //      }
Left            //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 0)          //
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] -= extra;
//              //      }
// Top Left       //      if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
//              //      {
//              //          Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] -= extra;
//              //      }
//              //}
//              //}

// Potentially a lot of problems in here, but see how it
goes!

int repeat; // want to loop through this process twice!
int x, y, n, i;
int ex, wy, en;
double[] HeightDiff = new double[4];
double[] LocalAngle = new double[4];
double[] AmountStable = new double[4];
double[] PercentASTable = new double[4];
double[] Values = new double[4];
double ASTableTotal = 0;
double HeightThresholdDry = 4;
double HeightThresholdWet = 4;
double AmountAvailable;
int HighestIndex = 0;

double WetCell;
double WetCellT;
double WetCellR;
double WetCellB;
double WetCellL;

double[] Change = new double[4];

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

double Count;

for (repeat = 0; repeat < 2; repeat++)
{
    //if (counter % 10 != 0)
    //{
        //    //Loop through the array and apply diffusion
        //    for (i = 1; i < TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
        //    {
            Count = 0;

            //    // What are the values in the cells?
            //    Values[0] = TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i +
1]]; //Top
            //    Values[1] = TElevationDomain[X[i + 1],
Y[i]]; // Right
            //    Values[2] = TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i -
1]]; // Bottom
            //    Values[3] = TElevationDomain[X[i - 1],
Y[i]]; // left

            //    // What is the HeightDiff between cell x
and its neighbours?
            //    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
            //    {
                //    HeightDiff[n] =
TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] - Values[n];
            //    }

            //    // How much material is needed to make
cells stable?
            //    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
            //    {
                //    // Done this so I don't get weird
numbers if there is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other
problems (est. too much available)
                //    if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
                //    {
                    //    HeightDiff[n] = 0;
                //    }

                //    AmountStable[n] = ((HeightDiff[n] -
HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

                //    if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
                //    {
                    //    AmountStable[n] = 0;
                //    }

                //    AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
            //    }

            //    // Percentage of total material needed
for each cell
            //    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
            //    {
                //    PercentAStable[n] =
((AmountStable[n] / AStableTotal) * 100);
            //    }
        //    }
    //    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          if (double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n])
|| HeightDiff[n] == 0)
//          {
//              PercentAStable[n] = 0;
//          }

//          // How much material is available to
move?
//          HighestIndex = Array.IndexOf(HeightDiff,
(HeightDiff.Max())); //Using Height not values incase on is
higher than x
//          AmountAvailable =
HeightDiff[HighestIndex] / 2;

//          // Give each cell 50% of it's percentage
of what's available - but be careful that its not more than it needs
//          for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
//          {
//              Change[n] = (((PercentAStable[n] /
100) * AmountAvailable));

//              if (Change[n] > AmountStable[n])
//              {
//                  Change[n] = AmountStable[n];
//              }

//              Count += Change[n];
//          }

//          SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i]] -= Count;
// Cell x

//          SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i + 1]] +=
(Change[0]); // Top
//          SedimentChange[X[i + 1], Y[i]] +=
(Change[1]); // Right
//          SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i - 1]] +=
(Change[2]); // Bottom
//          SedimentChange[X[i - 1], Y[i]] +=
(Change[3]); // left

//          AStableTotal = 0;
//      }
//}

///// Whole domain - Loop through the array and
apply diffusion
//else
//{
for (x = 1; x < pbEnd - 1; x++)
{
    for (y = 1; y < ymax - 1; y++)
    {
        Count = 0;

        // What are the values in the cells?
Values[0] = TElevationDomain[x, y + 1];
//Top

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

Values[1] = TElevationDomain[x + 1, y];
// Right
Values[2] = TElevationDomain[x, y - 1];
// Bottom
Values[3] = TElevationDomain[x - 1, y];
// left

// What is the HeightDiff between cell x
and its neighbours?
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
    HeightDiff[n] = TElevationDomain[x, y]
- Values[n];
}

// How much material is needed to make
cells stable?
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
    // Done this so I don't get weird
numbers if there is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other
problems (est. too much available)
    if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
    {
        HeightDiff[n] = 0;
    }

    AmountStable[n] = ((HeightDiff[n] -
HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

    if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
    {
        AmountStable[n] = 0;
    }

    AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
}

// Percentage of total material needed for
each cell
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
    PercentAStable[n] = ((AmountStable[n]
/ AStableTotal) * 100);

    if (double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n]) ||
HeightDiff[n] == 0)
    {
        PercentAStable[n] = 0;
    }
}

// How much material is available to move?
HighestIndex = Array.IndexOf(HeightDiff,
//Using Height not values incase on is
(HighestDiff.Max()));
higher than x

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

                                AmountAvailable = HeightDiff[HighestIndex]
/ 2;

                                // Give each cell 50% of it's percentage
of what's availabe - but be careful that its not more than it needs
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
                                {
                                Change[n] = (((PercentAStable[n] /
100) * AmountAvailable));

                                if (Change[n] > AmountStable[n])
                                {
                                    Change[n] = AmountStable[n];
                                }

                                Count += Change[n];
                                }

                                SedimentChange[x, y] -= Count;

// Cell x

                                SedimentChange[x, y + 1] += (Change[0]);
// Top

                                SedimentChange[x + 1, y] += (Change[1]);
// Right

                                SedimentChange[x, y - 1] += (Change[2]);
// Bottom

                                SedimentChange[x - 1, y] += (Change[3]);
// left

                                AStableTotal = 0;
                                }
                                }
                                }
                                DepthElevation();
}

void OopsImLandsliding()
{

    int CellCount = 0;
    int xHolder;
    int s = 0;

    // Potentially a lot of problems in here, but see how it
goes!

    int repeat; // want to loop through this process twice!
    int x, y, n, i;
    int ex, wy, en;
    double[] HeightDiff = new double[4];
    double[] LocalAngle = new double[4];
    double[] AmountStable = new double[4];
    double[] PercentAStable = new double[4];
    double[] Values = new double[4];
    double AStableTotal = 0;
    double HeightThresholdDry = 1.01;
    double HeightThresholdWet = 4;
    double AmountAvailable;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

int HighestIndex = 0;

double WetCell;
double WetCellT;
double WetCellR;
double WetCellB;
double WetCellL;

double[] Change = new double[4];
double Count;

//if (counter % 100 == 0)
//{
//    for (i = 1; i < TotalBeachCells; i++)
//    {
//        if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] >
maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + WDThreshold + 1)
//        {
//            double change_value = TElevationDomain[X[i],
Y[i]] - (maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + WDThreshold + 1);

//            SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i]] -= change_value;

//            if (direction[i] == 1)
//            {
//                SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] +=
change_value;
//            }
//            else if (direction[i] == 3)
//            {
//                SedimentChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] +=
change_value;
//            }
//            else if (direction[i] == 5)
//            {
//                SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] +=
change_value;
//            }
//            else if (direction[i] == 7)
//            {
//                SedimentChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] +=
change_value;
//            }
//        }
//    }
//}

if (counter % 10 == 0 /*|| FlagLandslide == 1*/)
{
    for (repeat = 0; repeat < 2; repeat++)
    {
        for (x = 2; x < pbEnd - 2; x++)
        {
            for (y = 2; y < ymax - 2; y++)
            {
                //if (AboveWater[x, y] == 0 &&
InShadow_domain[x, y] == 1)
                //{
                //}
                //else

```

```

//{
Count = 0;

// What are the values in the cells?
Values[0] = TElevationDomain[x, y +
1]; //Top
Values[1] = TElevationDomain[x + 1,
y]; // Right
Values[2] = TElevationDomain[x, y -
1]; // Bottom
Values[3] = TElevationDomain[x - 1,
y]; // left

// What is the HeightDiff between cell
x and its neighbours?
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
HeightDiff[n] =
TElevationDomain[x, y] - Values[n];
}

// How much material is needed to make
cells stable?
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
// Done this so I don't get weird
numbers if there is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other
problems (est. too much available)
if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
{
HeightDiff[n] = 0;
}

AmountStable[n] = ((HeightDiff[n]
- HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
{
AmountStable[n] = 0;
}

AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
}

// Percentage of total material needed
for each cell
for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1;
n++)
{
PercentAStable[n] =
((AmountStable[n] / AStableTotal) * 100);

if
(double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n]) || HeightDiff[n] == 0)
{
PercentAStable[n] = 0;
}
}
}

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     //{
//                                     Count = 0;

//                                     // What are the values in the cells?
//                                     Values[0] = TElevationDomain[x, y +
1]; //Top
//                                     Values[1] = TElevationDomain[x + 1,
y]; // Right
//                                     Values[2] = TElevationDomain[x, y -
1]; // Bottom
//                                     Values[3] = TElevationDomain[x - 1,
y]; // left

//                                     // What is the HeightDiff between
cell x and its neighbours?
//                                     for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)
//                                     {
//                                     HeightDiff[n] =
TElevationDomain[x, y] - Values[n];
//                                     }

//                                     // How much material is needed to
make cells stable?
//                                     for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)
//                                     {
//                                     // Done this so I don't get
weird numbers if there is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other
problems (est. too much available)
//                                     if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
//                                     {
//                                     HeightDiff[n] = 0;
//                                     }

//                                     AmountStable[n] =
((HeightDiff[n] - HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

//                                     if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
//                                     {
//                                     AmountStable[n] = 0;
//                                     }

//                                     AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
//                                     }

//                                     // Percentage of total material
needed for each cell
//                                     for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)
//                                     {
//                                     PercentAStable[n] =
((AmountStable[n] / AStableTotal) * 100);

//                                     if
(double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n]) || HeightDiff[n] == 0)
//                                     {
//                                     PercentAStable[n] = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// How much material is available to
move?
// HighestIndex =
Array.IndexOf(HeightDiff, (HeightDiff.Max())); //Using
Height not values incase on is higher than x
// AmountAvailable =
HeightDiff[HighestIndex] / 2;

// Give each cell 50% of it's
percentage of what's available - but be careful that its not more than
it needs
// for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)
// {
// Change[n] = (((PercentAStable[n]
/ 100) * AmountAvailable) / 2);
// if (Change[n] > AmountStable[n])
// {
// Change[n] = AmountStable[n];
// }
// Count += Change[n];
// }
// SedimentChange[x, y] -= Count;
// Cell x
// SedimentChange[x, y + 1] +=
(Change[0]); // Top
// SedimentChange[x + 1, y] +=
(Change[1]); // Right
// SedimentChange[x, y - 1] +=
(Change[2]); // Bottom
// SedimentChange[x - 1, y] +=
(Change[3]); // left

// AStableTotal = 0;
// //}

// //}
// }
// }
// }
// }

///// if XY cell is too full
//if (counter % 1 == 0)
//{
// for (int j = 0; j < TotalBeachCells; j++)
// {
// if (TElevationDomain[X[j], Y[j]] >
TElevationDomain[X[j], Y[j] - 1])
// {
// double difference = (TElevationDomain[X[j],
Y[j]] - TElevationDomain[X[j], Y[j] - 1]);
// SedimentChange[X[j], Y[j]] -= difference;

```

```

//          int count = 0;

//          if (AboveWater[X[j], Y[j] + 1] == 0)
//          {
//              count++;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j] + 1, Y[j]] == 0)
//          {
//              count++;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j], Y[j] - 1] == 0)
//          {
//              count++;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j] - 1, Y[j]] == 0)
//          {
//              count++;
//          }

//          difference = difference / count;

//          if (AboveWater[X[j], Y[j] + 1] == 0)
//          {
//              SedimentChange[X[j], Y[j] + 1] -=
difference;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j] + 1, Y[j]] == 0)
//          {
//              SedimentChange[X[j] + 1, Y[j]] -=
difference;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j], Y[j] - 1] == 0)
//          {
//              SedimentChange[X[j], Y[j] - 1] -=
difference;
//          }
//          if (AboveWater[X[j] - 1, Y[j]] == 0)
//          {
//              SedimentChange[X[j] - 1, Y[j]] -=
difference;
//          }
//          }
//      }
//      DepthElevation();
//  }

///// Sweep underwater
//if (counter % 100 == 0)
//{
//    for (repeat = 0; repeat < 5; repeat++)
//    {
//        for (x = 2; x < pbEnd - 2; x++)
//        {
//            for (y = 2; y < ymax - 2; y++)
//            {
//                if (AboveWater[x, y] == 0 ||
ShorelineCell[x, y] == 1)
//                {
//                    Count = 0;

//                    // What are the values in the cells?

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

1];          //          Values[0] = TElevationDomain[x, y +
//Top
//          Values[1] = TElevationDomain[x + 1,
y];          // Right
//          Values[2] = TElevationDomain[x, y -
1];          // Bottom
//          Values[3] = TElevationDomain[x - 1,
y];          // left

//          // What is the HeightDiff between
cell x and its neighbours?
//          for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)      //
//          {
//          HeightDiff[n] =
TElevationDomain[x, y] - Values[n];
//          }

//          // How much material is needed to
make cells stable?
//          for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)      //
//          {
//          // Done this so I don't get
weird numbers if there is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other
problems (est. too much available)
//          if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
//          {
//          HeightDiff[n] = 0;
//          }

//          AmountStable[n] =
((HeightDiff[n] - HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

//          if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
//          {
//          AmountStable[n] = 0;
//          }

//          AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
//          }

//          // Percentage of total material
needed for each cell
//          for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)      //
//          {
//          PercentAStable[n] =
((AmountStable[n] / AStableTotal) * 100);

//          if
(double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n]) || HeightDiff[n] == 0)
//          {
//          PercentAStable[n] = 0;
//          }

//          // How much material is available to
move?

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// HighestIndex =
Array.IndexOf(HeightDiff, (HeightDiff.Max())); //Using
Height not values incase on is higher than x
// AmountAvailable =
HeightDiff[HighestIndex] / 2;

// // Give each cell 50% of it's
percentage of what's availabe - but be careful that its not more than
it needs
// for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length -
1; n++)
// {
// Change[n] = (((PercentAStable[n]
/ 100) * AmountAvailable) / 2);

// if (Change[n] > AmountStable[n])
// {
// Change[n] = AmountStable[n];
// }

// Count += Change[n];
// }

// SedimentChange[x, y] -= Count;
// Cell x

// SedimentChange[x, y + 1] +=
(Change[0]); // Top
// SedimentChange[x + 1, y] +=
(Change[1]); // Right
// SedimentChange[x, y - 1] +=
(Change[2]); // Bottom
// SedimentChange[x - 1, y] +=
(Change[3]); // left

// AStableTotal = 0;
// }
// }
// DepthElevation();
// }
//}

//if (counter % 1 == 0)
//{
// for (x = 0; x < pbEnd - 1; x++)
// {
// for (y = 1; y < ymax - 1; y++)
// {
// if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >=
TElevationDomain[x, y - 1])
// if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >
TElevationDomain[x, y - 1] + 1)
// {
// SedimentChange[x, y] -=
(TElevationDomain[x, y] - TElevationDomain[x, y - 1]);
// SedimentChange[x, y + 1] +=
(TElevationDomain[x, y] - TElevationDomain[x, y - 1]);
// }
// }
// }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      DepthElevation();
//}

//Array.Clear(Linear_Shoreline, 0,
Linear_Shoreline.Length);

//for (int xx = 0; xx < pbEnd; xx++)
//{
//    for (int yy = ymax - 1; yy > 0; yy--)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[xx, yy] == 1)
//        {
//            Linear_Shoreline[xx, yy] = 1;
//            break;
//        }
//        else
//        {
//            Linear_Shoreline[xx, yy] = 0;
//        }
//    }
//}

//if (counter % 365 == 0)
//{
//    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd - 1; x++)
//    {
//        for (y = 1; y < ymax - 1; y++)
//        {
//            if (Linear_Shoreline[x, y] == 1)
//            {
//                //if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >=
TElevationDomain[x, y - 1])
//                if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >
TElevationDomain[x, y - 1])
//                {
//                    double change = (TElevationDomain[x,
y] - TElevationDomain[x, y - 1]) + HeightThresholdDry;
//                    SedimentChange[x, y] -= change;
//                    SedimentChange[x, y + 1] += change;
//                }
//            }
//        }
//    }
//    DepthElevation();
//}

///// If a cell is on it's own, bring it back to the coast
//if (counter % 1 == 0)
//{
//    for (x = 2; x < pbEnd - 2; x++)
//    {
//        for (y = 2; y < ymax - 2; y++)
//        {
//            // if a cell is on it's own
//            if (AboveWater[x, y] == 1 &&
//                AboveWater[x, y + 1] == 0 &&
//                AboveWater[x + 1, y] == 0 &&
//                AboveWater[x, y - 1] == 0 &&
//                AboveWater[x - 1, y] == 0)
//            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     double Amount = AboveWater[x, y];
// How much is in the cell
//                                     double SurCAvg = ((TElevationDomain[x, y
+ 1] + TElevationDomain[x + 1, y] + TElevationDomain[x, y - 1] +
TElevationDomain[x - 1, y]) / 4); // Average value of
surrounding cell
//                                     double reduce = TElevationDomain[x, y] -
SurCAvg;
// How much to get rid of

//                                     if (AboveWater[x - 2, y] == 1)
//                                     {
//                                     SedimentChange[x - 1, y] += reduce;
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y] -= reduce;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[x + 2, y] == 1)
//                                     {
//                                     SedimentChange[x + 1, y] += reduce;
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y] -= reduce;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y] -= reduce;
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y] += reduce / 5;
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y + 1] += reduce /
5;
//                                     SedimentChange[x + 1, y] += reduce /
5;
//                                     SedimentChange[x, y - 1] += reduce /
5;
//                                     SedimentChange[x - 1, y] += reduce /
5;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     DepthElevation();
//}
}

void ShorelineLandslide()
{
    int CellCount = 0;
    int xHolder;
    int s = 0;

    // Potentially a lot of problems in here, but see how it
goes!

    int repeat; // want to loop through this process twice!
    int x, y, n, i;
    double[] HeightDiff = new double[4];
    double[] LocalAngle = new double[4];
    double[] AmountStable = new double[4];
    double[] PercentASTable = new double[4];
    double[] Values = new double[4];
    double ASTableTotal = 0;
    double HeightThresholdDry = 1.01;
    double AmountAvailable;
    int HighestIndex = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

double[] Change = new double[4];
double Count;

for (i = 1; i < TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
{
    Count = 0;
    // What are the values in the cells?
    Values[0] = TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + 1];
//Top
    Values[1] = TElevationDomain[X[i] + 1, Y[i]];           //
Right
    Values[2] = TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] - 1];
// Bottom
    Values[3] = TElevationDomain[X[i] - 1, Y[i]];
// left

    // What is the HeightDiff between cell x and its
neighbours?
    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1; n++)
    {
        HeightDiff[n] = TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] -
Values[n];
    }

    // How much material is needed to make cells stable?
    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1; n++)
    {
        // Done this so I don't get weird numbers if there
is a higher neighbour.. this might cause other problems (est. too much
available)
        if (HeightDiff[n] < 0)
        {
            HeightDiff[n] = 0;
        }

        AmountStable[n] = ((HeightDiff[n] -
HeightThresholdDry) / 2);

        if (AmountStable[n] < 0)
        {
            AmountStable[n] = 0;
        }

        AStableTotal += AmountStable[n];
    }

    // Percentage of total material needed for each cell
    for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1; n++)
    {
        PercentAStable[n] = ((AmountStable[n] /
AStableTotal) * 100);

        if (double.IsNaN(PercentAStable[n]) ||
HeightDiff[n] == 0)
        {
            PercentAStable[n] = 0;
        }
    }

    // How much material is available to move?

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        HighestIndex = Array.IndexOf(HeightDiff,
(HeightDiff.Max()));          //Using Height not values incase on is
higher than x
        AmountAvailable = HeightDiff[HighestIndex] / 2;

        // Give each cell 50% of it's percentage of what's
availabe - but be careful that its not more than it needs
        for (n = 0; n < HeightDiff.Length - 1; n++)
        {
            Change[n] = (((PercentAStable[n] / 100) *
AmountAvailable) / 2);

            if (Change[n] > AmountStable[n])
            {
                Change[n] = AmountStable[n];
            }

            Count += Change[n];
        }

        SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i]] -= Count;          //
Cell x

        SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] += (Change[0]); //
Top
        SedimentChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] += (Change[1]); //
Right
        SedimentChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] += (Change[2]); //
Bottom
        SedimentChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] += (Change[3]); //
left

        AStableTotal = 0;
    }
    DepthElevation();
}

void VolumeRecal()
{
    // Using changed volume, recalculate vertical
measurements
    int x, y;

    //StreamWriter VolChang_FILE = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Volchange_" + counter + ".out");

    //for (y = 0; y <= ymax - 1; y++)
    //{
    //    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    //    {
    //        VolChang_FILE.Write(VolumeChange[x, y] + " ");
    //    }
    //    VolChang_FILE.Write(Environment.NewLine);
    //}
    //VolChang_FILE.Close();

    // DEBUGGING START

```

```

        if (counter == 365)
        {
            StreamWriter DEBUG_FILE_ENDVol =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/DEBUG_FILE_ENDVol.out");
            for (int s = ymax - 1; s >= 0; s--)
            {
                for (int r = 0; r < pbEnd; r++)
                {
                    DEBUG_FILE_ENDVol.Write(VolumeChange[r, s] + "
");
                }
                DEBUG_FILE_ENDVol.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            }
            DEBUG_FILE_ENDVol.Close();
        }
        // DEBUGGING END

        for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
        {
            for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
            {
                ////if (VolumeChange[x, y] > 3)
                ////{
                ////    if (counter == 0)
                ////    {
                ////        StreamWriter VolChangeFile = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
                ////        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " "
+ VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
                ////        VolChangeFile.Close();
                ////    }
                ////    else
                ////    {
                ////        StreamWriter VolChangeFile =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
                ////        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " "
+ VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
                ////        VolChangeFile.Close();
                ////    }

                ////    //VolumeChange[x, y] = 3;
                ////}
                ////if (VolumeChange[x, y] < -3)
                ////{
                ////    if (counter == 0)
                ////    {
                ////        StreamWriter VolChangeFile = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
                ////        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " "
+ VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
                ////        VolChangeFile.Close();
                ////    }
                ////    else
                ////    {
                ////        StreamWriter VolChangeFile =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
                ////        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " "
+ VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
                ////        VolChangeFile.Close();

```

```

        ////    }

        ////    //VolumeChange[x, y] = -3;
        ////}
        ////else
        ////{
        //    Volume[x, y] += VolumeChange[x, y];
        ////}

        //if (Volume[x, y] < 0)
        //{
        //    Volume[x, y] = 0;
        //}

        //TElevationCS[x, y] = Volume[x, y] / (CellWidth *
CellWidth);
        //TElevationDomain[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] +
DomainDepthCS[x, y];

        //if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold) //WetDryThreshold)
        //{
        //    AboveWater[x, y] = 1;

        //}
        //else
        //{
        //    AboveWater[x, y] = 0;
        //}

        //if (VolumeChange[x, y] > 3)
        //{
        //    if (counter == 0)
        //    {
        //        StreamWriter VolChangeFile = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
        //        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " " +
VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
        //        VolChangeFile.Close();
        //    }
        //    else
        //    {
        //        StreamWriter VolChangeFile =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/VolChangeExtra.out");
        //        VolChangeFile.Write(x + " " + y + " " +
VolumeChange[x, y] + Environment.NewLine);
        //        VolChangeFile.Close();
        //    }
        //}

        ///
        /// Trying a new technique - 06/12/17
        ///

        //TElevationCS[x, y] += VolumeChange[x, y];

        //if (TElevationCS[x, y] < 0)
        //{

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //      TElevationCS[x, y] = 0;
        //}

        //TElevationDomain[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] +
DomainDepthCS[x, y];
        //Volume[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] * (CellWidth *
CellWidth);

        //if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold)      //WetDryThreshold)
        //{
        //      AboveWater[x, y] = 1;

        //}
        //else
        //{
        //      AboveWater[x, y] = 0;
        //}

        ///
        /// Trying a new technique - 06/12/17
        ///

        if (VolumeChange[x, y] < 0)
        { }

        VolumeChange[x, y] = VolumeChange[x, y]
*(CellWidth * CellWidth);
        Volume[x, y] += VolumeChange[x, y];

        TElevationCS[x, y] = Volume[x, y] / (CellWidth *
CellWidth);
        TElevationDomain[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] +
DomainDepthCS[x, y];

        if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold)      //WetDryThreshold)
        {
            AboveWater[x, y] = 1;

        }
        else
        {
            AboveWater[x, y] = 0;
        }
    }
}

    Array.Clear (VolumeChange, 0, VolumeChange.Length);
}

void DepthElevation()
{
    // Recalculate arrays using depths and elevation etc after
all material has moved during each iteration
    int x, y;

    //StreamWriter SedChange = new StreamWriter
("OUTPUT_FILES/sedchange.out");

```

```

for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
{
    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    {
        TElevationCS[x, y] += SedimentChange[x, y];

        // Not thinking about eroding the bed etc
        if (TElevationCS[x, y] < 0)
        {
            TElevationCS[x, y] = 0;
        }

        TElevationDomain[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] +
DomainDepthCS[x, y];
        Volume[x, y] = TElevationCS[x, y] * (CellWidth *
CellWidth);

        if (TElevationDomain[x, y] >= WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold) //WetDryThreshold)
        {
            AboveWater[x, y] = 1;
        }
        else
        {
            AboveWater[x, y] = 0;
        }

        //SedChange.Write(SedimentChange[x, y] + " ");
    }
    //SedChange.Write(Environment.NewLine);
}

//SedChange.Close();
Array.Clear(SedimentChange, 0, SedimentChange.Length);
}

// Calculate sediment transport
void DetermineAngles()
{
    // Function to determine beach angles for all beach cells
from left to right
    // By convention, the ShorelineAngle will apply to
current cell and right neighbor
    // This function will determine global arrays:
ShorelineAngle[], UpWind[], SurroundingAngle[]
    // This function will use but not affect the following
arrays and values: X[], Y[], PercentFull[][], AllBeach[][], WaveAngle
    // ADA Revised underside, SurroundingAngle 6/03
    // ADA Rerevised, 3/04

    int i, j, k;

    // Compute ShorelineAngle[]
    // Not equal to TotalBeachCells because angle between cell
and rt neighbor

    for (i = 1; i < TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
    {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (X[i] > X[i + 1])
        // On bottom side of Spit (assuming we must be if
going right)
        {
            ShorelineAngle[i] = pi - Math.Atan((Y[i + 1] -
(AboveWater[X[i + 1], Y[i + 1]])) - (Y[i] - (AboveWater[X[i],
Y[i]]))));

            if (ShorelineAngle[i] > pi)
            {
                ShorelineAngle[i] -= 2.0 * pi;
            }
        }

        else if ((X[i] < X[i + 1]))
        {
            ShorelineAngle[i] = Math.Atan((Y[i + 1] +
(AboveWater[X[i + 1], Y[i + 1]])) - (Y[i] + (AboveWater[X[i],
Y[i]]))));
        }

        else if (X[i] == X[i + 1] && Y[i] > Y[i + 1])
        // Shore up and down, on right side
        {
            ShorelineAngle[i] = -pi / 2.0 + Math.Atan((X[i +
1] + (AboveWater[X[i + 1], Y[i + 1]])) - (X[i] + (AboveWater[X[i],
Y[i]]))));
        }

        else if (X[i] == X[i + 1] && Y[i] < Y[i + 1])
        // Shore up and down, on left side
        {
            ShorelineAngle[i] = pi / 2.0 + Math.Atan((X[i + 1]
+ (AboveWater[X[i + 1], Y[i + 1]])) - (X[i] + (AboveWater[X[i],
Y[i]]))));
        }
    }

    for (k = 1; k < TotalBeachCells; k++)
    {
        // Compute SurroundingAngle array
        // Averaging doesn't work on bottom of spits
        // Use trick that x is less if on bottom of spit -
angles must be different signs as well

        if ((X[k - 1] - X[k + 1] == 2) &&
(copysign(ShorelineAngle[k - 1], ShorelineAngle[k]) !=
ShorelineAngle[k - 1]))
        {
            SurroundingAngle[k] = (ShorelineAngle[k - 1] +
ShorelineAngle[k]) / 2 + pi;

            if (SurroundingAngle[k] > pi)
            {
                SurroundingAngle[k] -= 2.0 * pi;
            }
        }

        else
        {
            SurroundingAngle[k] = (ShorelineAngle[k - 1] +
ShorelineAngle[k]) / 2;

```

```

    }
}

// Determine Upwind/downwind condition
// Note - Surrounding angle is based upon left and right
cell neighbors and is centered on cell, not on right boundary

for (j = 1; j < TotalBeachCells; j++)
{
    if (Math.Abs(WaveAngle - SurroundingAngle[j]) >= 42.0
/ radtodeg)
    {
        UpWind[j] = 'u';
    }
    else
    {
        UpWind[j] = 'd';
    }
}

ShorelineAngle[0] = ShorelineAngle[1];
SurroundingAngle[0] = SurroundingAngle[1];
UpWind[0] = UpWind[1];

ShorelineAngle[TotalBeachCells - 1] =
ShorelineAngle[TotalBeachCells - 2];
SurroundingAngle[TotalBeachCells - 1] =
SurroundingAngle[TotalBeachCells - 2];
UpWind[TotalBeachCells - 1] = UpWind[TotalBeachCells - 2];

}

void DetermineSedTransport()
{
    // Loop function to determine which neighbor/situation to use
for sediment transport calcs
    // Once situation is determined, will use function SedTrans
to determine actual transport
    // This function will call ( which will determine global
array: VolumeAcrossBorder[]
    // This function will use but not affect the following arrays
and values: X[], Y[], InShadow[], UpWind[], ShorelineAngle[],
PercentFullSand[][], AllBeach[][], WaveAngle

    int i;
    double ShoreAngleUsed = 0;
    int CalcCell;
    int Next, Last;
    int Correction;
    char UpWindLocal;
    char MaxTrans;
    int DoFlux;

for (i = 1 ; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1 ; i++)
{
    MaxTrans = 'n';

    // Is littoral transport going left or right?

    if ((WaveAngle - ShorelineAngle[i]) > 0)
    {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// Transport going right, center on cell to left
side of border
// Next cell in positive direction, no correction
term needed
// This actually shows material moving left!!!

CalcCell = i;
Next = 1;
Last = -1;
Correction = 0;
DirectionAcrossBorder[i] = 'r';
}
else
{
// Transport going left, center on cell to right
side of border
// Next cell in negative direction, correction
term needed

CalcCell = i + 1;
Next = -1;
Last = 1;
Correction = -1;
DirectionAcrossBorder[i] = 'l';
}

if (InShadow[CalcCell] == 'n')
{
// Adjustment for maximum transport when passing
through 45 degrees
// This adjustment is only made for moving from
downwind to upwind conditions
// purposefully done before shadow adjustment, only
use maxtran when transition from dw to up not because of shadow
// keeping transition from uw to dw - does not seem to
be big deal

if (((UpWind[CalcCell] == 'd') &&
(UpWind[CalcCell+Next] == 'u') && (InShadow[CalcCell + Next] == 'n'))
||
((UpWind[CalcCell+Last] == 'u') &&
(UpWind[CalcCell] == 'd') && (InShadow[CalcCell+Last] == 'n'))) )
{
MaxTrans = 'y';
}

// Upwind/Downwind adjustment Make sure sediment
is put into shadows
// If Next cell is in shadow, use UpWind condition

DoFlux = 1;
UpWindLocal = UpWind[CalcCell];

if (InShadow[CalcCell+Next] == 'y')
{
UpWindLocal = 'u';
}

// If coming out of shadow, downwind should be
used
// HOWEVER - if high angle, will result in same
flux in/out problem solution - no flux for high angle waves

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if ((InShadow[CalcCell+Last] == 'y')
&&(UpWindLocal == 'u'))
        {
            DoFlux = 0;
        }

        // Use upwind or downwind shoreline angle for
calcs

        if (UpWindLocal == 'u')
        {
            ShoreAngleUsed =
ShorelineAngle[CalcCell+Last+Correction];
        }
        else if (UpWindLocal == 'd')
        {
            ShoreAngleUsed =
ShorelineAngle[CalcCell+Correction];
        }

        // !!! Do not do transport on underneath 'cause it
gets all messed up
        if ((Math.Abs(ShoreAngleUsed)) > pi/2.0)
        {
            DoFlux = 0;
        }

        // Send to SedTrans to calculate VolumeIn and
VolumeOut

        if (DoFlux == 1)
        {
            SedTrans(i, ShoreAngleUsed, MaxTrans);
        }

        //StreamWriter VolAc_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/VolAc_File.out");
        //VolAc_File.Write(counter + " " +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + Environment.NewLine);
        //VolAc_File.Close();
    }
}
    DirectionAcrossBorder[0] = DirectionAcrossBorder[1];
    DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 1] =
DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 2];
}

void SedTrans(int i, double ShoreAngle, char MaxT)
{
    // This central function will calculalte the sediment
transported from the cell i-1 to the cell at i, using the input
ShoreAngle LMV
    // This function will caluclate and determine the global
arrays: VolumeAcrossBorder[]
    // This function will use the global values defining the
wave field:
    // WaveAngle, Period, OffShoreWvHt
    // Revised 6/02 - New iterative calc for refraction and
breaking, parameters revised

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        // Coefficients - some of these are important

        double StartDepth = 3 * OffShoreWvHt;           // m, depth to
begin refraction calcs (needs to be beyond breakers)
        double RefractStep = .2;                       // m, step
size to iterate depth for refraction calcs
        double KBreak = 0.4;                           // coefficient
for wave breaking threshold
        double rho = 1020;                             // kg/m3 -
density of water and dissolved matter

        // Variables

        double AngleDeep;                              // rad, Angle of waves to
shore at inner shelf
        double Depth = StartDepth;                    // m, water depth for
current iteration

        double Angle;                                  // rad, calculation angle
        double CDeep;                                  // m/s, phase velocity in
deep water
        double LDeep;                                  // m, offshore wavelength
        double C;                                       // m/s, current step phase
velocity
        double kh;                                      // wavenumber times depth
        double n;
        double WaveLength;                             // m, current wavelength
        double WvHeight;                               // m, current wave height

        // Primary assumption is that waves refract over shore-
parallel contours
        // New algorithm 6/02 iteratively takes wave onshore until
they break, then computes Qs
        // See notes 06/05/02

        AngleDeep = WaveAngle - ShoreAngle;

        if (MaxT == 'Y')
        {
            AngleDeep = pi / 4.0;
        }

        // Don't do calculations if over 90 degrees, should be in
shadow
        if (AngleDeep > 0.995 * pi / 2.0 || AngleDeep < -0.995 *
pi / 2.0)
        {
            return;
        }

        else
        {
            // Calculate Deep Water Celerity & Length, Komar 5.11
c = gT / pi, L = CT

            CDeep = g * Period / (2.0 * pi);
            LDeep = CDeep * Period;

            while (TRUE == 1)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        {
            // non-iterative eqn for L, from Fenton & McKee

            WaveLength = LDeep *
Raise(Math.Tanh(Raise(Raise(2.0 * pi / Period, 2) * Depth / g, .75)),
2.0 / 3.0);

            C = WaveLength / Period;

            // Determine n = 1/2(1+2kh/sinh(kh)) Komar 5.21
            // First Calculate kh = 2 pi Depth/L from k = 2
pi/L

            kh = 2 * pi * Depth / WaveLength;
            n = 0.5 * (1 + 2.0 * kh / Math.Sinh(2.0 * kh));

            // Calculate angle, assuming shore parallel
contours and no conv/div of rays

            Angle = Math.Asin(C / CDeep *
Math.Sin(AngleDeep));

            Angle_1[i] = Angle;

            // Determine Wave height from refract calcs -
Komar 5.49

            WvHeight = OffShoreWvHt * Raise(CDeep *
Math.Cos(AngleDeep) / (C * 2.0 * n * Math.Cos(Angle)), 0.5);

            if (WvHeight > Depth * KBreak || Depth <=
RefractStep)
            {
                break;
            }
            else
            {
                Depth -= RefractStep;
            }
        }

        // Now Determine Transport
        // eq. 9.6b (10.8) Komar, including assumption of sed
density = 2650 kg/m3
        // additional accuracy here will not improve an
already suspect eqn for sed transport
        // (especially with poorly constrained coefficients),
        // so no attempt made to make this a more perfect
imperfection

        VolumeAcrossBorder[i] = (((Math.Abs(1.1 * rho *
Raise(g, 3.0 / 2.0) * Raise(WvHeight, 2.5) * Math.Cos(Angle) *
Math.Sin(Angle) * TimeStepValue)) /* (CellWidth/100) / 2)*/));

        //if (counter == 0)
        //{
            StreamWriter SedTrans_FILE =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SedTrans_FILE.out");
            // SedTrans_FILE.Write(counter + " " +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + Environment.NewLine);
            // SedTrans_FILE.Close();

```

```

        //}

        if (i == 1)
        {
            VolumeAcrossBorder[0] = VolumeAcrossBorder[1];
        }

        /// CM bit at the end trying to check scaling! Need to
        check this... won't make any difference at 100m cells.

        //VolumeIn/Out is now calculated in AdjustShore

        //string DepthSedFile =
        "OUTPUT_FILES/DepthSedTrans.out";

        //if (counter == 0)
        //{
        //    StreamWriter DepthSedTrans = new
        StreamWriter(DepthSedFile);
        //    DepthSedTrans.WriteLine(counter + " " + X[i] + "
        " + Y[i] + VolumeAcrossBorder[i]);
        //    DepthSedTrans.Close();
        //}
        //else
        //{
        //    StreamWriter DepthSedTrans =
        File.AppendText(DepthSedFile);
        //    DepthSedTrans.WriteLine(counter + " " + X[i] + "
        " + Y[i] + VolumeAcrossBorder[i]);
        //    DepthSedTrans.Close();
        //}
        //string VolAcrrs_File = "OUTPUT_FILES/VolAcrrs.out";
        //StreamWriter VolAcross =
        File.AppendText(VolAcrrs_File);
        //VolAcross.WriteLine(counter + " " + X[i] + " " +
        Y[i] + " " + VolumeAcrossBorder[i]);
        //VolAcross.Close();
    }
}

void FlowInCell()
{
    // This function will determine if sediment transport into a
    cell is from right, from left, converging into the cell, or diverging
    out */
    // Purpose is to address problems with insufficient sand, fix
    losing sand problem
    // Moves from left to right direction
    // This function will affect and determine the global arrays:
    FlowThroughCell[]
    // This function uses TotalBeachCells
    // Uses but does not affect the global arrays:
    DirectionAcrossBorder[]

    int i;
    double TotalPercentInBeaches = 0;

    for (i = 1; i <= TotalBeachCells; i++)
    {
        if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[i - 1] == 'r') &&
        (DirectionAcrossBorder[i] == 'r'))

```

```

        {
            // right
            FlowThroughCell[i] = 'R';
        }
        else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[i - 1] == 'r') &&
(DirectionAcrossBorder[i] == 'l'))
        {
            // convergent
            FlowThroughCell[i] = 'C';
        }
        else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[i - 1] == 'l') &&
(DirectionAcrossBorder[i] == 'r'))
        {
            // divergent
            FlowThroughCell[i] = 'D';
        }
        else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[i - 1] == 'l') &&
(DirectionAcrossBorder[i] == 'l'))
        {
            // left
            FlowThroughCell[i] = 'L';
        }

        //CM added
        else
        {
        }

        //Total Volumes in beaches!?
        //TotalPercentInBeaches += (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]] + PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]]);

        TotalPercentInBeaches += TElevationCS[X[i],Y[i]];
    }

    if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 1] == 'r') &&
(DirectionAcrossBorder[0] == 'r'))
    {
        // right
        FlowThroughCell[0] = 'R';
    }
    else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 1] ==
'r') && (DirectionAcrossBorder[0] == 'l'))
    {
        // convergent
        FlowThroughCell[0] = 'C';
    }
    else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 1] ==
'l') && (DirectionAcrossBorder[0] == 'r'))
    {
        // divergent
        FlowThroughCell[0] = 'D';
    }
    else if ((DirectionAcrossBorder[TotalBeachCells - 1] ==
'l') && (DirectionAcrossBorder[0] == 'l'))
    {
        // left
        FlowThroughCell[0] = 'L';
    }
    else
    {
        // right

```

```

        FlowThroughCell[0] = 'R';
    }
}

void FixFlow()
{
    // Checks and distributes sediment in adjacent cells based
on FlowThroughCell[]
    // Sweeps left to right to check cells where
DirectionAcrossBorder='r' (D to R, D to C, R to R, R to C)
    // Sweeps right to left to check cells where
DirectionAcrossBorder='l' (D to L, D to C, L to L, L to C)
    // This function uses TotalBeachCells
    // Uses but does not affect the global arrays:
FlowThroughCell[], VolumeAcrossBorder[], PFS[][]
    // reminder--VolumeAcrossBorder[] is always on right side
of cell

    int i;
    int x, y;
    double AmountSand = 0;           // amount of sand
available for transport (includes amount in cell behind)

    /////StreamWriter DepthE = new
StreamWriter("TEST_FILES/DepthE.dat");

    //for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
    {
        ActualVolumeAcross[i] = VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
    }
    // Divergent Cells - get the actual volumes across for
left and right borders
for (i = 1; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
    {
        // calculate effective depth
Depth = InitialDepth + ((Y[i] - InitBeach) * CellWidth
* ShelfSlope);
        Distance = Depth / (ShorefaceSlope - ShelfSlope *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]));
        Yintercept = Y[i] + Distance *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]) / CellWidth;
        DepthEffective = (InitialDepth + ((Yintercept -
InitBeach) * CellWidth * ShelfSlope));

        if (DepthEffective < DepthShoreface)
        {
            DepthEffective = DepthShoreface;
        }

        // set the D's first - left and right border set
if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
        {
            // Flow from a Divergent cell (to a Convergent
cell or a Right cell)
            if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
            {
                //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
                //{
                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] +
PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];
        AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

        //}
        //else
        //{
        //    AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
        //    AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
        //}
    }

    else
        // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
    {
        //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]) *
CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

        //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];
        AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;
    }

    if ((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i]) <= AmountSand)
    {
        ActualVolumeAcross[i] = VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
        ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1];
    }
    if ((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i]) > AmountSand)
        // divide up proportionally
    {
        ActualVolumeAcross[i] =
((VolumeAcrossBorder[i] / (VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])) * AmountSand);
        ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] / (VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])) * AmountSand);
    }
}
//StreamWriter D_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/D.dat");
//D_File.WriteLine(AmountSand);
//D_File.Close();
}

// Right Cells - get the actual volumes across right
borders for R cells
for (i = 1; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
{
    // calculate effective depth
    Depth = InitialDepth + ((Y[i] - InitBeach) * CellWidth
* ShelfSlope);
    Distance = Depth / (ShorefaceSlope - ShelfSlope *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]));
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        Yintercept = Y[i] + Distance *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]) / CellWidth;
        DepthEffective = InitialDepth + ((Yintercept -
InitBeach) * CellWidth * ShelfSlope);

        if (DepthEffective < DepthShoreface)
        {
            DepthEffective = DepthShoreface;
        }

// Flow from a Right cell (to a Right cell or a
Convergent cell)
        if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
        {
            if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
            {
                //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
                //{
                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] +
PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

                //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];
                AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

                //}
                //else
                //{
                //    //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
                //    AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
                //}
            }

            else
                // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
            {
                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]) *
CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

                //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];
                AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

                if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] + AmountSand) >=
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])
                {
                    ActualVolumeAcross[i] = VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
                }
                if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] + AmountSand) <
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])
                {
                    ActualVolumeAcross[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i -
1] + AmountSand;
                }
            }

            //StreamWriter R_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/R.dat");

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //R_File.WriteLine(AmountSand);
        //R_File.Close();
    }

    // Left Cells - get the volumes across left side of cell
for L cells
    for (i = TotalBeachCells - 1; i >= 1; i--)
    {
        Depth = InitialDepth + ((Y[i] - InitBeach) * CellWidth
* ShelfSlope);
        Distance = Depth / (ShorefaceSlope - ShelfSlope *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]));
        Yintercept = Y[i] + Distance *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]) / CellWidth;
        DepthEffective = InitialDepth + ((Yintercept -
InitBeach) * CellWidth * ShelfSlope);

        if (DepthEffective < DepthShoreface)
        {
            DepthEffective = DepthShoreface;
        }

        // Flow from a Left cell (to a Convergent cell or a
Left cell)
        if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
        {
            if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
            {
                //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
                //{
                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] +
PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

                //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];
                AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

                //}
                //else
                //{
                //    //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
                //    AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
                //}
            }
            else
            // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
            {
                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]) *
CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

                //AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];
                AmountSand = CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;
            }

            if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand) >=
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1])

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        {
            ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1];
        }
        if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand) <
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1])
        {
            ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand;
        }
    }
    //StreamWriter L_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/L.dat");
    //L_File.WriteLine(AmountSand);
    //L_File.Close();
}

ActualVolumeAcross[0] = VolumeAcrossBorder[1];

////////StreamWriter DepthE = new
StreamWriter("TEST_FILES/DepthE.dat");

////////for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
////////{
////////    ActualVolumeAcross[i] = VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
////////}

////// Divergent Cells - get the actual volumes across for
left and right borders
//for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
//{
//    //// calculate effective depth
//    //Depth = InitialDepth + ((Y[i] - InitBeach) *
CellWidth * ShelfSlope);
//    //Distance = Depth / (ShorefaceSlope - ShelfSlope *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]));
//    //Yintercept = Y[i] + Distance *
Math.Cos(ShorelineAngle[i]) / CellWidth;
//    //DepthEffective = (InitialDepth + ((Yintercept -
InitBeach) * CellWidth * ShelfSlope));

//    //if (DepthEffective < DepthShoreface)
//    //{
//        //    DepthEffective = DepthShoreface;
//    }

//    // set the D's first - left and right border set
//    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
//    {
//        // Flow from a Divergent cell (to a Convergent
cell or a Right cell)
//        if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
//        {
//            //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
//            //{
//                //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]
+ PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

//                //A    AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth))) +
//          (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] - WaterLevel) *
(CellWidth * CellWidth)));

//
//}
//          //else
//          //{
//          //      AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
//          //      AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
//          //}
//          }

//          else
//          // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
//          {
//          //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]])
* CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

//          //A      AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];
//          //          AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth)));
//          }

//          if ((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i]) <= AmountSand)
//          {
//          //          ActualVolumeAcross[i] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
//          //          ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1];
//          }
//          if ((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i]) > AmountSand)
//          // divide up proportionally
//          {
//          //          ActualVolumeAcross[i] =
((VolumeAcrossBorder[i] / (VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])) * AmountSand);
//          //          ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
((VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] / (VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1] +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])) * AmountSand);
//          }
//          }
//          //StreamWriter SandAmountFile;
//          //SandAmountFile =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandAmount_File.dat");
//          //SandAmountFile.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " +
FlowThroughCell[i] + " " + AmountSand);
//          //SandAmountFile.Close();

//          // Flow from a Right cell (to a Right cell or a
Convergent cell)
//          if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
//          {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
//      {
//          //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
//          //{
//              //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]
+ PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

//          //A AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];

//          AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth))) +
//          (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] - WaterLevel) *
(CellWidth * CellWidth)));

//          //}
//          //else
//          //{
//              //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
//              // AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
//          //}
//      }

//      else
//      // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
//      {
//          //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]])
* CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

//          //A AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];

//          AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth)));
//      }

//      if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] + AmountSand) >=
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])
//      {
//          ActualVolumeAcross[i] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i];
//      }
//      if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] + AmountSand) <
VolumeAcrossBorder[i])
//      {
//          ActualVolumeAcross[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i
- 1] + AmountSand;
//      }
//      }
//      //StreamWriter SandAmountFile;
//      //SandAmountFile =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandAmount_File.dat");
//      //SandAmountFile.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " +
FlowThroughCell[i] + " " + AmountSand);
//      //SandAmountFile.Close();

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      // Flow from a Left cell (to a Convergent cell or a
Left cell)
//      if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
//      {
//          if (AboveWater[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] == 1)
//          {
//              //if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
//              //{
//                  //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]]
+ PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth *
DepthEffective;

//                  //A      AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]];

//                  AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth))) +
//                  (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] - WaterLevel) *
(CellWidth * CellWidth)));

//              //}
//              //else
//              //{
//                  //      //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]]) * CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;
//                  //      AmountSand = (Volume[X[i], Y[i]]);
//                  //}
//              }
//              else
//              // I don't know how much I have, just figure it
out and give me some sand
//              {
//                  //AmountSand = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]])
* CellWidth * CellWidth * DepthEffective;

//                  //A      AmountSand = Volume[X[i], Y[i]];

//                  AmountSand = (((CellWidth * CellWidth) *
MaxDist) + ((Elevation[X[i], Y[i]] - WaterLevel) * (CellWidth *
CellWidth)));
//              }

//              if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand) >=
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1])
//              {
//                  ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1];
//              }
//              if ((ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand) <
VolumeAcrossBorder[i - 1])
//              {
//                  ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1] =
ActualVolumeAcross[i] + AmountSand;
//              }
//          }

//      //StreamWriter AmSand =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/AmSand2.out");
//      //AmSand.Write(X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " + counter + "
" + AmountSand + Environment.NewLine);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //AmSand.Close();

//if (counter == 0 || counter % 365 == 0)
//{
//      StreamWriter VolumeAcrossBorder_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/VolumeAcrossBorder.out");
//      VolumeAcrossBorder_File.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//      VolumeAcrossBorder_File.Write(counter + " " +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + Environment.NewLine);
//      VolumeAcrossBorder_File.Close();

//      StreamWriter ActualVolumeAcross_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/ActualVolumeAcross.out");
//      ActualVolumeAcross_File.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//      ActualVolumeAcross_File.Write(counter + " " +
ActualVolumeAcross[i] + Environment.NewLine);
//      ActualVolumeAcross_File.Close();
//}

//StreamWriter AmountS_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/AmountS_FILE.out");
//AmountS_File.Write(AmountSand + Environment.NewLine);
//AmountS_File.Close();

//}

}

void TransportSedimentSweep()
{
// Sweep through cells to place transported sediment
// Call function AdjustShore() to move sediment.
// If cell full or overempty, call OopsImFull or
OopsImEmpty()
// This function doesn't change any values, but the
functions it calls do
// Uses but doesn't change: X[], Y[], PercentFullSand[]
// sweepsign added to ensure that direction of actuating
changes does not
// produce unwanted artifacts (e.g. make sure symmetrical

int i,ii,sweepsign;

if (RandZeroToOne() * 2 > 1)
{
sweepsign = 1;
}
else
{
sweepsign = 0;
}

for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
{

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (sweepsign == 1)
        {
            ii = i;
        }
        else
        {
            ii = TotalBeachCells - 1 - i;
        }

        AdjustShore(ii);
        //VolumeRecal();
        ErodeTheBeach(ii);
    }
}

///
/// AdjustShore 1234 - exponentially decay amount of material
in each block - problem, each block isn't the same size.
/// AdjustShore_Part2 - reduce by % at each block (try 10%,
20%)
/// AdjustShore
///
void AdjustShore_1234(int i)
{
    // Complete mass balance for incoming and outgoing sediment
    // This function will change the global data array
PercentFullSand[][]
    // Uses but does not adjust arrays: X[], Y[],
ShorelineAngle[], ActualVolumeAcross LMV
    // Uses global variables: ShelfSlope, CellWidth,
ShorefaceSlope, InitialDepth

    //FIND EFFECTIVE DEPTH, Deff, HERE
    //Deff = FROM SOLUTION TO:
    //A*Distance^n = D(X) -
OverallSlope*cos(ShorelineAngle[X][Y])*Distance
    //Where Distance is from shore, perpendicular to
ShorelineAngle;
    //Brad's stuff not being used right now (linear slope for
now) :
    //Xintercept = X + Distance*cos(ShorelineAngle), and n =
2/3.
    //THEN Deff = D(Xintercept);
    //FIND "A" FROM DEPTH OF 10METERS AT ABOUT 1000METERS.
    //FOR NOW, USE n = 1:

    double DeltaArea;        // Holds change in area for cell
(m^2)

    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'C')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        VolumeOut[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];

```

```

    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    }

    DeltaArea = ((VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / 100);
    //Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += DeltaArea;
    //DeltaArea = (VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]);

    //StreamWriter Volsout =
    File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/Vols2.out");
    //Volsout.Write(X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " + DeltaArea + " "
+ counter + Environment.NewLine);
    //Volsout.Close();

    //DeltaArea = ((VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / numCells[i])
/ 100;

    //string DeltaAreaFile = "OUTPUT_FILES/DeltaArea.out";

    //if (counter == 0)
    //{
    //    StreamWriter DeltaAreaSW = new
StreamWriter(DeltaAreaFile);
    //    DeltaAreaSW.WriteLine(counter + " " + X[i] + " " +
Y[i] + DeltaArea);
    //    DeltaAreaSW.Close();
    //}
    //else
    //{
    //    StreamWriter DeltaAreaSW =
File.AppendText(DeltaAreaFile);
    //    DeltaAreaSW.WriteLine(counter + " " + X[i] + " " +
Y[i] + DeltaArea);
    //    DeltaAreaSW.Close();
    //}

    //if (numCells[i] < 20)
    //{
    //    if (DeltaArea != 0)
    //    {
    //        DeltaArea = DeltaArea/100;
    //    }
    //}

    if (DeltaArea != 0)
    {

        double firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / (9000 /
CellWidth); //numCells[i];

        double[] block_Count = new double[200];
        double blockCount = 0;
        int blocks = 0;

```

```

        Array.Clear(block_Count, 0, block_Count.Length);

        block_Count[0] = 0;

        if (double.IsInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]) ||
double.IsNegativeInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]))
        { }

        // if numcells[i] is smaller than this number, the
material will be shared between cells and block diffusion will occur
        if (numCells[i] <= 20)
        {
            //
            // Direction = 1
            //
            if (direction[i] == 1)
            {
                int a = 0;
                int j = 1;

                // If current cell is above the water, move to
the next cell
                if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
                {
                    a = 1;
                }

                if (numCells[i] - a <= 0)
                {
                    firstDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    firstDeltaArea /= numCells[i] - a;
                }

                int Count_1 = numCells[i] - a;
                double leftovers = 0;

                int z = a;
                // Give equal amount to the row of original
numcells[i]
                for (int aa = a; aa < numCells[i]; aa++)
                {
                    if (Y[i] + aa > ymax - 1 || Y[i] + aa < 0)
                    {
                        // ingnore cell
                        leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
                        goto get_out_1;
                    }
                    if (X[i] < 0 || X[i] > pbEnd - 1)
                    {
                        int stop = 1;
                    }
                    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + aa] == 0)
                    {
                        Volume[X[i], Y[i] + aa] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                    }
                    else

```

```

        {
            leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
        }
get_out_1:
    z++;
}

// how many blocks until we reach 80ish cells?
for (blocks = 0; Count_1 < 80; blocks++)
{
    int xHolder = X[i] + blocks + 1;
    int yHolder = Y[i] + numCells[i] - a;
    int c, d, e, f, g, h;

    h = 0;

    // Right side - top half
    for (c = 0; c <= (blocks + 1); c++)
    {
        if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_1;
        }
        if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
        {
            if (xHolder < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
        {
            Count_1++;
            h++;
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
    }

    y_out_1:
        blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side
for (d = 1; d <= ((blocks + 1) * 2); d++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell

```

```

        h++;
        goto y_out_2;
    }
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder - h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }

y_out_2:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Left Side
for (e = 1; e < ((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
{
    if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_3;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;

```

```

    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }

y_out_3:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Bottom Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_4;
    }
    if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder + h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }

y_out_4:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side - Bottom part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1 + (numCells[i]
- a) - 2; g++)
{
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;

```

```

        goto y_out_5;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
    y_out_5:
        blockCount++;
    }

    block_Count[j] = blockCount;
    blockCount++;
    j++;
}

//How many blocks? How much for each block?
int posNeg;
if ((DeltaArea - (firstDeltaArea * numCells[i]
- a) + leftovers) < 0)
{
    posNeg = -1;
}
else
{
    posNeg = 1;
}

double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // How much
material do we have?
double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // Keep
tracks of little bits that are left.
double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers);
// End Amount
double P = 1;
// Start Amount
double t = blocks;
// time

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//double decayRate = Math.Log(A / P) / t;
// r, decay rate
double decayRate = (Math.Log(A / P)) / t;

int emptyflag = 0;
blockCount = 0;
j = 0;

// Now give those active cells some material
for (blocks = 0; (totalDeltaArea > 0) &&
(emptyflag == 0); blocks++)
{
    int xHolder = X[i] + blocks + 1;
    int yHolder = Y[i] + numCells[i] - a;
    int c, d, e, f, g, h;

    j++;
    h = 0;

    if (blocks <= t)
    {
        //extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs(((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / 5) / numCells[i]);
        extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / numCells[i]);
    }

    if (extraDeltaArea == 0)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea;
    }

    if ((double.IsInfinity(extraDeltaArea)) ||
(double.IsNegativeInfinity(extraDeltaArea)))
    { }

    // Right side - top half
    for (c = 0; c <= (blocks + 1); c++)
    {
        if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
        {
            // ingnore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_1a;
        }
        if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
        {
            if (xHolder < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

== 0)
extraDeltaArea)
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
extraDeltaArea;

if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
{
  if (totalDeltaArea <=
  {
    Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    emptyflag = 1;
    h++;
    break;
  }
  else
  {
    Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
    totalDeltaArea -=
    h++;
  }
}
else
{
  h++;
}
y_out_1a:
  blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
  emptyflag = 1;
  break;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side
for (d = 1; d <= ((blocks + 1) * 2); d++)
{
  if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
  {
    // ingnore cell
    h++;
    goto y_out_2a;
  }
  if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
  {
    if (xHolder - h < 0)
    {
      xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
    }
    else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
    {
      xHolder = 0;
    }
    h = 0;
  }
}

```

```

== 0)
extraDeltaArea)
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
extraDeltaArea;

if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
{
  if (totalDeltaArea <=
  {
    Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    emptyflag = 1;
    h++;
    break;
  }
  else
  {
    Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
    totalDeltaArea -=
    h++;
  }
}
else
{
  h++;
}
y_out_2a:
  blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
  emptyflag = 1;
  break;
}

xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Left Side
for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
{
  if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
  {
    // ignore cell
    h++;
    goto y_out_3a;
  }
  if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
  {
    if (xHolder < 0)
    {
      xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
    }
    else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
    {
      xHolder = 0;
    }
  }
}

```

```

== 0)
extraDeltaArea)
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
extraDeltaArea;

if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
{
  if (totalDeltaArea <=
  {
    Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]
    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    emptyflag = 1;
    h++;
    break;
  }
  else
  {
    Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]
    totalDeltaArea -=
    h++;
  }
}
else
{
  h++;
}
y_out_3a:
  blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
  emptyflag = 1;
  break;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Bottom Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
  if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
  {
    // ignore cell
    h++;
    goto y_out_4a;
  }
  if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
  {
    if (xHolder + h < 0)
    {
      xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
    }
    else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
    {
      xHolder = 0;
    }
    h = 0;
  }
}

```

```

== 0)
extraDeltaArea)
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
extraDeltaArea;

if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
{
  if (totalDeltaArea <=
  {
    Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    emptyflag = 1;
    h++;
    break;
  }
  else
  {
    Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
    totalDeltaArea -=
    h++;
  }
}
else
{
  h++;
}
y_out_4a:
  blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
  emptyflag = 1;
  break;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side - Bottom part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1 + (numCells[i]
- a) - 2; g++)
{
  if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
  {
    // ignore cell
    h++;
    goto y_out_5a;
  }
  if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
  {
    if (xHolder < 0)
    {
      xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
    }
    else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
    {
      xHolder = 0;
    }
  }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

== 0)
extraDeltaArea)
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
extraDeltaArea;

if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
{
    if (totalDeltaArea <=
    {
        Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
        totalDeltaArea = 0;
        emptyflag = 1;
        h++;
        break;
    }
    else
    {
        Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
        totalDeltaArea -=
        h++;
    }
}
y_out_5a:
    blockCount++;
}
if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}
}
}

//
// Direction = 5
//
else if (direction[i] == 5)
{
    int a = 0;
    int j = 1;

    // If current cell is above the water, move to
the next cell
    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
    {
        a = 1;
    }

    if (numCells[i] - a <= 0)
    {
        firstDeltaArea = 0;
    }
    else
    {
        firstDeltaArea /= numCells[i] - a;
    }

    int Count_1 = numCells[i] - a;

    double leftovers = 0;

```

```

int z = a;
// Give equal amount to the row of original
numcells[i]
for (int aa = a; aa < numCells[i]; aa++)
{
    if (Y[i] - aa > ymax - 1 || Y[i] - aa < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
        goto get_out_2;
    }
    if (X[i] < 0 || X[i] > pbEnd - 1)
    {
        int stop = 1;
    }
    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - aa] == 0)
    {
        Volume[X[i], Y[i] - aa] +=
firstDeltaArea;
    }
    else
    {
        leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
    }
get_out_2:
    z++;
}

blockCount = 0;

// how many blocks until we reach 80ish cells?
for (blocks = 0; Count_1 < 80; blocks++)
{
    int xHolder = X[i] + blocks + 1;
    int yHolder = Y[i] - a;
    int c, d, e, f, g, h;

    h = 0;

    // Right side - top half
    for (c = 0; c <= (blocks + 1); c++)
    {
        if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_6;
        }
        if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
        {
            if (xHolder < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

== 0)
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_6:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side
for (d = 1; d <= ((blocks + 1) * 2); d++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_7;
    }
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder - h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_7:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Left Side
for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
{
    if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)

```

```

    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_8;
    }
1) if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_8:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Bottom Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_9;
    }
    if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder + h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
}

```

```

        else
        {
            h++;
        }
y_out_9:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side - Bottom part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1 + (numCells[i]
- a) - 2; g++)
{
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_10;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_10:
    blockCount++;
}

block_Count[j] = blockCount;
blockCount++;
j++;
}

//How many blocks? How much for each block?
int posNeg;
if ((DeltaArea - (firstDeltaArea * numCells[i]
- a) + leftovers) < 0)
{
    posNeg = -1;
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

else
{
    posNeg = 1;
}

double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // How much
material do we have?
double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // Keep
tracks of little bits that are left.
double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers);
// End Amount
double P = 1;
// Start Amount
double t = blocks;
// time

double decayRate = (Math.Log(A / P)) / t;
// r, decay rate

int emptyflag = 0;
j = 0;
blockCount = 0;

// Now give those active cells some material
for (blocks = 0; (totalDeltaArea > 0) &&
(emptyflag == 0); blocks++)
{
    int xHolder = X[i] + blocks + 1;
    int yHolder = Y[i] - a;
    int c, d, e, f, g, h;
    h = 0;
    j++;

    if (blocks <= t)
    {
        //extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs(((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / 5) / numCells[i]);
        extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / numCells[i]);
    }

    if (extraDeltaArea == 0)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea;
    }

    if ((double.IsInfinity(extraDeltaArea)) ||
(double.IsNegativeInfinity(extraDeltaArea)))
    { }

    // Right side - top half
    for (c = 0; c <= (blocks + 1); c++)
    {
        if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_6a;

```

```

    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
}
y_out_6a:
    blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side
for (d = 1; d <= ((blocks + 1) * 2); d++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_7a;
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

pbEnd - 1)
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
    {
        if (xHolder - h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
        {
            Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea -=
            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_7a:
    blockCount++;
}
if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}
xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;
// Left Side
for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
{
    if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
    {
        // ingnore cell
        h++;
    }
}

```

```

        goto y_out_8a;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - e]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_8a:
    blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Bottom Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_9a;
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

pbEnd - 1)
    if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
    {
        if (xHolder + h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
        {
            Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea -=
            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_9a:
    blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side - Bottom part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1 + (numCells[i]
- a) - 2; g++)
{
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ingnore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_10a;
    }
}

```

```

    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
    y_out_10a:
    blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}
}

//
// Direction = 3
//
else if (direction[i] == 3)
{
    int a = 0;
    int j = 1;
    double leftovers = 0;

    // If current cell is above the water, move to
the next cell

```

```

        if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
        {
            a = 1;
        }

        if (numCells[i] - a <= 0)
        {
            firstDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            firstDeltaArea /= numCells[i] - a;
        }

        int Count_1 = numCells[i] - a;

        int z = a;
        // Give equal amount to the row of original
numcells[i]
        for (int aa = a; aa < numCells[i]; aa++)
        {
            if (Y[i] > ymax - 1 || Y[i] < 0)
            {
                // ignore cell
                leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
                goto get_out_3;
            }
            if (X[i] + z < 0 || X[i] + z > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                if (X[i] + z < 0)
                {
                    z = pbEnd - 1;
                }
                else if (X[i] + z > pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    z = 0;
                }
            }
            if (AboveWater[X[i] + z, Y[i]] == 0)
            {
                Volume[X[i] + z, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
            else
            {
                leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
            }
        }
        get_out_3:
            z++;
    }

    // how many blocks until we reach 80ish cells?
    for (blocks = 0; Count_1 < 80; blocks++)
    {
        int xHolder = X[i] + numCells[i] - a;
        int yHolder = Y[i] + blocks + 1;

        int c, d, e, f, g, h;

        h = 1;

        // Top side - Left half

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

numCells[i] - a - 1); c++)
    for (c = 0; c < ((blocks + 1) +
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_11;
        }
        if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder - h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
            h = 0;
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
        {
            Count_1++;
            h++;
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
        y_out_11:
            blockCount++;
        }

        xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
        h = 1;

        // Left Side
        for (d = 1; d <= (blocks + 1) * 2; d++)
        {
            if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
            {
                // ignore cell
                h++;
                goto y_out_12;
            }
            if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
            {
                if (xHolder < 0)
                {
                    xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
                }
                else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    xHolder = 0;
                }
            }
        }
    }

```

```

if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_12:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

// Bottom Side
for (e = 1; e < ((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_13;
        }
        if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder + h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
            h = 0;
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
        {
            Count_1++;
            h++;
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
y_out_13:
        blockCount++;
    }

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
    {
        if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)

```

```

    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_14;
    }
1) if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_14:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side - Right part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1; g++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_15;
    }
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder - h < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
}

```

```

        else
        {
            h++;
        }
        y_out_15:
        blockCount++;
    }

    block_Count[j] = blockCount;
    blockCount++;
    j++;
}

//How many blocks? How much for each block?
int posNeg;
if ((DeltaArea - (firstDeltaArea * numCells[i]
- a) + leftovers) < 0)
{
    posNeg = -1;
}
else
{
    posNeg = 1;
}

    double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // How much
material do we have?
    double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); // Keep
tracks of little bits that are left.
    double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers);
// End Amount
    double P = 1;
// Start Amount
    double t = blocks;
// time

    double decayRate = (Math.Log(A / P)) / t;
// r, decay rate

    int emptyflag = 0;
    j = 0;

    // Now give those active cells some material
for (blocks = 0; (totalDeltaArea > 0) &&
(emptyflag == 0); blocks++)
    {
        int xHolder = X[i] + numCells[i] - a;
        int yHolder = Y[i] + blocks + 1;
        int c, d, e, f, g, h;

        j++;

        if (blocks <= t)
        {
            //extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs(((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / 5) / numCells[i]);
            extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / numCells[i]);

```

```

    }

    if (extraDeltaArea == 0)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea;
    }

    if ((double.IsInfinity(extraDeltaArea)) ||
(double.IsNegativeInfinity(extraDeltaArea)))
    { }

    h = 1;

    // Top side - Left half
    for (c = 0; c < ((blocks + 1) +
numCells[i] - a - 1); c++)
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_11a;
        }
        if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder - h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
            h = 0;
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
            {
                Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                emptyflag = 1;
                h++;
                break;
            }
            else
            {
                Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

                h++;
            }
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
    }
}

```

```

y_out_11a:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Left Side
for (d = 1; d <= (blocks + 1) * 2; d++)
{
    if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_12a;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
}
y_out_12a:

```

```

        blockCount++;
    }

    yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
    h = 1;

    if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
    {
        emptyflag = 1;
        break;
    }

    // Bottom Side
    for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_13a;
        }
        if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder + h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
            h = 0;
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
            {
                Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                emptyflag = 1;
                h++;
                break;
            }
            else
            {
                Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

                h++;
            }
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
    }
}

```

```

y_out_13a:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Right Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (counter == 6)
    {
        int stop = 1;
    }
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_14a;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

            h++;
        }
    }
    else

```

```

        {
            h++;
        }
    y_out_14a:
        blockCount++;
    }

    yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
    h = 1;

    if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
    {
        emptyflag = 1;
        break;
    }

    // Top Side - Right part
    for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1; g++)
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_15a;
        }
        if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder - h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
            h = 0;
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
            {
                Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                emptyflag = 1;
                h++;
                break;
            }
            else
            {
                Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;

                totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

                h++;
            }
        }
    }
    else

```

```

        {
            h++;
        }
    y_out_15a:
        blockCount++;
    }

    if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
    {
        emptyflag = 1;
        break;
    }
}
//
// Direction = 7
//
else if (direction[i] == 7)
{
    int a = 0;
    int j = 1;
    double leftovers = 0;

    // If current cell is above the water, move to
the next cell
    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
    {
        a = 1;
    }

    if (numCells[i] - a <= 0)
    {
        firstDeltaArea = 0;
    }
    else
    {
        firstDeltaArea /= numCells[i] - a;
    }

    int Count_1 = numCells[i] - a;

    int z = a;

    // Give equal amount to the row of original
numcells[i]
    for (int aa = a; aa < numCells[i]; aa++)
    {
        if (Y[i] > ymax - 1 || Y[i] < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
            goto get_out_4;
        }
        if (X[i] - z < 0 || X[i] - z > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (X[i] - z < 0)
            {
                z = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (X[i] - z > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                z = 0;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
  }
  if (AboveWater[X[i] - z, Y[i]] == 0)
  {
    Volume[X[i] - z, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
  }
  else
  {
    leftovers += Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);
  }
get_out_4:
  z++;
}

// how many blocks until we reach 80ish cells?
for (blocks = 0; Count_1 < 80; blocks++)
{
  int xHolder = X[i] - a;
  int yHolder = Y[i] + blocks + 1;

  int c, d, e, f, g, h;

  h = 0;

  // Top side - Left half
  for (c = 0; c < ((blocks + 1) +
numCells[i] - a - 1); c++)
  {
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
      // ignore cell
      h++;
      goto y_out_11;
    }
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
      if (xHolder - h < 0)
      {
        xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
      }
      else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
      {
        xHolder = 0;
      }
      h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
      Count_1++;
      h++;
    }
    else
    {
      h++;
    }
  }
y_out_11:
  blockCount++;

```

```

    }

    xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
    h = 1;

    // Left Side
    for (d = 1; d <= (blocks + 1) * 2; d++)
    {
        if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_12;
        }
        if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
        {
            if (xHolder < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
            }
        }
        if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
        {
            Count_1++;
            h++;
        }
        else
        {
            h++;
        }
    }
    y_out_12:
    blockCount++;
}

    yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
    h = 1;

    // Bottom Side
    for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
    {
        if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
        {
            // ignore cell
            h++;
            goto y_out_13;
        }
        if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
        {
            if (xHolder + h < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            }
            else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_13:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Right Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_14;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        Count_1++;
        h++;
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_14:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

// Top Side - Right part

```

```

        for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1; g++)
        {
            if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
            {
                // ignore cell
                h++;
                goto y_out_15;
            }
            if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
            {
                if (xHolder - h < 0)
                {
                    xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
                }
                else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    xHolder = 0;
                }
                h = 0;
            }
            if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
            {
                Count_1++;
                h++;
            }
            else
            {
                h++;
            }
            y_out_15:
                blockCount++;
        }

        block_Count[j] = blockCount;
        blockCount++;
        j++;
    }

    //How many blocks? How much for each block?
    int posNeg;
    if ((DeltaArea - (firstDeltaArea * numCells[i]
- a) + leftovers) < 0)
    {
        posNeg = -1;
    }
    else
    {
        posNeg = 1;
    }

    double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); //
How much material do we have?
    double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers); //
Keep tracks of little bits that are left.

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
(firstDeltaArea * numCells[i] - a) + leftovers);
// End Amount
        double P = 1;
// Start Amount
        double t = blocks;
// time

        double decayRate = (Math.Log(A / P)) / t;
// r, decay rate

        if (counter == 555 && i == 119)
        { }

        int emptyflag = 0;
        j = 0;

        // Now give those active cells some material
        for (blocks = 0; (totalDeltaArea > 0) &&
(emptyflag == 0); blocks++)
        {
            int xHolder = X[i] - a;
            int yHolder = Y[i] + blocks + 1;
            int c, d, e, f, g, h;

            j++;

            if (blocks <= t)
            {
                //extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs(((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / 5) / numCells[i]);
                extraDeltaArea =
Math.Abs((totalDeltaArea * decayRate) / numCells[i]);
            }

            if (extraDeltaArea == 0)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea;
            }

            if ((double.IsInfinity(extraDeltaArea)) ||
(double.IsNegativeInfinity(extraDeltaArea)))
            { }

            h = 0;

            // Top side - Left half
            for (c = 0; c < ((blocks + 1) +
numCells[i] - a - 1); c++)
            {
                if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
                {
                    // ignore cell
                    h++;
                    goto y_out_11a;
                }
                if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    if (xHolder - h < 0)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea -=
            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
}
y_out_11a:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Left Side
for (d = 1; d <= (blocks + 1) * 2; d++)
{
    if (yHolder - h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
- h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_12a;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder - h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder - h]

            totalDeltaArea -=
            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
    y_out_12a:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder - h + 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Bottom Side
for (e = 1; e < (((blocks + 1) * 2) +
numCells[i] - a); e++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_13a;
    }
    if (xHolder + h < 0 || xHolder + h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder + h < 0)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder + h > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
        h = 0;
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder + h, yHolder]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder + h, yHolder]
            totalDeltaArea -=
            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
}
y_out_13a:
    blockCount++;
}

xHolder = xHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Right Side
for (f = 1; f <= (blocks + 1) * 2; f++)
{
    if (yHolder + h > ymax - 1 || yHolder
+ h < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_14a;
    }
    if (xHolder < 0 || xHolder > pbEnd -
1)
    {
        if (xHolder < 0)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        }
        else if (xHolder > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
        }
    }
    if (AboveWater[xHolder, yHolder + h]
== 0)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            emptyflag = 1;
            h++;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder, yHolder + h]

            totalDeltaArea -=

            h++;
        }
    }
    else
    {
        h++;
    }
y_out_14a:
    blockCount++;
}

yHolder = yHolder + h - 1;
h = 1;

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}

// Top Side - Right part
for (g = 1; g <= blocks + 1; g++)
{
    if (yHolder > ymax - 1 || yHolder < 0)
    {
        // ignore cell
        h++;
        goto y_out_15a;
    }
    if (xHolder - h < 0 || xHolder - h >
pbEnd - 1)
    {
        if (xHolder - h < 0)
        {

```

```

        xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
    }
    else if (xHolder - h > pbEnd - 1)
    {
        xHolder = 0;
    }
    h = 0;
}
if (AboveWater[xHolder - h, yHolder]
== 0)
{
    if (totalDeltaArea <=
extraDeltaArea)
    {
        Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= totalDeltaArea * posNeg;

        totalDeltaArea = 0;
        emptyflag = 1;
        h++;
        break;
    }
    else
    {
        Volume[xHolder - h, yHolder]
+= extraDeltaArea * posNeg;
        totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
        h++;
    }
}
else
{
    h++;
}
y_out_15a:
    blockCount++;
}

if (totalDeltaArea <= 0)
{
    emptyflag = 1;
    break;
}
}
}

else if (DeltaArea > 0 && numCells[i] > 20)
{
    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
    {
        if (direction[i] == 1)
        {
            Volume[X[i], Y[i] + 1] += firstDeltaArea;
            //Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 2)
        {
            Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;

```

```

        //X[i] = X[i] + 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 3)
    {
        Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
        //X[i] = X[i] + 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 4)
    {
        Volume[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        //X[i] = X[i] + 1;
        //Y[i] = Y[i] - 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 5)
    {
        Volume[X[i], Y[i] - 1] += firstDeltaArea;
        //Y[i] = Y[i] - 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 6)
    {
        Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        //X[i] = X[i] - 1;
        //Y[i] = Y[i] - 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 7)
    {
        Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
        //X[i] = X[i] - 1;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 8)
    {
        Volume[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        //Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
        //X[i] = X[i] - 1;
    }
    //Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += 0;
    numCells[i]--;
}
else
{
    Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
    numCells[i]--;
}

int xHolder;
int s = 0;

double extraDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
// How much material do we have?
double totalDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
// Keep tracks of little bits that are left.
double A = DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea;

// End Amount
double P = 1;
// Start Amount
double t = numCells[i];
// time

if (numCells[i] <= 0)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        {
            numCells[i] = 1;
            t = 1;
        }

double decayRate = Math.Log(A / P) / t;    // r,
decay rate

        if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
        {
            for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
                {
                    Volume[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                }
                else
                {
                    Volume[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
extraDeltaArea;
                }
                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
        {
            xHolder = X[i];

            for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    xHolder = 0;
                    s = 0;
                }
                if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
                {
                    Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                    s++;
                }
                else
                {
                    Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
extraDeltaArea;
                    s++;
                }
                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
        {
            for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

                                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                                if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
                                {
totalDeltaArea;
                                    Volume[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
                                }
                                else
                                {
extraDeltaArea;
                                    Volume[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
                                }
                                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
                                }
                                }
                                else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
                                {
                                    xHolder = X[i];

                                for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
                                {
decayRate;
                                    extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *

                                if (xHolder - s < 0)
                                {
                                    xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
                                    s = 0;
                                }

                                if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
                                {
totalDeltaArea;
                                    Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
                                }
                                else
                                {
extraDeltaArea;
                                    Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
                                    s++;
                                }

                                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
                                }
                                }
                                }

                                // int CellCount = 0;
                                // int xHolder;

                                // int s = 0;

                                // // How many cells out does the slope extend
                                // (only to a dip in the coastline)
                                // if (direction[i] == 1) // Top
                                // {
                                //     for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      {
//          Volume[X[i], Y[i] + s] += DeltaArea;
//          s++;
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 2) // Top Right
//  {
//      for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
//      {
//          Volume[X[i] + s, Y[i] + s] +=
DeltaArea;
//          s++;
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
//  {
//      xHolder = X[i];
//
//      //if (AboveWater[xHolder + 1, Y[i]] ==
1)
//          //{
//              Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
//          }
//
//      for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
//      {
//          if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
//          {
//              xHolder = 0;
//              s = 0;
//              Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
DeltaArea;
//              s++;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//              Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
DeltaArea;
//              s++;
//          }
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 4) // Bottom Right
//  {
//      for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
//      {
//          Volume[X[i] + s, Y[i] - s] +=
DeltaArea;
//          s++;
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
//  {
//      for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
//      {
//          Volume[X[i], Y[i] - s] += DeltaArea;
//          s++;
//      }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //      }
        //      else if (direction[i] == 6) // Bottom Left
        //      {
        //          for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
        //          {
        //              Volume[X[i] - s, Y[i] - s] +=
DeltaArea;
        //              s++;
        //          }
        //      }
        //      else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
        //      {
        //          xHolder = X[i];

        //          //if (AboveWater[xHolder - 1, Y[i]] ==
1)
        //          //{
        //              //      Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
        //          //}

        //          for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
        //          {
        //              if (xHolder - s < 0)
        //              {
        //                  xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
        //                  s = 0;
        //                  Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
DeltaArea;
        //                  s++;
        //              }
        //              else
        //              {
        //                  Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
DeltaArea;
        //                  s++;
        //              }
        //          }
        //      }
        //      else if (direction[i] == 8) // Top Left
        //      {
        //          for (CellCount = 0; CellCount <
numCells[i]; CellCount++)
        //          {
        //              Volume[X[i] - s, Y[i] + s] +=
DeltaArea;
        //              s++;
        //          }
        //      }
    }

    else if (DeltaArea < 0 && numCells[i] > 20)
    {
        Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
        numCells[i]--;

        int xHolder;
        int s = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea); // How much material do we have?
double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea); // Keep tracks of little bits that are
left.
double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
double P = 1;
// Start Amount
double t = numCells[i];
// time

if (numCells[i] <= 0)
{
    numCells[i] = 1;
    t = 1;
}

double decayRate = Math.Log(A / P) / t; // r,
decay rate

if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
{
    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
        {
            Volume[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
{
    xHolder = X[i];

    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
            s = 0;
        }
        if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
        {
            Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;
            s++;
        }
        else

```

```

        {
            Volume[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;
            s++;
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
        {
            Volume[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
totalDeltaArea;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
{
    xHolder = X[i];

    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i]; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        if (xHolder - s < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            s = 0;
        }

        if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
        {
            Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;
        }
        else
        {
            Volume[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;
            s++;
        }

        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
}

if (double.IsInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]) ||
double.IsNegativeInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]))

```

```

        { }
    }
    if (double.IsInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]) ||
double.IsNegativeInfinity(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]))
    { }
}

void AdjustShore_Part2(int i)
{
    // Complete mass balance for incoming and outgoing sediment
    // This function will change the global data array
PercentFullSand[][]
    // Uses but does not adjust arrays: X[], Y[],
ShorelineAngle[], ActualVolumeAcross LMV
    // Uses global variables: ShelfSlope, CellWidth,
ShorefaceSlope, InitialDepth

    //FIND EFFECTIVE DEPTH, Deff, HERE
    //Deff = FROM SOLUTION TO:
    //A*Distance^n = D(X) -
OverallSlope*cos(ShorelineAngle[X][Y])*Distance
    //Where Distance is from shore, perpendicular to
ShorelineAngle;
    //Brad's stuff not being used right now (linear slope for
now) :
    //Xintercept = X + Distance*cos(ShorelineAngle), and n =
2/3.
    //THEN Deff = D(Xintercept);
    //FIND "A" FROM DEPTH OF 10METERS AT ABOUT 1000METERS.
    //FOR NOW, USE n = 1:

double DeltaArea;        // Holds change in area for cell
(m^2)

if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
{
    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
}
if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'C')
{
    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    VolumeOut[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
}
if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
{
    VolumeIn[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
    VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
}
if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
{
    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
    VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
}

//if (X[i] == xDisplayStart)
//{

```

```

        //}

        //if (X[i] == pbEnd / 2)
        //{
            StreamWriter SandOut_File_m =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandOut_middle.out");
            //    SandOut_File_m.Write(counter + " " + X[i] + " " +
Y[i] + " " + ((VolumeOut[i] / CellWidth) / 2) + Environment.NewLine);
            //    SandOut_File_m.Close();
        //}

        //if (X[i] == xDisplayEnd)
        //{
            StreamWriter SandOut_File_e =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandOut_end.out");
            //    SandOut_File_e.Write(counter + " " + X[i] + " " +
Y[i] + " " + ((VolumeOut[i] / CellWidth) / 2) + Environment.NewLine);
            //    SandOut_File_e.Close();
        //}

        //DeltaArea = (((VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / 100) /
2));
        DeltaArea = (VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth);

        //if (X[i] == 1000 && Y[i] > 250 && hit == 0)
        //{
            StreamWriter SandOut_File_s =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandOut_start.out");
            //    //StreamWriter Delta_File =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/Delta_File.out");

            //    ////if (X[i] == 1)
            //    ////{
            //    ////    SandOut_File_s.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            //    ////    Delta_File.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            //    ////}

            //    //Delta_File.Write(counter + " " + X[i] + " " + Y[i]
+ " " + DeltaArea + Environment.NewLine);
            //    //Delta_File.Close();

            //    SandOut_File_s.Write(counter + " " +
DirectionAcrossBorder[i] + " " + X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " +
(VolumeIn[i] / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + (VolumeOut[i] /
(CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + DeltaArea + " " +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + " " + ActualVolumeAcross[i] +
Environment.NewLine);
            //    SandOut_File_s.Close();

            //    hit = 1;

        //}

        if (HaveSinks == 1)
        {
            for (int Sx = 0; Sx < SinkX.Length; Sx++)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        {
            if (X[i] == SinkX[Sx])
            {
                DeltaArea = 0;
            }
        }
    }

    int CellCount = 0;
    double firstDeltaArea;
    double A2;
// End Amount
    double P2;
// Start Amount
    double t2;
    double A3;
// End Amount
    double P3;
// Start Amount
    double t3;
// time
    double decayRate1;

    double averageChange = Math.Abs(DeltaArea / MaxDist);
    int shortShoreface = 10;

    if (DeltaArea != 0)
    {
        // Delta Area > 0
        //
        if (DeltaArea > 0)
        {

            if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
            {
                //double firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea /
numCells[i];
                firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / MaxDist;
                A2 = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
                P2 = 1;
// Start Amount
                t2 = MaxDist;
            }
            else
            {
                firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / numCells[i];
                A2 = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
                P2 = 1;
// Start Amount
                t2 = numCells[i];
// time
            }

            if (numCells[i] <= 1)
            {
                numCells[i] = 2;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        t2 = 1;
    }

    decayRate1 = (Math.Log(A2 / P2)) / t2;
// r, decay rate

    //double firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea * decayRate1;

    int jj = 0;

    if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
    {
        if (direction[i] == 1)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + 1] == 0)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 2)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 3)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 0)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 4)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 5)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - 1] == 0)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 6)
        {
            if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

                                VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                                }
                                }
                                else if (direction[i] == 7)
                                {
                                    if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 0)
                                    {
                                        VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                                        }
                                    }
                                else if (direction[i] == 8)
                                {
                                    if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
                                    {
                                        VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                                        }
                                    }
                                numCells[i]--;
                                jj = 2;
                                }
                                else
                                {
                                    if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] < averageChange
&& AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 0)
                                    {
                                        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                                        }
                                    numCells[i]--;
                                    jj = 1;
                                }
                                }

                                int xHolder;
                                int s = 0;

                                double extraDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
                                // How much material do we have?
                                double totalDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
                                // Keep tracks of little bits that are left.
                                double A = DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea;
                                // End Amount

                                double P = 1;
                                // Start Amount

                                double t;

                                if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
                                {
                                    t = MaxDist - jj;
                                // time
                                }
                                else
                                {
                                    t = numCells[i] - jj;
                                }

                                double decayRate = (Math.Log(A / P)) / t;    //
r, decay rate

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
        {
            for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                //if (j == numCells[i] - 1 &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0)
                //{
                //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                //}
                if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
                {
                    lost += totalDeltaArea;
                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] < averageChange)
                {
                    if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                    {
                        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                        totalDeltaArea = 0;
                        extraDeltaArea = 0;
                    }
                    else
                    {
                        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
extraDeltaArea;
                    }
                }
                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
        {
            xHolder = X[i];

            for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
                {
                    xHolder = 0;
                    s = 0;
                }
                else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
                {
                    if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                    {
                        VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                        totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    }
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        extraDeltaArea = 0;
    }
    else
    {
        VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
extraDeltaArea;
    }
    s++;
}
totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
}

// Turn direction to up
// Share rest with north going cells, along
all X-numcells
if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
{
    int k = 1;

    //int n = 0;

    // while (totalDeltaArea > 0)
    // {

    // for (int m = 0; m < numCells[i]
&& totalDeltaArea > 0; m++)
    // {
    //     extraDeltaArea =
totalDeltaArea * decayRate;

    //     if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
    //     {
    //         lost += totalDeltaArea;
    //         totalDeltaArea = 0;
    //         break;
    //     }
    //     else if (xHolder + n > pbEnd
- 1)
    //     {
    //         xHolder = 0;
    //         n = 0;
    //     }
    //     if (AboveWater[xHolder + n,
Y[i] + k] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + n, Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
    //     {
    //         if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
    //         {
    //             VolumeChange[xHolder
+ n, Y[i] + k] += totalDeltaArea;
    //         }
    //         else
    //         {
    //             VolumeChange[xHolder
+ n, Y[i] + k] += extraDeltaArea;
    //         }
    //     }

    //     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

```

```

//          n++;
//      }
//      n = 0;
//      xHolder = X[i];
//      k++;
//  }

for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
{
    extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

    //if (Y[i] + k < ymax &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] == 0)
    //{
    //if (j == MaxDist - 1)
    //{
    //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] +=
totalDeltaArea;
    //}
    if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
    {
        lost += totalDeltaArea;
        totalDeltaArea = 0;
    }
    else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
totalDeltaArea = 0;
            extraDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    k++;
    totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    //}
    //else
    //{
    //    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    //    break;
    //}
}
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
    for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//if (j == numCells[i] - 1 &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0)
//{
//    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
totalDeltaArea;
//}
if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
{
    lost += totalDeltaArea;
    totalDeltaArea = 0;
}
else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] < averageChange)
{
    if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
    {
        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
totalDeltaArea;
        totalDeltaArea = 0;
        extraDeltaArea = 0;
    }
    else
    {
        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
}
}
else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
{
    xHolder = X[i];
    for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;
        if (xHolder - s < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            s = 0;
        }
        //if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
        //{
        //    VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea;
        //}
        else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

                                VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
extraDeltaArea;
                                }
                                s++;
                                }

                                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
                                }

                                //// Turn direction to up
                                //// Share rest with north going cells, along
all X-numcells
                                //if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
                                //{
                                //    int k = 1;
                                //    int n = 0;

                                //    while (totalDeltaArea > 0)
                                //    {

                                //        for (int m = 0; m < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; m++)
                                //        {
                                //            extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea
* decayRate;

                                //            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
                                //            {
                                //                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                                //                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                                //                break;
                                //            }
                                //            else if (xHolder - n < 0)
                                //            {
                                //                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
                                //                n = 0;
                                //            }
                                //            if (AboveWater[xHolder - n, Y[i]
+ k] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - n, Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
                                //            {
                                //                if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
                                //                {
                                //                    VolumeChange[xHolder -
n, Y[i] + k] += totalDeltaArea;
                                //                }
                                //                else
                                //                {
                                //                    VolumeChange[xHolder -
n, Y[i] + k] += extraDeltaArea;
                                //                }
                                //            }

                                //            totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;

                                //            n++;
                                //        }
                                //        n = 0;
                                //        xHolder = X[i];
                                //        k++;
                                //    }

```

```

        if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
        {
            // Turn direction to up

            int k = 1;

            for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
            {
                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

                //if (Y[i] + k < ymax &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] == 0)
                //{
                //if (j == MaxDist - 1)
                //{
                //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] +=
totalDeltaArea;
                //}
                if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
                {
                    lost += totalDeltaArea;
                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
                {
                    if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
                    {
                        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] =
+totalDeltaArea;

                        totalDeltaArea = 0;
                        extraDeltaArea = 0;
                    }
                    else
                    {
                        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
                    }
                }
                k++;
                totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
                //}
                //else
                //{
                //    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                //    break;
                //}
            }
        }
    }

    //
    // Delta Area < 0
    //
    else if (DeltaArea < 0)
    {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        averageChange = averageChange * -1;

        if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
        {
            //double firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea /
numCells[i];
            firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / MaxDist;
            A3 = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
            P3 = 1;
// Start Amount
            t3 = MaxDist;
        }
        else
        {
            firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / numCells[i];
            A3 = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
            P3 = 1;
// Start Amount
            t3 = numCells[i];
// time
        }

        if (numCells[i] <= 1)
        {
            numCells[i] = 2;
            t3 = 1;
        }

        decayRate1 = (Math.Log(A3 / P3)) / t3;
// r, decay rate

        //double firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea * decayRate1;
// /2 works with DeltaArea/100

        if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] > averageChange)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
        }
        numCells[i]--;

        int xHolder;
        int s = 0;

        double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea);
        // How much material do we have?
        double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea);
        // Keep tracks of little bits that are
left.
        double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
        double P = 1;
// Start Amount
        double t;

        if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
        {
            t = MaxDist - 1;
// time

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

    }
    else
    {
        t = numCells[i] - 1;
    }
    //
time

    double decayRate = Math.Log(A / P) / t;    // r,
decay rate

    if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
    {
        for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

            //if (j == numCells[i] - 1 &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0)
            //{
            //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
            //}
            if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] > averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
totalDeltaArea;
                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
                }
            }
            totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
    {
        xHolder = X[i];

        for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

            if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
            {

```

```

        xHolder = 0;
        s = 0;
    }
    //if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
    //{
    //    VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;
        //    s++;
    //}
    else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
        {
            VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            extraDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;
        }
        s++;
    }
    totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
}

//if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//{
//    int k = 1;
//    int n = 0;

//    while (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//    {

//        for (int m = 0; m < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; m++)
//        {
//            extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea
* decayRate;

//            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//            {
//                lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                break;
//            }
//            else if (xHolder + n > pbEnd -
1)
//            {
//                xHolder = 0;
//                n = 0;
//            }
//            if (AboveWater[xHolder + n, Y[i]
+ k] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + n, Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
//            {
//                if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//                {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder +
n, Y[i] + k] -= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder +
n, Y[i] + k] -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     n++;
//                                     }
//                                     n = 0;
//                                     xHolder = X[i];
//                                     k++;
//                                     }
//                                     }

if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
{
    // Turn direction to up

    int k = 1;

    for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        //if (Y[i] + k < ymax &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] == 0)
        //{
        //if (j == MaxDist - 1)
        //{
        //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] +=
totalDeltaArea;
        //}
        if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
        {
            lost += totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= extraDeltaArea;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        k++;
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        //}
        //else
        //{
        //    totalDeltaArea = 0;
        //    break;
        //}
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        //if (j == numCells[i] - 1 &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0)
        //{
        //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
totalDeltaArea;
        //}
        if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
        {
            lost += totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
totalDeltaArea;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
extraDeltaArea;

            }
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
{
    xHolder = X[i];

    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;

        if (xHolder - s < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;

```

```

        s = 0;
    }

    //if (j == numCells[i] - 1)
    //{
    //    VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;
    //}
    else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
    {
        if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
        {
            VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;

            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            extraDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;
        }
        s++;
    }

    totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
}

///// Turn direction to up
///// Share rest with north going cells, along
all X-numcells

//if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//{
//    int k = 1;
//    int n = 0;

//    while (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//    {

//        for (int m = 0; m < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; m++)
//            {
//                extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea
* decayRate;

//                if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//                {
//                    lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                    break;
//                }
//                else if (xHolder - n < 0)
//                {
//                    xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
//                    n = 0;
//                }
//                if (AboveWater[xHolder - n, Y[i]
+ k] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - n, Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
//                    {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//          {
//          VolumeChange[xHolder -
n, Y[i] + k] -= totalDeltaArea;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//          VolumeChange[xHolder -
n, Y[i] + k] -= extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//          }
//          totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//          n++;
//          }
//          n = 0;
//          xHolder = X[i];
//          k++;
//          }
//      }

if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
{
    // Turn direction to up
    int k = 1;
    for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = totalDeltaArea *
decayRate;
        //if (Y[i] + k < ymax &&
AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] == 0)
        //{
        //if (j == MaxDist - 1)
        //{
        //    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] +=
totalDeltaArea;
        //}
        if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
        {
            lost += totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {

```

```

VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= extraDeltaArea;
    }
    k++;
    totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    //}
    //else
    //{
    //    totalDeltaArea = 0;
    //    break;
    //}
    }
    }
    }
    }
    //BlockTooBig:
    //    DeltaArea = 0;
}

void AdjustShore_reducePercnt1(int i)
{
    // Complete mass balance for incoming and outgoing sediment
    // This function will change the global data array
    PercentFullSand[][]
    // Uses but does not adjust arrays: X[], Y[],
    ShorelineAngle[], ActualVolumeAcross LMV
    // Uses global variables: ShelfSlope, CellWidth,
    ShorefaceSlope, InitialDepth

    //FIND EFFECTIVE DEPTH, Deff, HERE
    //Deff = FROM SOLUTION TO:
    //A*Distance^n = D(X) -
    OverallSlope*cos(ShorelineAngle[X][Y])*Distance
    //Where Distance is from shore, perpendicular to
    ShorelineAngle;
    //Brad's stuff not being used right now (linear slope for
    now) :
    //Xintercept = X + Distance*cos(ShorelineAngle), and n =
    2/3.
    //THEN Deff = D(Xintercept);
    //FIND "A" FROM DEPTH OF 10METERS AT ABOUT 1000METERS.
    //FOR NOW, USE n = 1:

    double DeltaArea; // Holds change in area for cell
    (m^2)

    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'C')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        VolumeOut[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')

```

```

    {
        VolumeIn[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    }
    if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
    {
        VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
    }

    DeltaArea = ((VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth)) / 100;

    if (X[i] == 1000 && Y[i] > 250 && hit == 0)
    {
        StreamWriter SandOut_File_s =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandOut_start.out");
        SandOut_File_s.Write(counter + " " +
DirectionAcrossBorder[i] + " " + X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " +
(VolumeIn[i] / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + (VolumeOut[i] /
(CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + DeltaArea + " " +
VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + " " + ActualVolumeAcross[i] +
Environment.NewLine);
        SandOut_File_s.Close();

        hit = 1;
    }

    if (HaveSinks == 1)
    {
        for (int Sx = 0; Sx < SinkX.Length; Sx++)
        {
            if (X[i] == SinkX[Sx])
            {
                DeltaArea = 0;
            }
        }
    }

    int CellCount = 0;
    double firstDeltaArea;
    double A2;
// End Amount
    double P2;
// Start Amount
    double t2;
    double A3;
// End Amount
    double P3;
// Start Amount
    double t3;
// time
    double decayRate1;

    double averageChange = 10;
    int shortShoreface = 100;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (DeltaArea != 0)
        {
            //
            // Delta Area > 0
            //
            if (DeltaArea > 0)
            {
                firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / 80; //
Give 20% to the first cell

                if (numCells[i] <= 1)
                {
                    numCells[i] = 2;
                }

                int jj = 0;

                if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
                {
                    if (direction[i] == 1)
                    {
                        if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + 1] == 0)
                        {
                            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                        }
                    }
                    else if (direction[i] == 2)
                    {
                        if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
                        {
                            VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                        }
                    }
                    else if (direction[i] == 3)
                    {
                        if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 0)
                        {
                            VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                        }
                    }
                    else if (direction[i] == 4)
                    {
                        if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
                        {
                            VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
                        }
                    }
                    else if (direction[i] == 5)
                    {
                        if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - 1] == 0)
                        {
                            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

    }
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 6)
    {
        if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 7)
    {
        if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 0)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 8)
    {
        if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    numCells[i]--;
    jj = 2;
}
else
{
    if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] < averageChange
&& AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 0)
    {
        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
    }
    numCells[i]--;
    jj = 1;
}

int xHolder;
int s = 0;

double extraDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
// How much material do we have?
double totalDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
// Keep tracks of little bits that are left.
double A = DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea;
// End Amount
double P = 1;
// Start Amount
double t;

if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
{
    t = MaxDist - jj;
// time
}

```

```

else
{
    t = numCells[i] - jj;
}

double decayRate = firstDeltaArea / 20;    // r,
decay rate
double previousDA = firstDeltaArea;

if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
{
    for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

        if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
        {
            lost += totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] < averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
totalDeltaArea;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] +=
extraDeltaArea;

            }
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
{
    xHolder = X[i];

    for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

        if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
            s = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

totalDeltaArea;
VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea = 0;
extraDeltaArea = 0;
}
else
{
VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] +=
extraDeltaArea;
}
s++;
}
totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
}

// Turn direction to up
// Share rest with north going cells, along
all X-numcells
if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
{
int k = 1;
for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
{
extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
{
lost += totalDeltaArea;
totalDeltaArea = 0;
}
else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
{
if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
{
VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= totalDeltaArea;
totalDeltaArea = 0;
extraDeltaArea = 0;
}
else
{
VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
}
}
k++;

totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
}
}
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)

```

```

        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

            if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] < averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
totalDeltaArea;

                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] +=
extraDeltaArea;

                }
            }
            totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
            previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
    {
        xHolder = X[i];

        for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

            if (xHolder - s < 0)
            {
                xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
                s = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
totalDeltaArea;

                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] +=
extraDeltaArea;

                }
                s++;
            }
        }

        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }
}

```

```

    }

    if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
    {
        // Turn direction to up
        int k = 1;
        for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= totalDeltaArea;

                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
                }
            }
            k++;
            totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
            previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
        }
    }

    //
    // Delta Area < 0
    //
    else if (DeltaArea < 0)
    {
        averageChange = averageChange * -1;

        firstDeltaArea = DeltaArea / 80;
// Give 20% to the first cell

        if (numCells[i] <= 1)
        {
            numCells[i] = 2;
        }

        if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] > averageChange)
        {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] += firstDeltaArea;
    }
    numCells[i]--;

    int xHolder;
    int s = 0;

    double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea +
firstDeltaArea);
        // How much material do we have?
    double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea +
firstDeltaArea);
        // Keep tracks of little bits that are
left.

    double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea + firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount

    double P = 1;
// Start Amount

    double t;

    if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
    {
        t = MaxDist - 1;
// time
    }
    else
    {
        t = numCells[i] - 1;
//
time
    }

    double decayRate = Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea / 20);
// r, decay rate

    double previousDA = Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);

    if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
    {
        for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

            if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] > averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
totalDeltaArea;

                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
                }
            }
        }
    }

```

```

        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
{
    xHolder = X[i];

    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

        if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
        {
            xHolder = 0;
            s = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;

                s++;
            }
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }

    if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
    {
        // Turn direction to up

        int k = 1;

        for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
            {

```

```

        if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
            extraDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else
        {
            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= extraDeltaArea;
        }
    }
    k++;
    totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
    previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
}
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;
        if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
        {
            lost += totalDeltaArea;
            totalDeltaArea = 0;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
            }
        }
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
{
    xHolder = X[i];
    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
    {
        extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;
        if (xHolder - s < 0)

```

```

        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            s = 0;
        }

        else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] ==
0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
        {
            if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea)
            {
                VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
totalDeltaArea;

                totalDeltaArea = 0;
                extraDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else
            {
                VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
extraDeltaArea;

            }
            s++;
        }

        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }

    if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
    {
        // Turn direction to up

        int k = 1;

        for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
        {
            extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
            {
                lost += totalDeltaArea;
                totalDeltaArea = 0;
            }
            else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
            {
                if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= totalDeltaArea;

                    totalDeltaArea = 0;
                    extraDeltaArea = 0;
                }
                else
                {
                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -
= extraDeltaArea;

                }
            }
        }
    }

```

```

        k++;
        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
    }
}
}
}

void AdjustShore(int i)
{
    // Complete mass balance for incoming and outgoing sediment
    // This function will change the global data array
    PercentFullSand[][]
    // Uses but does not adjust arrays: X[], Y[],
    ShorelineAngle[], ActualVolumeAcross LMV
    // Uses global variables: ShelfSlope, CellWidth,
    ShorefaceSlope, InitialDepth

    //FIND EFFECTIVE DEPTH, Deff, HERE
    //Deff = FROM SOLUTION TO:
    //A*Distance^n = D(X) -
    OverallSlope*cos(ShorelineAngle[X][Y])*Distance
    //Where Distance is from shore, perpendicular to
    ShorelineAngle;
    //Brad's stuff not being used right now (linear slope for
    now) :
    //Xintercept = X + Distance*cos(ShorelineAngle), and n =
    2/3.
    //THEN Deff = D(Xintercept);
    //FIND "A" FROM DEPTH OF 10METERS AT ABOUT 1000METERS.
    //FOR NOW, USE n = 1:

    //// DEBUGGING START
    //if (counter == 365 &&((i == 88) || (i == 89) || (i ==
    90) || (i == 91) || (i == 92) || (i == 93) || (i == 94) || (i == 95)
    || (i == 96) || (i == 97) || (i == 98) || (i == 99) || (i == 100)))
    //{
    //    Array.Clear(VolumeChange, 0, VolumeChange.Length);
    //}
    //// DEBUGGIN END

    double DeltaArea; // Holds change in area for cell
    (m^2)

    if (i == 0)
    {
        //if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
        //{
        //    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        //    VolumeOut[i] =
        ActualVolumeAcross[TotalBeachCells - 1];
        //}
        //else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'C')
        //{
        //    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        //    VolumeOut[i] = -
        ActualVolumeAcross[TotalBeachCells - 1];
        //}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
        //{
        //    VolumeIn[i] = -
ActualVolumeAcross[TotalBeachCells - 1];
        //    VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        //}
        //else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
        //{
        //    VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[TotalBeachCells
- 1];
        //    VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        //}
        //else
        //{
        //}
    }
    else
    {
        if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'L')
        {
            VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
            VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        }
        else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'C')
        {
            VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
            VolumeOut[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
        }
        else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'D')
        {
            VolumeIn[i] = -ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
            VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        }
        else if (FlowThroughCell[i] == 'R')
        {
            VolumeIn[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i - 1];
            VolumeOut[i] = ActualVolumeAcross[i];
        }
        else
        {
            if (counter == 0)
            {
                FlowZeroCount = 0;
            }
            else if (counter == 1)
            {
                FlowZeroCount++;
            }
        }
    }
}

DeltaArea = ((VolumeIn[i] - VolumeOut[i]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth));

VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] += DeltaArea;

// Save results data
if (counter % Resuldata_freq == 0 && i == pbEnd - 2)
{
    string filelocation_results;
    if (autorestart == 1)

```

```

        {
            Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Results");
            filelocation_results = "OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Results/";
        }
        else
        {
            Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Results");
            filelocation_results = "OUTPUT_FILES/Results/";
        }

        if (counter == 0)
        {
            StreamWriter Delta_Area = new
StreamWriter(filelocation_results + "DeltaArea.out");
            Delta_Area.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " +
DeltaArea + " Counter i DeltaArea");
            Delta_Area.Close();
        }
        else
        {
            StreamWriter Delta_Area =
File.AppendText(filelocation_results + "DeltaArea.out");
            Delta_Area.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " +
DeltaArea);
            Delta_Area.Close();
        }
    }

    //// DEBUGGING START
    //if (counter == 365 && ((i == 88) || (i == 89) || (i ==
90) || (i == 91) || (i == 92) || (i == 93) || (i == 94) || (i == 95)
|| (i == 96) || (i == 97) || (i == 98) || (i == 99) || (i == 100)))
    //{
        //    StreamWriter DEBUG_FILE_DELTA =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/DEBUG_FILE_DELTA_" + i + ".out");
        //    DEBUG_FILE_DELTA.Write(counter + " " + i + " " +
X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " + DeltaArea + " " + VolumeIn[i] + " " +
VolumeOut[i] + " " + VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + " " +
ActualVolumeAcross[i] + Environment.NewLine);
        //    DEBUG_FILE_DELTA.Close();
    //}
    //// DEBUGGING END

    ////if (DeltaArea > 0)
    ////{
    ////    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] += DeltaArea;
    ////}
    ////else
    ////{
    ////    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] += DeltaArea;
    ////}

    ////int a = 0;

    ////double TotalDelta = Math.Abs(DeltaArea);
    ////double DeltaChange = TotalDelta / 10;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        ////if (DeltaArea < 0)
        ////{
        ////    while (TotalDelta > 0)
        ////    {
        ////        if (DeltaChange < TotalDelta)
        ////        {
        ////            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + a] -=
TotalDelta;
        ////            a++;
        ////
        ////            TotalDelta = 0;
        ////            DeltaChange = 0;
        ////        }
        ////        else
        ////        {
        ////            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + a] -=
DeltaChange;
        ////            a++;
        ////        }
        ////
        ////        TotalDelta -= DeltaChange;
        ////    }
        ////}
        ////else if (DeltaArea > 0)
        ////{
        ////    while (TotalDelta > 0)
        ////    {
        ////        if (DeltaChange < TotalDelta)
        ////        {
        ////            a++;
        ////            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + a] +=
TotalDelta;
        ////
        ////            TotalDelta = 0;
        ////            DeltaChange = 0;
        ////        }
        ////        else
        ////        {
        ////            a++;
        ////            VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + a] += DeltaArea;
        ////        }
        ////
        ////        TotalDelta -= DeltaChange;
        ////    }
        ////}

        ////_____//

        ////StreamWriter delta =
File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/delta.out");
        ////delta.Write(counter + " " + DeltaArea +
Environment.NewLine);
        ////delta.Close();

        ////
        //// PRINT FILES
        ////

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        ////if (counter >= 10220)
        ////{
        //    //if (X[i] == 800 && hit == 0)
        //    //{
        //        //StreamWriter SandOut_File_s =
        File.AppendText("OUTPUT_FILES/SandOut_start.out");
        //        //SandOut_File_s.Write(counter + " " +
        DirectionAcrossBorder[i] + " " + X[i] + " " + Y[i] + " " +
        (VolumeIn[i] / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + (VolumeOut[i] /
        (CellWidth * CellWidth)) + " " + DeltaArea + " " +
        VolumeAcrossBorder[i] + " " + ActualVolumeAcross[i] +
        Environment.NewLine);
        //        //SandOut_File_s.Close();

        //        //hit = 1;
        //    //}
        ////}

        //////////
        ////////// Sinks
        //////////

        ////if (HaveSinks == 1)
        ////{
        ////    for (int Sx = 0; Sx < SinkX.Length; Sx++)
        ////    {
        ////        if (X[i] == SinkX[Sx])
        ////        {
        ////            DeltaArea = 0;
        ////        }
        ////    }
        ////}

        //int CellCount = 0;
        //double firstDeltaArea;
        //double A2;
// End Amount
        //double P2;
// Start Amount
        //double t2;
        //double A3;
// End Amount
        //double P3;
// Start Amount
        //double t3;
// time
        //double decayRate1;

        //double averageChange = 100;
        //int shortShoreface = 5;
        //int sidewaysLimit = 5;

        //////////
        ////////// If there is material to move...
        //////////

        //double firstpercent = 0.01;
        //double UPpercent = 0.01;
        //double LRPercent = UPpercent/2;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //if (DeltaArea != 0)
        //{
        //    ///
        //    /// Delta Area > 0
        //    ///
        //    if (DeltaArea > 0)
        //    {
        //        firstDeltaArea = ((DeltaArea * firstpercent));
// Give X% to the first cell

        //        if (numCells[i] <= 1)
        //        {
        //            numCells[i] = 2;
        //        }

        //        int jj = 0;

        //        if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 1)
        //        {
        //            if (direction[i] == 1)
        //            {
        //                if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + 1] == 0)
        //                {
        //                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        //                }
        //            }
        //            //else if (direction[i] == 2)
        //            //{
        //                if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
        //                {
        //                    VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] + 1]
+= firstDeltaArea;
        //                }
        //            }
        //            else if (direction[i] == 3)
        //            {
        //                if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 0)
        //                {
        //                    VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
        //                }
        //            }
        //            //else if (direction[i] == 4)
        //            //{
        //                if (VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
        //                {
        //                    VolumeChange[X[i] + 1, Y[i] - 1]
+= firstDeltaArea;
        //                }
        //            }
        //            else if (direction[i] == 5)
        //            {
        //                if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - 1] == 0)
        //                {
        //                    VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - 1] +=
firstDeltaArea;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          }
//          }
//          //else if (direction[i] == 6)
//          //{
//          //      if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1] == 0)
//          //          {
//          //              VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] - 1]
+= firstDeltaArea;
//          //          }
//          //      }
//          //      else if (direction[i] == 7)
//          //      {
//          //          if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 0)
//          //              {
//          //                  VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
//          //              }
//          //          }
//          //      }
//          //      else if (direction[i] == 8)
//          //      {
//          //          if (VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange && AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1] == 0)
//          //              {
//          //                  VolumeChange[X[i] - 1, Y[i] + 1]
+= firstDeltaArea;
//          //              }
//          //          }
//          //      }
//          //      numCells[i]--;
//          //      jj = 2;
//          //      }
//          //      else
//          //      {
//          //          if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] < averageChange
&& AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] == 0)
//          //              {
//          //                  VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] +=
firstDeltaArea;
//          //              }
//          //          }
//          //          //numCells[i]--;
//          //          jj = 1;
//          //      }

//          int xHolder;
//          int s = jj;

//          double extraDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
//          // How much material do we have?
//          double totalDeltaArea = DeltaArea -
firstDeltaArea;
//          // Keep tracks of little bits that are left.
//          double A = DeltaArea - firstDeltaArea;
//          // End Amount
//          double P = 1;
//          // Start Amount
//          double t;

//          //if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
//          //{
//          //      t = MaxDist - jj;
//          //}

// time

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //}
//      //else
//      //{
//      t = numCells[i] - jj;
//      //}

//      double decayRate = firstDeltaArea * UPpercent;
// r, decay rate
//      double previousDA = firstDeltaArea;

//      //if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
//      //{
//      //      for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
//      //      {
//      //      lost += totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + j] ==
0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j] < averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + j]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //}

//      if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
//      {
//      xHolder = X[i];

//      for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      {

//      extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

//      if (Y[i] + j >= ymax)
//      {
//      lost += totalDeltaArea;
//      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          else if (AboveWater[xHolder, Y[i] + j]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] + j] < averageChange)
//          {
//          //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//          if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//          {
//          VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] + j]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//          totalDeltaArea = 0;
//          extraDeltaArea = 0;
//          }
//          else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//          {
//          VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] + j]
+= decayRate;
//          extraDeltaArea = 0;
//          totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//          previousDA = decayRate;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//          VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] + j]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//          totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//          previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//          s++;
//          //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//          //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//          }

//          // Turn direction right/left
//          if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//          {
//          // Go right
//          if (WaveAngleIn > -90 && WaveAngleIn <
90)
//          {
//          int k = 1;

//          for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//          {

//          extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

//          if (xHolder + k > pbEnd - 1)
//          {
//          xHolder = 0;
//          k = 0;
//          }
//          else if (AboveWater[xHolder + k,
Y[i] + 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + k, Y[i] + 1] < averageChange)
//          {
//          if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
+= decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     s++;
//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     // Turn direction to up
//                                     // Share rest with north going cells, along
all X-numcells
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//                                     {
//                                     int k = 1;

//                                     for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//                                     if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//                                     {
//                                     lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }

//                                     ///
//                                     else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k]
== 0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0
&& totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     k++;

//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
//                                     {
//                                     xHolder = X[i];

//                                     for (int j = jj; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {

//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;

//                                     if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
//                                     {
//                                     lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[xHolder, Y[i] - j]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] - j] < averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] - j]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] - j]
+= decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] - j]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     s++;
//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     // Turn direction right/left
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//                                     {
//                                     if (WaveAngleIn > -90 && WaveAngleIn <
90) // Go right
//                                     {
//                                     int k = 1;

//                                     for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     ////extraDeltaArea = previousDA
- decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

//                                     if (xHolder + k > pbEnd - 1)
//                                     {
//                                     xHolder = 0;
//                                     k = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[xHolder + k,
Y[i] - 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + k, Y[i] - 1] < averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] += totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <=
0 && totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] += decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA =
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     k++;

//                                     //totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }

//     else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
//     {
//         xHolder = X[i];

//         for (int j = jj; ((j < numCells[i]) && (j <
sidewaysLimit)) && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//         {
//             ////extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;
//             extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

//             if (xHolder - s < 0)
//             {
//                 xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
//                 s = 0;
//             }
//             else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
//             {
//                 //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                 if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                 {
//                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                 }
//                 else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                 {
//                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
+= decayRate;
//                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                 }
//                 else
//                 {
//                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
+= extraDeltaArea;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     s++;
//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//                                     {
//                                     // Turn direction to up

//                                     int k = 1;

//                                     for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     //
//                                     //                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//                                     //                                     if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//                                     //                                     {
//                                     //                                     lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                                     //                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     //                                     }
//                                     //                                     else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k]
== 0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] < averageChange)
//                                     //                                     {
//                                     //                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     //                                     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     //                                     {
//                                     //                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     //                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     //                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     //                                     }
//                                     //                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     //                                     {
//                                     //                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= decayRate;
//                                     //                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     //                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     //                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     //                                     }
//                                     //                                     else
//                                     //                                     {
//                                     //                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //                                     }
//                                     //                                     }
//                                     //                                     k++;
//                                     //                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }

// //
// // Delta Area < 0
// //
// // else if (DeltaArea < 0)
// // {
// //     averageChange = averageChange * -1;

// //     firstDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea *
firstpercent);

//     if (numCells[i] <= 1)
//     {
//         numCells[i] = 2;
//     }

//     if (VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] > averageChange)
//     {
//         VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i]] -= firstDeltaArea;
//     }
//     numCells[i]--;

//     int xHolder;
//     int s = 0;

//     double extraDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea +
firstDeltaArea);
//     // How much material do we have?
//     double totalDeltaArea = Math.Abs(DeltaArea +
firstDeltaArea);
//     // Keep tracks of little bits that are
left.
//     double A = Math.Abs(DeltaArea + firstDeltaArea);
// End Amount
//     double P = 1;
// Start Amount
//     double t;

//     //if (numCells[i] < shortShoreface)
//     //{
//     //    t = MaxDist - 1;
// time
//     //}
//     //else
//     //{
//     //    t = numCells[i] - 1;
// time
//     //}

//     double decayRate = 0.01;
//Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea); // Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea * UPpercent);
// r, decay rate
//     double previousDA = Math.Abs(firstDeltaArea);

//     if (direction[i] == 1) // Up
//     {
//         xHolder = X[i];

```



```

// if (xHolder - k < 0)
// {
//     xHolder = 0;
//     k = pbEnd - 1;
// }
// else if (AboveWater[xHolder - k,
Y[i] - 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - k, Y[i] - 1] < averageChange)
// {
//     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//     {
//         VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//         totalDeltaArea = 0;
//         extraDeltaArea = 0;
//     }
//     else if ((extraDeltaArea <=
0 && totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//     {
//         VolumeChange[xHolder - k, Y[i]
- 1] -= decayRate;
//         extraDeltaArea = 0;
//         totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//         previousDA = decayRate;
//     }
//     else
//     {
//         VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//         totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//         previousDA =
//     }
// }
// k++;
//totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
// }
// }
// }
// else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
// {
//     xHolder = X[i];
//     for (int j = 1; ((j < numCells[i]) && (j <
sidewaysLimit)) && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//     {
//         ////extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;
//         extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
//          {
//              xHolder = 0;
//              s = 0;
//          }
//          else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
//          {
//              //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//              if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//              {
//                  VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
-= totalDeltaArea;
//                  totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                  extraDeltaArea = 0;
//              }
//              else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//              {
//                  VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] -=
decayRate;
//                  extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                  totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                  previousDA = decayRate;
//              }
//              else
//              {
//                  VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
-= extraDeltaArea;
//                  totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                  previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//              }
//              s++;
//              //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//              //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//      }

//          if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//          {
//              // Turn direction to up
//              int k = 1;
//              for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//              {
//                  extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;
//              }
//              if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//              {
//                  lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                  totalDeltaArea = 0;
//              }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k]
== 0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
//          {
//          //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//          if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//          {
//          VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
-= totalDeltaArea;
//          totalDeltaArea = 0;
//          extraDeltaArea = 0;
//          }
//          else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//          {
//          VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -=
decayRate;
//          extraDeltaArea = 0;
//          totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//          previousDA = decayRate;
//          }
//          else
//          {
//          VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
-= extraDeltaArea;
//          totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//          previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//          }
//          k++;
//          //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//          //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          }
//          }
//          else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
//          {
//          xHolder = X[i];
//          for (int j = 1; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//          {
//          extraDeltaArea = previousDA - decayRate;
//          if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
//          {
//          lost += totalDeltaArea;
//          totalDeltaArea = 0;
//          }
//          else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - j] == 0
&& VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] > averageChange)
//          {
//          //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//          if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//          {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j] -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     s++;
//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     // Turn direction right/left
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//                                     {
//                                     if (WaveAngleIn > -90 && WaveAngleIn <
90) // Go right
//                                     {
//                                     int k = 1;

//                                     for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     ////extraDeltaArea = previousDA
- decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

//                                     if (xHolder + k > pbEnd - 1)
//                                     {
//                                     xHolder = 0;
//                                     k = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[xHolder + k,
Y[i] - 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + k, Y[i] - 1] < averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;

```



```

//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder - k, Y[i]
- 1] -= decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA =
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     k++;
//                                     //totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
//                                     {
//                                     xHolder = X[i];

//                                     for (int j = 1; ((j < numCells[i]) && (j <
sidewaysLimit)) && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     ////extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
(decayRate/2);

//                                     if (xHolder - s < 0)
//                                     {
//                                     xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
//                                     s = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] > averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea < extraDeltaArea
|| totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
-= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {

```

```

//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] -=
decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;
//                                     }
//                                     else
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
-= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//                                     previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }
//                                     s++;
//                                     }

//                                     //totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//                                     //previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//                                     }

//                                     if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//                                     {
//                                     // Turn direction to up
//                                     int k = 1;
//                                     for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//                                     {
//                                     //
//                                     extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//                                     if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)
//                                     {
//                                     lost += totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if (AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + k]
== 0 && VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] > averageChange)
//                                     {
//                                     //if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || extraDeltaArea < 0)
//                                     if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea || totalDeltaArea < decayRate)
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k]
-= totalDeltaArea;
//                                     totalDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     }
//                                     else if ((extraDeltaArea <= 0 &&
totalDeltaArea > 0) || (extraDeltaArea < decayRate))
//                                     {
//                                     VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] + k] -=
decayRate;
//                                     extraDeltaArea = 0;
//                                     totalDeltaArea -= decayRate;
//                                     previousDA = decayRate;

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //      for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      if (xHolder + k > pbEnd - 1)
//      //      {
//      //      xHolder = 0;
//      //      k = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder +
k, Y[i] + 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + k, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] + 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] + 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      k++;

//      //      totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      else // go left
//      //      {
//      //      int k = 1;

//      //      for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      //      if (xHolder - k < 0)
//      //      //      {
//      //      //      xHolder = 0;
//      //      //      k = pbEnd - 1;
//      //      //      }
//      //      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder -
k, Y[i] + 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - k, Y[i] + 1] <
averageChange)
//      //      //      {
//      //      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      //      {
//      //      //      VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] + 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] + 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      k++;

//      //      totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      //}

//      //else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
//      //{
//      //      xHolder = X[i];

//      //      for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
//      //      {
//      //      xHolder = 0;
//      //      s = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder + s,
Y[i]] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder + s,
Y[i]] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      s++;
//      //      }
//      //      totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }

//      //      // Turn direction to up
//      //      // Share rest with north going cells,
along all X-numcells
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//      //      {
//      //      int k = 1;

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //      //      VolumeChange[X[i], Y[i] - j]
+= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      //      }
//      //      //      }
//      //      //      totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      //      }
//      //      //      }
//      //      //      }

//      //else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
//      //{
//      //      xHolder = X[i];

//      //      for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      if (Y[i] - j >= ymax)
//      //      {
//      //      lost += totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder, Y[i] - j]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] - j] < averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] -
j] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder, Y[i] -
j] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      s++;
//      //      }
//      //      totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }

//      //      // Turn direction right/left
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//      //      {
//      //      if (WaveAngleIn > -90 && WaveAngleIn <
90) // Go right
//      //      {
//      //      int k = 1;

//      //      for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//      //      if (xHolder + k > pbEnd - 1)
//      //      {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      //      xHolder = 0;
//      //      k = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder + k, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder +
k, Y[i] - 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      k++;
//      //      totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//      //      previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      else // go left
//      //      {
//      //      int k = 1;
//      //      for (int j = numCells[i]; j <
MaxDist && totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//      //      {
//      //      extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;
//      //      if (xHolder - k < 0)
//      //      {
//      //      xHolder = 0;
//      //      k = pbEnd - 1;
//      //      }
//      //      else if (AboveWater[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] == 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - k, Y[i] - 1] <
averageChange)
//      //      {
//      //      if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] -= totalDeltaArea;
//      //      totalDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      extraDeltaArea = 0;
//      //      }
//      //      else
//      //      {
//      //      VolumeChange[xHolder -
k, Y[i] - 1] -= extraDeltaArea;
//      //      }
//      //      }
//      //      k++;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          //          totalDeltaArea -=
extraDeltaArea;
//          //          previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          //          }
//          //          }
//          //          }
//          //          }

//          //else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
//          //{
//          //    xHolder = X[i];

//          //    for (int j = 0; j < numCells[i] &&
totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//          //    {
//          //        extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//          //        if (xHolder - s < 0)
//          //        {
//          //            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
//          //            s = 0;
//          //        }
//          //        else if (AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
== 0 && VolumeChange[xHolder - s, Y[i]] < averageChange)
//          //        {
//          //            if (totalDeltaArea <
extraDeltaArea)
//          //            {
//          //                VolumeChange[xHolder - s,
Y[i]] -= totalDeltaArea;
//          //                totalDeltaArea = 0;
//          //                extraDeltaArea = 0;
//          //            }
//          //            else
//          //            {
//          //                VolumeChange[xHolder - s,
Y[i]] -= extraDeltaArea;
//          //            }
//          //            s++;
//          //        }

//          //        totalDeltaArea -= extraDeltaArea;
//          //        previousDA = extraDeltaArea;
//          //    }

//          //    if (totalDeltaArea > 0)
//          //    {
//          //        // Turn direction to up

//          //        int k = 1;

//          //        for (int j = numCells[i]; j < MaxDist
&& totalDeltaArea > 0; j++)
//          //        {
//          //            extraDeltaArea = previousDA -
decayRate;

//          //            if (Y[i] + k >= ymax)

```


Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //double PercentEroded = 0.0;

        //if (InShadow[i] == 'n')
        //{
            //    //PercentEroded = ((ErosionRatePerYear *
TimeStepValue) / 365) / CellWidth;
            //    PercentEroded = ((ErosionRatePerYear * CellWidth *
TElevationCS[X[i], Y[i]] * TimeStepValue) / 365);
        //}
        //else if (InShadow[i] == 'y')
        //{
            //    PercentEroded = 0.0;
        //}

        //// Not enough sand...
        ////if (PercentEroded > PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]])
        //if (PercentEroded > Volume[X[i], Y[i]])
        //{
            //    // ...and no rock
            //    if (PercentFullRock[X[i], Y[i]] == 0.0)
            //    {
                //        // ...but there is sand behind that can be
stolen
                //        //if (PercentEroded < (PercentFullSand[X[i],
Y[i]] + PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]))
                //        if (PercentEroded < (Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]))
                //        {
                    //            //PercentFullSand[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] -=
PercentEroded - PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]];
                    //            //PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
                    //            Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] -=
PercentEroded - Volume[X[i], Y[i]];
                    //            Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
                //        }

                //        //else if (PercentEroded >
(PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] + PercentFullSand[XBehind[i],
YBehind[i]]))
                //        else if (PercentEroded > (Volume[X[i], Y[i]] +
Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]]))
                //        {
                    //            Volume[XBehind[i], YBehind[i]] = 0.0;
                    //            Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
                //        }
                //    }
            //    else
            //    {

                //        Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
            //    }
        //}

        ////normal case, enough sand
        //else
        //{
            //    Volume[X[i], Y[i]] -= PercentEroded;
        //}
    }

void FixBeach()

```

```

    {
        // Hopefully addresses strange problems caused by
        // filling/emptying of cells
        // Looks at entire data set
        // Find unattached pieces of sand and moves them back
        // to the shore
        // Takes care of 'floating bits' of sand
        // Also takes care of over/under filled beach pieces
        // Revised 5/21/02 to move sand to all adjacent
        // neighbors sandrevt.c
        // Changes global variable PercentFullSand[][]
        // Uses and can change AllBeach[][]
        // sandrevx.c - added sweep sign to reduce chances of
        // asymmetrical artifacts
        // LMV rock fix - do not fix bare bedrock cells

        //int i, x, y, sweep sign, done, counter;
        //int fillcells3 = 0;
        //int Corner = 0;
        //int ystart;

        //if (RandZeroToOne() * 2 > 1)
        //{
            // sweep sign = 1;
        //}
        //else
        //{
            // sweep sign = 0;
        //}

        //for (y = 1; y < ShadowYMax - 1; y++)
        //{
            // for (i = 1; i < pbEnd - 1; i++)
            // {
                // if (sweep sign == 1)
                // {
                    // x = i;
                // }
                // else
                // {
                    // x = (pbEnd - 1) - i;
                // }

                // Corner = 0;

                // Take care of 'loose' bits of sand

                // if (Corner == 0)
                // {
                    // fillcells3 = 0;

                    // Beach in cell, but bottom, top,
                    // right, and left neighbors have some in
                    // if ((Elevation[x, y] != 0.0) &&
                    // (Elevation[x, y + 1] > 0) &&
                    // (Elevation[x + 1, y] > 0) &&
                    // (Elevation[x, y - 1] > 0) &&
                    // (Elevation[x - 1, y] > 0) &&
                    // (AboveWater[x, y] == 0))
                    // {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// distribute to partially full
neighbors //
MaxFillCell) && // if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] <
// ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0))
// //if (((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) < WaterHeight) &&
// //((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0))
// {
// fillcells3 += 1;
// }

// if (((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < MaxFillCell) &&
// ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0))
// //if (((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < WaterHeight) &&
// //((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0))
// {
// fillcells3 += 1;
// }
// if (((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < MaxFillCell) &&
// ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0))
// //if (((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < WaterHeight) &&
// //((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0))
// {
// fillcells3 += 1;
// }
// if (((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < MaxFillCell) &&
// ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0))
// //if (((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < WaterHeight) &&
// //((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0))
// {
// fillcells3 += 1;
// }

// if ((fillcells3 > 0) && (fillcells3
<= 4))
// {
// if (((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1]
+ PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) < MaxFillCell) &&
// ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1]
+ PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0))
// //if (((PercentFullSand[x, y -
1] + PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) < WaterHeight) &&
// //((PercentFullSand[x, y -
1] + PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > 0.0))
// {
// PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / fillcells3;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          }
//          if (((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1]
+ PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < MaxFillCell) &&
//          ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1]
+ PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0))
//          //if (((PercentFullSand[x, y +
1] + PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) < WaterHeight) &&
//          //          ((PercentFullSand[x, y +
1] + PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > 0.0))
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / fillcells3;
//          }
//          if (((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y]
+ PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < MaxFillCell) &&
//          ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y]
+ PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0))
//          //if (((PercentFullSand[x + 1,
y] + PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) < WaterHeight) &&
//          //          ((PercentFullSand[x + 1,
y] + PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > 0.0))
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / fillcells3;
//          }
//          if (((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y]
+ PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < MaxFillCell) &&
//          ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y]
+ PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0))
//          //if (((PercentFullSand[x - 1,
y] + PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) < WaterHeight) &&
//          //          ((PercentFullSand[x - 1,
y] + PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > 0.0))
//          {
//          PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y] / fillcells3;
//          }
//          }
//          else
//          {
//          ystart = ymax - 1;
//          while (AllBeach[x, ystart] == 0)
//          {
//          ystart -= 1;
//          }
//          ystart += 1;
//          PercentFullSand[x, ystart] +=
PercentFullSand[x, y];
//          PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//          AllBeach[x, y] = 0;
//          ystart = ymax - 1;
//          while (AllRock[x, ystart] ==
'n')
//          {
//          ystart -= 1;
//          }
//          ystart += 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//                                     PercentFullRock[x, ystart] +=
PercentFullRock[x, y];
//                                     PercentFullRock[x, y] = 0.0;
//                                     AllRock[x, y] = 'n';

//                                     if (PercentFullRock[x, ystart]
>= MaxFillCell)
//                                     //if (PercentFullRock[x, ystart]
> WaterHeight)
//                                     {
//                                     AllRock[x, ystart] = 'y';
//                                     PercentFullRock[x, ystart +
1] += (PercentFullRock[x, ystart] - 1);
//                                     PercentFullRock[x, ystart] =
MaxFillCell;
//                                     }
//                                     }

//                                     PercentFullSand[x, y] = 0.0;
//                                     AllBeach[x, y] = 0;

//                                     // If we have overfilled any of the
cells in this loop, need to OopsImFull()
//                                     if ((PercentFullSand[x, y - 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y - 1]) > MaxFillCell)
//                                     {
//                                     OopsImFull(x, y - 1);
//                                     }
//                                     if ((PercentFullSand[x - 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x - 1, y]) > MaxFillCell)
//                                     {
//                                     OopsImFull(x - 1, y);
//                                     }
//                                     if ((PercentFullSand[x + 1, y] +
PercentFullRock[x + 1, y]) > MaxFillCell)
//                                     {
//                                     OopsImFull(x + 1, y);
//                                     }
//                                     if ((PercentFullSand[x, y + 1] +
PercentFullRock[x, y + 1]) > MaxFillCell)
//                                     {
//                                     OopsImFull(x, y + 1);
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }
//                                     }

// // now make sure there aren't any overfull or
underfull cells

// done = FALSE;

// for (counter = 0; counter < 10 && done == 0;
counter++)
// {
//     done = TRUE;

//     for (y = 1; y < ymax - 1; y++)
//     {
//         for (x = 1; x < pbEnd - 1; x++)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //          {
        //          if ((PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y] > MaxFillCell)
        //          || (PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y] < 0.0)
        //          || PercentFullSand[x, y] < 0.0)
        //          {
        //          done = FALSE;
        //          }
        //          if (PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y] > MaxFillCell)
        //          {
        //          OopsImFull(x, y);
        //          }
        //          if (PercentFullSand[x, y] +
PercentFullRock[x, y] < -0.000001)
        //          {
        //          OopsImEmpty(x, y);
        //          }
        //          if (PercentFullSand[x, y] < -0.000001)
        //          {
        //          OopsImEmpty(x, y);
        //          }
        //          }
        //          }
        //          }
        //          }
    }

    //CM - New Slope
    void FindAverageShoreface()
    {
        // Use the ShorelineAngle[] to find which angle the
shoreline is facing
        // Calculate the local shoreface slope
        // Calculate which cells will gain/lose material (where
the shoreface slope is drawn)

        int i;

        int MinDist = 1;
        //int MaxDist = 20;

        int[] xSFCell = new int[MaxBeachLength];           //
x position of the end of the shoreface slope
        int[] ySFCell = new int[MaxBeachLength];           //
y position of the end of the shoreface slope

        int[] count = new int[MaxBeachLength];
        int j;
        int k;
        double TotalX;
        double TotalY;
        double XY;
        double Xsq;
        double Ysq;

        Array.Clear(direction, 0, direction.Length);
        Array.Clear(numCells, 0, numCells.Length);

        // Direction we are looking in

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
        {
            //if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 0.3926991) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -0.3926991))
            //{
                direction[i] = 1;           // Top
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -0.3926991) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -1.178097))
            //{
                direction[i] = 2;           // Top Right
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -1.178097) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -1.9634954))
            //{
                direction[i] = 3;           // Right
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -1.9634954) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -2.7488936))
            //{
                direction[i] = 4;           // Bottom Right
            //}
            //else if (((ShorelineAngle[i] < -2.7488936) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -3.15905)) || ((ShorelineAngle[i] <= 3.15905) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 2.7488936)))
            //{
                direction[i] = 5;           // Bottom
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 2.7488936) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 1.9634954))
            //{
                direction[i] = 6;           // Bottom Left
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 1.9634954) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 1.178097))
            //{
                direction[i] = 7;           // Left
            //}
            //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 1.178097) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 0.3926991))
            //{
                direction[i] = 8;           // Top Left
            //}

            //if (ShorelineAngle[i] < 0)
            //{
                Angle_1[i] = Angle_1[i] * -1;
            //}

            if ((ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ <= 0.785398)
&& (ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ > -0.785398)) //
0.785...radians = 45o
            {
                direction[i] = 1;           // Up
            }
            else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ <= -
0.785398) && (ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ > -
2.35619449060255))
            {
                direction[i] = 3;           // Right
            }
        }
    
```

```

    }
    else if (((ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ <=
3.141592654) && (ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ >
2.35619449060255)) || ((ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ <= -
2.35619449060255) && (ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ >= -
3.141592654))) // 3.141...radians = 180o
    {
        // CM 07.12.17 - if it's the cell on the end of
the spit, it's direction should go right (longshore drift)
        if (X[i] > X[i + 1] && X[i] > X[i - 1])
        {
            direction[i] = 3;
        }
        else
        {
            direction[i] = 5;          // Down
        }
    }
    else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ <=
2.35619449060255) && ShorelineAngle[i] /*+ Angle_1[i]*/ > 0.785398)
// 2.35... radians = 135o
    {
        direction[i] = 7;          // Left
    }
    else
    {
        direction[i] = 1;          // Up
    }

//else if (ShorelineAngle[i] + Angle_1[i] ==
0.785398163397448)
//{
//    Random rand = new Random();
//    int RandNo = rand.Next(0, 2);

//    if (RandNo == 0)
//    {
//        RandNo = 5;
//    }
//    else if (RandNo == 1)
//    {
//        RandNo = 7;
//    }

//    direction[i] = RandNo;
//}
//else if (ShorelineAngle[i] + Angle_1[i] == -
0.785398163397448)
//{
//    Random rand = new Random();
//    int RandNo = rand.Next(0, 2);

//    if (RandNo == 0)
//    {
//        RandNo = 1;
//    }
//    else if (RandNo == 1)
//    {
//        RandNo = 7;
//    }

```

```

        // direction[i] = RandNo;
        //}
        //else if (ShorelineAngle[i] + Angle_1[i] ==
2.35619449060255)
        //{
        // Random rand = new Random();
        // int RandNo = rand.Next(0, 2);

        // if (RandNo == 0)
        // {
        //     RandNo = 3;
        // }
        // else if (RandNo == 1)
        // {
        //     RandNo = 5;
        // }

        // direction[i] = RandNo;
        //}
        //else if (ShorelineAngle[i] + Angle_1[i] == -
2.35619449060255)
        //{
        // Random rand = new Random();
        // int RandNo = rand.Next(0, 2);

        // if (RandNo == 0)
        // {
        //     RandNo = 1;
        // }
        // else if (RandNo == 1)
        // {
        //     RandNo = 3;
        // }

        // direction[i] = RandNo;
        //}

        //if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 0.3926991) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -0.3926991)) // +-22.5
        //{
        // direction[i] = 1; // Up
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -0.3926991) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -1.178097)) // -22.5^o - -67.5^o
        //{
        // direction[i] = 1; // Top Right
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -1.178097) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -1.9634954)) // -67.5^o - -112.5^o
        //{
        // direction[i] = 3; // Right
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -1.9634954) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -2.7488936)) // -112.5^o - -157.5^o
        //{
        // direction[i] = 3; // Bottom Right
        //}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        //else if (((ShorelineAngle[i] < -2.7488936) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= -3.14159)) || ((ShorelineAngle[i] <= 3.14159) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 2.7488936))) // (=-)157.5^o - 180^o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 5;          // Bottom
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 2.7488936) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 1.9634954)) // 157.5^o - 112.5^o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 7;          // Bottom Left
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 1.9634954) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 1.178097)) // 112.5^o - 67.5^o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 7;          // Left
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 1.178097) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] >= 0.3926991)) // 67.5^o - 22.5^o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 1;          // Top Left
        //}

        //if ((ShorelineAngle[i] > -0.785398) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] < 0.785398) || (ShorelineAngle[i] == -0.785398) ||
(ShorelineAngle[i] == -2.35619)) // 0.785...radians = 45o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 1;          // Up
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < -0.785398) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] > -2.35619) || (ShorelineAngle[i] == 2.35619))
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 3;          // Right
        //}
        //else if (((ShorelineAngle[i] < -2.35619) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] > -3.14159)) || ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 3.14159) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] > 2.35619))) // 3.141...radians = 180o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 5;          // Down
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] < 2.35619) &&
(ShorelineAngle[i] > 0.785398) || (ShorelineAngle[i] == 0.785398)) //
2.35... radians = 135o
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 7;          // Left
        //}
        //else if ((ShorelineAngle[i] == 0.785398) ||
(ShorelineAngle[i] == -0.785398) || (ShorelineAngle[i] == 2.35619) ||
(ShorelineAngle[i] == -2.35619))
        //{
        //    Random rand = new Random();
        //    int RandNo = rand.Next(1, 5);

        //    ShorelineAngle[i] = RandNo;
        //}

        //count[i] = 0;
        //TotalX = 0;
        //TotalY = 0;
        //XY = 0;
        //Xsq = 0;
        //Ysq = 0;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]);
//Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth), 2);
//Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]]), 2);
//TotalY += TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]];
//TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//count[i]++;

// // Average Shoreface Slope
// if (direction[i] == 1)
// {
//     k = Y[i] + 1;

//     while (k < ymax && AboveWater[X[i], k] == 0)
//     {
//         XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[X[i], k]);
//         Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//         Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[X[i],
k]), 2);
//         TotalY += TElevationDomain[X[i], k];
//         TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//         k++;
//         count[i]++;
//     }
// }

// else if (direction[i] == 2)
// {
//     j = X[i] + 1;
//     k = Y[i] + 1;

//     while (j < pbEnd && j >= 0 && k >= 0 && k <
ymax && AboveWater[j, k] == 0)
//     {
//         XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, k]);
//         Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//         Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
k]), 2);
//         TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, k];
//         TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//         j++;
//         k++;
//         count[i]++;
//     }
// }

// else if (direction[i] == 3)
// {
//     j = X[i] + 1;

//     while (j < pbEnd && AboveWater[j, Y[i]] ==
0)
//     {
//         XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, Y[i]]);
//         Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
Y[i]]), 2);
//          TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, Y[i]];
//          TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//          j++;
//          count[i]++;

//          if (j == pbEnd - 1)
//          {
//              j = 0;
//          }
//      }

//      else if (direction[i] == 4)
//      {
//          j = X[i] + 1;
//          k = Y[i] - 1;

//          while (j < pbEnd && j >= 0 && k >= 0 && k <
ymax && AboveWater[j, k] == 0)
//          {
//              XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, k]);
//              Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//              Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
k]), 2);
//              TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, k];
//              TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//              j++;
//              k--;
//              count[i]++;
//          }
//      }
//      else if (direction[i] == 5)
//      {
//          j = Y[i] - 1;

//          while (j >= 0 && AboveWater[X[i], j] == 0)
//          {
//              XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[X[i], j]);
//              Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//              Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[X[i],
j]), 2);
//              TotalY += TElevationDomain[X[i], j];
//              TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//              j--;
//              count[i]++;
//          }
//      }
//      else if (direction[i] == 6)
//      {
//          j = X[i] - 1;
//          k = Y[i] - 1;

//          while (j < pbEnd && j >= 0 && k >= 0 && k <
ymax && AboveWater[j, k] == 0)
//          {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, k]);
//          Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//          Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
k]), 2);
//          TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, k];
//          TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//          j--;
//          k--;
//          count[i]++;
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 7)
//  {
//      j = X[i] - 1;
//
//      while (j >= 0 && AboveWater[j, Y[i]] == 0)
//      {
//          XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, Y[i]]);
//          Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//          Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
Y[i]]), 2);
//          TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, Y[i]];
//          TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//          j--;
//          count[i]++;
//
//          if (j == 0)
//          {
//              j = pbEnd - 1;
//          }
//      }
//  }
//  else if (direction[i] == 8)
//  {
//      j = X[i] - 1;
//      k = Y[i] + 1;
//
//      while (j < pbEnd && j >= 0 && k >= 0 && k <
ymax && AboveWater[j, k] == 0)
//      {
//          XY += ((count[i] + 1) * CellWidth) *
(TElevationDomain[j, k]);
//          Xsq += Math.Pow(((count[i] + 1) *
CellWidth), 2);
//          Ysq += Math.Pow((TElevationDomain[j,
k]), 2);
//          TotalY += TElevationDomain[j, k];
//          TotalX += (count[i] + 1) * CellWidth;
//          j--;
//          k++;
//          count[i]++;
//      }
//  }
//
//  localSFS[i] = Math.Abs((count[i] * (XY) -
(TotalX) * (TotalY)) / (count[i] * (Xsq) - (Math.Pow(TotalX, 2))));
//
//  count[i] = 0;

```

```

//      if (direction[i] == 1) // Top
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;

//          while ((Y[i] + s < ymax - 1) &&
(AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }

//          count[i] = n;

//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 2) // Top Right
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;

//          while ((X[i] + s < pbEnd - 1) && (Y[i] + s <
ymax - 1) && (AboveWater[X[i] + s, Y[i] + s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }

//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;

//          while ((X[i] + s < pbEnd - 1) &&
(AboveWater[X[i] + s, Y[i]] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }

//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 4) // Bottom Right
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;

//          while ((X[i] + s < pbEnd - 1) && (Y[i] - s >
1) && (AboveWater[X[i] + s, Y[i] - s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }

//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          while ((Y[i] - s > 1) && (AboveWater[X[i],
Y[i] - s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }
//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 6) // Bottom Left
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;
//
//          while ((X[i] - s > 1) && (Y[i] - s > 1) &&
(AboveWater[X[i] - s, Y[i] - s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }
//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;
//
//          while ((X[i] - s > 1) && (AboveWater[X[i] -
s, Y[i]] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }
//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      if (direction[i] == 8) // Top Left
//      {
//          int n = 1;
//          int s = 1;
//
//          while ((X[i] - s > 1) && (Y[i] + s < ymax -
1) && (AboveWater[X[i] - s, Y[i] + s] == 0))
//          {
//              n++;
//              s++;
//          }
//          count[i] = n;
//      }
//      }
//
//      int numstep = 1;
//      double extraAmount = 0.1;
//
//      //newdirection:
//
//      // How many cells out does the slope extend (only to a
dip in the coastline)
//      if (direction[i] == 1) // Top

```

```

    {
        int n = 1;
        int s = 1;

        while ((Y[i] + s < ymax - 1) &&
            (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + (s
            - numstep)] + extraAmount) && (numCells[i] < MaxDist) &&
            AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + s] == 0)
        {
            n++;
            s++;
        }

        numCells[i] = n;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 2) // Top Right
    {
        int n = 1;
        int s = 1;

        while ((X[i] + s < pbEnd - 1) && (Y[i] + s < ymax
            - 1) && (TElevationDomain[X[i] + s, Y[i] + s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i]
            + (s - numstep), Y[i] + (s - numstep)] + extraAmount) &&
            AboveWater[X[i] + s, Y[i] + s] == 0)
        {
            n++;
            s++;
        }

        numCells[i] = n;
    }
    else if (direction[i] == 3) // Right
    {
        //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 1)
        //{
        //    direction[i] = 1;
        //    goto newdirection;
        //}

        int n = 1;
        int s = 1;

        int xHolder = X[i];
        int breakflag = 0;

        //if (AboveWater[X[i] + 1, Y[i]] == 1)
        //{
        //    Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
        //}

        while (n < MaxDist && breakflag == 0)
        {
            if (xHolder + s > pbEnd - 1)
            {
                xHolder = 0;
                int pbIt = -2;

                for (s = 0; (s < 2) && (n < MaxDist); s++)
                {
                    if ((TElevationDomain[xHolder + s,
                    Y[i]] <= TElevationDomain[pbEnd + pbIt, Y[i]] + extraAmount) &&
                    AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] == 0)

```

```

        {
            n++;
            pbIt++;
        }
        else
        {
            breakflag = 1;
            break;
        }
    }
}
else if ((TElevationDomain[xHolder + s, Y[i]]
<= TElevationDomain[xHolder + (s - numstep), Y[i]] + extraAmount) &&
AboveWater[xHolder + s, Y[i]] == 0)
{
    n++;
    s++;
}
else
{
    break;
}
}
numCells[i] = n;

//if (numCells[i] < 5)
//{
//    direction[i] = 1;
//    goto newdirection;
//}

breakflag = 0;
}
else if (direction[i] == 4) // Bottom Right
{
    int n = 1;
    int s = 1;

    while ((X[i] + s < pbEnd - 1) && (Y[i] - s > 1) &&
(TElevationDomain[X[i] + s, Y[i] - s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i] + (s -
numstep), Y[i] - (s - numstep)] + extraAmount) && AboveWater[X[i] + s,
Y[i] - s] == 0)
    {
        n++;
        s++;
    }

    numCells[i] = n;
}
else if (direction[i] == 5) // Bottom
{
    int n = 1;
    int s = 1;

    while ((Y[i] - s > 1) && (TElevationDomain[X[i],
Y[i] - s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] - (s - numstep)] +
extraAmount) && AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] - s] == 0)
    {
        n++;
        s++;
    }
}

```

```

    }

    numCells[i] = n;

    //if (numCells[i] < 5)
    //{
    //    direction[i] = 3;
    //    goto newdirection;
    //}
}
else if (direction[i] == 6) // Bottom Left
{
    int n = 1;
    int s = 1;

    while ((X[i] - s > 1) && (Y[i] - s > 1) &&
(TElevationDomain[X[i] - s, Y[i] - s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i] - (s -
numstep), Y[i] - (s - numstep)] + extraAmount) && AboveWater[X[i] - s,
Y[i] - s] == 0)
    {
        n++;
        s++;
    }

    numCells[i] = n;
}
else if (direction[i] == 7) // Left
{
    //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 1)
    //{
    //    direction[i] = 1;
    //    goto newdirection;
    //}

    int n = 1;
    int s = 1;

    int xHolder = X[i];
    int breakflag = 0;

    //if (AboveWater[X[i] - 1, Y[i]] == 1)
    //{
    //    Y[i] = Y[i] + 1;
    //}

    while (n < MaxDist && breakflag == 0)
    {
        if (xHolder - s < 0)
        {
            xHolder = pbEnd - 1;
            int pbIt = 1;

            for (s = 0; (s < 2) && (n < MaxDist); s++)
            {
                if ((TElevationDomain[xHolder - s,
Y[i]] <= TElevationDomain[0 + pbIt, Y[i]] + extraAmount) &&
AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] == 0)
                {
                    n++;
                    pbIt--;
                }
            }
            else
                836

```

```

        {
            breakflag = 1;
            break;
        }
    }
}
else if ((TElevationDomain[xHolder - s, Y[i]]
<= TElevationDomain[(xHolder - s) + numstep, Y[i]] + extraAmount) &&
AboveWater[xHolder - s, Y[i]] == 0)
{
    n++;
    s++;
}
else
{
    break;
}
}

numCells[i] = n;

//if (numCells[i] < 5)
//{
//    direction[i] = 1;
//    goto newdirection;
//}

breakflag = 0;
}
else if (direction[i] == 8) // Top Left
{
    int n = 1;
    int s = 1;

    while ((X[i] - s > 1) && (Y[i] + s < ymax - 1) &&
(TElevationDomain[X[i] - s, Y[i] + s] <= TElevationDomain[X[i] - (s -
numstep), Y[i] + (s - numstep)] + extraAmount) && AboveWater[X[i] - s,
Y[i] + s] == 0)
    {
        n++;
        s++;
    }

    numCells[i] = n;
}

if (numCells[i] > MaxDist)
{
    numCells[i] = MaxDist;
}
}
}

void RedrawCoastline()
{
    //int i;
    //int repeat = 1;

    //int repeat2 = 1;
    //double celldifference = 0;
    //int a = 1;

```

```

//for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells; i++)
//{
//    //repeat = 1;
//    //    Acreting
//    //while (repeat == 1)
//    //{
//        if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] >=
maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + WetDryThreshold)
//        {
//            AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] = 1;

//            //while (repeat2 == 1)
//            //{
//                celldifference = (CellWidth * a) *
Math.Tan((ShorefaceSlope * CellWidth) * (Math.PI / 180));

//                if ((TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + (a -
1)] >= maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + (WetDryThreshold *
WetDryThreshold)))
//                {
//                    TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + a] =
(maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + WetDryThreshold);
//                    TElevationCS[X[i], Y[i] + a] =
(DomainDepthCS[X[i], Y[i] + a] - TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i] + a]);
//                    Volume[X[i], Y[i] + a] =
TElevationCS[X[i], Y[i] + a] * (CellWidth * CellWidth);

//                    AboveWater[X[i], Y[i] + a] = 1;

//                    //repeat2 = 1;
//                    //a++;

//                    //if (a + Y[i] >= ymax)
//                    //{
//                        //    repeat2 = 0;
//                    //}

//                    //else
//                    //{
//                        //    repeat2 = 0;
//                    //}

//                    //Y[i] = Y[i] + a;

//                    //a = 1;
//                    //repeat = 0;

//                else if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] <
maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel + WetDryThreshold)
//                {
//                    if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] >=
maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel - WetDryThreshold)
//                    {
//                        AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] = 1;
// Still remains the coastline cell, it is still above the water, but
not completely
//                        //repeat = 0;
//                    }
//                else if (TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] <
maxDomainDepth + WaterLevel - WetDryThreshold)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          {
//          AboveWater[X[i], Y[i]] = 0;
//          TElevationCS[X[i], Y[i]] = 0;
//          TElevationDomain[X[i], Y[i]] =
DomainDepthCS[X[i], Y[i]];
//          Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0;

//          //Y[i] = Y[i] - 1;
//          //repeat = 1;
//          }
//          }
//          //}
//          //}
}

// Sources and Sinks
void DoSink()
{
// Empties of sand any cell that has been designated a
sink

int s, i;
int foundOne = 0;

if (HaveSinks == 0 || RandZeroToOne() > Sinkiness)
{
return;
}

if (ColumnSinks == 1)
// Treat sink as any beach cell at a particular y-value
{
for (s = 0; s < NumSinks; s++)
{
for (i = 0; i < MaxBeachLength; i++)
{
if (X[i] == SinkX[s])
{
//PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
foundOne = 1;
}
}
}
}
else
{
// Treat sink as a specific cell; empty it if it is on
the beach

for (s = 0; s < NumSinks; s++)
{
for (i = 0; i < MaxBeachLength; i++)
{
if (X[i] == SinkX[s] && Y[i] == SinkY[s])
{
//PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
Volume[X[i], Y[i]] = 0.0;
foundOne = 1;
}
}
}
}
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

    }
  }
}

void DoSource()
{
  // Adds sediment from external sources to specified cells

  int s, i;
  int foundOne = 0;
  double sandvol;

  if (ColumnSources == 1)
  // Treat source as any beach cell at a particular y-value
  {
    for (s = 0; s < NumSources; s++)
    {
      for (i = 0; i < MaxBeachLength; i++)
      {
        if (X[i] == SourceX[s])
        {
          //find initial cell volume from
          PercentFullSand

          //PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] = 1;
          Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += 0.001;
          foundOne = 1;
        }
      }
    }
  }
  else
  {
    // Treat source as a specific cell; add some sediment
    if it is on the beach
    for (s = 0; s < NumSources; s++)
    {
      for (i = 0; i < MaxBeachLength; i++)
      {
        if (X[i] == SourceX[s] && Y[i] == SourceY[s])
        {
          ////find initial cell volume from
          PercentFullSand

          //sandvol = (PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] *
          2500);

          ////add source sand
          //sandvol += 100;

          ////calculate new PercentFullSand
          //PercentFullSand[X[i], Y[i]] = (sandvol /
          2500);

          //foundOne = 1;

          // Little fudgey, need to work this out
          better later
          Volume[X[i], Y[i]] += (5 * CellWidth *
          CellWidth);

          foundOne = 1;
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
}

//Shadow
void ShadowSweep()
{
// Moves along beach and tests to see if cells are in shadow
// This function will use and determine the Global array:
InShadow[]
// This function will use and adjust the variable:
ShadowYMax
// This function will use but not adjust the variable:
TotalBeachCells
// Find maximum extent of beach to use as a limit for shadow
searching
// ShadowYMax = XMaxBeach(ShadowYMax) + 3;
// if(ShadowYMax > Xmax) ShadowYMax = Xmax; RCL
// Determine if beach cells are in shadow

    int i;

    for (i = 0; i <= TotalBeachCells; i++)
    {
        InShadow[i] = FindIfInShadow(X[i], Y[i], ShadowYMax);
    }

//ShadowSweep_domain();
}

char FindIfInShadow(int xin, int yin, int ShadMax)
{
//Function to determine if particular cell xin,yin is in
shadow
//Returns a character 'y' or 'n' to indicate
//This function will use but not affect the global
arrays:
//AllBeach[][] and PercentFull[][]
//This function refers to global variables: WaveAngle,
ShadowStepDistance

    double xdistance, ydistance;
    int xcheck = xin;
    int ycheck = yin;
    int iteration = 1;

    while ((ycheck < ShadMax) && (xcheck > -1) && (xcheck <
(pbEnd)))
    {
        // Find a cell along the projection line moving
against wave direction
        ydistance = iteration * ShadowStepDistance *
Math.Cos(WaveAngle);
        ycheck = yin + (int)Math.Round(ydistance);

        xdistance = -iteration * ShadowStepDistance *
Math.Sin(WaveAngle);
        xcheck = xin + (int)Math.Round(xdistance);

        if (ycheck >= ymax - 1 || xcheck >= pbEnd - 1)

```

```

        {
            return 'n';
        }

        if (ycheck < 0 || xcheck < 0)
        {
            return 'n';
        }

        if ((AboveWater[xcheck, ycheck] == 1)
            && (((ycheck + 1) > (yin + (AboveWater[xin, yin])
+ Math.Abs((xcheck - xin) / Math.Tan(WaveAngle))))))
            && (xcheck > -1) && (xcheck < pbEnd - 1))
        {
            return 'y';
        }

        // Compare a partially full cell's x - distance to a
        line projected from the starting beach cell's x-distance
        // This assumes that beach projection is in x-
        direction (not too bad)
        // RCL this could be contributing to the
        jaggedness...need to take into account the way it's facing or could
        just ignore partially full cells completely...

        iteration++;
    }

    // No shadow was found
    return 'n';

    //int Shadow_direction = -9999;
    // 1 = left, 2 = top left, 3 = top, 4 = top right, 5 = right

    //if (WaveAngle >= 0 && WaveAngle <= 0.261799388)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 1;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle > 0.261799388 && WaveAngle <= 1.309)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 2;
    //}
    //else if ((WaveAngle > 1.309 && WaveAngle <= 1.6) ||
(WaveAngle > -1.6 && WaveAngle < -1.309))
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 3;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle >= -1.309 && WaveAngle < -0.261799)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 4;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle >= -0.261799 && WaveAngle <= 0)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 5;
    //}
    //else
    //{

    //}

    //int a = 1;
    //int flag = 0;

```

```

//if (Shadow_direction == 1)
//{
//    while (X[xin] - a > 0 && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] - a, Y[yin]] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 2)
//{
//    while (X[xin] - a > 0 && Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag
== 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] - a, Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 3)
//{
//    a += 2;

//    while (Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin], Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 4)
//{
//    while (X[xin] + a > 0 && Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag
== 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] + a, Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 5)
//{
//    while (X[xin] + a > 0 && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] + a, Y[yin]] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}

//if (flag == 1)

```

```

        //{
        //    return 'y';
        //}

        //return 'n';

    }

    void ShadowSweep_domain()
    {
        // Moves along beach and tests to see if cells are in
shadow
        // This function will use and determine the Global array:
InShadow[]
        // This function will use and adjust the variable:
ShadowYMax
        // This function will use but not adjust the variable:
TotalBeachCells
        // Find maximum extent of beach to use as a limit for
shadow searching
        // ShadowYMax = XMaxBeach(ShadowYMax) + 3;
        // if(ShadowYMax > Xmax) ShadowYMax = Xmax; RCL
        // Determine if beach cells are in shadow

        int i;

        Array.Clear(InShadow_domain, 0, InShadow_domain.Length);

        for (int x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        {
            for (int y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
            {
                {
                    InShadow_domain[x, y] =
FindIfInShadow_domain(x, y, ShadowYMax);
                }
            }
        }

        double FindIfInShadow_domain(int xin, int yin, int ShadMax)
        {
shadow
            //Function to determine if particular cell xin,yin is in
shadow
            //Returns a character 'y' or 'n' to indicate
            //This function will use but not affect the global arrays:
            //AllBeach[][] and PercentFull[][]
            //This function refers to global variables: WaveAngle,
ShadowStepDistance

            double xdistance, ydistance;
            int xcheck = xin;
            int ycheck = yin;
            int iteration = 1;

            while ((ycheck < ShadMax) && (xcheck > -1) && (xcheck <
(pbEnd)))
            {
                // Find a cell along the projection line moving
against wave direction
                ydistance = iteration * ShadowStepDistance *
Math.Cos(WaveAngle);

```

```

        ycheck = yin + (int)Math.Round(ydistance);

        xdistance = -iteration * ShadowStepDistance *
Math.Sin(WaveAngle);
        xcheck = xin + (int)Math.Round(xdistance);

        if (ycheck >= ymax - 1 || xcheck >= pbEnd - 1)
        {
            return 0;
        }

        if (ycheck < 0 || xcheck < 0)
        {
            return 0;
        }

        if ((AboveWater[xcheck, ycheck] == 1)
            && (((ycheck + 1) > (yin + (AboveWater[xin, yin])
+ Math.Abs((xcheck - xin) / Math.Tan(WaveAngle))))
            && (xcheck > -1) && (xcheck < pbEnd - 1))
        {
            return 1;
        }

        // Compare a partially full cell's x - distance to a
line projected from the starting beach cell's x-distance
        // This assumes that beach projection is in x-
direction (not too bad)
        // RCL this could be contributing to the
jaggedness...need to take into account the way it's facing or could
just ignore partially full cells completely...

        iteration++;
    }

    // No shadow was found
    return 0;

    //int Shadow_direction = -9999;
// 1 = left, 2 = top left, 3 = top, 4 = top right, 5 = right

    //if (WaveAngle >= 0 && WaveAngle <= 0.261799388)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 1;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle > 0.261799388 && WaveAngle <= 1.309)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 2;
    //}
    //else if ((WaveAngle > 1.309 && WaveAngle <= 1.6) ||
(WaveAngle > -1.6 && WaveAngle < -1.309))
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 3;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle >= -1.309 && WaveAngle < -0.261799)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 4;
    //}
    //else if (WaveAngle >= -0.261799 && WaveAngle <= 0)
    //{
    //    Shadow_direction = 5;
    //}

```

```

//else
//{

//}

//int a = 1;
//int flag = 0;

//if (Shadow_direction == 1)
//{
//    while (X[xin] - a > 0 && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] - a, Y[yin]] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 2)
//{
//    while (X[xin] - a > 0 && Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag
== 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] - a, Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 3)
//{
//    a += 2;

//    while (Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin], Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 4)
//{
//    while (X[xin] + a > 0 && Y[yin] + a < ymax && flag
== 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] + a, Y[yin] + a] == 1)
//        {
//            flag = 1;
//        }
//        a++;
//    }
//}
//else if (Shadow_direction == 5)
//{
//    while (X[xin] + a > 0 && flag == 0)
//    {
//        if (AboveWater[X[xin] + a, Y[yin]] == 1)
//        {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          flag = 1;
//      }
//      a++;
//  }
//}

//if (flag == 1)
//{
//    return 'y';
//}

//return 'n';
}

// Calculate Overwash
void CheckOverwashSweep()
{
    // Just a loop to call overwash check founction
CheckOverwash
// Nothing done here, but can be down when CheckOverwash
is called

    int i, ii;
    int sweepsign;

    if (RandZeroToOne() * 2 > 1)
    {
        sweepsign = 1;
    }
    else
    {
        sweepsign = 0;
    }

    OWflag = 0;

    for (i = 0; i < TotalBeachCells - 1; i++)
    {
        if (sweepsign == 1)
        {
            ii = i;
        }
        else
        {
            ii = TotalBeachCells - 1 - i;
        }

        // To do test shoreline should be facing seaward
        // don't worry about shadow here, as overwash is not
set to a time scale with AST

        if ((Math.Abs(SurroundingAngle[ii]) < (OverwashLimit /
radtodeg)) && (InShadow[ii] == 'n'))
        {
            CheckOverwash(ii);
        }
    }
}

```

```

void CheckOverwash(int icheck)
{
    // Step back pixelwise in direction of SurroundingAngle[]
to check 'needage' (?)
    // icheck is passed from CheckOverwashSweep() and is the
index of the shoreline cell being checked for overwash
    // Calls DoOverwash(). 'x' and 'y' hold real-space
(floating point) values, and will be mapped onto integer array

    double slope; // slope of zero goes
straight back
    int xsign; // holder for going left
or right alongshore
    double x, y; // holders for 'real'
location of x and y
    double xin, yin; // starting 'real'
locations
    int xtest, ytest; // cell looking at
    double xint, yint; // intercepts of overwash
line in overwashable cell
    int NextXInt, NextYInt; // holder vairables for
cell to check
    double Xdown, DistanceDown; // when going to next x
cell, what other values
    double Yside, DistanceSide; // when gpoing to next y
cell,other values
    double checkdistance; // distance of checking
line- minimum, not actual width, ends loop
    double measwidth; // actual barrier width
between cells
    int AllBeachFlag; // flag to see if overwash
line has passed over at least one AllBeach cell

    // convert angle to a slope and the direction of steps
    // note that for case of shoreline, positive angle will be
minus y direcyion

    if (SurroundingAngle[icheck] == 0.0)
    {
        // unlikely, but make sure no div by zero
        slope = 0.00001;
    }
    else if (Math.Abs(SurroundingAngle[icheck]) == 90.0)
    {
        slope = 9999.9;
    }
    else
    {
        slope = Math.Abs(Math.Tan(SurroundingAngle[icheck]));
    }

    if (SurroundingAngle[icheck] > 0)
    {
        xsign = 1; // check right
    }
    else
    {
        xsign = -1; // check left
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (AboveWater[X[icheck], Y[icheck] - 1] == 1
// if the cell below is all beach
        || ((AboveWater[X[icheck] - 1, Y[icheck]] == 1)
// or if the cell to the left is all beach
        && (AboveWater[X[icheck] + 1, Y[icheck]] == 1)))
// and the cell to the right is all beach
        // 'regular condition'
        // plus 'stuck in the middle' situation (unlikely
scenario)
        {
            yin = Y[icheck] + AboveWater[X[icheck], Y[icheck]];
            xin = X[icheck] + 0.5;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[icheck] - 1, Y[icheck]] == 1) //if
the cell to the left is all beach
        // on right side
        {
            yin = Y[icheck] + 0.5;
            xin = X[icheck] + AboveWater[X[icheck], Y[icheck]];
        }
        else if (AboveWater[X[icheck] + 1, Y[icheck]] == 1)
        // on left side
        {
            yin = Y[icheck] + 0.5;
            xin = X[icheck] + 1.0 - AboveWater[X[icheck],
Y[icheck]];
        }
        else
        // underneath, no overwash
        {
            return;
        }

        x = xin;
        y = yin;
        checkdistance = 0;
        AllBeachFlag = 0;
        int countno = 0;

        while ((checkdistance < CritBWidth) && (x > 0) && (x <
pbEnd) && (y > 1))
        {
            NextYInt = Convert.ToInt32(Math.Ceiling(y) - 1);

            if (xsign > 0)
            {
                NextXInt = Convert.ToInt32((int)Math.Floor(x) +
1);
            }
            else
            {
                NextXInt = Convert.ToInt32(Math.Ceiling(x - 1));
            }

            // Moving to next whole 'y' position, what is x
position?
            Xdown = x + (y - NextYInt) * slope * xsign;
            DistanceDown = Raise(((Xdown - x) * (Xdown - x) +
(NextYInt - y) * (NextYInt - y)), 0.5);

            // Moving to next whole 'x' position, what is y
position?

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        Yside = y - Math.Abs(NextXInt - x) / slope;
        DistanceSide = Raise(((NextXInt - x) * (NextXInt - x)
+ (Yside - y) * (Yside - y)), 0.5);

        if (DistanceDown < DistanceSide)
        // Next cell is the down cell
        {
            y = NextYInt;
            x = Xdown;
            ytest = NextYInt - 1;
            xtest = Convert.ToInt32(Math.Floor(x));
        }
        else
        // Next cell is the side cell
        {
            y = Yside;
            x = NextXInt;
            ytest = Convert.ToInt32(Math.Floor(y));
            xtest = Convert.ToInt32(x + (xsign - 1) / 2);
        }

        checkdistance = Raise(((y - yin) * (y - yin) + (x -
xin) * (x - xin)), 0.5) * CellWidth;

        if (xtest >= 0 && ytest >= 0 && AboveWater[xtest,
ytest] == 1)
        {
            AllBeachFlag = 1;
        }

        if (xtest >= 0 && ytest >= 0 && (AllBeach[xtest,
ytest] == 'n') && (AllBeachFlag == 1)) /*&& !(((Y[icheck] - ytest) >
MaxFillCell) || (Math.Abs(xtest - X[icheck]) > MaxFillCell))*/
        // if passed through an allbeach and a neighboring
partial cell, jump out, only bad things follow
        {
            return;
        }

        if (xtest >= 0 && ytest >= 0 && (AllBeach[xtest,
ytest] == 0) && (AllBeachFlag == 1)) /*&& (ytest < Y[icheck]) &&
(((Y[icheck] - ytest) > MaxFillCell) || (Math.Abs(xtest - X[icheck]) >
MaxFillCell))*/
        // Looking for shore cells, but don't want immediate
neighbors, and go backwards
        // Also mush pass though an allbeach cell along the
way
        {

            if (AboveWater[xtest, ytest + 1] == 1)
            // 'regular condition' - UNDERNEATH, here
            {
                yint = (ytest + 1 - AboveWater[xtest, ytest]);
                xint = xin + (yin - yint) * xsign * slope;

                if ((xint > xtest + 1.0) || (xint < xtest))
                // This cell isn't actually an overwash cell
                {
                    measwidth = CritBWidth;
                }
            }
            else

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        {
            measwidth = CellWidth * Raise((yint - yin)
* (yint - yin) + (xint - xin) * (xint - xin), 0.5);
        }
    }
    else if (AboveWater[xtest - 1, ytest] == 1)
    // On right side
    {
        xint = (xtest + AboveWater[xtest, ytest]);
        yint = yin - Math.Abs(xin - xint) / slope;

        if (yint < ytest)
        // This cell isn't actually an overwash cell
        {
            measwidth = CritBWidth;
        }
        else
        {
            measwidth = CellWidth * Raise((yint - yin)
* (yint - yin) + (xint - xin) * (xint - xin), 0.5);
        }
    }
    else if (AboveWater[xtest + 1, ytest] == 1)
    // on left side
    {
        xint = (xtest + 1 - AboveWater[xtest, ytest]);
        yint = yin - Math.Abs(xin - xint) / slope;

        if (yint < ytest)
        // This cell isn't actually an overwash cell
        {
            measwidth = CritBWidth;
        }
        else
        {
            measwidth = CellWidth * Raise((yint - yin)
* (yint - yin) + (xint - xin) * (xint - xin), 0.5);
        }
    }
    else if (AboveWater[xtest, ytest - 1] == 1)
    // 'regular condition'
    // plus 'stuck in the middle' situation
    {
        yint = (ytest + AboveWater[xtest, ytest]);
        xint = xin + (yin - yint) * xsign * slope;

        if ((xint > xtest + 1.0) || (xint < xtest))
        // This cell isn't actually an overwash cell
        {
            measwidth = CritBWidth;
        }
        else
        {
            measwidth = CellWidth * Raise((yint - yin)
* (yint - yin) + (xint - xin) * (xint - xin), 0.5);
        }
    }
    else if (AboveWater[xtest, ytest] > 0)
    // uh oh - not good situation, no allbeach on
sides
    // assume this is an empty cell
    {

```

```

        xint = x;
        yint = y;

        measwidth = CellWidth * Raise((yint - yin) *
(yint - yin) + (xint - xin) * (xint - xin), 0.5);
    }
    else
    // empty cell - oughta fill 'er up - fill max
barrier width
    {
        xint = x;
        yint = y;
        measwidth = CritBWidth - CellWidth;
    }

    checkdistance = measwidth;

    if (measwidth < CritBWidth)
    {
        DoOverwash(X[icheck], Y[icheck], xtest, ytest,
xint, yint, measwidth, icheck);

        // jump out of loop
        OWflag = 1;
        return;
    }

    }
    countno++;
}
}

void DoOverwash(int xfrom, int yfrom, int xto, int yto, double
xintto, double yintto, double widthin, int ishore)
{
    // Given a cell where overwash is needed ,move sediment
back
    // for 'true' overwash based on shoreline angles will
change and use PercentFull[][] and AllBeach [][]

    double BBneed, delBB, delShore;
    double DepthBB; // holds effective
backbarrier depth

    DepthBB = GetOverwashDepth(xto, yto, xintto, yintto,
ishore);

    // Calculated value of most that backbarrier can move
given geometry (true, non-iterative solution)

    if (DepthBB == DepthShoreface)
    {
        BBneed = MaxOver;
    }
    else
    {
        BBneed = (CritBWidth - widthin) / CellWidth / (1 -
(DepthBB / DepthShoreface));
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (BBneed <= MaxOver)
        // do all overwash
        {
            delShore = BBneed * DepthBB / DepthShoreface;
            delBB = BBneed;
        }
        else
        // only do overwash to max change)
        {
            delShore = MaxOver * DepthBB / DepthShoreface;
            delBB = MaxOver;
        }

        Volume[xto, yto] += delBB * CellWidth * DepthShelf[xto,
yto];
        Volume[xfrom, yfrom] -= delShore * CellWidth *
DepthShelf[xfrom, yfrom];
    }

    double GetOverwashDepth(int xin, int yin, double xinfl, double
yinfl, int ishop)
    {
        // Routine finds corresponding overwash depths
        // OWType = 0 take the depth at neighbor to the backing
cell
        // OWType = 1 geometric rule based upon distance from back
to shoreline
        {
            int ydepth;
            double Depth;
            double BBDistance;           // Distance from
backshore to next shore
            double slope;               // slope of zero goes
straight back
            int xsign;                  // holder for going
left or right alongshore
            double x, y;                // holders for 'real'
location of x and y
            int xtest = 0;              // cell looking at
            int ytest = 0;              // cell looking at
            int NextXInt, NextYInt;     // holder variables
            for cell to check
            double Xdown, DistanceDown; // when going to next
x cell, what other values
            double Yside, DistanceSide; // when going to next
y cell, other values
            int BackFlag;               // Flag to indicate if
hit backbarrier
            int Backi = -1;             // i for backbarrier
            intersection
            int i, j;                   // counters
            int FoundFlag;              // Backbarrier
            intersection flag
            double AngleSin, AngleUsed;

            if (OWType == 0)
            // Use Cell Depths for overwash depths
            {
                ydepth = yin;
                //Depth = CellDepth[xin, ydepth];

```

```

        Depth = TElevationCS[xin, ydepth];

        while ((Depth < 0) && (ydepth > 0))
        {
            //Depth = CellDepth[xin, ydepth];
            Depth = TElevationCS[xin, ydepth];
            ydepth--;
        }

        if (Depth == DepthShoreface)
        {
            Depth = 6.0;
        }

        return Depth;
    }
    else if (OWType == 1)
        // Geometric relation to determine depth through
intersection of shorefaces
        // look in line determined by shoreline slope - reuse
stepping function (again)
        {
            x = xinfl;
            y = yinfl;

            if (SurroundingAngle[ishore] == 0.0)
            {
                // unlikely, but make sure no div by zero
                slope = 0.00001;
            }
            else if (Math.Abs(SurroundingAngle[ishore]) ==
90.0)
            {
                slope = 9999.9;
            }
            else
            {
                slope =
Math.Abs(Math.Tan(SurroundingAngle[ishore]));
            }

            BackFlag = 0;

            if (SurroundingAngle[ishore] > 0)
            {
                xsign = 1;
            }
            else
                xsign = -1;

            while ((BackFlag == 0) && (x > 1) && (x < pbEnd)
&& (y > 1))
            {
                NextYInt = ((int)Math.Ceiling(y) - 1);

                if (xsign > 0)
                {
                    NextXInt = ((int)Math.Floor(x) + 1);
                }
                else
                {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        NextXInt = ((int)Math.Ceiling(x - 1));
    }

    // moving to next whole 'x' position, what is
y position?
    Xdown = x + (y - NextYInt) * slope * xsign;
    DistanceDown = Raise(((Xdown - x) * (Xdown -
x) + (NextYInt - y) * (NextYInt - y)), 0.5);

    // moving to next whole 'y' position, what is
x position?
    Yside = y - Math.Abs(NextXInt - x) / slope;
    DistanceSide = Raise(((NextXInt - x) *
(NextXInt - x) + (Yside - y) * (Yside - y)), 0.5);

    // next cell is the down cell
    if (DistanceDown < DistanceSide)
    {
        y = NextYInt;
        x = Xdown;
        ytest = NextYInt - 1;
        xtest = ((int)Math.Floor(x));
    }
    // next cell is the side cell
    else
    {
        y = Yside;
        x = NextXInt;
        ytest = ((int)Math.Floor(y));
        xtest = ((int)x + (xsign - 1) / 2);
    }

    if (AboveWater[xtest, ytest] > 0)
    {
        BackFlag = 1;
    }
}

// Try to find the i for the cell found
// If you have a better idea how to do this, go
ahead

    i = 2;
    FoundFlag = 0;

    while ((i < TotalBeachCells - 1) && (FoundFlag ==
0))
    {
        if ((Y[i] == ytest) && (X[i] == xtest))
        {
            FoundFlag = 1;
            Backi = i;
        }

        i++;
    }

    if (BackFlag == 0)
        // The search for the backbarrier went out of
bounds - not good, assume big = depthshoreface

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

// Periodic B.C.'s should make this not so
important
{
    Depth = DepthShoreface;
}
else
{
    BBDistance = Raise(((yinfl - ytest -
AboveWater[xtest, ytest]) * (yinfl - ytest - AboveWater[xtest,
ytest])) + ((xinfl - xtest - 0.5) * (xinfl - xtest - 0.5)), 0.5);

    if (FoundFlag == 0)
// The backbarrier intersection isn't on the
shoreline
// Assume 1/2 of the length applies to this
case
{
    Depth = BBDistance / 2 * ShorefaceSlope *
CellWidth;
}
else
// Use the fancy geometry thing
{
    AngleUsed = 0;

    for (j = -1; j < 2; j++)
    {
        AngleUsed += SurroundingAngle[Backi +
j];
    }

    AngleUsed = AngleUsed / 5;

    if (Math.Abs(AngleUsed) > pi / 4.0)
    {
        AngleUsed = pi / 4.0;
    }

    AngleSin = Math.Sin(pi / 2.0 -
Math.Abs(SurroundingAngle[ishore] + AngleUsed));

    Depth = BBDistance * AngleSin / (1 +
AngleSin);
}
}

if (Depth < OWMinDepth)
{
    Depth = OWMinDepth;
}
else if (Depth > DepthShoreface)
{
    Depth = DepthShoreface;
}

return Depth;
}

PauseRun(xin, yin, -1);
return DepthShoreface;
}

```

```

    }

    // Misc Equations
    static double copysign(double x, double y)
    {
        if (Math.Sign(x) != Math.Sign(y))
        {
            return x *= -1;
        }

        return x;
    }

    double Raise(double b, double e)
    {
        // Function calculates b to the e power. pow has problems if b
    <= 0
        // Note you can't use this at all when b is negative--it'll be
        wrong in cases when the answer returned should have been positive, as
        x^2 when x < 0.

        if (b > 0)
        {
            return Math.Pow(b, e);
        }
        else
        {
            PauseRun(-1, -1, -1);
            return 0;
        }
    }

    double RandZeroToOne()
    {
        // Returns a random number between zero and one

        Random rand = new Random();
        double RandNo = rand.Next(0, 1000);
        RandNo = ((RandNo + 1) / 1000);
        return RandNo;
    }

    void ZeroVars()
    {
        // Resets all arrays recalculated at each time step to 'zero'
    conditions

        int z;
        int x,y;

        for (z = 0; z <= (MaxBeachLength-1); z++)
        {
            X[z] = -1;
            Y[z] = -1;
            XRock[z] = -1;
            YRock[z] = -1;
            XBehind[z] = -1;
            YBehind[z] = -1;
            XRockBehind[z] = -1;
            YRockBehind[z] = -1;

```

```

        InShadow[z] = '?';
        ShorelineAngle[z] = -999;
        UpWind[z] = '?';

        VolumeAcrossBorder[z] = 0.0;
        ActualVolumeAcross[z] = 0.0;
    }
}

// Save Functions
void SaveImageFuncnt()
{
    int RockCheck = 1;        // Need all three to be checked
for JPEG - need to sort this later!
    int SandCheck = 1;        // 1 = checked, 0 = not checked
    int XYCheck = 1;        // This is so they can be changed
back after

        updateGraphics_Click_1(updateGraphicsButton,
EventArgs.Empty);

    // Save image
    // Batch
    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        m_objDrawingSurface.MakeTransparent();
        m_objDrawingSurface.Save("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Simulation/" + savefilename + "_" + imageCount +
".png", System.Drawing.Imaging.ImageFormat.Png);
    }
    else
    {
        m_objDrawingSurface.MakeTransparent();
        m_objDrawingSurface.Save("OUTPUT_FILES/Simulation/" +
savefilename + "_" + imageCount + ".png",
System.Drawing.Imaging.ImageFormat.Png);
    }

    // Output Arrays too...

    int x, y;

    imageCount++;
}

void SaveLineToFile()
{
    //// Saves data line of shoreline position rather than
entire array
    //// Main concern is to have only one data point at each
alongshore location
    //// Save file name will add extension '.' and the
TimeStepValue

    //int y, x, xtop, i;
    //double xsave;
    //string fileName = Convert.ToString(counter /
SaveSpacing);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        ///MessageBox.Show("Saving Line to File \n Saving as: " +
"TEST_FILES/" + fileName + ".out");
        //StreamWriter saveLineFile = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Simulation/" + fileName + ".out");

        //for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
        //{
        //    x = xDisplayStart;
        //    xtop = xmax;

        //    // Step back to where we encounter allbeach
        //    while (AllBeach[x, y] == 0)
        //    {
        //        x -= 1;
        //    }

        //    // If on side of shape, need to average
        //    if (PercentFullSand[x + 2, y] > 0)
        //    {
        //        xtop = x + 1;
        //        while (PercentFullSand[xtop, y] > 0)
        //        {
        //            xtop += 1;
        //        }

        //        xsave = x;

        //        for (i = x + 1; i < xtop; i++)
        //        {
        //            xsave += PercentFullSand[i, y];
        //        }
        //    }

        //    // Otherwise Regular Beach Condition
        //    else
        //    {
        //        xsave = x + PercentFullSand[x + 1, y];
        //    }

        //    // note this assumes average of beach locations
        //    // should be 0.5 percentfull
        //    saveLineFile.Write(xsave - InitBeach + 0.5);
        //}
        //saveLineFile.Close();
        ///MessageBox.Show("Line file saved!");
    }

    void SaveSandToFile()
    {
        ///Saves current AllBeach[][] and PercentFullSand[][]
        data arrays to file
        ///Save file name will add extension '.' and the
        TimeStepValue
        ///LMV - Save AllRock[][], PercentFullRock[][],
        TypeOfRock[][]

        //int x, y;

        //StreamWriter saveSandFile = new
        StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/Sand" + "Sand" + "_" + counter + ".out");

        //if (SaveFile == 1)

```

```

//{
//  for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//      saveSandFile.Write(.TypeOfRock[x, y]);
//    }
//  }

//  for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//      saveSandFile.Write(PercentFullRock[x, y]);
//    }
//  }

//  for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//      saveSandFile.Write(PercentFullSand[x, y]);
//    }
//  }

//  if (SaveAge == 1)
//  {
//    for (y = 0; y < ymax; y++)
//    {
//      for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd;
x++)
//      {
//        saveSandFile.Write(Age[x, y]);
//      }
//    }
//  }
//}

/////Array output
//if (SaveFile == 2)
//{
//  for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//      saveSandFile.Write(.TypeOfRock[x, y]);
//    }
//    saveSandFile.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//  }

//  for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
//    {
//      saveSandFile.Write(PercentFullRock[x, y]);
//    }
//    saveSandFile.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//  }

//  for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
//  {
//    for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//      {
//          saveSandFile.Write(PercentFullSand[x, y]);
//      }
//      saveSandFile.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//  }

//  if (SaveAge == 1)
//  {
//      for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
//      {
//          for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd;
x++)
//          {
//              saveSandFile.Write(Age[x, y]);
//          }
//          saveSandFile.Write(Environment.NewLine);
//      }
//  }
//}

//saveSandFile.Close();
}

void SandOutput()
{
    int x, y;
    double SandAmount = 0;
    string MovedSedVolPath = "OUTPUT_FILES/MovedSedVol.dat";
    StreamWriter TDomain = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/TDomain.out");

    for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
    {
        for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        {
            //SandAmount += (Volume[x, y]);
            TDomain.WriteLine(TElevationDomain[x, y] + " ");
        }
        TDomain.WriteLine(Environment.NewLine);
    }
    TDomain.Close();

    StreamWriter SandAmountFile = new
StreamWriter(MovedSedVolPath);
    SandAmountFile.Write(counter + " " + SandAmount +
Environment.NewLine);
    SandAmountFile.Close();

    SandAmount = 0;
}

void WaveOutFile()
{
    StreamWriter WaveFileOutput;
    if(counter == 0)
    {
        WaveFileOutput = new StreamWriter(wavesavename);
        WaveFileOutput.WriteLine(WaveAngle + " " + Period + "
" + OffShoreWvHt);
    }
    else
    {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        WaveFileOutput = File.AppendText(wavesavename);
        WaveFileOutput.WriteLine((-WaveAngle * radtodeg) + " "
+ Period + " " + OffShoreWvHt);
        //WaveFileOutput.WriteLine(WaveAngle + " " + Period +
" " + OffShoreWvHt);

    }

    WaveFileOutput.Close();
}

void MetaFile()
{
    // Input Wave Distribution

    StreamWriter metaFile = new
StreamWriter("OUTPUT_FILES/metaFile.out");

    metaFile.WriteLine("OffShoreWvHt = " + OffShoreWvHt);
    metaFile.WriteLine("Period = " + Period);
    metaFile.WriteLine("Asym = " + Asym);
    metaFile.WriteLine("Highness = " + (1 - Highness));
    metaFile.WriteLine("TimeStepValue (counter) = " +
counter);
    metaFile.WriteLine("Duration = " + Duration);
    metaFile.WriteLine("SlowWeatherCoeff = " +
SlowWeatherCoeff);
    metaFile.WriteLine("FastWeatherCoeff = " +
FastWeatherCoeff);
    metaFile.WriteLine("PercentFineFast = " +
PercentFineFast);
    metaFile.WriteLine("PercentFineSlow = " +
PercentFineSlow);
    metaFile.WriteLine("ErosionRatePerYear = " +
ErosionRatePerYear);
    metaFile.WriteLine("coastrotation = " + coastrotation);
    metaFile.WriteLine("waveheightchange = " +
waveheightchange);
    metaFile.WriteLine("waveperiodchange = " +
waveperiodchange);

    metaFile.Close();

}

void ResultsData()
{
    //
    // CM - records data used for analysing evolution of the
coastline
    // Each piece of data has it's own file with timestamp
    //
    string filelocation_results;

    if (autorestart == 1)
    {
        Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Results");
        filelocation_results = "OUTPUT_FILES/Run_" +
Restart_count + "/Results/";
    }
    else

```

```

    {
        Directory.CreateDirectory("OUTPUT_FILES/Results");
        filelocation_results = "OUTPUT_FILES/Results/";
    }

    // Water
    StreamWriter Water;

    if (counter == 0)
    {
        Water = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"Water.out");

        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + Asym + " " + Highness
+ " Counter asym highness");
        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + WaterLevel + " " +
HighWaterHeight + " Counter Tideslow Tidehigh");
        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + SLR + " " + SLRrate +
" Counter SLR SLRrate");
        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + maxDomainDepth + " " +
WDThreshold + " Counter MaxDomaiDepth WDThreshold");
        Water.Write(Environment.NewLine);
        Water.WriteLine("Counter WaterLevel");
        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + WaterLevel);
        Water.Close();
    }
    else
    {
        Water = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"Water.out");
        Water.WriteLine(counter + " " + WaterLevel + " " +
Asym + " " + Highness);
        Water.Close();
    }

    // Sinuosity
    StreamWriter Sinuosity;
    double sinuosity = (double)TotalBeachCells / pbEnd;

    if (counter == 0)
    {
        Sinuosity = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"Sinuosity.out");
        Sinuosity.WriteLine("Counter Sinuosity");
        Sinuosity.WriteLine(counter + " " + sinuosity);
        Sinuosity.Close();
    }
    else
    {
        Sinuosity = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"Sinuosity.out");
        Sinuosity.WriteLine(counter + " " + sinuosity);
        Sinuosity.Close();
    }

    // Volume Wet-Dry
    StreamWriter above_water = new
StreamWriter(filelocation_results + "above_water.out");

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        StreamWriter Volume_File = new
StreamWriter(filelocation_results + "Volume.out");

        int y_it = 0;
        int x_it = 0;

        for (y_it = 0; y_it < ymax; y_it++)
        {
            for (x_it = 0; x_it < pbEnd; x_it++)
            {
                if (AboveWater[x_it, y_it] == 1)
                {
                    Vol_Dry += Volume[x_it, y_it];
                    Cells_Dry++;
                }
                else if (AboveWater[x_it, y_it] == 0)
                {
                    Vol_Wet += Volume[x_it, y_it];
                    Cells_Wet++;
                }
                else
                {
                }

                above_water.Write(AboveWater[x_it, y_it] + " ");
                Volume_File.Write(Volume[x_it, y_it] + " ");
            }
            above_water.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            Volume_File.Write(Environment.NewLine);
        }
        above_water.Close();
        Volume_File.Close();

        StreamWriter Vol_WetDry;
        if (counter == 0)
        {
            StreamWriter cs_elev = new
StreamWriter(filelocation_results + "cs_elev.out");
            for (int cs_Y = ymax - 1; cs_Y >= 0; cs_Y--)
            {
                for (int cs_X = 0; cs_X < pbEnd; cs_X++)
                {
                    cs_elev.Write(Volume[cs_X, cs_Y] + " ");
                }
                cs_elev.Write(Environment.NewLine);
            }
            cs_elev.Close();

            double starting_pert_cells = 96;
            // Taking from DEM, need to change if change DEM!!
            double starting_pert_vol = 149580000;
            // Taking from DEM, need to change if change DEM!!

            Start_Vol_Wet = Vol_Wet + starting_pert_vol;
            Start_Cells_Wet = Cells_Wet + starting_pert_cells;
            Start_Vol_Dry = Vol_Dry - starting_pert_vol;
            Start_Cells_Dry = Cells_Dry - starting_pert_cells;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        Vol_WetDry = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"Vol_WetDry.out");
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine("Counter StartCount_Pert
StartVol_Pert");
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine(counter + " " +
starting_pert_cells + " " + starting_pert_vol);
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine(Environment.NewLine);
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine("Counter CellsWet VolWet CellsDry
VolDry");
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine(counter + " " + Cells_Wet + " " +
Vol_Wet + " " + Cells_Dry + " " + Vol_Dry);
        Vol_WetDry.Close();
    }
    else
    {
        Vol_WetDry = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"Vol_WetDry.out");
        Vol_WetDry.WriteLine(counter + " " + Cells_Wet + " " +
Vol_Wet + " " + Cells_Dry + " " + Vol_Dry);
        Vol_WetDry.Close();
    }

    // Shoreface Slope (Linear Regression)
    int xx = 0;
    double[] SF_Slope = new double[4];
    double SF_Average = 0;
    for (int repeat = 0; repeat < 4; repeat++)
    {
        double SumX = 0;
        double SumY = 0;
        double SumXY = 0;
        double SumX2 = 0;
        double SumY2 = 0;
        int xcount = 0;

        int yy = ymax - 2;
        xx += pbEnd / 5;

        while (AboveWater[xx, yy] == 0)
        {
            xcount++;
            SumX += CellWidth * xcount;
            SumY += TElevationDomain[xx, yy];
            SumXY += (CellWidth * xcount) *
(TElevationDomain[xx, yy]);
            SumX2 += (CellWidth * xcount) * (CellWidth *
xcount);
            SumY2 += (TElevationDomain[xx, yy] *
TElevationDomain[xx, yy]);

            yy--;
        }
        SF_Slope[repeat] = (((xcount * SumXY) - (SumX * SumY))
/ ((xcount * SumX2) - (SumX * SumX)));
    }

    for (int i = 0; i < 4; i++)
    {
        SF_Average += SF_Slope[i];
    }

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        SF_Average /= 4;

        StreamWriter SFS;
        if (counter == 0)
        {
            SFS = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"SF_Slope.out");
            SFS.WriteLine("Counter ShorefaceSlope");
            SFS.WriteLine(counter + " " + SF_Average);
            SFS.Close();
        }
        else
        {
            SFS = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"SF_Slope.out");
            SFS.WriteLine(counter + " " + SF_Average);
            SFS.Close();
        }

        // Local Beach Slope
        int xxx = 0;
        double[] B_Slope = new double[4];
        double B_Average = 0;
        for (int repeat = 0; repeat < 4; repeat++)
        {
            double SumX = 0;
            double SumY = 0;
            double SumXY = 0;
            double SumX2 = 0;
            double SumY2 = 0;
            int xcount = 0;

            int yy = 3;
            xxx += pbEnd / 5;

            while (AboveWater[xxx, yy] == 1)
            {
                xcount++;
                SumX += CellWidth * xcount;
                SumY += TElevationDomain[xxx, yy];
                SumXY += (CellWidth * xcount) *
(TElevationDomain[xxx, yy]);
                SumX2 += (CellWidth * xcount) * (CellWidth *
xcount);
                SumY2 += (TElevationDomain[xxx, yy] *
TElevationDomain[xxx, yy]);

                yy++;
            }
            B_Slope[repeat] = (((xcount * SumXY) - (SumX * SumY))
/ ((xcount * SumX2) - (SumX * SumX)));
        }

        for (int i = 0; i < 4; i++)
        {
            B_Average += B_Slope[i];
        }

        B_Average = (B_Average / 4) * -1;

        StreamWriter B_slope;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        if (counter == 0)
        {
            B_slope = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"B_Slope.out");
            B_slope.WriteLine("Counter BeachSlope");
            B_slope.WriteLine(counter + " " + B_Average);
            B_slope.Close();
        }
        else
        {
            B_slope = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"B_Slope.out");
            B_slope.WriteLine(counter + " " + B_Average);
            B_slope.Close();
        }

        // Net Erosion/Accretion
        StreamWriter XY_array;
        if (counter == 0)
        {
            XY_array = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"XY_array.out");
            XY_array.WriteLine("Counter i X Y");

            for (int i = 0; i < TotalBeachCells; i++)
            {
                XY_array.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " + X[i]
+ " " + Y[i]);
            }
            XY_array.WriteLine(Environment.NewLine);
            XY_array.Close();
        }
        else
        {
            XY_array = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"XY_array.out");

            for (int i = 0; i < TotalBeachCells; i++)
            {
                XY_array.WriteLine(counter + " " + i + " " + X[i]
+ " " + Y[i]);
            }
            XY_array.WriteLine(Environment.NewLine);

            XY_array.Close();
        }

        // Lifecycle of features
        int flag_lifecycle = 0;
        int flag_prevpeak = 0;
        int flag_its = 0;
        int Peak_count = 0;
        double CrossShore = 0;           // How far into the
sea do the features project?
        double LongShore = 0;           // How far/rate of
longshore movement

```

```

for (int Yy = ymax - 3; Yy > 2; Yy--)
{
    for (int Xx = 4; Xx < pbEnd - 2; Xx++)
    {
        if (AboveWater[Xx, Yy] == 1 && flag_lifecycle ==
0)
        {
            CrossShore = Yy;
            LongShore = Xx;

            flag_lifecycle = 1;
            flag_its++;
            Peak_count = 1;
        }
        else if (AboveWater[Xx, Yy] == 1 && flag_lifecycle
== 1 && AboveWater[Xx - 1, Yy] == 0 && AboveWater[Xx - 2, Yy] == 0 &&
AboveWater[Xx - 3, Yy] == 0)
        {
            Peak_count += 1;
        }
    }
    if (flag_lifecycle == 1)
    {
        if (flag_its == 1 && Peak_count < 3 || Peak_count
> flag_prevpeak)
        {
            // Look at the next row down
            // Likely to have caught only one of the
peaks, just check!

            flag_prevpeak = Peak_count;
            Peak_count = 0;
        }
        else if (Peak_count < flag_prevpeak)
        {
            Peak_count = flag_prevpeak;
            break;
        }
        else
        {
            break;
        }
    }
}

StreamWriter Lifecycle;
if (counter == 0)
{
    Lifecycle = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"Lifecycle.out");
    Lifecycle.WriteLine("Counter CrossShore Longshore
Peak_count");
    Lifecycle.WriteLine(counter + " " + CrossShore + " " +
LongShore + " " + Peak_count);
    Lifecycle.Close();
}
else
{
    Lifecycle = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"Lifecycle.out");

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        Lifecycle.WriteLine(counter + " " + CrossShore + " " +
LongShore + " " + Peak_count);
        Lifecycle.Close();
    }

    // Average size of landforms
    double Landform_size = 0; //
Area (number of cells!)
    double Lanform_volume = 0; //
Volume

    Landform_size = (Start_Cells_Wet - Cells_Wet) /
Peak_count;
    Lanform_volume = (Start_Vol_Wet - Vol_Wet) / Peak_count;

    StreamWriter LandformSize;
    if (counter == 0)
    {
        LandformSize = new StreamWriter(filelocation_results +
"LandformSize.out");
        LandformSize.WriteLine("Counter LandformSize
LandformVol PeakCount");
        LandformSize.WriteLine(counter + " " + Landform_size +
" " + Lanform_volume + " " + Peak_count);
        LandformSize.Close();
    }
    else
    {
        LandformSize = File.AppendText(filelocation_results +
"LandformSize.out");
        LandformSize.WriteLine(counter + " " + Landform_size +
" " + Lanform_volume + " " + Peak_count);
        LandformSize.Close();
    }

    // Above Average Shoreline position
    // Calculate average position of the shoreline,
anything above water, seaward of this line is considered a
perturbation
    int averageY = 0;
    double Feature_vol = 0;
    double Feature_cells = 0;

    for (int ii = 0; ii < TotalBeachCells; ii++)
    {
        averageY += Y[ii];
    }
    if (TotalBeachCells > 0)
    {
        averageY = (averageY / TotalBeachCells) + 1;
    }

    for (int y_start = averageY; y_start < ymax; y_start++)
    {
        for (int x_start = 0; x_start < pbEnd; x_start++)
        {
            if (AboveWater[x_start, y_start] == 1)
            {
                Feature_vol += Volume[x_start, y_start];
            }
        }
    }

```

```

        Feature_cells++;
    }
}

StreamWriter LandformSize_avgShoreline;
if (counter == 0)
{
    LandformSize_avgShoreline = new
StreamWriter(filelocation_results + "LandformSize_avgShrln.out");
    LandformSize_avgShoreline.WriteLine("Counter AverageY
TotalLandformSize TotalLandformVol PeakCount Landformsize
Landformvol");
    LandformSize_avgShoreline.WriteLine(counter + " " +
averageY + " " + Feature_cells + " " + Feature_vol + " " + Peak_count
+ " " + (Feature_vol/Peak_count) + " " + (Feature_cells/Peak_count));
    LandformSize_avgShoreline.Close();
}
else
{
    LandformSize_avgShoreline =
File.AppendText(filelocation_results + "LandformSize_avgShrln.out");
    LandformSize_avgShoreline.WriteLine(counter + " " +
averageY + " " + Feature_cells + " " + Feature_vol + " " + Peak_count
+ " " + (Feature_vol / Peak_count) + " " + (Feature_cells /
Peak_count));
    LandformSize_avgShoreline.Close();
}
}

void PauseRun(int x, int y, int in_)
{
    // Pauses run until the 'q' key is pressed
    // Can Print or Plot Out Useful info

    //MessageBox.Show("Paused");

    if (SaveLine == 1)
    {
        SaveLineToFile();
    }
    if (SaveFile == 1 || SaveFile == 2)
    {
        SaveSandToFile();
    }

    if (NoPauseRun == 1)
    {
        return;
    }

    //MessageBox.Show("End Pause");
}

/*.....
.....*/

```

```

//Graphics
void drawwater(System.Drawing.Graphics graphics)
{
    Graphics objGraphics;
    objGraphics = Graphics.FromImage(m_objDrawingSurface);
    objGraphics.Clear(SystemColors.Control);

    int x, y;
    int t = 0;

    int redcol = 0, greencol = 0, bluecol = 0;
    int alphacol = 255;

    double zDEM;
    double zCalc;           // Value to help identify min,
max elevation values
    double zMin = 0.0;
    double zMax = 10.0;
    double zRange;

    double hueMin;
    double hueMax;
    double satMin;
    double satMax;
    double valMin;
    double valMax;

    //Elevation
    double zElevRange;

    //Depth
    double zDepthRange;

    // Set Graphics Display Size
    if (xmax <= 0) xmax = 1;

    //set scaling of graphics - so X bmp pixels to every model
pixel.
    t = graphics_scale;

    //// Colour PercentFullSand
    //if (menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked == true)
    //{
    //    int b = -1;
    //    int alpha;
    //    for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
    //    {
    //        b++;

    //        for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
    //        {
    //            if (PercentFullSand[x, y] > 0.0)
    //            {
    //                alpha = 255;

    //                SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(alpha, 255, 0, 0));

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//          objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x *
t), ((b - 1) * t), t, t);
//          }
//      }
//  }
//}

///// Colour Elevation
//if (menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked == true)
//{
//    int ex, wy;
//    int la = -1;
//    int alpha = 255;

//    for (wy = ymax - 1; wy >= 0; wy--)
//    {
//        la++;

//        for (ex = 0; ex < pbEnd; ex++)
//        {
//            if (TElevationDomain[ex, wy] > WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth + WDThreshold)
//                //if(AboveWater[ex, wy] > 0)
//                {
//                    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(alpha, 255, 255, 0));
//                    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (ex *
t), ((la - 1) * t), t, t);
//                }
//            else
//            {
//                SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(alpha, Color.AliceBlue));
//                objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (ex *
t), ((la - 1) * t), t, t);
//            }
//        }
//    }
//}

//int exs, wys;
//int las = -1;
//for (wys = ymax - 1; wys >= 0; wys--)
//{
//    las++;

//    for (exs = 0; exs < pbEnd; exs++)
//    {
//        if (DepthShelfMaterial[exs, wys] !=
DepthShelf[exs, wys] && Elevation[exs, wys] > 0)
//        {
//            SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Red);
//            objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (exs * t),
((las - 1) * t), t, t);
//        }
//    }
//}

// Colour Depth
if (menuItemGraphicDepth.Checked == true)
{

```

```

int b = -1;
hueMin = 225.0;
hueMax = 225.0;
satMin = 0.00;
satMax = 0.95;
valMin = 1.00;
valMax = 1.00;

//First find max, min and range of DEM
if (counter == 0)
{
    for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
    {
        for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        {
            zCalc = (WaterLevel + maxDomainDepth) -
TElevationDomain[x, y];

            if (zCalc != -9999)
            {
                if (zCalc < zDepthvMin)
                {
                    zDepthvMin = zCalc;
                }
                if (zCalc > zDepthMax)
                {
                    zDepthMax = zCalc;
                }
            }
        }
    }
    zDepthRange = zDepthMax - zDepthvMin;

    for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
    {
        b++;

        for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        {
            zDEM = (WaterLevel + maxDomainDepth) -
TElevationDomain[x, y];

            // Hue
            hue = hueMax - (((zDEM - zDepthvMin) /
(zDepthRange)) * (hueMax - hueMin));
            // Saturation
            sat = (((zDEM - zDepthvMin) / (zDepthRange)) *
(satMax - satMin)) + satMin;
            // Value
            val = (((zDEM - zDepthvMin) / (zDepthRange)) *
(valMax - valMin)) + valMin;

            if (double.IsInfinity(hue))
            {
            }

            Color_HSVtoRGB();
            redcol = System.Convert.ToInt32(red * 255);
            greencol = System.Convert.ToInt32(green *
255);
            bluecol = System.Convert.ToInt32(blue * 255);

```

```

        alphacol = 50;

        if (AboveWater[x, y] == 0)
        {
            SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(alphacol, redcol, greencol, bluecol));
            objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x * t),
((b - 1) * t), t, t);
        }
    }
}

// Colour Elevation
if (menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked == true)
{
    int b = -1;
    ////Yellow
    //hueMin = 58.0;
    //hueMax = 59.0;
    //satMin = 0.20;
    //satMax = 0.95;
    //valMin = 1.00;
    //valMax = 1.00;

    //Grey
    hueMin = 0.00;
    hueMax = 0.00;
    satMin = 0.00;
    satMax = 0.00;
    valMin = 0.40;
    valMax = 0.50;

    //First find max, min and range of DEM
    if (counter == 0)
    {
        for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
        {
            for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
            {
                zCalc = TElevationDomain[x, y] -
(WaterLevel + maxDomainDepth);

                if (zCalc != -9999 && zCalc > 0)
                {
                    if (zCalc < zElevMin)
                    {
                        zElevMin = zCalc;
                    }
                    if (zCalc > zElevMax)
                    {
                        zElevMax = zCalc;
                    }
                }
            }
        }

        zElevRange = zElevMax - zElevMin;

        for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)

```

```

        {
            b++;

            for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
            {
                zDEM = TElevationDomain[x, y] - (WaterLevel +
maxDomainDepth);

                // Hue
                hue = hueMax - (((zDEM - zElevMin) /
(zElevRange)) * (hueMax - hueMin));

                if (double.IsInfinity(hue))
                {
                }
                // Saturdation
                sat = (((zDEM - zElevMin) / (zElevRange)) *
(satMax - satMin)) + satMin;
                // Value
                val = (((zDEM - zElevMin) / (zElevRange)) *
(valMax - valMin)) + valMin;

                Color_HSVtoRGB();
                redcol = System.Convert.ToInt32(red * 255);
                greencol = System.Convert.ToInt32(green *
255);

                bluecol = System.Convert.ToInt32(blue * 255);
                alphacol = 100;

                //if (zDEM == 0.0)
                //{
                //    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(50,Color.AliceBlue));
                //    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x *
t), ((b - 1) * t), t, t);
                //}
                if (AboveWater[x, y] == 1)
                {
                    //SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(alphacol, redcol, greencol, bluecol));
                    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Gray);
                    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x * t),
((b - 1) * t), t, t);
                }
                //else
                //{
                //    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(50, Color.AliceBlue));
                //    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x *
t), ((b - 1) * t), t, t);
                //}
            }
        }

        ///// Colour PercentFullRock
        /////if (menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked == true)
        /////{
        /////    int a = -1;
        /////    for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
        /////    {

```

```

        ////          a++;

        ////          for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        ////          {
        ////              if (PercentFullRock[x, y] > 0.0)
        ////              {
        ////                  SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.SaddleBrown);
        ////                  objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (x *
t), ((a - 1) * t), t, t);
        ////              }
        ////          }
        ////      }
        ////  }
        ////}

        //Colour AboveTideOLD = FALSE
        //int c = -1;
        //for (y = ymax - 1; y >= 0; y--)
        //{
        //    c++;

        //    //for (x = xDisplayStart; x < xDisplayEnd; x++)
        //    for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        //    {
        //        // PercentFull Sand
        //        if (AboveTideOLD[x, y] == false)
        //        {
        //            SolidBrush semiTransBrush = new
SolidBrush(Color.FromArgb(50, 100, 149, 237));
        //            //SolidBrush semiTransBrush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Turquoise);
        //            objGraphics.FillRectangle(semiTransBrush,
((x /*- xDisplayStart*/) * t), ((c - 1) * t), t, t);
        //        }
        //    }
        //}

        // Colour the X[] Y[] array (beach/tide mark)
        if (menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked == true)
        {
            int d = 0;
            int e = 0;
            int f;
            int g;
            while (X[d] > -1 && Y[d] > -1 && d < (X.Length - 1))
            {
                f = X[d];
                g = Y[e];

                SolidBrush brush = new SolidBrush(Color.Blue);
                objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (f * t), ((ymax
- 2) - g) * t), t, t);

                //if (InShadow[d] == 'y')
                //{
                //    SolidBrush brush_red = new
SolidBrush(Color.Red);
                //    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush_red, (f *
t), (((ymax - 2) - g) * t), t, t);
                //}

                d++;

```

```

        e++;
    }
}

// Initial XY
if (menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Checked == true)
{
    int d = 0;
    int e = 0;
    int f;
    int g;
    while (initialX[d] > -1 && initialY[d] > -1 && d <
(initialX.Length - 1))
    {
        f = initialX[d];
        g = initialY[e];

        SolidBrush brush = new SolidBrush(Color.DarkBlue);
objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (f * t), ((ymax
- 2) - g) * t), t, t);

        d++;
        e++;
    }
}

// Shadow
if (menuItemShadow.Checked == true)
{
    this.waveAnglePanel.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveAngle
* radtodeg);

    int bb = -1;

    for (int yy = ymax - 1; yy >= 0; yy--)
    {
        bb++;
        for (int xx = 0; xx < pbEnd; xx++)
        {
            if (InShadow_domain[xx, yy] == 1 &&
AboveWater[xx, yy] == 0)
            {
                SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Orange);
objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx * t),
((bb - 1) * t), t, t);
            }
        }
    }
}

// RED / GREEN for +- material > 2m
if (menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked == true)
{
    int bb = -1;

    for (int yy = ymax - 1; yy >= 0; yy--)
    {
        bb++;
        for (int xx = 0; xx < pbEnd; xx++)
        {

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

//if (((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx,
yy]) / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) < -0)
//{
//    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Green);
//    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);

//    //// Qw Status panel
//    //this.QwStatusPanel.Text = xx + "," +
yy + " : " + ((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth));
//}
//else if (((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] -
Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) > 0)
//{
//    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Red);
//    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);

//    //// Qs Status panel
//    //this.QsStatusPanel.Text = xx + "," +
yy + " : " + ((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth));
//}
if (Linear_Shoreline[xx, yy] == 1)
{
    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Green);
    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx * t),
((bb - 1) * t), t, t);
}
//else if (AboveWater[xx, yy] == 1)
//{
//    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.LightGray);
//    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);
//}

//if (((((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx,
yy]) / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) < -0) && AboveWater[xx, yy] == 1)
//{
//    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Green);
//    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);

//    // Qw Status panel
//    this.QwStatusPanel.Text = xx + "," + yy
+ " : " + ((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth));
//}
//else if (((((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] -
Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth * CellWidth)) > 0) && AboveWater[xx, yy]
== 1)
//{
//    SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.Red);
//    objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);

```

```

// // Qs Status panel
// this.QsStatusPanel.Text = xx + "," + yy
+ " : " + ((PreviousVolume[xx, yy] - Volume[xx, yy]) / (CellWidth *
CellWidth));
//}
//else
//{
// SolidBrush brush = new
SolidBrush(Color.LightGray);
// objGraphics.FillRectangle(brush, (xx *
t), ((bb - 1) * t), t, t);
//}
}
}

string drawString1 = "0";
string drawString2 = Convert.ToString(xDisplayStart);
string drawString3 = Convert.ToString(xmax);
string drawString4 = Convert.ToString(xDisplayEnd);
string drawString5 = Convert.ToString(pbEnd);
string drawString6 = Convert.ToString(ymax/2);
string drawString7 = Convert.ToString(ymax);

Font drawFont = new Font("Arial", 5);
SolidBrush TextBrush = new SolidBrush(Color.Black);

objGraphics.DrawString(drawString1, drawFont, TextBrush,
(0 * t), ((ymax-2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString2, drawFont, TextBrush,
(xDisplayStart * t), ((ymax - 2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString3, drawFont, TextBrush,
(xmax * t), ((ymax - 2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString4, drawFont, TextBrush,
(xDisplayEnd * t), ((ymax - 2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString5, drawFont, TextBrush,
((pbEnd-(drawString5.Length)) * t), ((ymax - 2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString6, drawFont, TextBrush,
(0 * t), ((ymax / 2) * t));
objGraphics.DrawString(drawString7, drawFont, TextBrush,
(0 * t), ((0) * t));

drawFont.Dispose();
TextBrush.Dispose();

objGraphics.Dispose();
zoomPanImageBox1.Image = m_objDrawingSurface;
}
void Color_HSVtoRGB()
{
// Convert HSV to RGB.

if (sat == 0)
{
// If sat is 0, all colors are the same - this is some
flavor of gray.
red = val;
green = val;
blue = val;

```

```

    }
    else
    {
        double pFactor;
        double qFactor;
        double tFactor;

        double fractionalSector;
        int sectorNumber;
        double sectorPos;

        // The color wheel consists of six 60 degree sectors
        // Figure out which sector you are in.
        sectorPos = hue / 60;

        sectorNumber = (int)(Math.Floor(sectorPos));

        // get the fractional part of the sector.
        // That is, how many degrees into the sector are you?
        fractionalSector = sectorPos - sectorNumber;

        // Calculate values for the three axes of the color.
        pFactor = val * (1 - sat);
        qFactor = val * (1 - (sat * fractionalSector));
        tFactor = val * (1 - (sat * (1 - fractionalSector)));

        // Assign the fractional colors to r, g, and b based
on the sector the angle is in.
        switch (sectorNumber)
        {
            case 0:
                red = val;
                green = tFactor;
                blue = pFactor;
                break;
            case 1:
                red = qFactor;
                green = val;
                blue = pFactor;
                break;
            case 2:
                red = pFactor;
                green = val;
                blue = tFactor;
                break;
            case 3:
                red = pFactor;
                green = qFactor;
                blue = val;
                break;
            case 4:
                red = tFactor;
                green = pFactor;
                blue = val;
                break;
            case 5:
                red = val;
                green = pFactor;
                blue = qFactor;
                break;
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
    private void Form1_Resize(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        zoomPanImageBox1.Height = this.Height - 225;
        zoomPanImageBox1.Width = this.Width - 20;
    }
    private void zoomPanImageBox1_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
    }

    private void statusBar1_PanelClick(object sender,
System.Windows.Forms.StatusBarPanelClickEventArgs e)
    {
        // No action
    }

    //File Tab
    private void menuItemFileOpen_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
    {
        XmlTextReader xreader;

        OpenFileDialog ConfigOpen = new OpenFileDialog();
        ConfigOpen.InitialDirectory =
Directory.GetCurrentDirectory();
        ConfigOpen.Filter = "cfg files (*.xml)|*.xml|All files
(*.*)|*.*";
        ConfigOpen.FilterIndex = 1;
        ConfigOpen.RestoreDirectory = false;

        if (ConfigOpen.ShowDialog() == DialogResult.OK)
        {
            ConfigName = ConfigOpen.FileName;

            xreader = new XmlTextReader(ConfigName);

            //Read the file
            if (xreader != null)
            {
                xreader.ReadStartElement("Parameters");

                // DEM
                xreader.ReadStartElement("DigitalElevationModel");
                DEMTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("DEMTick"));
                DEMTextBox.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("DEMTextBox");
                CompDEMTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("CompDEMTick"));
                NormTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("NormTick"));
                WigglyTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("WigglyTick"));
                BlockTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("BlockTick"));
                ColumnTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("ColumnTB");
                RowsTB.Text = xreader.ReadElementString("RowsTB");
                xreader.ReadEndElement();

                // Wave Climate
                xreader.ReadStartElement("WaveClimate");

```

```

        ManWavTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("ManWavTick"));
        WaveFileTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("WaveFileTick"));
        BinnedTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("BinnedTick"));
        WAngleTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WAngleTB");
        WPeriodTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WPeriodTB");
        WHeightTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WHeightTB");
        WaveFileTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WaveFileTB");
        WLoadTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WLoadTB");
        WPLoadTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WPLoadTB");
        WHLoadTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WHLoadTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        // Tides
        xreader.ReadStartElement("Tides");
        DoTidesTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("DoTidesTick"));
        LowTideTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("WaterHeightTB");
        HighTideTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("HighTideTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        // Erosion and Weathering
        xreader.ReadStartElement("ErosionWeathering");
        ErosRateTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("ErosRateTB");
        PercentFastTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("PercentFastTB");
        PercentSlowTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("PercentSlowTB");
        RockWeatherTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("RockWeatherTB");
        SlowWeatherTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("SlowWeatherTB");
        FastWeatherTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("FastWeatherTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        // Sources and Sinks
        xreader.ReadStartElement("SourcesSinks");
        SourceTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("SourceTick"));
        ColSourceTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("ColSourceTick"));
        NumSourceTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("NumSourceTB");
        XSourceTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("XSourceTB");
        YSourceTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("YSourceTB");
        SinkTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("SinkTick"));

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        ColSinkTick.Checked =
XmlConvert.ToBoolean(xreader.ReadElementString("ColSinkTick"));
        NumSinkTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("NumSinkTB");
        SinkinessTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("SinkinessTB");
        XSinkTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("XSinkTB");
        YSinkTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("YSinkTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        // Outputs
        xreader.ReadStartElement("OutputsTab");
        OutputNameTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("OutputNameTB");
        SaveFreqTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("SaveFreqTB");
        RunLengthTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("RunLengthTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        // Description
        xreader.ReadStartElement("DescripTB");
        DescripTB.Text =
xreader.ReadElementString("DescripTB");
        xreader.ReadEndElement();

        xreader.Close();

        this.Text = basetext + " (" +
Path.GetFileName(ConfigName) + ")";
        loadDataButton.Enabled = true;
        startButton.Enabled = false;
    }
}
}
private void menuItemFileSave_Click(object sender,
System.EventArgs e)
{
    XmlTextWriter xwriter;

    if ((sender == menuItemFileSaveAs) || (ConfigName ==
null))
    {
        SaveFileDialog saveAsConfig = new SaveFileDialog();

        saveAsConfig.InitialDirectory =
Directory.GetCurrentDirectory();
        saveAsConfig.Filter = "cfg files (*.xml)|*.xml|All
files (*.*)|*.*";
        saveAsConfig.FilterIndex = 1;
        saveAsConfig.RestoreDirectory = false;

        if (saveAsConfig.ShowDialog() == DialogResult.OK)
        {
            ConfigName = saveAsConfig.FileName;
        }
    }

    if (ConfigName != null)
    {

```

```

        //Create a new XmlTextWriter.
        xwriter = new XmlTextWriter(ConfigName,
System.Text.Encoding.UTF8);

        //Write the beginning of the document including the
document declaration. Standalone is true.
        //Use indentation for readability.
        xwriter.Formatting = Formatting.Indented;
        xwriter.Indentation = 4;

        xwriter.WriteStartDocument(true);

        //Write the beginning of the "data" element. This is
the opening tag to our data
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("Parameters");

        // DEM
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("DigitalElevationModel");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("DEMTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(DEMTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("DEMTextBox",
DEMTextBox.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("CompDEMTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(CompDEMTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("NormTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(NormTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WigglyTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(WigglyTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("BlockTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(BlockTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("ColumnTB", ColumnTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("RowsTB", RowsTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Wave Climate
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("WaveClimate");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("ManWavTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(ManWavTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WaveFileTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(WaveFileTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("BinnedTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(BinnedTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WAngleTB", WAngleTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WPeriodTB",
WPeriodTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WHeightTB",
WHeightTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WaveFileTB",
WaveFileTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WALoadTB", WALoadTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WPLoadTB", WPLoadTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WHLoadTB", WHLoadTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Tides
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("Tides");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("DoTidesTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(DoTidesTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("WaterHeightTB",
LowTideTB.Text);

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        xwriter.WriteElementString("HighTideTB",
HighTideTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Erosion and Weathering
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("ErosionWeathering");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("ErosRateTB",
ErosRateTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("PercentFastTB",
PercentFastTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("PercentSlowTB",
PercentSlowTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("RockWeatherTB",
RockWeatherTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("SlowWeatherTB",
SlowWeatherTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("FastWeatherTB",
FastWeatherTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Sources and Sinks
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("SourcesSinks");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("SourceTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(SourceTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("ColSourceTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(ColSourceTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("NumSourceTB",
NumSourceTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("XSourceTB",
XSourceTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("YSourceTB",
YSourceTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("SinkTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(SinkTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("ColSinkTick",
XmlConvert.ToString(ColSinkTick.Checked));
        xwriter.WriteElementString("NumSinkTB",
NumSinkTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("SinkinessTB",
SinkinessTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("XSinkTB", XSinkTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("YSinkTB", YSinkTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Outputs
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("OutputsTab");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("OutputNameTB",
OutputNameTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("SaveFreqTB",
SaveFreqTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteElementString("RunLengthTB",
RunLengthTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        // Description
        xwriter.WriteStartElement("DescripTB");
        xwriter.WriteElementString("DescripTB",
DescripTB.Text);
        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

        xwriter.WriteEndElement();

```

```

        //End the document
        xwriter.WriteEndDocument();

        //Flush the xml document to the underlying stream and
        //close the underlying stream. The data will not be
        //written out to the stream until either the Flush()
        //method is called or the Close() method is called.
        xwriter.Close();

        this.Text = basetext + " (" +
Path.GetFileName(ConfigName) + ")";
    }

    // Graphics Tab
    private void menuItemGraphicsRock_Click(object sender,
EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsRock.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemGraphicsSand_Click(object sender,
EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsSand.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemGraphicsXY_Click(object sender, EventArgs
e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicsXY.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
    }

```

```

        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemGraphicDepth_Click(object sender,
EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicDepth.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicDepth.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicDepth.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicDepth.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemGraphicVolume_Click(object sender,
EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicVolume.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemGraphicInitialXY_Click(object sender,
EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemGraphicInitialXY.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void menuItemShadow_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (menuItemShadow.Checked == true)
        {
            menuItemShadow.Checked = false;
        }
        else if (menuItemShadow.Checked == false)
        {
            menuItemShadow.Checked = true;
        }

        updateClick = 1;

```

```

        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }

    // Scroll Bars
    private void trackBar1_Scroll(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        contrastMultiplier = contrastFactor[trackBar1.Value];
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    private void trackBar2_Scroll(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        magnifyValue = zoomFactor[this.trackBar2.Value];
        zoomPanImageBox1.SetZoom();
    }
    private void comboBox1_SelectedValueChanged(object sender,
    EventArgs e)
    {
        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }

    // Quick Buttons
    private void updateGraphics_Click_1(object sender,
    System.EventArgs e)
    {
        updateClick = 1;
        this.Refresh();
        drawwater(mygraphics);
    }
    void quitSaveButton_Click(object sender, System.EventArgs e)
    {
        save_data(1, 9999);
        this.Close();
    }
    private void resumeButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        gameClock.Start();
    }
    private void pauseButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        this.updateGraphics_Click_1(updateGraphicsButton,
    EventArgs.Empty);
        this.QwStatusPanel.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveAngle);
        this.QsStatusPanel.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveAngle *
    (180.0 / Math.PI));
        gameClock.Stop();
    }
    private void SeeTabsButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (this.MainWindowTabs.Visible == true)
        {
            MainWindowTabs.Visible = false;
            SeeTabsButton.Text = "See Tabs";
        }
        else if (this.MainWindowTabs.Visible == false)
        {
            MainWindowTabs.Visible = true;
            SeeTabsButton.Text = "Simulation";
        }
    }
}

```

```

// DEM
private void DEMFileExplorer_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    string[] DEMLineArray = new string[3];
    string[] DEMLineArray2 = new string[2];
    int z;
    int xFromFile;
    int yFromFile;

    OpenFileDialog DEMFileName = new OpenFileDialog();
    DEMFileName.InitialDirectory =
Directory.GetCurrentDirectory();

    if (DEMFileName.ShowDialog() == DialogResult.OK)
    {
        DEMFilePath = DEMFileName.FileName;
        DEMTextBox.Text = DEMFileName.SafeFileName;

        Stream fileStream = DEMFileName.OpenFile();
        StreamReader reader = new StreamReader(fileStream);

        for (z = 1; z <= 3; z++)
        {
            DEMLineArray[z - 1] = reader.ReadLine();
        }

        // get xmax and ymax from input headers
        DEMLineArray2 = DEMLineArray[0].Split(new char[] { ' '
}); // Number of Columns
        int sp = 1;
        while (DEMLineArray[sp] == "")
        {
            sp++;
        }
        xFromFile = int.Parse(DEMLineArray2[sp]);

        DEMLineArray2 = DEMLineArray[1].Split(new char[] { ' '
}); // Number of Rows
        sp = 1;
        while (DEMLineArray2[sp] == "")
        {
            sp++;
        }
        yFromFile = (int.Parse(DEMLineArray2[sp]) / 3);

        ColumnTB.Text = Convert.ToString(xFromFile);
        RowsTB.Text = Convert.ToString(yFromFile);

        fileStream.Close();
    }
}
private void DEMTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    if (DEMTick.Checked == true)
    {
        DEMTextBox.Enabled = true;
        DEMTextBox.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        DEMBrowseButton.Enabled = true;
        DEMBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    }
}

```

```

        CompDEMTick.Checked = false;

        ColumnTB.ReadOnly = true;
        RowsTB.ReadOnly = true;
        ColLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        RowLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;

        if (string.IsNullOrEmpty(this.DEMTextBox.Text))
        {
            ColumnTB.Text = "";
            RowsTB.Text = "";
        }
        else
        {
            //Find x and y values for DEM in textbox
            string[] DEMLineArray = new string[3];
            string[] DEMLineArray2 = new string[2];
            int z;

            StreamReader reader = new
StreamReader("INPUT_FILES/" + DEMTextBox.Text);

            for (z = 1; z <= 3; z++)
            {
                DEMLineArray[z - 1] = reader.ReadLine();
            }

            // get xmax and ymax from input headers
            DEMLineArray2 = DEMLineArray[0].Split(new char[] {
' ' }); // Number of Columns
            int sp = 1;
            while (DEMLineArray[sp] == "")
            {
                sp++;
            }
            xmax = int.Parse(DEMLineArray2[sp]);

            DEMLineArray2 = DEMLineArray[1].Split(new char[] {
' ' }); // Number of Rows
            sp = 1;
            while (DEMLineArray2[sp] == "")
            {
                sp++;
            }
            ymax = (int.Parse(DEMLineArray2[sp]) / 3);

            ColumnTB.Text = Convert.ToString(xmax);
            RowsTB.Text = Convert.ToString(ymax);
        }
    }
    else if (DEMTick.Checked == false)
    {
        DEMTextBox.Enabled = false;
        DEMTextBox.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        DEMBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
        DEMBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

        ColumnTB.Enabled = false;
        RowsTB.Enabled = false;
        ColumnTB.ReadOnly = true;
        RowsTB.ReadOnly = true;
        ColLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

```

```

        RowLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        ColumnTB.Text = "";
        RowsTB.Text = "";
        DEMTextBox.Text = "";
    }
}
private void CompDEMTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (CompDEMTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NormLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        NormTick.Enabled = true;
        WigglyLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WigglyTick.Enabled = true;
        BlockLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        BlockTick.Enabled = true;
        InitPertLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        InitPertTick.Enabled = true;
        PertLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        PertTick.Enabled = true;

        DEMTick.Checked = false;

        ColumnTB.Enabled = true;
        RowsTB.Enabled = true;
        ColumnTB.ReadOnly = false;
        RowsTB.ReadOnly = false;
        ColLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        RowLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        ColLabel.Font = new Font(ColLabel.Font,
FontStyle.Bold);
        RowLabel.Font = new Font(RowLabel.Font,
FontStyle.Bold);
    }
    else if (CompDEMTick.Checked == false)
    {
        NormLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        NormTick.Enabled = false;
        NormTick.Checked = false;
        WigglyLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WigglyTick.Enabled = false;
        WigglyTick.Checked = false;
        BlockLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        BlockTick.Enabled = false;
        BlockTick.Checked = false;
        InitPertLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        InitPertTick.Enabled = false;
        InitPertTick.Checked = false;
        PertLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        PertTick.Enabled = false;
        PertTick.Checked = false;

        ColumnTB.Enabled = false;
        RowsTB.Enabled = false;
        ColumnTB.ReadOnly = true;
        RowsTB.ReadOnly = true;
        ColLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        RowLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        ColLabel.Font = new Font(ColLabel.Font,
FontStyle.Regular);
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        RowLabel.Font = new Font(RowLabel.Font,
FontStyle.Regular);
        ColumnTB.Text = "";
        RowsTB.Text = "";
    }
}
private void NormTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    if (NormTick.Checked == true)
    {
        WigglyTick.Checked = false;
        BlockTick.Checked = false;
        InitPertTick.Checked = false;
        PertTick.Checked = false;
    }
}
private void WigglyTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (WigglyTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NormTick.Checked = false;
        BlockTick.Checked = false;
        InitPertTick.Checked = false;
        PertTick.Checked = false;
    }
}
private void BlockTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    if (BlockTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NormTick.Checked = false;
        WigglyTick.Checked = false;
        InitPertTick.Checked = false;
        PertTick.Checked = false;
    }
}
private void InitPertTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (InitPertTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NormTick.Checked = false;
        WigglyTick.Checked = false;
        BlockTick.Checked = false;
        PertTick.Checked = false;
    }
}
private void PertTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    if (PertTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NormTick.Checked = false;
        WigglyTick.Checked = false;
        BlockTick.Checked = false;
        InitPertTick.Checked = false;
    }
}
}

```

```

// Waves
private void WaveBrowseButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    OpenFileDialog WaveFileName = new OpenFileDialog();
    WaveFileName.InitialDirectory =
Directory.GetCurrentDirectory();

    if (WaveFileName.ShowDialog() == DialogResult.OK)
    {
        WaveFileTB.Text = WaveFileName.SafeFileName;

        Stream fileStream = WaveFileName.OpenFile();
        StreamReader reader = new StreamReader(fileStream);

        // Get 1st Wave Angle, Period, Height in file
        realWave_Content = reader.ReadLine();

        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\r\n", "
");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\t", "
");
        realWave_Content = Regex.Replace(realWave_Content,
@"\s+", " ");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Trim();
        realWave_Split = realWave_Content.Split(' ');

        fileStream.Close();

        WaveAngleIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[0]);
        WavePeriodIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[1]);
        WaveHeightIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[2]);

        WALoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveAngleIn);
        WPLoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WavePeriodIn);
        WHLoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveHeightIn);
    }
}
private void WaveFileTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (WaveFileTick.Checked == true)
    {
        WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = true;
        WaveFileTB.Enabled = true;
        WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = false;
        WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;

        WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;

        ManWavTick.Checked = false;
        ManWavLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WAngleTB.Text = "";
        WPeriodTB.Text = "";
        WHeightTB.Text = "";
        WAngleTB.Enabled = false;

```

```

        WPeriodTB.Enabled = false;
        WHeightTB.Enabled = false;
        WAngleTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WPeriodTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WHeightTB.ReadOnly = true;

        UA_WaveTick.Checked = false;
        UALab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        AsymLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        HighLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        AsymTB.Text = "";
        HighTB.Text = "";
        AsymTB.Enabled = false;
        HighTB.Enabled = false;
        AsymTB.ReadOnly = true;
        HighTB.ReadOnly = true;

        // CM - not using this for now
        //BinnedLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        //BinnedTick.Enabled = true;
    }
    else if (WaveFileTick.Checked == false)
    {
        WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
        WaveFileTB.Enabled = false;
        WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WaveFileTB.Text = "";
        WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

        WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WALoadTB.Text = "";
        WHLoadTB.Text = "";
        WPLoadTB.Text = "";

        //CM - not using this for now
        //BinnedLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        //BinnedTick.Enabled = false;
    }
}
private void ManWavTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (ManWavTick.Checked == true)
    {
        ManWavLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WHeightTB.Enabled = true;
        WPeriodTB.Enabled = true;
        WAngleTB.Enabled = true;
        WAngleTB.ReadOnly = false;
        WPeriodTB.ReadOnly = false;
        WHeightTB.ReadOnly = false;

        WaveFileTick.Checked = false;
        WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
        WaveFileTB.Enabled = false;
        WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = true;

```

```

WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

UA_WaveTick.Checked = false;
UALab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
AsymLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
HighLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
AsymTB.Text = "";
HighTB.Text = "";
AsymTB.Enabled = false;
HighTB.Enabled = false;
AsymTB.ReadOnly = true;
HighTB.ReadOnly = true;

//BinnedTick.Checked = false;
}
else if (ManWavTick.Checked == false)
{
ManWavLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WHeightTB.Enabled = false;
WPeriodTB.Enabled = false;
WAngleTB.Enabled = false;
WHeightTB.Text = "";
WPeriodTB.Text = "";
WAngleTB.Text = "";
}
}
private void UA_WaveTickTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
if (UA_WaveTick.Checked == true)
{
UA_WaveTick.Checked = true;
UALab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
AsymLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
HighLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
AsymTB.Enabled = true;
HighTB.Enabled = true;
AsymTB.ReadOnly = false;
HighTB.ReadOnly = false;

WaveFileTick.Checked = false;
WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
WaveFileTB.Enabled = false;
WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = true;
WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

ManWavTick.Checked = false;
WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
WHeightTB.Enabled = false;

```

```

        WPeriodTB.Enabled = false;
        WAngleTB.Enabled = false;
        WHeightTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WPeriodTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WAngleTB.ReadOnly = true;
        WHeightTB.Text = "";
        WPeriodTB.Text = "";
        WAngleTB.Text = "";
    }
else if (UA_WaveTick.Checked == false)
{
    UA_WaveTick.Checked = false;
    UALab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    AsymLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    HighLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    AsymTB.Text = "";
    HighTB.Text = "";
    AsymTB.Enabled = false;
    HighTB.Enabled = false;
    AsymTB.ReadOnly = true;
    HighTB.ReadOnly = true;
}
}

/*
private void WaveFileTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (WaveFileTick.Checked == true)
    {
        WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = true;
        WaveFileTB.Enabled = true;
        WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = false;
        WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;

        WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;

        BinnedLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        BinnedTick.Enabled = true;

        ManWavTick.Checked = false;
    }
else if (WaveFileTick.Checked == false)
{
    WaveBrowseButton.Enabled = false;
    WaveFileTB.Enabled = false;
    WaveFileTB.ReadOnly = true;
    WaveFileTB.Text = "";
    WaveBrowseButton.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    WaveFileLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;

    BinnedLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    BinnedTick.Enabled = false;

    WALoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    WHLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    WPLoadLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    WALoadTB.Text = "";
    WHLoadTB.Text = "";
}
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        WPLoadTB.Text = "";
    }
}
private void WaveBrowseButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    OpenFileDialog WaveFileName = new OpenFileDialog();
    WaveFileName.InitialDirectory =
Directory.GetCurrentDirectory();

    if (WaveFileName.ShowDialog() == DialogResult.OK)
    {
        WaveFileTB.Text = WaveFileName.SafeFileName;

        Stream fileStream = WaveFileName.OpenFile();
        StreamReader reader = new StreamReader(fileStream);

        // Get 1st Wave Angle, Period, Height in file
        realWave_Content = reader.ReadLine();

        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\r\n", "
");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Replace("\t", "
");
        realWave_Content = Regex.Replace(realWave_Content,
@"\s+", " ");
        realWave_Content = realWave_Content.Trim();
        realWave_Split = realWave_Content.Split(' ');

        fileStream.Close();

        WaveAngleIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[0]);
        WavePeriodIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[1]);
        WaveHeightIn = Convert.ToDouble(realWave_Split[2]);

        WALoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveAngleIn);
        WPLoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WavePeriodIn);
        WHLoadTB.Text = Convert.ToString(WaveHeightIn);
    }
}
private void ManWavTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (ManWavTick.Checked == true)
    {
        WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        WHeightTB.Enabled = true;
        WPeriodTB.Enabled = true;
        WAngleTB.Enabled = true;

        WaveFileTick.Checked = false;
        BinnedTick.Checked = false;
    }
    else if (ManWavTick.Checked == false)
    {
        WHeightLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WPeriodLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WAngleLabel.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        WHeightTB.Enabled = false;
        WPeriodTB.Enabled = false;
    }
}

```

```

        WAngleTB.Enabled = false;
        WHeightTB.Text = "";
        WPeriodTB.Text = "";
        WAngleTB.Text = "";
    }
}
private void UA_WaveTickTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (UA_WaveTick.Checked == true)
    {
        WaveIn = 0;
    }
}
*/

// Tides
private void DoTidesTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (DoTidesTick.Checked == true)
    {
        LowTideLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        LowTideTB.Enabled = true;
        LowTideTB.ReadOnly = false;

        HighTideLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        HighTideTB.Enabled = true;
        HighTideTB.ReadOnly = false;
    }
    else if (DoTidesTick.Checked == false)
    {
        LowTideLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        LowTideTB.Enabled = false;
        LowTideTB.ReadOnly = true;
        LowTideTB.Text = "";

        HighTideLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        HighTideTB.Enabled = false;
        HighTideTB.ReadOnly = true;
        HighTideTB.Text = "";
    }
}

// SLR
private void DoSLRTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    if (DoSLRTick.Checked == true)
    {
        SLRLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        SLR_TB.Enabled = true;
        SLR_TB.ReadOnly = false;

        RateSLRLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        RateSLR_TB.Enabled = true;
        RateSLR_TB.ReadOnly = false;

        StepSLR_Lab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        StepSLR_Tick.Enabled = true;
    }
}

```

```

else if (DoTidesTick.Checked == false)
{
    SLRLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    SLR_TB.Enabled = false;
    SLR_TB.ReadOnly = true;
    SLR_TB.Text = "";

    RateSLRLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    RateSLR_TB.Enabled = false;
    RateSLR_TB.ReadOnly = true;
    RateSLR_TB.Text = "";

    StepSLR_Lab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    StepSLR_Tick.Checked = false;
    StepSLR_Tick.Enabled = false;
}
}

// Sources&Sinks
private void SourceTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (SourceTick.Checked == true)
    {
        NumSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        NumSourceTB.Enabled = true;
        NumSourceTB.ReadOnly = false;

        ColSourceTick.Checked = false;
        ColSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        ColSourceTick.Enabled = true;

        XSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        XSourceTB.Enabled = true;
        XSourceTB.ReadOnly = false;
        YSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        YSourceTB.Enabled = true;
        YSourceTB.ReadOnly = false;
    }
    else if (SourceTick.Checked == false)
    {
        NumSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        NumSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        NumSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        NumSourceTB.Text = "";

        ColSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        ColSourceTick.Enabled = false;

        XSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        XSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        XSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        XSourceTB.Text = "";
        YSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        YSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        YSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
        YSourceTB.Text = "";
    }
}
private void SinkTick_CheckedChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{

```

```

if (SinkTick.Checked == true)
{
    NumSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    NumSinkTB.Enabled = true;
    NumSinkTB.ReadOnly = false;

    ColSinkTick.Checked = false;
    ColSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    ColSinkTick.Enabled = true;

    XSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    XSinkTB.Enabled = true;
    XSinkTB.ReadOnly = false;
    YSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    YSinkTB.Enabled = true;
    YSinkTB.ReadOnly = false;

    SinkinessLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
    SinkinessTB.Enabled = true;
    SinkinessTB.ReadOnly = false;
}
else if (SinkTick.Checked == false)
{
    NumSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    NumSinkTB.Enabled = false;
    NumSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
    NumSinkTB.Text = "";

    ColSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    ColSinkTick.Enabled = false;

    XSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    XSinkTB.Enabled = false;
    XSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
    XSinkTB.Text = "";
    YSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    YSinkTB.Enabled = false;
    YSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
    YSinkTB.Text = "";

    SinkinessLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
    SinkinessTB.Enabled = false;
    SinkinessTB.ReadOnly = true;
    SinkinessTB.Text = "";
}
}

private void ColSinkTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if(ColSinkTick.Checked == true)
    {
        YSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        YSinkTB.Text = "";
        YSinkTB.Enabled = false;
        YSinkTB.ReadOnly = true;
    }
    else if(ColSinkTick.Checked == false)
    {
        YSinkLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        YSinkTB.Enabled = true;
    }
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

        YSinkTB.ReadOnly = false;
    }
}
private void ColSourceTick_CheckedChanged(object sender,
EventArgs e)
{
    if (ColSourceTick.Checked == true)
    {
        YSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Gray;
        YSourceTB.Text = "";
        YSourceTB.Enabled = false;
        YSourceTB.ReadOnly = true;
    }
    else if (ColSourceTick.Checked == false)
    {
        YSourceLab.ForeColor = Color.Black;
        YSourceTB.Enabled = true;
        YSourceTB.ReadOnly = false;
    }
}
private void toolTip1_Popup(object sender, PopupEventArgs e)
{
}

//Debug
private void SandOutputButton_Click(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    int x, y;
    StreamWriter percentSandFile = new
StreamWriter("TEST_FILES/percentSand" + counter + ".dat");

    percentSandFile.Write(counter + Environment.NewLine);

    for (y = ymax-1; y >= 0; y--)
    {
        for (x = 0; x < pbEnd; x++)
        {
            percentSandFile.Write("ElevationDomain[x, y] + "
");
        }

        percentSandFile.Write(Environment.NewLine);
    }
    percentSandFile.Close();
}

}

class point
{
    //lat long variables
    public double xcoord;
    public double ycoord;
    double transParallelX = 446.448;
    double transParallelY = -125.157;
    double transParallelZ = 542.060;
}

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```

double scaleChange = -20.4894 * 0.000001;
double rotX = (0.1502 / 3600) * (Math.PI / 180);
double rotY = (0.2470 / 3600) * (Math.PI / 180);
double rotZ = (0.8421 / 3600) * (Math.PI / 180);
double a = 6377563.396; //airy 1830 semi-major axis
double b = 6356256.910; //airy 1830 semi-minor axis
double a2 = 6378137.000;
double b2 = 6356752.3142;
double eSquared = 0;
double eSquared2 = 0;
double n0 = -100000; //northing of true origin
double e0 = 400000; //easting of true origin
double f0 = 0.9996012717; //scale factor
double latTrue = 49.0 * (Math.PI / 180.0); //latitude of true
origin
double longTrue = -2.0 * (Math.PI / 180.0); //longitude of true
origin
double psiHash, MBig, v, v2, v3, nLittle, rho, nSquare = 0;
double vii, viii, ix, Tx2, xi, xii, xiia = 0;
double helmertX, helmertY, helmertZ, cartX, cartY, cartZ;
double Height2 = 0;
double finalLati, finalLongi, latiRad, longiRad = 0;
double rootXYSqr = 0;
double PHI1, PHI2, PHI = 0;

public point(double theXcoord, double theYcoord) //constructor
{
    this.xcoord = theXcoord;
    this.ycoord = theYcoord;
}

public void transformPoint() //british os to lat long
{
    eSquared = (Math.Pow(a, 2) - Math.Pow(b, 2)) / Math.Pow(a,
2);
    Height2 = 0;

    //OSGB36 easting and northing to OSGB36 latitude and
longitude (lower left corner of DTM)
    psiHash = ((this.ycoord - n0) / (a * f0)) + latTrue;
    nLittle = (a - b) / (a + b);
    MBig = b * f0 * (((1 + nLittle + ((5.0 / 4.0) *
Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) + ((5.0 / 4.0) * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) *
(psiHash -
        latTrue))
        - (((3.0 * nLittle) + (3.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) +
((21.0 / 8.0) * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) *
        Math.Sin(psiHash - latTrue) * Math.Cos(psiHash +
latTrue))
        + (((15.0 / 8.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) + (15.0 / 8.0 *
Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) * Math.Sin(2.0 * (psiHash - latTrue)) *
Math.Cos(2.0 * (psiHash + latTrue)))
        - ((35.0 / 24.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3)) * Math.Sin(3.0
* (psiHash - latTrue)) * Math.Cos(3.0 * (psiHash + latTrue)))));

    if (Math.Abs((this.ycoord - n0 - MBig)) >= 0.01)
    {
        while (Math.Abs((this.ycoord - n0 - MBig)) >= 0.01)
        {
            psiHash = ((this.ycoord - n0 - MBig) / (a * f0)) +
psiHash;

```

```

        MBig = b * f0 * (((1 + nLittle + ((5.0 / 4.0) *
Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) + ((5.0 / 4.0) * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) *
(psiHash -
        latTrue))
        - (((3.0 * nLittle) + (3.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) +
((21.0 / 8.0) * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) *
        Math.Sin(psiHash - latTrue) * Math.Cos(psiHash
+ latTrue))
        + (((15.0 / 8.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 2)) + (15.0 / 8.0
* Math.Pow(nLittle, 3))) * Math.Sin(2.0 * (psiHash - latTrue)) *
Math.Cos(2.0 * (psiHash + latTrue)))
        - ((35.0 / 24.0 * Math.Pow(nLittle, 3)) *
Math.Sin(3.0 * (psiHash - latTrue)) * Math.Cos(3.0 * (psiHash +
latTrue)))));
    }
}

    v = a * f0 * Math.Pow(1 - eSquared *
Math.Pow(Math.Sin(psiHash), 2), -0.5);
    rho = a * f0 * (1 - eSquared) * Math.Pow(1.0 - eSquared *
Math.Pow(Math.Sin(psiHash), 2), -1.5);
    nSquare = v / rho - 1.0;
    vii = (Math.Tan(psiHash)) / (2.0 * rho * v);
    viii = ((Math.Tan(psiHash)) / (24.0 * rho * Math.Pow(v,
3))) * (5 + 3.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2) + nSquare - 9.0 *
(Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2) * nSquare));
    ix = (Math.Tan(psiHash) / ((720.0 * rho * Math.Pow(v,
5)))) * (61 + 90.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2) + 45.0 *
Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 4));
    Tx2 = (1.0 / Math.Cos(psiHash)) / v;
    xi = (1.0 / Math.Cos(psiHash)) / (6.0 * Math.Pow(v, 3)) *
((v / rho) + (2.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2)));
    xii = (1.0 / Math.Cos(psiHash)) / (120.0 * Math.Pow(v, 5))
* (5.0 + (28.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2)) + (24.0 *
Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 4)));
    xiia = ((1.0 / Math.Cos(psiHash)) / (5040.0 * Math.Pow(v,
7))) * (61.0 + (662.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 2)) + (1320.0 *
Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash), 4)) + (720.0 * Math.Pow(Math.Tan(psiHash),
6)));
    latiRad = psiHash - (vii * Math.Pow((this.xcoord - e0),
2)) + (viii * Math.Pow((this.xcoord - e0), 4)) - (ix *
Math.Pow((this.xcoord - e0), 6));
    longiRad = longTrue + (Tx2 * (this.xcoord - e0)) - (xi *
(Math.Pow((this.xcoord - e0), 3))) + (xii * (Math.Pow((this.xcoord -
e0), 5))) - (xiia * (Math.Pow((this.xcoord - e0), 7)));

    v2 = a / (Math.Sqrt(1 - (eSquared *
((Math.Pow(Math.Sin(latiRad), 2))))));
    cartX = (v2 + Height2) * Math.Cos(latiRad) *
Math.Cos(longiRad);
    cartY = (v2 + Height2) * (Math.Cos(latiRad) *
Math.Sin(longiRad));
    cartZ = ((v2 * (1 - eSquared)) + Height2) *
Math.Sin(latiRad);

    helmertX = cartX + (cartX * scaleChange) - (cartY * rotZ)
+ (cartZ * rotY) + transParallelX;
    helmertY = (cartX * rotZ) + cartY + (cartY * scaleChange)
- (cartZ * rotX) + transParallelY;
    helmertZ = (-1 * cartX * rotY) + (cartY * rotX) + cartZ +
(cartZ * scaleChange) + transParallelZ;

```

Appendix 2 | CEM2D Source Code

```
        rootXYSqr = Math.Sqrt((Math.Pow(helmertX, 2)) +
(Math.Pow(helmertY, 2)));
        eSquared2 = (Math.Pow(a2, 2) - Math.Pow(b2, 2)) /
Math.Pow(a2, 2);
        PHI1 = Math.Atan(helmertZ / (rootXYSqr * (1 -
eSquared2)));
        v3 = a2 / (Math.Sqrt(1.0 - (eSquared2 *
((Math.Pow(Math.Sin(PHI1), 2))))));
        PHI2 = Math.Atan((helmertZ + (eSquared2 * v3 *
(Math.Sin(PHI1)))) / rootXYSqr);

        while (Math.Abs(PHI1 - PHI2) > 0.000000001)
        {
            PHI1 = PHI2;
            v3 = a2 / (Math.Sqrt(1 - (eSquared2 *
((Math.Pow(Math.Sin(PHI1), 2))))));
            PHI2 = Math.Atan((helmertZ + (eSquared2 * v3 *
(Math.Sin(PHI1)))) / rootXYSqr);
        }

        PHI = PHI2;
        finalLati = PHI * (180.0 / Math.PI);
        finalLongi = (Math.Atan(helmertY / helmertX)) * (180.0 /
Math.PI);
        this.xcoord = finalLongi;
        this.ycoord = finalLati;
    }
}
```